

From Hoodlums to Businessmen:
The Development of South Korean Gangster
Cinema (1958 to Present)

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This thesis is submitted to Dundalk Institute of Technology
for the award of PhD

November 2025

School of Informatics and Creative Arts
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Abstract

From Hoodlums to Businessmen: The Development of South Korean Gangster Cinema (1958 to Present)

Brian Culley

Dressed in suits, based in high-rise offices, and overseeing vast criminal empires, contemporary Korean gangsters resemble businessmen. Yet, the Korean gangster has not always been depicted this way – the genre’s first gangsters were little more than hoodlums.

Since its emergence in the postwar period, the Korean gangster genre has undergone a remarkable development, with almost every element of the genre changing with several shifts. Whereas the first iteration of Korean gangster cinema was more akin to a sub-genre of melodrama than a full-fledged genre, the most recent iteration is a multifaceted genre that incorporates elements of the thriller and noir.

Despite its remarkable development, the Korean gangster genre is significantly under-researched in English-language scholarship. Many scholars who otherwise comprehensively examine Korean cinema overlook the genre, and the little scholarship that exists is limited in scope.

The thesis addresses the lack of extant research by examining the development of Korean gangster cinema across three distinct periods: the ‘Pre-Revival Era’ (1958 - 1989), during which censorship and melodrama hindered the genre’s development, the ‘Revival Era’ (1990 - 2006), during which a new generation of filmmakers revived the genre to significant success, and the ‘Post-Revival Era’ (2007 - Present), during which genre-bending and notable socio-cultural phenomena – namely social inequality and corruption – reshaped many of the genre’s characteristics.

In doing so, the thesis explores how various determinants – including internal genre changes, socio-cultural events such as the IMF Crisis, and industrial factors such as censorship – shaped the genre’s core elements, including its portrayal of social inequality and its representation of violence.

The thesis specifically explores the transformation of the gangster protagonist, or ‘gangster-hero’, detailing how changes made to the gangster-hero’s portrayal, whether in terms of class, rank or morality, are the principal reasons for the differences between each of the genre’s periods.

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A Note on Romanisation

Most Korean names and words have been Romanised according to the Revised Romanisation system, the official system developed by the South Korean Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism. Exceptions have been made for names and words that are commonly Romanised according to a different system.

Exceptions have also been made for the names of cited authors. Author names are cited as they appear in the cited source, regardless of the Romanisation system they follow. Korean names are written surname first, given name second, in keeping with Korean practice, unless the name appears given name first, surname second in the cited source. Where an author's name appears differently across multiple sources, the thesis uses each version.

If a name is hyphenated, for example, as 'Park Chan-wook', it appears in the reference list as Park, C. If a given name is not hyphenated, for example, Park Chan Wook, it appears in the reference list as Park, C.W.

If there are multiple translations for a film title, the thesis uses the English-language title as it appears on the Korean Film Archive's Korean Movie Database (KMDB). Where possible, character names have also been taken from KMDb.

Chapter I: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Force-feeding a man concrete and dumping him in the sea, beating a man to death with a shovel, threatening to sexually assault and kill a female police officer, and cold-bloodedly murdering someone in a bloody knife-fight – these are just some of the terrible acts committed by the gangsters in the film *New World* (*Sinsegye*, Park 2013).

Yet, to look at them, one would not think that these gangsters are capable of such acts or are even gangsters at all. Dressed in their professional suits, the gangsters of *New World* seem more akin to businessmen – they meet on the upper floors of a gleaming skyscraper, they refer to their gang as a company, and they discuss their plans while seated at a grand conference table. The businesslike depiction of gangsters in *New World* is typical of contemporary Korean cinema. Affluent, powerful and directly involved in both business and politics, contemporary Korean gangsters are as much denizens of high society as they are of the underworld.

However, Korean gangsters have not always been depicted this way. In fact, the businesslike depiction of gangsters is not a byproduct of gradual genre development but a sudden shift that seems to have occurred sometime in the late 2000s. Before this shift, gangsters were typically young, low-ranking, lower-class individuals – they were representative of normal Koreans in the same way that contemporary gangsters are now representative of Korea's wealthiest citizens. Whereas recent gangster films seem focused on vilifying those with immense power and wealth, films made in the 1990s and early 2000s focus on issues such as social inequality and generational division.

Overall, this thesis illustrates that the Korean gangster genre has not developed gradually and continuously. Rather, it can be divided into three distinct periods: the Pre-

Revival Era (1958 - 1989)¹, the Revival Era (1990 - 2006)², and the Post-Revival Era (2007 - Present).³ These are not meant to replace the well-established periods used to discuss Korean cinema – the Golden Age, the Dark Age, the Korean New Wave and New Korean Cinema. While both sets of periods overlap, they should not be considered synonymous. The thesis uses the broader historical periods, such as New Korean Cinema, when discussing Korean cinema and industry-wide trends, and the ‘Revival framework’ when focusing on developments specific to the gangster genre.

With each era, certain elements of the genre have disappeared entirely, new elements have emerged, and many more have changed, resulting in a rather discontinuous development. For example, although the theme of corruption is almost completely absent in the Pre-Revival Era, it is present in most gangster films made during the Post-Revival Era. Simultaneously, the depiction of social inequality has changed across the genre’s three eras – although somewhat evident in the Pre-Revival Era, it is the dominant theme of the Revival Era. While the theme of social inequality remains important in the Post-Revival Era, its treatment has changed: whereas Revival Era films depict social inequality by highlighting the tribulations of being underprivileged, Post-Revival Era gangster films depict social inequality by showcasing the corrupt machinations of the upper classes.

Several of the genre’s elements have not only emerged or disappeared across all three eras, but have been reshuffled, their importance rising or falling. For example, while the age

¹ The Pre-Revival Era encompasses two established periods of Korean Cinema, the Golden Age – periodised by Abelmann and McHugh (2005, p.2) and Jeong (2006, p.130) as being between 1955 to 1972 – and the Dark Age – a period that many scholars, including Lee, S. (2019, p.16) and Park (2007, p.16), believe lasted throughout the 1970s and 1980s. Although grouped together in the same era, the thesis addresses the gangster films of the Golden Age and the Dark Age separately due to the unique industrial factors that characterise each period.

² The Revival Era encompasses the Korean New Wave, a period that scholars such as Yecies and Shim (2016, p.138) and Gateward (2007, p.5) associate with the 1980s, and New Korean Cinema. Although there is a lack of consensus regarding the beginning of New Korean Cinema, the thesis sides with Darcy Paquet’s (2009, p.78) suggestion that it began when “the Korean New Wave drew to a close in 1996.”

³ The Post-Revival Era begins with the end of New Korean Cinema, which Paquet (2009, pp.110-111) ascribes to the “bursting of the film finance bubble” and a severe decline in film exports in 2006. Jin (2020, p.47) notes that the same year saw the domestic market share of Korean films fall from a record high of 63.8% in 2006 to 42% in 2008.

of the gangster-hero is tied to their rank and status in the Pre-Revival Era, the Revival Era highlights the harmful effects of generational division in the underworld and Korean society.

The Korean gangster genre's development is most evident when considering its central figure: the gangster protagonist, or, as the thesis refers to them, the gangster-hero. As the focal point to which all other elements of the genre connect, changes made to the gangster-hero's portrayal, whether in terms of class, rank, relatability or morality, have resulted in major differences between the different eras of Korean gangster cinema.

The idea of focusing on the gangster-hero when examining the gangster genre is drawn from Simon Pate's (2016) PhD thesis on Hollywood and Japanese gangster cinema. Pate (2016, p.11) uses the term 'gangster-hero' to distinguish between films that feature a gangster protagonist and films that only focus on efforts to defeat gangsters or in which the underworld is merely a backdrop to the film's narrative. Aside from using the term throughout its discussion of the Korean gangster genre, this thesis uses the gangster-hero as the sole criterion by which it creates an *a priori* definition of the gangster genre. Accordingly, every film in the thesis's corpus features a gangster-hero.

The decision to focus on the gangster-hero stems from the unique nature of the gangster genre. As genre theorist Ron Wilson (2015, p.3) states, the gangster genre is, unlike genres such as the Western, action and science fiction, "the only genre whose nomenclature is centred on an individual, rather than a concept."⁴ Accordingly, the thesis considers – at least for its purposes – that the gangster figure is the *defining* element of the gangster genre. More specifically, the thesis proceeds on the assumption that a gangster *protagonist* is the defining element of the gangster genre.

Hence, the thesis's main objective is to chart the Korean gangster genre's development, with a particular emphasis on the changing representation of the 'gangster-

⁴ Wilson's (2015, p.3) statement does not seem entirely correct. Although the nomenclature of the gangster genre certainly centres on an individual rather than a concept, one could argue that this is also true of the superhero genre.

hero'. To achieve this objective, the thesis examines a corpus of forty-five films across the three eras of Korean gangster cinema, the Pre-Revival Era, the Revival Era and the Post-Revival Era.

1.2 Research Gaps and Scholarly Contributions

Many scholars who have otherwise comprehensively examined Korean cinema either do not discuss the genre or even acknowledge it. For example, although Brian Yecies and Aegyung Shim (2016) refer to two films as gangster films, *Guns & Talks (Killeodeurui suda*, Jang 2001) (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.164) and *The Anarchists (Anakiseuteu*, Yoo 2000) (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.234), in their book covering Korean cinema from 1960 to 2015, they neither examine these films nor the gangster genre more broadly.⁵ Similarly, while Dal Yong Jin (2020, p.121) remarks on the success of the gangster film *General's Son (Janggunui adeul*, Im 1990) in his book *Transnational Korean Cinema: Cultural Politics, Film Genres, and Digital Technologies*, he does not refer to the gangster genre nor examine gangster films.

Although some English-language research exists on Korean gangster cinema, it mainly focuses on a few specific aspects, films or periods of the genre. A typical example of such scholarship is Mark R. Plaice's (2020) article on the representation of domestic spaces in Korean gangster films. Many scholars only indirectly discuss the gangster genre. For example, Jungmin Kwon (2023) only tangentially examines the gangster genre while examining the 'bromance' between the two protagonists of *New World*.

English-language discussion of Korean gangster cinema also focuses predominantly on films made during New Korean Cinema. Only two English-language scholars, Jinhee Choi (2010a, pp.60-84; 2010b, pp.46-55) and Jinsoo An (2018), acknowledge the existence

⁵ Yecies and Shim's (2016) decision to refer to *Guns & Talks* (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.164) and *The Anarchists* (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.234) as gangster films is questionable. The four protagonists of *Guns & Talks* are more akin to assassins than gangsters, and the characters in *The Anarchists* are guerrilla freedom fighters trying to undermine Japanese colonial rule in 1920s China. Accordingly, it seems an oversimplification to refer to both films as gangster films. At the very least, an explanation seems necessary, if only because no other English-language scholar refers to either film as a gangster film.

of pre-1990s Korean gangster cinema, with most other scholars only *indirectly* suggesting that the Korean gangster genre existed before 1990 when they refer to gangster films made during the late-1990s and early-2000s as a “shift” (Kim 2019, p.510), a “new cycle” (Plaice 2020, p.3) or “new gangster cinema” (Min et al. 2003, p.173).

Due to the lack of extant literature on pre-1990s Korean gangster cinema, the thesis mainly builds upon Jinhee Choi’s (2010a; 2010b) work. Principally, it supports her (2010a, p.60; 2010b, p.48) observation that the Korean gangster genre entered a decline – both in terms of popularity and quality – during the 1970s, before almost disappearing in the 1980s.

Fortunately, more literature exists on gangster films made after 2006 than on gangster films made before 1990. Some scholars have observed a shift that has occurred since 2006. While discussing *New World*, Graham Neil Gillespie (2016, p.67) notes that the film transposes “the gangster narrative to the elite domain of the boardroom, where sharp-suited henchmen meet on the uppermost floors of a faceless corporate skyscraper.” Mark R. Plaice (2019b) highlights a similar shift in films such as *The Merciless* (*Bulhandang: nappeun nomdeurui sesang*, Byun 2017) and *Inside Men* (*Naebujadeul*, Woo 2015), suggesting that the boundaries between the noir and gangster genres have blurred. In addition, Se Young Kim (2019, p.516, italics in original) states that the film *Veteran* (Ryoo 2015), which sees a detective battle with a powerful businessman, is “indicative of a new amalgamated anxiety about the gangster, a corporate gangster who is indicative of the resentment towards the *chaebol* class.”⁶

The thesis expands upon the work of these scholars by analysing the factors for the genre’s transformation since 2006, highlighting how the gangster-hero’s transformation into a member of high society parallels increasing rates of both corruption and inequality in Korean society.

⁶ A *chaebol* is a large Korean family-owned conglomerate.

The lack of scholarly writing on the Korean gangster genre is likely due to a broader dearth of scholarship on Korean genre cinema. As Yuhee Park (2019, pp.108-109) notes, “full-fledged debate on [Korean] genre films” only began to take place in the 2010s. English-language Korean film scholarship is also rather recent. Writing in 2003, Eungjin Min, Jinsook Joo and Han Ju Kwak (2003, p.1) remarked that “[d]espite a rise in the global market and recent political progress, Korea is still an understudied country. From misinformed stereotypes to outdated information, Korea has been treated as an addendum to China or Japan.” Although significant research has been produced on Korean cinema since Min et al. (2003) made this statement, Lee, S. (2019, p.11) claims that the extant scholarship has not yet discussed many aspects of Korean cinema and tends to focus on a few “canonised” films.

The lack of writing on the Korean gangster genre might also be attributed to the American-centric nature of English-language Film Genre Studies, a fact acknowledged by most preeminent genre theorists.⁷ As Barry Langford (2005, p.x) notes, “genre studies have historically been dominated by analysis of the major Hollywood genres.” Steve Neale (2000, p.7) makes a similar point, arguing that “most of the writing on genre and genres in the cinema has focused on the commercial feature film and Hollywood.” In addition, Barry Keith Grant (2012, p.xxii) states that “genre criticism has concentrated on (mainstream) American cinema.”

The American-centric nature of Genre Studies is particularly relevant to the thesis’s discussion of Korean gangster cinema, as critical discourse has often linked the gangster genre to America. Law Wing-sang (2008, p.523) states that discourse on the gangster genre generally suggests “that within the global screenscape [sic], the gangster genre is American territory proper.” Law’s point (2008, p.523) is evidenced by Langford’s (2005, p.147) statement that while “indigenous variants of the gangster genre” have emerged in different

⁷ From this point onwards, the term ‘Genre Studies’ is used in place of ‘Film Genre Studies’.

nations, “[f]ew...have used the figure of the gangster himself in the culturally and socially paradigmatic manner of his American incarnation.” Similarly, Grant (2007, p.105) suggests that while national iterations of genres, including the gangster genre, address concerns specific to their nation, they “depend on their generic American predecessors for their meaning.”

To avoid furthering the American-centric nature of Genre Studies, the thesis solely draws on research that focuses on Korea.⁸ Accordingly, the thesis does not draw on research on American gangster cinema or other national gangster cinemas to examine the Korean gangster genre. This decision stems from the belief that relying on research that examines other national gangster cinemas would fail to account for the unique historical and cultural influences that have shaped the Korean gangster genre. As Nancy Abelmann and Kathleen McHugh (2005, p.3) remark, “Western critical understandings of...genre cannot be lifted wholesale and imposed on other cinemas.” Indeed, Daniel Martin (2015, p.127) notes that many Western critics malign or ignore aspects of Korean films that challenge Western conceptions of genre.

Two major motivations of this thesis are to address the lack of research on Korean gangster cinema and to offset the American-centric nature of Genre Studies. Indeed, it is important to emphasise that the thesis is the first English-language text to examine pre-1990s Korean gangster cinema. In addition, the thesis examines Korean gangster cinema more extensively than any other existing English-language text. Although authors such as Jinhee Choi (2016; 2010a; 2010b), Graham Neil Gillespie (2016) and Mark R. Plaice (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c) comment on the genre’s development, they do not *chart* it. Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c) also focus on specific aspects of the gangster genre. Gillespie (2016) examines how neoliberal ideology has changed the gangster genre in recent

⁸ There is only one exception: Pate’s (2016) PhD thesis on Hollywood and Japanese gangster cinema. Even then, this thesis solely refers to Pate’s (2016) work as it pertains to the concept of the gangster-hero.

years, and only examines one film, *New World*. Although Plaice (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c) attends to numerous aspects of the gangster genre, he mainly examines the genre's settings and its history of genre-bending.

This is not meant as a criticism of these scholars, but rather as an illustration of the thesis's contributions. Attempting to examine the genre's entire development allows the thesis to contextualise each period of the genre by comparing it with preceding and succeeding periods. Examining the genre's entire development also allows the thesis to better examine the underlying processes influencing said development. This is especially important due to the unique nature of the genre's development, which, as noted earlier in this chapter, appears to have been marked by several shifts rather than gradual evolution. The importance of examining the genre's development is evidenced by the many scholars, such as Utin (2016, p.49) and Yecies and Shim (2016, p.210), who highlight the tendency of Korean filmmakers to 'bend' genres.

The thesis also contributes to the fields of Genre Studies and Korean Film Studies by combining Rick Altman's (1984, p.10) semantic/syntactic approach, which suggests that genre development stems from semantic and/or syntactic change, with Neale's (2000, p.201) hypothesis that genres and defining elements within genres are constantly reshuffled. Combining these two approaches allows the thesis to more thoroughly examine the Korean gangster genre. Indeed, genre theorist Leger Grindon (2007, p.406) notes that whereas Altman's (1984) approach highlights stability, Neale's (2000) approach highlights change.⁹

The use of Pate's (2016) gangster-hero definition to define the gangster genre also represents a unique theoretical contribution. Although certain scholars may disagree with the decision to restrict the definition of a gangster film to 'a film that features a gangster protagonist', this decision builds on two extant approaches to categorisation: Lakoff's (1987)

⁹ This citation is from Grindon's (2012) article as it appears in Grant's (2012) edited book *Film Genre Reader IV*, but the article was originally published in 2011.

prototype concept and Ludwig Wittgenstein's (1958) family resemblances concept. The use of the gangster-hero to define the gangster genre is also based on the unique nomenclature of the gangster genre, which, as noted previously in this chapter, is based on a character rather than a concept.

The thesis also contributes to extant research by using criminological research to enrich its discussion of Korean gangster cinema.¹⁰ Although this may seem a minor contribution, it advances discussion of the gangster genre by emphasising that it is grounded in and often reflective of real-world phenomena.

In addition to examining organised crime in Korea, the thesis examines a wide range of topics while charting the development of the Korean gangster genre. In terms of external social influences, the thesis highlights events such as Park Chung-hee's 1961 coup, the Park administration's turn to "full-fledged authoritarianism" in 1972 (Porteux 2013, p.99), the IMF Crisis – in which the International Monetary Fund (IMF) restructured Korea's economy following an economic crash in 1997 (Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.124) – and the worsening of social inequality and corruption in the late-2000s and 2010s. The thesis also examines topics specific to the Korean film industry, including government censorship in the 1960s, the adverse effects of the film import quota system in the 1970s, the rise of a new generation of filmmakers during New Korean Cinema, and the increasing prevalence of genre-mixing in the late 2000s and 2010s.

1.3: An Overview of The Thesis's Structure, Chapters and Questions

The Literature Review explores many of these socio-cultural topics when considering literature that examines the history of Korean cinema. However, before doing so, the Literature Review provides an overview of the field of Genre Studies. It details the most

¹⁰ Although De Caires et al. (2012) refer to criminological research when discussing Korean gangster cinema, they use the genre's films to understand criminological research rather than use criminological research to understand the genre's films. This is likely because De Caires et al. (2012) are criminologists, not film scholars.

common approaches that film genre scholars have used to study genre, discusses extant opinions on genre hybridity and classification, and reviews literature focused on Korean genre filmmaking. Additionally, the Literature Review addresses existing literature on Korean gangster cinema, identifying important gaps in academic knowledge, such as the lack of studies on the genre's development, the lack of work focused on the gangster character and the lack of work that examines pre-1990 and post-2006 gangster films.

The next chapter, Chapter III: Methodology, begins by outlining the thesis's approach to genre development, which is based upon three frameworks: Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach, Neale's (2000) approach to genre development, and Grindon's (2007, p.409) categories of historical influences: external social influences, film industry factors and internal genre changes. The chapter then establishes the thesis's *a priori* definition of the gangster genre, which is based on Pate's (2016) 'gangster-hero' concept, before describing how it uses the *a priori* definition to compile a corpus of films selected from extant literature, online discourse and the Korean Movie Database, or KMDb.

Although Chapters IV and V both focus on the Pre-Revival Era, they discuss different periods of it. Chapter IV focuses on films made during the Golden Age and begins by addressing the dearth of research on Korean gangster films made during this time. Due to this dearth of research, the chapter does not examine *how* the gangster genre developed in the postwar period but rather whether it emerged at all. Accordingly, the chapter's central research question is: '*Considering the thesis's definition of a gangster film, did the gangster genre emerge during the Golden Age?*' To answer this question, the chapter examines how President Park Chung-hee's efforts to eradicate organised crime impacted real-world gangsters and their cinematic depiction.

In doing so, the chapter finds that the genre's earliest gangster-heroes are more akin to hoodlums than criminals – violent, troublesome and young, they are often lower class, engaging in criminal activities out of necessity or delinquency rather than for professional

or selfish reasons.¹¹ In fact, the strict censorship of the postwar period seems to have inhibited depictions of crime and violence, hindering the genre's development. The genre's development during this time seems to have also been influenced by the most popular genre of the time, melodrama.

Whereas Chapter IV examines films made during the Golden Age, Chapter V examines films made during the Dark Age. Due to a lack of films available to study, the chapter only discusses one film, *Cruel History of Myeong Dong* (*Myeongdongjanhogs*, Byun, Im and Choe 1972). Accordingly, Chapter V avoids making new statements regarding the state of Korean gangster cinema during this time. Instead, the chapter builds upon Choi's (2010b, p.48) assertion that the genre declined during the Dark Age due to censorship. The chapter also examines how censorship and policies such as the film import policy adversely affected the genre's development. Specifically, the chapter asks, '*How did government interference and censorship impact the gangster genre's development during the Dark Age?*' Ultimately, the chapter finds that the government's restrictive policies prevented filmmakers from making meaningful gangster films, turning the genre into a form of propagandistic action cinema, with gangster-heroes transforming into indistinct action heroes.

Chapter VI: The Young, The Poor and The Dangerous examines gangster cinema during the Revival Era, when the genre resurfaced to significant success following a prolonged absence during the 1980s. The chapter asks: '*What elements define the Revival Era?*' and ii) '*What socio-cultural, industrial or generic factors influenced the genre's revival?*'

¹¹ The decision to use the word 'hoodlum' throughout the thesis stems from the word's association with less professional criminals who may, but do not necessarily, belong to a gang. For example, Merriam-Webster (2025) and Britannica (2025) define 'hoodlum' as a "violent criminal", yet Cambridge (2025) and Collins (2025) state that 'hoodlum' describes a violent *person*, "especially" if they are part of a gang. The fact that the term is only partially associated with gangs makes it a better descriptor of the Pre-Revival Korean gangster-hero, whose status as a gangster is sometimes negligible or debatable. Furthermore, the fact that 'hoodlum' is a slightly more old-fashioned term makes it a more apt descriptor of Korea's earliest onscreen gangsters.

The thesis examines several aspects of the Revival Era, including its unique use of the high school setting, its young protagonists, its emphasis on social inequality, the gangster-hero's inability to reconcile their identity as an individual with their identity as a gangster, and the thematic meaning of the genre's violence.

Overall, the chapter finds that the gangster genre's resurgence seems to have been catalysed by the IMF Crisis, with several gangster films directly reflecting socio-cultural issues exacerbated by this profound societal crisis. A new generation of directors, the elimination of censorship and the popularity of Hong Kong gangster films seem to have also contributed to the genre's resurgence.

The final findings chapter, Chapter VII: Business Class, is rooted in conflicting statements regarding the gangster genre's development since the end of New Korean Cinema, with Choi (2010b, p.53) stating that the genre was "followed and/or replaced by crime-thrillers" and scholars Kim (2019), Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c), suggesting that the genre diversified and changed. Accordingly, the chapter asks, *'Has the Korean gangster genre, as Choi (2016, p.231; 2010, p.53) suggests, been followed or replaced by crime thrillers, or has it, as Plaice (2020, p.3; 2019b), Kim (2019, p.518) and Gillespie (2016, p.70) infer, diversified and expanded?'* The chapter also asks, *'Has the genre diversified enough to create a new, divergent genre?'*

To answer these questions, the chapter identifies differences between the Revival Era gangster-hero and the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero, highlighting the latter's improved social status and higher rank. In doing so, Chapter VII finds that the Post-Revival Era primarily focuses on powerful, businesslike gangs. No longer relegated to the shadows, Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes are increasingly indistinguishable from the politicians and businessmen they now interact with, a change that denigrates Korea's social elite.

The chapter finds that the reconfiguration of the gangster-hero seems to have been influenced by worsening social inequality and corruption, mainly caused by neoliberal

policies implemented during the IMF Crisis. Instead of directly highlighting social inequality as they did during New Korean Cinema, filmmakers used the gangster genre to criticise those the Korean public believes are responsible for these issues: the upper class. Extensive genre-bending seems to have also influenced the genre's development, leading to its frequent combination with the noir, thriller, romance and family drama genres.

The thesis's final chapter, Chapter VIII: Conclusion, synthesises the most important insights from Chapters IV to VII to make several statements regarding the development of Korean gangster cinema. It establishes that the genre *did* exist before the Revival Era but was stifled by government censorship, that Revival Era gangster films share certain similarities with Pre-Revival Era gangster films, and finally, that the Korean gangster genre has developed so significantly in the last two decades that much of English-language literature on the genre is now outdated.

Chapter II: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The Literature Review engages with the two main areas of study relevant to the thesis: Genre Studies and Korean Film Studies, both of which are relatively new fields marked by frequent debate and notable research gaps.

For example, Genre Studies is characterised by differing approaches to defining, examining and charting the development of genres. Rick Altman (1999, p.14) underscores the complexity of genre, noting that it “is not our average descriptive term, but a complex concept with multiple meanings.” The many approaches scholars have taken when studying genre, namely the ritual, ideological and iconographic approaches, are discussed in section 2.2 No Wrong Answers. This section highlights Altman’s semantic/syntactic approach, which is also discussed with respect to genre development in section 2.3, The Process. Other topics discussed in section 2.3 include genre hybridity and genre classification. Similar topics are explored in section 2.4 Overlooked, specifically within the context of Korean Genre Studies. Topics of unique relevance to Korean Genre Studies, such as the importance of melodrama and genre-bending, are also discussed in this section.

English-language writing on Korean Cinema is discussed further in section 2.5 Influences and Determinants, which examines the history of the Korean film industry and refers to specific socio-cultural topics that contextualise its development. Although much has been written on topics such as the nation’s auteurs and the genre’s revival during New Korean Cinema, there are many critical research gaps owing to Korean Film Studies being a relatively new field. Writing in 2005, Julian Stringer (2005a, p.1) notes that there is a paucity of critical writing on Korean cinema.

The relatively recent nature of Korean Film Studies is most apparent when considering English-language literature on the Korean gangster genre, as discussed in

section 2.6 The Missing Genre. Indeed, there are several notable research gaps in extant literature: a lack of writing on the genre's development, a lack of work focused on the gangster character and a lack of work that considers the genre's reflection of real-life organised crime. Overall, most texts only tangentially discuss the genre or focus solely on gangster films made between the late 1990s and mid-2000s.

2.2 No Wrong Answers: Differing Approaches to Genre Analysis

Grant (2012, p.xvii) states that despite the “central place of genre in the cinema, critical recognition of its importance is a relatively recent development.” The relatively recent nature of Film Genre Studies may explain why there are many conflicting approaches to interpreting and examining genres.

Genre theorist Sarah Berry-Flint (2004, p.29) notes that early genre criticism often approached genre as ‘myth’, relating genre successes and declines to socio-cultural changes and the whim of audiences. Neale (2000, p.208) states that many scholars, regardless of their approach to genre, argue that “genres are important sociocultural phenomena and...perform important sociocultural functions.” However, Neale (2000, p.208) notes that the mythological approach described by Berry-Flint (2004, p.29) – or the ritual approach, as she and genre theorist Altman (1984, p.9) refer to it – posits that genres are *dictated* by culture, with genres being dependent on audience responses. Indeed, although many theorists invoke ritualistic ideas, the ritual approach suggests that “generic change relies on the degree to which commercial film genres reflect the collective sensibilities of a mass audience” (Berry-Flint 2004, p.29).

Scholars such as Berry-Flint (2004), Neale (2000), and Langford (2005) have criticised the ritual approach. Berry-Flint (2004, p.35) criticises the approach because it assumes the film industry is unaffected by hegemonic markets or anti-competitive distribution systems. Similarly, Langford (2005, p.19) criticises the approach's suggestion

that the audience is a “homogenous and largely notional presence.” Although Altman (1984, p.9) credits the ritual approach for recording how audiences engage with genre films, he also critiques the suggestion that audiences dictate a genre’s development.

Neale (2000, pp.210-214) is particularly critical of the ritual approach. Besides describing the same issues discussed by Berry-Flint (2004), Langford (2005) and Altman (1984), Neale (2000, pp.210-214) criticises the limited range of genres considered by genre theorist Thomas Schatz (1981), who subscribes to the ritual approach in his book *Hollywood Genres*. Specifically, Neale (2000, p.211) challenges Schatz’s (1981) suggestion that socio-cultural issues can be divided amongst genres. Here, Neale (2000, p.211) is referring to Schatz’s (1981, pp.27-28) efforts to divide Hollywood genres into specific categories: genres of determinate space (westerns, gangster films and detective films), which celebrate social order, and genres of indeterminate space (musicals, comedies and melodramas), which celebrate social integration. In addition, Neale (2000, p.211) argues that while a genre’s sustained success might be an index of approval, there is no reason to assume its success is due to its ideological content.

While the ritual approach attributes ultimate authorship to the audience, the ideological approach posits that Hollywood is manipulating the ideological beliefs of audiences. As Altman (1984, p.9) notes, the ideological approach claims that Hollywood exploits the audience’s investment in a film to convince them of specific ideological positions. Inherently, the ideological approach suggests that genres are a form of social control (Grindon 2012, p.48).

Although Neale (2000, p.215) acknowledges that Hollywood’s influence on society is an important topic, he argues that the ideological approach and other approaches which draw on it are “[f]unctionalist, reductive,...profoundly pessimistic [and]...more or less immune to empirical argument, political nuance, and the actualities of socio-cultural change.” Langford (2005, p.21) also criticises the ideological approach, highlighting its

inability to reconcile differing genre interpretations and its failure to explain why a controlled genre system would change over time. Grindon (2012, p.49) highlights the overly simplistic nature of both the ritual and ideological approaches, noting that they mistakenly suggest that genres are tied to a “fixed constellation of values.”

Aside from the ritual and ideological approaches – which Neale (2000, p.208) refers to as socio-cultural theories – there are also approaches based on the aesthetic characteristics of genres. Neale (2000, p.195) notes that these “aesthetic theories” examine the repetition, variation and complexity of specific elements. Although Neale (2000, p.195) does not specify what these “elements” are, he is likely referring to what Grindon (2012, p.44) calls a genre’s “conventions”, namely its plots, characters and settings. Indeed, Neale (2000, pp.195-201) mentions plot, characters and settings while discussing aesthetic theories.

Although the terms ‘elements’ and ‘conventions’ are often used interchangeably, Grant (2007, pp.9-21) uses ‘elements’ as an umbrella term to refer to conventions (“frequently-used stylistic techniques or narrative devices”), iconography, settings, stories and themes, characters, actors and stars and viewers and audiences.

While Grant (2007, pp.9-21) subdivides a genre’s elements into categories, most scholars do not. However, there are exceptions. Genre theorist Daniel Chandler (1997, p.13) notes that most film scholars discuss a genre’s narrative, characterisation (characters), themes, setting and iconography. Schatz’s (1981, pp.22-25) list of elements differs: iconography, character and setting, plot structure, and narrative strategy and social function. Genre theorist Douglas Pye’s (2012, p.241) list of elements differs again: plot, “other structural features”, characters, time and space (setting), iconography and themes.¹²

As these lists highlight, scholars have yet to reach a consensus on the fundamental elements of a genre. There also seems to be a specific issue with the definition of the term

¹² This citation is from Pye’s (2012) article as it appears in Grant’s (2012) edited book *Film Genre Reader IV*. The article was originally published in 2003.

'iconography'. Although Chandler (1997, p.13), Schatz (1981, pp.22-25) and Pye (2012, p.242) distinguish between characters and iconography, Grant (2007, p.12) asserts that characters are *part* of a genre's iconography. In addition, although Grant (2007, pp.10-12) classifies a film's mise-en-scène as part of a genre's conventions, he notes that it may also be part of a genre's iconography. The definition of iconography is also obfuscated by the fact that some theorists use the term without defining it (Neale 2012, p.181; Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.25; Min et al. 2003, p.174).

Further complicating the definition of iconography is the fact that the term 'iconographic analysis' is used by certain scholars, such as Berry-Flint (2004, p.32) and Neale (2000, p.14), to refer to a form of genre analysis rather than the act of analysing a genre's iconography. As with the ritual and ideological approaches, iconographic analysis has been subject to critique. Neale (2000, p.14) argues that it fails to account for the many genres that lack a specific iconography, such as the biopic and romantic drama, and Langford (2005, p.14) states that iconographic analysis fails to account for visual elements such as camera movement and editing. According to Neale (2000, p.14), the limitations of iconographic analysis led some scholars to develop alternative ideas of examining genre definition, genre identification, and the overall purpose of genre theory.

One such idea is Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach. Unlike the approaches discussed above, Altman's (1984, p.10) approach examines a genre using its semantic characteristics – "building blocks" such as props, characters, locations and sets – and a genre's syntax – structures which bind the blocks together, such as narrative, direction, lighting and themes. Accordingly, Altman's (1984, p.9) approach combines the ritual and ideological approaches with iconographic analysis. Indeed, Berry-Flint (2004, p.35) notes that Altman's (1984) approach combines iconographic and interpretive definitions of genre. Inherently, "whereas semantic elements derive their meanings from pre-existing social

codes, generic syntax is more specific...and thus more fully expresses the meaning(s) of a given genre” (Langford 2005, p.16).

As Flint (2004, p.35) details, the semantic/syntactic approach allows scholars to interpret genre in nuanced ways, allowing them to analyse films that combine semantic elements of one genre with the syntax of a different genre. In Altman’s (1984, p.12) opinion, the approach also allows scholars to examine how films are individually linked to a genre, and to more accurately describe “inter-generic connections.” Overall, Altman (1984, p.13) stresses that by simultaneously examining a genre’s semantics and syntax, scholars are less likely to incorrectly classify films and are better able to describe films which feature elements from various genres.

Many scholars have noted the merits of the semantic/syntactic approach. Langford (2005, p.16) states that it usefully combines the ritual and ideological approaches, and Neale (2000, p.203) argues that it possesses “considerable heuristic value.” The approach is validated by its use throughout Film Studies. Hye Seung Chung and David Scott Diffrient (2015, p.96) use it to examine the Korean Manchurian Western, and Simon Pate (2016, p.36) uses it to examine Japanese and American gangster films. The semantic/syntactic approach is also used by Mark Plaice (2019c), a Korean film scholar who examines the transformation of 1990s Korean gangster cinema.¹³

However, Altman’s (1984) approach is not without its flaws. Neale (2000, p.204) highlights that Altman (1984) uses a narrow range of genres to illustrate his approach. There is also the issue of ascertaining what exactly comprises a semantic or syntactic element. As Langford (2005, pp.16-17) notes, the approach fails to account for semantic elements with syntactic value. For example, Neale (2000, p.204) suggests that while the shootout in a

¹³ Aside from his use of the semantic/syntactic approach, Plaice’s (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c) work shares various similarities with this thesis: it focuses on the genre’s development, examines the changing representation of the gangster character and highlights the influence of genre-bending. Despite these similarities, Plaice (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c) mainly focuses on the iconographic development of the gangster genre. In addition, Plaice (ibid.) only examines the genre from the 1990s onwards.

western is technically a semantic element that lacks any meaning of its own, it may also be syntactically meaningful; if a shootout is a central part of a western narrative, is it not therefore entwined with the film's syntax?

The issue of differentiating between semantic and syntactic elements is exacerbated by the lack of definitions for both terms. Rather than strictly defining either term, Altman (1984, p.10) merely suggests that semantics include "a list of common traits, attitudes, characters, shots, locations, sets, and the like", and that a genre's syntax is the "constitutive relationships between undesignated and variable placeholders." Accordingly, Altman's (1984) approach further suggests that genre theorists have been unable to reach a consensus regarding the fundamental elements of genre.

However, one could argue that the lack of consensus indicates that a genre's fundamental elements are subject to interpretation. As Langford's (2005, pp.16-17) and Neale's (2000, p.204) critiques of the semantic/syntactic approach highlight, a genre's seemingly most basic elements can sometimes be its most complex. Grindon (2012, p.49) echoes this point, arguing that a genre's conventions "function more like a vocabulary...whose meaning may shift from cycle to cycle or film to film."

Writing many years after he devised the semantic/syntactic approach, Altman (1999, p.207) acknowledged that it under-emphasised the fact that "genres look different to different audiences, and that disparate viewers may perceive quite disparate semantic and syntactic elements in the same film." However, despite his acknowledgement that "genres may have multiple conflicting audiences", Altman (1999, p.208) does not consider how a genre might be viewed or defined in different countries or by different cultures.

This issue is not specific to Altman (1984). Langford (2005, p.x) notes that "genre studies has historically been dominated by analysis of the major Hollywood genres." Similarly, Neale (2000, p.7) states that "most of the writing on genre and genres in the cinema has focused on the commercial feature film and Hollywood." Grant (2012, p.xxii)

states that “genre criticism has concentrated on (mainstream) American cinema”, admitting that most of the essays collected in his edited book, *Film Genre Reader IV*, “are no exception.”

To their credit, Langford (2005), Neale (2000) and Grant (2012) are some of the only genre theorists who explicitly acknowledge the American-centric nature of Film Genre Studies. Even so, they do not make a concerted effort to remedy the issue. Although Langford (2005) briefly examines differing national interpretations of certain genres, his book, *Film Genre: Hollywood and Beyond*, mainly focuses on genre within an American context.

Still, Langford (2005) does more than Neale (2000; 2012) and Grant (2012), who justify their focus on American genre cinema rather than remedying it. Grant (2012, p.xxii) justifies his focus on American genre cinema by stating that much of the work in his edited book tackles questions with relevance beyond the Hollywood context. In addition, Grant (ibid.) states that “all national cinemas have been influenced to some degree by American genre movies.” Although logical, Grant’s (2012, p.xxii) reasoning is undercut by the fact that he highlighted the American-centric nature of Genre Studies five years before the publication of *Film Genre Reader IV*. Writing in 2007, Grant (2007, pp.107-108) stated that significant work remained to be undertaken on non-English genres. Grant (2007, p.107) also referred to genre theorist Alan Williams’s (1984, p.124) contention that genre “is not exclusively or even primarily a Hollywood phenomenon” and that, therefore, genre theorists need “to get out of the United States.”

Although Neale (2012, p.178) also refers to Williams’s (1984, p.124) point about the American-centric nature of Genre Studies, he chooses to focus on Hollywood genre cinema due to “the enormous amount of research to be done on what is the most powerful

national cinema in the world” and “partly because most of the work published on genre to date has tended to overwhelmingly concern itself with Hollywood.”¹⁴

The latter point is problematic as it equates a *volume* of research with *importance*. Accordingly, Neale (2012, p.178) appears to argue that theorists should only study the *most* studied topics in a specific field. Considering the hegemonic nature of American cinema, as noted by many scholars (Jin 2020, p.51; Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.26; Berry-Flint 2004, p.39; Min et al. 2003, p.149; Schatz 1981, p.6), it seems pertinent to do the opposite.

Of course, Neale (2000; 2012), Grant (2012; 2007), and Langford (2005) are accomplished, renowned scholars in the field of Genre Studies. Although each scholar’s decision to confine their area of interest to Hollywood genres is questionable, their respective reputations are nonetheless merited.

2.3 The Process: Debating Genre Development, Hybridity and Classification

Although there is much debate about *how* to approach genre analysis, there is significant consensus regarding the *nature* of genres, with most scholars agreeing that they are processes. Indeed, Neale (2000, p.204) states that many theorists argue that genres are best considered as processes, Langford (2005, p.5, italics in original) notes that “genre is a *process* rather than a fact”, and Grant (2007, p.34) states that “genres are neither static nor fixed...genres are processes that are ongoing.” In addition, genre theorist Chandler (1997, p.3) notes that while genres were traditionally regarded as “fixed forms”, contemporary theory now “emphasises that both their forms and functions are dynamic.”

Although most scholars agree that genres are processes, there are differing conceptions of these processes. Building upon his popular semantic/syntactic approach to genre analysis, Altman (1984, p.12) suggests that genres develop in one of two ways: “a

¹⁴ This citation is from Neale’s (2012) article as it appears in Grant’s (2012) edited book *Film Genre Reader IV*, but the article was originally published in 1990.

relatively stable set of semantics...is developed through syntactic experimentation into a coherent and durable syntax, or an already existing syntax adopts a new set of semantic elements.” Inherently, Altman (1984) suggests that a genre develops either due to shifts in its syntax or semantics.

Neale (2000, p.201) subscribes to a different conception of genre development, arguing that any conception of genre development should place genres within “wider generic and aesthetic” contexts, recognise that genre development is “a process of contestation and change” and emphasise “the role of hybridisation in the formation and dissolution of genres.”

Grindon (2007, p.405) surmises that Neale’s (2000, p.201) approach builds on the idea that a genre’s dominant and subordinate elements are constantly reshuffled, with certain elements characterising the genre for a certain period, only to diminish as the genre evolves. Grindon (2007, p.406) notes that whereas Altman’s (1984) model highlights stability, Neale’s (2000) model highlights change. Accordingly, Grindon (2007, p.406) argues that each model has distinct weaknesses: Neale’s (2000) “offers a rather simplistic recognition of endlessly shifting elements [and Altman’s (1984)]...suffers from an unclear boundary between the semantic and syntactic qualities of a genre.” Nevertheless, Grindon (2007, p.406) acknowledges that both models offer “flexible concepts for charting a film’s genre history.”

A lack of flexibility is the very reason why many scholars have criticised Schatz’s (1981, p.38) conception of genre development. Based on the ritual approach to genre analysis, Schatz (1981, p.38) argues that genre development is a phased process in which a genre attempts to explain, address and evaluate itself by progressing from “straightforward storytelling to self-conscious formalism” through a series of stages.

Since Schatz’s (1981) work is based on the much-criticised ritual approach, it is not surprising that scholars also criticise his conception of genre development. Although

Langford (2005, p.24) acknowledges that Schatz's (1981) conception of genre development is "appealingly straightforward", he argues that it "smacks of special pleading – seemingly designed to justify the critical attention already bestowed on certain groups and periods of genre film."

Williams (1984, p.123) takes issue with Schatz's (1981) suggestion that genre development is motivated by internal changes within a genre rather than changes in the film industry or the socio-cultural context. Langford (2005, p.25) makes a similar point, noting that Schatz (1981) puts too much emphasis on intra-generic factors of change and implies that genres are removed from industrial, social and cultural contexts. Neale (2000, p. 200) echoes this point, criticising Schatz's (1981) argument that socio-cultural or historic determinants only influence a genre until it has refined *itself* into a formula. Neale (2000, p.201) argues that socio-cultural and historical determinants influence a genre continuously and can be "detected even where genres...are at their most self-consciously self-referential."

As these criticisms highlight, scholars are particularly critical of Schatz's (1981) suggestion that socio-cultural and historical events do not influence genre development. This is not to say that a genre's internal changes are unimportant, only that Schatz's (1981) failure to acknowledge the influence of culture and history is problematic. As genre theorist Celestino Deleyto (2012, p.228) argues, "the history of genres, while dependent on...internal evolution, is also closely linked to social and cultural history."

Overall, Schatz (1981) is one of the few genre theorists who does not fully acknowledge the influence of culture and history on a genre's development. As Grindon (2012, p.52) notes, most film genre scholars agree that a genre's development arises from both "the surrounding culture and shifting internal elements [within a genre]." Langford (2005, p.18) notes that there is general agreement that genres are affected by changing socio-cultural issues, and Berry-Flint (2004, p.41) states that genres reflect "specific social formations." Grindon (2012, p.53) is more specific, suggesting that four main external

factors influence genre development: “commercial success, industrial compatibility, supporting cultural phenomena, and sociopolitical events.”

Grindon’s (ibid.) mention of commercial success and industrial compatibility highlights that a genre’s development depends on both culture and the film industry. Indeed, Kristof Van den Troost (2020, p.194) and Grindon (2012, p.54; 2007, p.407) suggest that censorship might even influence a genre’s identity. Even so, Van den Troost (2020, p.194) notes that there has been a lack of work considering the link between genre and censorship, suggesting that there are aspects of genre development that scholars have not yet discussed.

One aspect of genre development that scholars *have* discussed is genre-mixing, or as some refer to it, genre hybridity. Grindon (2007, p.406) states that “genre mixing has come to be understood as [another]...key catalyst for [genre] development”. Berry-Flint (2004, p.39) states that hybridity is a staple of genre, and Deleyto (2012, p.228) argues that genre mixing is inherent to genre. On a similar note, genre theorist Janet Staiger (2012, p.203) suggests that genres have never been pure, but have instead always been hybrid combinations of differing genre elements.¹⁵

If we are to assume no genre is ‘pure’, matters of classification or ‘genre taxonomy’ become rather complex. Indeed, Chandler (1997, p.1) notes that the “classification and hierarchical taxonomy of genres is not a neutral and ‘objective’ procedure.” Continuing this point, Chandler (ibid.) notes that there is significant disagreement amongst scholars regarding the definitions of specific genres. Chandler (1997, p.2) notes that many theorists have taken to describing genres in terms of ‘family resemblances’, a concept of Wittgenstein’s (1958) which describes how a series of characteristics rather than a strict set of traits dictate categorical membership. Grindon (2012, p.43) states that the family resemblances concept allows a film to be classified as a particular genre even if the film only

¹⁵ Although Staiger’s (2012) article was originally published in 1997, this citation is from the article as it appears in Grant’s (2012) edited book *Film Genre Reader IV*.

features a few of that genre's traits. Grindon (2012, pp.42-43) notes that the concept also "helps explain how a genre can establish identifying qualities...while being open to variation."

Grindon (2012, pp.42-43) makes the same point about Lakoff's (1987) prototype concept, which suggests that categories consist of prototypical works – agreed-upon and well-defined works – and marginal or lesser-known works.¹⁶ Chandler (1997, p.2) more succinctly states that the prototype concept suggests that "some texts would be widely regarded as being more typical members of a genre than others."

Grindon (2012, p.57) argues that both the prototype concept and the family resemblances idea "allow for continuity and flexibility in the selection of a body of films." However, Chandler (1997, p.2) makes an alternative point, suggesting that such ideas can make any text seem to resemble another text. Literary genre theorist David Fishelov (1991, p.125) shares Chandler's (1997, p.2) reservations about the family resemblances idea, believing it goes too far in implying the openness of genres. Fishelov's (1991, p.130) critique does not target the concept itself, however, but its use by genre theorists who misunderstand Wittgenstein's (1958) original idea.

...advocates of the family resemblance approach tend to create new problems and inconsistencies. These problems seem to stem from their radical, reductive, interpretations of Wittgenstein's concept. Instead of demonstrating the rich network of relations that does exist between members of a 'literary family', they have chosen to isolate the 'negative' aspect of the family resemblance, namely, the statement that there is no single trait shared by all members. This reductive-radical commitment has led them to unrealistic and unconvincing claims about specific genres as well as to certain inconsistencies in argumentation. (Fishelov 1991, p.130).

Although Fishelov (1991, p.136) does not deny the importance of the family resemblances idea, he suggests that theorists need a more balanced approach to the issue of genre definition that neither confines genre to a set of limited characteristics nor shuns efforts to perceive genres through "prototypical members" and "salient characteristics."

¹⁶ Although Grindon (2012, p.43) states that the "prototype concept is associated with George Lakoff [(1987)]", Lakoff (1987, p.7) credits psychologist Eleanor Rosch (1973) with the concept.

Overall, Deleyto (2012, p.221) notes that a genre's boundaries are never fixed, stating that "at the very most, we can draw a boundary for a special purpose, but that does not ensure that such a boundary will remain in place when our objective changes, or that the boundary drawn by one person will be accepted by another one with a different agenda." As a result, Deleyto (ibid.) suggests that Genre Studies would benefit from genre theorists focusing less on matters of generic purity and more on the "actual workings of generic elements." Nevertheless, Chandler (1997, p.3) suggests that it is possible to acknowledge the "fluidity" of genres without disregarding interpretive frameworks. Indeed, Chandler (1997, p.2) emphasises that the way we define a genre often depends on our purposes.

2.4 Overlooked: The Burgeoning Field of Korean Genre Studies

As noted in section 2.1, the field of Genre Studies has, to use Langford's (2005, p.x) phrase, been "dominated" by analysis of American cinema. Korean genre theorists Chung and Diffrient (2015, pp.116-117) emphasise this point, stating:

Thus far, virtually all major theories of film genre, whether those indebted to Schatz's evolutionary, ritual model; Neale's quest for historically-specific generic regimes; or Altman's linguistically-inspired semantic/syntactic/pragmatic approach, have neglected the question of transnational permutations - the necessarily politicized "poaching" or *détournement* ("hijacking" or "rerouting") of genres once they are mobilized out of Hollywood's dominant industrial models and narrative modes (Chung and Diffrient 2015, pp.116-117).

In addition, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.117) argue that a full understanding of genre "cannot be achieved without looking beyond US borders and examining the...manifestations of a given genre globally." Although Chung and Diffrient's (2015, pp.116-177) statements might seem damning, they are not controversial. As noted in section 2.2, most prominent English-language genre theorists agree that culture and history shape a genre's development. Neale (2000, p.7) even states that genre is "culturally relative".

Nevertheless, except for a few texts, such as Chung and Diffrient's (2015) *Movie Migrations: Transnational Genre Flows and South Korean Cinema*, there are almost no texts on Korean genre cinema as in-depth as those on American genre cinema. Most insights on

Korean genre cinema, at least within English-language academia, stem from broad studies on the Korean film industry or from journal articles examining specific genres, such as Daniel Martin's (2014) work on Korean war films or Chelsea McCracken's (2012) analysis of Korean noir. Examples of research specifically focused on genre itself include Ae-gyung Shim's (2011) examination of genre hybridity in 1960s Korean cinema and Julian Stringer's (2005b) consideration of genre classification with respect to Korean cinema.

The lack of English-language literature on Korean genre cinema is not only due to the American-centric nature of Film Genre Studies, but also due to the recent nature of Korean film genre scholarship. As Park (2019, pp.108-109) notes, discussion of Korean genres only began to take place in the 1990s, and full-fledged discussion only began to take place in the 2010s.¹⁷

The lack of research on Korean genre cinema reflects the recent nature of scholarship on Korean cinema. Lee, S. (2019, p.4) states that no major English-language study of Korean cinema existed before the 1980s. Lee, S. (2019, p.4) elaborates on this point, stating that Korean cinema has "been so consistently marginalised and ghettoized that even its adjacent regional peers overlooked films produced in Korea." In fact, Stringer (2005a, p.2) noted in 2005 that his and Chi-Yun Shin's edited book of essays, *New Korean Cinema*, was only the second English-language volume of academic essays focused on Korean film to appear outside Korea.

Due to the relatively recent development of Korean film scholarship, most scholars seem to have focused on a few key topics. One of the most recurrent topics is melodrama. Park (2019, p.108) notes that some of the first works on Korean genre cinema focused on melodrama, with research on it continuing steadily since. McCracken (2012, p.169) states that discussion of Korean genre cinema also focuses on melodrama. McCracken (2012,

¹⁷ Since Park (2019, pp.108-109) does not specifically refer to English-language scholarship, it seems likely that they are referring to *all* Korean film scholarship, regardless of language. Indeed, one of the texts they cite as being the first example of Korean genre analysis is in Korean.

p.169) and Park (2019, p.108) both attribute the scholarly focus on melodrama to the genre's pivotal status in the history of Korean cinema, with Park (2019, p.108) referring to melodrama as "the most longstanding mainstream genre in Korean film history."

The important role of melodrama is acknowledged by most Korean film scholars. Yau Shuk-ting Kinnia (2007, p.279) argues that melodrama provides a distinct articulation of Korea's traumatic history, and Jin (2020, p.113) states that melodrama has been the dominant genre in Korean cinema since 1945 "due in part to its ability to portray specific qualities of Korean society and people." Although Jin (2020, p.113) does not elaborate on this point, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.22) note that many scholars believe Korean melodrama centres on a unique national sentiment, *han*, which, depending on the context, might be defined as resentment, lamentation, unfulfilled desire or resignation.

Overall, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.23) believe that an overemphasis on *han* has contributed to an ethereal notion of Korea and Korean history. Famed Korean director Im Kwon-taek (2002 cited in Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.23, italics in original) makes a similar point, stating that "[*h*]an is not a concept that [even] Koreans can agree on...and as such, might be a difficult concept for non-Koreans to grasp fully." The cultural specificity of *han* substantiates Neale's (2000, p.7) point that genre is culturally relative. It also challenges Grant's (2007, p.105) statement that national iterations of genres, such as the South Korean melodrama, "depend on their generic American predecessors for their meaning."

Han is not the only culturally specific aspect of Korean melodrama. Chung and Different (2015, p.20) note that while "Eisenhower era" Hollywood melodramas often depicted upper-middle-class society, Korean melodramas of the same period focused on ordinary lower-middle-class and working-class people. Abelmann and McHugh (2005, p.4) note more generally that early Korean melodrama, "with its plot reversals, cataclysmic coincidences, and seismic narrative compressions, seemed uniquely suited to rendering the nation's dramatic history." Although Chung and Diffrient's (2015, p.20) and Abelmann and

McHugh's (2005, p.4) respective statements refer to early Korean melodrama, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.151) state that the genre has remained popular in Korea, with many of its elements remaining unchanged.

The pivotal role of melodrama in the history of Korean cinema is further evidenced by its frequent mention in research focused on other Korean genres. For example, Choi (2010a, p.68) highlights melodramatic traits in the gangster genre, and Martin (2014, p.99) considers Korean melodrama's influence on war films and espionage thrillers. As a result of the genre's prominence, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.142) argue that melodrama is "the key" to understanding Korea's cinematic development.

Hybridisation, or genre-mixing, is another key topic in Korean Genre Studies. Some scholars examine how specific filmmakers have employed genre-mixing. For example, Christina Klein (2008, p.873) details how director Bong Joon-ho reworks genre conventions, using them to critique uniquely Korean socio-cultural issues. Similarly, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.118) examine how director Kim Jee-woon combines the comedy, the martial arts film, the adventure film and the Western film in *The Good, The Bad, and The Weird* (*Joeun nom, nappeun nom, isanghan nom*, Kim 2008).

Other scholars highlight the role of genre-mixing in Korean cinema history. For example, Ae-gyung Shim (2011) examines generic hybridisation during the 1960s, and Yecies and Shim (2016, pp.207-224) examine genre transformations during the 2000s. Shim (2011, p.176) notes that terms such as 'hybridity' and 'genre-bending' frequently appear in both academic and cultural discourse surrounding contemporary Korean cinema.

Although both terms have similar meanings, the latter term, 'genre-bending', seems to have a particular association with Korean cinema. While Utin (2016, p.49) states that genre-bending "is part of a global phenomenon", Yecies and Shim (2016, p.210) note that the term was first used in non-academic discourse in the early 2000s to describe Korean cinema's "creative interweaving of Hollywood genre conventions." In addition, while

multiple Korean film scholars mention the term, Langford (2005, p.277) is the only major genre theorist mentioned in sections 2.2 and 2.3 who uses the term. Even then, he only uses the term a single time.

2.5 Influences and Determinants: The History of Korean Cinema

As noted in section 2.4, no major English-language study of Korean cinema existed before the 1980s (Lee, S. 2019, p.4). Writing in 2003, Eungjin Min, Jinsook Joo and Han Ju Kwak (2003, p.1) remarked that “[d]espite a rise in the global market and recent political progress, Korea is still an understudied country. From misinformed stereotypes to outdated information, Korea has been treated as an addendum to China or Japan.” More specifically, Min et al. (2003, p.1) note that Western studies of Korean culture are “very much in their infancy.”

Although significant research has been produced on Korean culture and Korean cinema since Min et al. (2003) made these statements, Lee, S. (2019, p.11) notes that extant scholarship has not yet discussed many aspects of Korean cinema. Specifically, Lee, S. (2019, p.11) states that Korea’s “rich cinematic heritage has not yet been appropriately treated”, noting that scholarly research on pre-1990s Korean films is rare. In addition, Lee, S. (2019, p.11) claims that scholarship on Korean cinema “has tended to focus on a small number of canonised texts and film festival favourites.” Lee, S. (2019, p.1) also states that “there is...a shortage of essays on individual films and directors.”

Whereas Lee, S. (2019, p.11) suggests that scholars must focus on discussing more and different films, Jin (2020, p.vii) suggests that scholars should focus on “the history of Korean cinema”, stating that Korean film scholars have not sufficiently discussed “the role of the socio-economic milieu surrounding the film industry.”

Lee, S. (2019, p.11) notes, there is a particular lack of work on early Korean cinema. Most work on early Korean cinema is focused on the Golden Age, which Abelmann and

McHugh (2005, p.2) periodise as being between 1955 and 1972. Yecies and Shim's (2016) overview of Korean cinema begins with the Golden Age, as does Paquet's (2005) brief discussion of Korean cinema history. Research on the Golden Age emphasises the role of government interference following the military coup of 1961, when General Park Chung-hee became president. In her PhD thesis, Ae-Gyung Shim (2010) offers a comprehensive overview of the many methods that the Park Chung-hee government used to control the film industry. More specifically, Shim (2010) details how the government used the National Film Production Centre (NFPC) and the Motion Picture Law (MPL) to implement strict censorship, regulate film imports and implement the "Producer Registration System", which, according to Shim (2010, p.26), regulated the number of producers and "controlled their activities (production, importing and exporting)."

In their book, *The Changing Face of Korean Cinema*, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.20) dedicate an entire chapter to the government interference in the film industry during the Golden Age, detailing how "almost overnight, the domestic film industry...was reduced to the status of a propaganda factory." Yecies and Shim (2016, p.99) also discuss how Golden Age filmmakers adapted to government regulations, noting that auteurs "such as Shin Sang-ok, Lee Man-hee, Yu Hyun-mok, and Im Kwon-taek, raised the bar in terms of aesthetic and narrative quality through [genre experimentation]."

As Yecies and Shim's (2016, p.99) statement implies, government interference did not diminish the creative output of Korea's most talented auteurs. Despite extensive government interference, most scholars emphasise that creativity flourished during the Golden Age. McHugh (2001, p.2) notes that the period was characterised by dynamic, engaging films that tackled themes of colonialism, national turmoil, war, systemic poverty, social unrest and Western influence. Shim (2011, p.182) suggests that genre-bending was particularly prevalent during this time, with Korean filmmakers mixing genres to simultaneously appease audiences, the government and provincial exhibitors.

In addition to being creatively successful, Golden Age films were also commercially successful. Yecies and Shim (2016, p.99) state that the 1960s saw a rise in the number of cinemas, viewers, talent and film productions. In fact, Jin (2020, p.18) notes that the number of films made in a year “increased from 15 in 1955, to 111 in 1959, to 229 in 1969.”

However, the Korean film industry’s success did not last. Just before Park Chung-hee’s presidency devolved into “full-fledged authoritarianism” in 1972 (Porteux 2013, p.99), various film statistics peaked in 1969/1970 before plummeting in 1971: the number of films produced fell from 229 in 1969 to 122 in 1972, and annual audience viewership fell from 170 million in 1969 to 75 million in 1975 (Cho 2019, p. 48). Due to the film industry’s decline, many scholars now refer to the 1970s as the “Dark Age” of Korean cinema (Jin 2020, p.119; Lee, S. 2019, p.16; Cho 2019, p.48; Yi 2019, p.79; Yecies and Shim 2016, p.81).

Although some scholars link the industry’s decline to the advent of home television (Cho 2019, p.48; Yecies and Shim 2016, p.145; Min et al. 2003, p.51), most agree that the primary cause was government interference (Jin 2020, p.116; Cho 2019, p.48; Yi 2019, p.79; Yecies and Shim 2016, p.107; Park 2007, p.16; Min et al 2003, p.49). Indeed, Min et al. (2003, p.49) note that “the Korean film industry underwent the most oppressive era of government control” during the 1970s.

Jin (2020, p.19) notes that a revision to the Motion Picture Law (MPL) in 1972 replaced the producer registration system with a permission system, allowing only a few companies to make films. Seung Hyun Park (2007, p.18) states that the MPL was revised again in 1971, allowing the government to implement stricter censorship, reorganise the screen quota system, and implement policies to incentivise the production of propagandistic films. Park (2007, p.18) notes that the revised MPL also allowed the government to create a subsidiary organisation, the Motion Picture Promotion Corporation (MPPC), to regulate the

film industry, manage Korea's national film awards, the Grand Bell Awards, and reward the production of propagandistic films.

Among the government's many oppressive policies and regulations, many scholars highlight the adverse effects of the import quota system. Min et al. (2003, p.50) state that the import quota restricted the number of foreign film imports to one-third of the number of domestic films produced each year. Since foreign films were so popular during the 1970s, Park (2007, p.18) suggests that the import quota system incentivised production companies to make domestic films purely to fulfil import quotas. Accordingly, the quality of Korean films declined severely during the 1970s. Indeed, Min et al. (2003, p.55) note that the 1970s "produced hardly any critically acclaimed films." Similarly, Nohchool Park (2009, p.46) notes that the 1970s "marked a period of low-quality" films.

Although Martin (2014, p.101) emphasises that it would be reductive to state that 1970s Korean cinema is "uninteresting and without artistic depth and merit", most scholars have not attempted to prove otherwise. Although Yecies and Shim (2016, pp.129-134) and Park (2009) celebrate 1970s film movements such as the Visual Age Group and Cultural Centre Generation, neither refutes the otherwise lacklustre state of 1970s Korean cinema. The lack of genuinely artistic films made during the 1970s may explain the lack of scholarship on the Dark Age – Sangjoon Lee (2018, p.140) states that there is an almost total lack of scholarly articles on 1970s Korean cinema.

Lee (2018, p.140) also states that there is a similar lack of scholarly articles on 1980s Korean cinema. Considering that some scholars, such as Lee, S. (2019, p.16) and Park (2007, p.16), believe that the Dark Age continued into the 1980s, it seems logical to assume that the quantity of English-language scholarship correlates with the film industry's success.¹⁸

¹⁸ Since the thesis does not discuss 1980s Korean cinema or any films made during the period, it is irrelevant to discuss it further in the literature review. This was not a deliberate choice – there are simply no 1980s gangster films available to study, and there is a total lack of research on 1980s Korean gangster cinema. The lack of research is discussed more in section 2.4 Overlooked.

Indeed, it seems to be no coincidence that most English-language literature focuses on New Korean Cinema, the industry's most successful period.

Before discussing this period, it is relevant to note that scholarship is divided on the starting point of New Korean Cinema. While some scholars suggest that the preceding cinematic period, the Korean New Wave, existed between the early to mid-1980s, others suggest that it lasted into the 1990s (Stringer 2005a, p.5). Although some scholars, such as Yecies and Shim (2016, p.138) and Francis Gateward (2007, p.5), suggest that the Korean New Wave occurred during the 1980s, Darcy Paquet (2009, p.78) states that it ended in 1996 and Junhyoung Cho (2019, p.55) states that it “faded away” in the mid-1990s. Choi (2010a, p.6) takes a more nuanced stance, stating that while “precise referent of the Korean New Wave shifts from author to author,...it is mostly associated with the directors born in the 1950s.”

Even so, Choi (2010a, p.6, italics in original) is wary of using the terms ‘Korean New Wave’ and ‘New Korean Cinema’ and refers to Korean cinema from the late-1980s onwards as “a second South Korean film *renaissance*.” Conversely, Stringer (2005a, p.6) advocates for the term ‘New Korean Cinema’, listing several elements that differentiate it from the “so-called New Wave of the 1980s.”

These elements include the impressive domestic box-office success of a range of recent home-grown films, together with changes in the availability of production capital and the emergence of concept movies such as the ‘Korean blockbuster’. They also include a generational shift in film-making which has created an industry dominated by young personnel in their twenties and thirties who became film-makers following their formal education in film, rather than through the industrial apprentice system...In addition, these elements encompass a generational shift in audiences (i.e. a domestic audience dominated by younger consumers), as well as the development of a committed film culture...[and] both the short and long-term effects of greater freedom of expression (Stringer 2005a, p.6).

Whether scholars use ‘New Korean Cinema’ or another term to describe it, the period beginning in the 1990s and ending in the mid-2000s is the most researched period of Korean cinema in English-language academia. Indeed, most English-language books on Korean cinema – including Choi’s (2010a) *The South Korean Film Renaissance*, Paquet’s (2009)

New Korean Cinema, and the edited books *Seoul Searching* (Gateward 2007) and *New Korean Cinema* (Shin and Stringer 2005) – focus exclusively on the period.

[During this time]...Korea's film output began to diversify in terms of subject matter, scale and genre. A new generation of directors started creating films that marked a clear break from the past and were popular with young viewers. Soon the New Korean Cinema began to attract attention internationally, both from mainstream audiences in Asia, and from festival attendees and film enthusiasts further afield. An eye-opening renaissance was underway (Paquet 2009, p.3).

Cho (2019, p.60) highlights that New Korean Cinema saw Korean films grow both in quantity and quality. In addition, several of Korea's most renowned directors – including Kim Ki-duk, Lee Chang-dong, Kim Jee-woon, Bong Joon-ho, Park Chan-wook and Ryoo Seung-wan – made their feature debuts during this time (ibid.).

One frequently discussed topic of New Korean Cinema is the entry of the *chaebols*, which Paquet (2009, p.54) describes as large family-owned conglomerates, into the film industry. Although Jin (2020, p.122-123) notes that the *chaebol's* investment in the film sector only lasted between 1990 and 1997, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.159) state that the *chaebol's* investment was pivotal to the film industry's transformation, allowing filmmakers to overcome “the financial hardships [they]...had been experiencing for decades.” In addition, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.159) state that the *chaebols* “effectively retooled the [film] industry by implementing comparatively transparent management and accounting systems, standardized box office tracking procedures, cross-platform marketing campaigns, and planning and internationalization strategies.”

Another frequently discussed topic is the emergence of the Korean blockbuster, large-scale commercial films that Cho (2019, p.60) argues symbolised the newfound “technical and commercial confidence” of Korean cinema. Indeed, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.2) note that the success of *Shiri* (*Swiri*, Kang 1999), which many scholars describe as Korea's first blockbuster (Jin 2020, p.25; Cho 2019, p.58; Kim 2019, p.512; Choi 2010a, p.31), was a pivotal moment for the Korean film industry and Korean cinema.

Aside from the *chaebol* and the Korean blockbuster, many scholars highlight the socio-cultural context surrounding New Korean Cinema. The elimination of censorship in 1996 under Korea's first civilian government is frequently highlighted, with Yecies and Shim (2016, p.2) stating that it made conditions “ripe for the production and exhibition of an increasing number of domestic films.”

New spaces for freedom of expression—held shut by decades of military dictatorship, preceded by three years of US military rule and 35 years of Japanese colonial rule—began to open...After censorship was lifted, a small army of creative and cultural practitioners immediately set about developing one of the world's fastest-growing film industries. Filmmakers began telling new and arresting stories that quickly gained a following at international film festivals (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.2).

The most frequently mentioned contextual topic in English-language discussion of Korean cinema is the 1997 Asian Financial Crisis and subsequent ‘IMF Crisis’, during which the Korean government availed of a \$57 billion bailout from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) that led to “fundamental reforms [mandated by the IMF] of the Korean economy and a contractionary economic policy of increased taxes, reduced government spending, and high interest rates” (Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.124).

These reforms incurred far-reaching social problems. Sociologist Park Gil-sung (2004, p.148) states that the IMF's reforms led to unemployment, social inequality and a compromised national identity. Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.124) echo this statement, noting that the IMF Crisis led to increased rates of crimes, divorces, child desertions and suicides. The effects of the IMF reforms were so widespread that Kim (2019, p.511) notes that the 1997 Asian Financial Crisis is better known as the ‘IMF Crisis’ in Korea. Indeed, although the government paid back the IMF loan in 2000, Seung-kyung Kim and John Finch (2002, p.135) state that “the shadow of the crisis” loomed over Korea for years afterwards.

Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.124) suggest that many films, such as *Peppermint Candy* (*Bakhasatang*, Lee 1999), directly confront the social issues that emerged from the IMF Crisis. In addition, Chi-Yun Shin (2005, p.123) suggests that the revival and popularity

of the gangster genre in the 2000s, discussed more in section 2.4, “can be seen as a consequence of, and a response to, the national economic crisis.”

Although the beginning of New Korean Cinema is a contentious topic, its ending is not. Paquet (2009, p.114) states that 2006 marks a “meaningful endpoint”, citing the “bursting of the film finance bubble” and the waning strength of the ‘Korean Wave’, a term used to refer to Korea’s increasing cultural influence during the 2000s. Paquet (2009, pp.110-111) notes that as the Korean Wave waned, film exports “crashed from \$76 million in 2005 to \$24 million in 2006 and only \$12.3 million in 2007.” In addition, 2006 saw a reduction in Korea’s screen quota, which was halved from 146 days to 73 days (Jin 2020, p.39; Paquet 2009, p.111). The most apparent indicator that 2006 marks the end of New Korean Cinema is the decreasing market share of domestic films, which Jin (2020, p.47) notes plunged from an all-time high of 63.8% in 2006 to 42% in 2008.

Even so, the end of New Korean Cinema did not signal the end of Korean cinema. Paquet (2009, p.114) states that the progress that occurred during New Korean Cinema created an environment that allowed new ideas and new voices to flourish. Following New Korean Cinema, the film industry was better able to support creative talent, with film directors retaining significant degrees of creative control (Paquet 2009, p.114).

Although the domestic share of Korean films has not since surpassed the 2006 figure, Jin (2020, p.48) claims that it “bounced back” to 51% in 2014. Writing in 2016, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.4) noted that “domestic films have consistently maintained an over 50 percent share of the local market” since 2011. In addition, foreign investment in the film industry has increased in the last few years. Caleb Kelso-Marsh (2021, p.25) notes that Netflix invested \$700 million in the Korean film industry between 2015 and 2020, and \$500 million in 2021 alone. Netflix followed these investments with an announcement in 2023 that it would invest \$2.5 billion in the Korean film industry over the next four years (Wan 2023).

Despite the Korean film industry's continued success, scholarship is far less extensive on the post-2006 period than on New Korean Cinema. In Cho, J.'s (2019, p.61) otherwise comprehensive history of Korean cinema, there is barely any discussion of the period. In addition, whereas Sangjoon Lee's (2019) edited book, *Rediscovering Korean Cinema*, dedicates ten chapters to films made between 2000 and 2006, only five focus on films made after 2006.

Overall, there is a lack of research considering the socio-political context of the post-2006 period, particularly from 2015 onwards. This is a major lacuna, as many socio-political events have occurred since 2006 that have likely influenced the development of Korean cinema. These include the continuing neoliberal restructuring of Korea's economy, as examined by sociologists such as Keith B. Wagner (2016) and Yoonkyung Lee (2015), rising social inequality, as noted by sociologists Hagen Koo (2021) and Yoonkyung Lee (2019), and increasingly apparent corporate and political corruption, a recurrent topic in the fields of Sociology and Political Science (Jun et al. 2019; Fermins and Robbins 2018; Murillo and Sang 2013; Choi and Woo 2012).

Socio-political events of specific relevance to the Korean film industry have also occurred since 2006, namely the return of censorship during the respective presidential terms of Lee Myung-bak (2008-2013) and Park Geun-hye (2013-2016), as noted by Jin (2020, pp.31-33) and sociologist Joowon Yuk (2019). In fact, Jin (2020, p.31) notes that Park Geun-hye's government maintained a blacklist of 9,473 creative professionals, including famed creatives such as director Park Chan-wook and actor Song Kang-ho.

2.6 The Missing Genre: Korean Gangster Cinema

Before discussing English-language scholarship on Korean gangster cinema, it is important to highlight English-language discussion of the gangster genre. Neale (2000, p.69) states that the gangster genre "occupies a privileged place in genre theory", stating that, along with the

Western, the genre was “a major reference point” for genre theorists writing in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Langford (2005, p.12) notes that one of the earliest studies of film genre, Robert Warshow’s (2002) *The Gangster as Tragic Hero*, originally published in 1948, was focused on the gangster genre.

Although Warshow (2002) deserves credit for pioneering the study of film genre, Langford (2005, p.12) notes that Warshow’s (2002) article on the gangster genre is based on just three films and treats genre history “rather casually.” Neale (2000, p. 70) makes a similar point, referring to the article as “very generalized” and “highly selective.” Despite these flaws, Neale (2000, p.69) and genre theorist George S. Larke-Walsh (2019, p.1) note that Warshow’s (2002) work has influenced the study of the gangster genre.

Warshow’s (2002) influence may explain why English-language study of the genre has mainly focused on American gangster cinema. Indeed, Law (2008, p.523) argues that discourse on the gangster genre has generally assumed “that within the global screenscape [sic], the gangster genre is American territory proper.” Indeed, while Langford (2005, p.147) acknowledges the existence of “indigenous variants of the gangster genre”, he implies that these “variants” are inferior to American gangster cinema, stating that “[f]ew...have used the figure of the gangster himself in the culturally and socially paradigmatic manner of his American incarnation.”

Fortunately, non-American gangster cinema has not been completely overlooked by English-language scholars. Larke-Walsh’s (2019) edited book, *A Companion to the Gangster Film*, covers gangster cinema across the Americas, Europe, and Asia. In addition, several journal articles focus on non-American gangster cinema, such as Peter Pozefsky’s (2008) article on Russian gangster films and Alex Hastie’s (2019) discussion of gangsters in Maghrebi-French cinema. In addition, there is an impressive quantity of English-language research on Asian gangster cinemas, namely Japanese yakuza cinema and Hong Kong gangster, or triad, cinema.

Nevertheless, it is important to note that the literature review does not address writing on other national gangster genres or use such writing to discuss the Korean gangster genre. This would only compromise the thesis's focus and expand its scope to an unfeasible degree. Furthermore, discussing the Korean gangster genre using research on the genre's foreign counterparts would risk implying that they are superior or more foundational forms of the genre. At the very least, it would complicate the understanding of the Korean gangster genre's uniquely national cultural and cinematic qualities.¹⁹

In contrast to English-language research on the Japanese and Hong Kong variants of the gangster genre, research on Korean gangster cinema is sparse, even when compared to English-language research on other Korean genres such as horror and comedy. Writing in 2011, Daniel Martin (2011, p.237) notes that the Korean gangster genre is one of many genres with domestic significance that has received “virtually no academic attention (or acknowledgement).”

Many scholars who have otherwise comprehensively examined Korean cinema have not explicitly discussed or mentioned the Korean gangster genre. In their expansive study of Korean cinema, Chung and Diffrient (2015) refer to the gangster film only five times, neither defining nor discussing the genre. Although Yecies and Shim (2016) mention two gangster films – *Guns & Talks* and *The Anarchists* – they neither examine nor refer to the gangster genre in their otherwise thorough analysis of Korean cinema from 1960 to 2015. Similarly, while Jin (2020, p.121) remarks on the success of the gangster film *General's Son*, he does not examine the gangster genre. More recent publications also overlook the gangster genre – the edited collection, *The South Korean Film Industry* (Lee et al. 2024), only briefly mentions a few gangster films, and the edited collection *Korean Film and History* (Lee 2024)

¹⁹ The thesis engages somewhat with the most significant foreign influence on the Korean gangster genre: Hong Kong gangster cinema. More specifically, Chapter 6 details how Hong Kong gangster cinema was partially responsible for the genre's revival in the late 1990s and early 2000s, highlighting parallels between certain Hong Kong and Korean gangster films.

does not mention the gangster genre. Of those who have produced broad studies of Korean cinema, Paquet (2009, pp.80-83) is the only scholar who examines gangster cinema. Even then, he (ibid.) mainly focuses on the comedy-gangster sub-genre.

Although other English-language scholars *have* examined Korean gangster cinema, such scholarship is mainly confined to book chapters and journal articles. Accordingly, existing research is limited in scope, often focusing on specific aspects, films or periods of the gangster genre. For example, Shin (2005, p.17) examines representations of gender and friendship in the gangster film *Friend (Chingu)*, Kwak 2001), Pierce Conran (2018, p.201) examines the “unique architectural and thematic potential of the modern apartment” in *Gangnam Blues (Gangnam 1970)*, Yoo 2015), and Keith B. Wagner and Michael A. Unger (2024) examine the use of the seaport setting, and topics such as spatiality and globalisation, in the films *The Yellow Sea (Hwanghae)*, Na 2010) and *New World*.

As these examples illustrate, most of the work on Korean gangster cinema is not actually focused on the gangster genre. Instead, many scholars simply use gangster films to discuss topics tangentially related to the gangster genre. For example, Moonim Baek (2024) uses *The Merciless* to discuss Korean female fandom, and Kate Taylor-Jones (2020) mentions gangster films when examining both footwear and female characters in Korean corporate crime dramas. Jieun Kiaer and Loli Kim (2022) also tangentially discuss gangster cinema, mentioning gangster films – mainly comedy-gangster films – when examining the intricacies of Korean body language.

Overall, there seems to be a lack of consensus in English-language scholarship regarding the definition of the Korean gangster genre. For example, although Choi (2010b, p.51) and Kim (2019, p.502) identify *A Bittersweet Life (Dalkomhan insaeng)*, Kim 2005) as a gangster film, Susie Jie Young Kim (2010, p.120) argues that the film is more akin to a noir. While certain scholars define *New World* as a noir (Wagner and Ungner 2024, p.4; Kwon 2023, p.9), others refer to it as a gangster film (Kim 2019, p.522; Gillespie 2016,

p.63). Furthermore, Kim Soyoung's (2005, p.97, author's italics) statement that "for the last few years *action movies featuring gangsters* have been topping the box office in Korea" seems to suggest they consider gangsters to be purely semantic elements.

Another issue with English-language discussion of Korean gangster cinema is its primary focus on films made during New Korean Cinema. In fact, two short book chapters written by Choi (2010a; 2010b) – each of which details the genre's development from the 1960s until the late 2000s – represent the most comprehensive discussions of Korean gangster cinema written to date. Even then, Choi (2010a; 2010b) mainly focuses on Korean gangster films made in the early 2000s.

Scholarly focus on New Korean Cinema is particularly apparent when considering research on early Korean gangster cinema – Choi (2010a, pp.60-61) is the only scholar to examine the genre before New Korean Cinema. Even then, Choi (ibid.) only does so briefly and does not name any film made before 1974.²⁰ The only other theorist to even *refer* to pre-1990s Korean gangster cinema is Jinsoo An (2018). However, An (2018) only examines one film made in the 1970s, *A True Story of Kim Du-han* (*Shillo* *Kim Du-han*, Kim 1974), and does not examine the gangster genre. Instead, An (2018) uses the film to discuss how marginalised figures inform cinematic portrayals of the colonial period.

There is even less writing on 1980s gangster films than on 1960s or 1970s gangster films. Aside from Choi's (2010a, p.60) statement that Korean gangster films experienced "a long absence...during the 1980s as a result of censorship", nothing has been written about 1980s Korean gangster cinema.

Fortunately, there is more literature, albeit only marginally, on gangster films made after New Korean Cinema. Gillespie's (2016, p.67) analysis of *New World* highlights how filmmakers during the 2010s transposed "the gangster narrative to the elite domain of the

²⁰ Choi (2010b, pp.47-48) directly refers to pre-1990s Korean gangster cinema in another book chapter, but she does not examine the genre.

boardroom, where sharp-suited henchmen meet on the uppermost floors of a faceless corporate skyscraper.” Plaice (2019b) highlights a similar genre shift in films such as *Asura: City of Madness* (*Asura*, Kim 2016), *The Merciless* and *Inside Men*, suggesting that these films blur the boundaries between the noir and gangster genres, and between gangsters and government officials.

Both Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2019b) point to neoliberalism as the reason for the genre’s transformation during this time. Gillespie (2016, p.63) argues that neoliberalism has reshaped the gangster genre to such a degree that it is necessary to reevaluate the genre. Kim (2019, p.518, italics in original) also highlights the genre’s evolution during this period, noting that the film *Veteran* is “indicative of a new amalgamated anxiety about the gangster, a corporate gangster who is indicative of the resentment towards the *chaebol* class.”

One topic Kim (2019) considers in her discussion of the gangster genre is violence, a topic of particular interest to English-language film scholars. Robert L. Cagle (2009) examines violence and morality in the film *A Bittersweet Life*, Gemma Ballard (2023) considers the transformative nature of violence in 2000s and 2010s gangster films, and Min et al. (2003, pp.176-177) discuss the symbolism of violence in the gangster genre, highlighting how, among other things, it acts as a means of achieving social mobility.

Social mobility and social inequality are also recurrent topics in English-language scholarship on Korean gangster cinema. Criminologists Richard J. De Caires, Paul T. Lankin, and Phillip C. Shon (2012, pp.51-52) note that the theme of “upward striving” permeates the gangster genre: “[t]he subtext of this motif becomes apparent in that the accumulation of wealth, power, and territory account for the allure of becoming a gangster.”

Shin (2005, p.123) argues that the popularity of the gangster genre in the post-IMF period is partly due to it offering “catharsis to Korean men suffering from political and economic depression.” Indeed, although most scholars note that the gangster genre underwent a dramatic revival in the 1990s, (Plaice 2020, p.2; Kim 2019, p.510; Plaice 2019c;

Choi 2016, p.218; Gillespie 2016, p.62; Choi 2010a, p.61; Choi 2010b, p.49; Min et al. 2003, p.173), many, including Choi (2010a, p.62) and Plaice (2020, p.3), believe that the genre did not become truly popular until the release of *Friend* four years after the IMF Crisis began.

However, Choi (2010a, p.64) also theorises that the genre's popularity – and particularly its revival – was driven by the rise of independent production companies and the waning success of Hong Kong gangster films in the late 1990s, which had been popular in Korea throughout the 1980s and early 1990s.

Despite the many aspects of Korean gangster cinema that have been explored by English-language scholars, there are notable research gaps in the extant literature. Aside from Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2019b), few scholars have discussed the symbolic meaning of the gangster character or examined how the portrayal of gangsters has changed throughout the genre's history. This is a notable oversight. As Wilson (2015, p.3) states, the gangster is, unlike genres such as the Western, action and science fiction, “the only genre whose nomenclature is centred on an individual, rather than a concept.”²¹

Accordingly, it seems logical to assume that a better understanding of the gangster *character* would lead to a better understanding of the gangster *genre*, particularly when discussing its overall development. Indeed, Larke-Walsh (2015, p.2) notes that the centrality of the gangster figure allows the gangster genre to have a “variety of narrative structures, character types, and settings.”

From assassins to politicians, street guys to made men, outlaws to company men and women, a vast array of individuals exist in the cinematic gangster universe. This level of variety is, on the one hand, an indication of the richness and significance of the genre, especially in terms of identity politics. However, this variety also indicates the elasticity of the genre's structural and thematic boundaries (Larke-Walsh 2019, p.2).

Another notable gap in English-language discussion of Korean gangster cinema is the omission of any data on real-life organised crime in Korea. While many scholars consider

²¹ As noted in Chapter I: Introduction, Wilson's (2015, p.3) statement is not entirely correct. Although the nomenclature of the gangster genre centres on an individual rather than a concept, the same statement could be made about the superhero genre.

how gangster films embody certain socio-cultural issues, only one article by criminologists De Caires, Lankin and Shon (2012) combines a discussion of Korean gangster films with a discussion of real-life organised crime. Even then, De Caires et al. (2012) use gangster films to understand real-life organised crime, rather than use data on real-life organised crime to understand Korean gangster films.

The lack of research that considers data on real-life Korean organised crime may be due to the general lack of writing on the topic. As criminologist Seungmug Lee (2006, p.62) states, “very few studies have been conducted which delve into the nature and extent of organized crime in South Korea.” Indeed, there seems to be only approximately a dozen English-language texts dedicated to discussing real-life organised crime in Korea, almost all of which are journal articles. Nevertheless, texts such as Youn Keun Lee’s (1998) article on organised crime in 1990s Korea, political scientist Erik Mobernd’s (2016) article on post-colonial organised crime, and Yong Kwan Park’s (2004) discussion of transnational organised crime in Korea allow the thesis to consider how the Korean gangster genre reflects real-world organised crime.

2.7 Conclusion

As the literature review details, several research gaps exist in Genre Studies and Korean Film Studies. These include a lack of writing on non-American genre cinema, a lack of research on the earliest and most recent periods of Korean cinema, and the paucity of writing on Korean gangster cinema, particularly outside of New Korean Cinema.

Even so, there is sufficient research in both fields to support the thesis’s efforts to examine and understand the development of the Korean gangster genre. Despite the American-centric nature of English-language Genre Studies, scholars have developed promising approaches to genre analysis. Of relevance is Altman’s (1984) semantic/syntactic approach, which provides a useful way to conceptualise genre *and* to examine genre

development. Scholars have also reached many useful conclusions regarding genre, namely that genres are processes, that socio-cultural factors influence a genre's development, that genre-mixing is inherent and inevitable, and that genre boundaries are more flexible than strict.

Research on Korean genre cinema, though limited, also provides valuable insights. Extant discussion of melodrama offers a basis for the thesis's discussion of early Korean gangster cinema, while scholarly studies on the Korean film industry's tendency to mix genres prove useful in examining the gangster genre's interactions with other genres, particularly in recent years. Thorough efforts to contextualise the development of the Korean film industry also assist in understanding the socio-cultural determinants affecting the gangster genre's development, such as the government's implementation of strict censorship in the 1970s, the socio-cultural impacts of the IMF Crisis, and the increasing levels of corruption and inequality in the mid to late-2010s.

Chapter III: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

As the thesis is focused on charting the development of Korean gangster cinema, the thesis's methodological approach is based on two frameworks that conceive of genre as a process: Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach, and Neale's (2000) theory of genre development, which suggests that dominant genres and genre elements are constantly reshuffled. These approaches are discussed in section 3.2 Genre as a Process, in addition to Grindon's (2007) work on genre, which demonstrates how Altman's (1984) and Neale's (2000) approaches are complementary. Grindon's (2007, p.408) work also informs the thesis's analysis of the gangster genre's development, specifically his argument that a genre's development is influenced by three determinants: external social influences, industrial factors and internal genre changes.

In contrast to the thesis's approach to defining and examining genre, the thesis's approach to defining the gangster genre, discussed in section 3.3 The Gangster-hero, is based on just one idea: Simon Pate's (2016) gangster-hero concept, which differentiates between films featuring gangster protagonists and films that are merely set in the underworld or that feature gangster antagonists. By using only Pate's (2016) concept, the thesis avoids relying on extant understandings of the gangster genre to define Korean gangster cinema, which, due to their American-centric nature, would likely fail to encompass its unique cultural and cinematic qualities. Pate's (2016) concept also allows the thesis to create an *a priori* definition that is flexible enough to allow the thesis to create a diverse film corpus, the contents of which are discussed in 3.4 Korean Gangster Cinema.

3.2 Genre as a Process: Approaches to Genre and Genre Development

Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach is the cornerstone of this thesis's methodology. As noted in the literature review, Altman's (1984, p.9) approach combines the ritual approach, the ideological approach and iconographic analysis. Inherently, as Berry-Flint (2004, p.35) notes, the semantic/syntactic approach combines interpretive definitions of genre, which emphasise a genre's underlying themes, with iconographic definitions of genre, which emphasise a genre's visual elements. In Altman's (1984, p.16) own words, semantics are the "primary, linguistic elements of which all texts are made", and syntactic elements are "the secondary, textual meanings which are sometimes constructed...between primary [semantic] elements."

Unfortunately, Altman (1984, p.10) only vaguely defines semantic and syntactic elements, referring to semantic elements as "a list of common traits, attitudes, characters, shots, locations, sets, and the like" and syntax as "the constitutive relationships between undesignated and variable placeholders." As noted in the literature review, Altman's (1984, p.10) vague classifications exacerbate the lack of consensus in Genre Studies regarding a genre's fundamental elements.

To overcome this lack of consensus, the thesis uses its own definitions; it defines semantics as 'visual elements' and syntax as the 'underlying elements that lend semantics meaning'. More specifically, the thesis classifies semantics as a film's characters, settings and iconography (other visual elements such as props, *mise-en-scène* and specific actors). In addition, it classifies syntax as a film's narrative, aesthetics (formal elements such as editing, cinematography and lighting), and themes.

These classifications synthesise the elements of genre listed by Pye (2012, p.241), Chandler (1997, p.13), Schatz (1981, pp.22-25) and Grant (2007, pp.9-21) and discussed in

the literature review.²² Although each scholar's list of elements differs, they each include characters, settings, iconography, narrative and themes. Grant (2007, pp.9-21) and Chandler (1997, p.13) also highlight the role of a genre's formal elements – Grant (2007, pp.10-11) refers to formal elements under the heading of 'conventions' and Chandler (1997, p.13) considers formal elements to be part of a genre's iconography.

With the fundamental elements of a given genre established, it is important to discuss the use of Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach in the thesis. One of the principal benefits of the semantic/syntactic approach is its flexibility. Since the approach does not suggest that certain elements are more important than others, a film may be defined as a specific genre even if it lacks certain semantic or syntactic elements. As Altman (1984, p.12) notes, the semantic/syntactic approach allows scholars "to deal critically with differing levels of genericity [sic]."

Altman (ibid.) also notes that the approach "permits a far more accurate description of the numerous inter-generic connections typically suppressed by [more restrictive approaches]." Accordingly, the semantic/syntactic approach helps us understand whether certain gangster films feature the semantic elements of one genre and the syntax of a different genre. The semantic/syntactic approach also assists in demonstrating that specific elements of the Korean gangster genre are derived from other genres. Genre theorist Berry-Flint (2004, p. 35) utilises elements of this approach to make such a point about film noir, stating that while the genre is "semantically distinctive", it "shares its syntactical patterns with larger categories like the thriller and detective film." Ultimately, the semantic/syntactic

²² Douglas Pye's (2012, p.241) list: plot, "other structural features", character, time and space (setting), iconography, and themes. Grant's (2007, pp.9-21) list: conventions ("frequently-used stylistic techniques or narrative devices"), iconography, setting, stories and themes, characters, actors and stars, and viewers and audiences. Daniel Chandler's (1997, p.13) list: narrative, characterisation (characters), themes, setting and iconography. Schatz's (1981, pp.22-25) list: iconography, character and setting, plot structure, narrative strategy and social function.

approach allows the thesis to establish its own conclusions regarding the generic identity of particular gangster films and the generic heredity of the Korean gangster genre.

Of course, as noted in the literature review, the semantic/syntactic approach is not without issues. One of the approach's flaws, as highlighted by scholars such as Langford (2005, pp.16-17) and Neale (2000, p.204), is its inability to account for genre elements that are simultaneously semantic and syntactic. Indeed, both Langford (2005, pp.16-17) and Neale (2000, p.204) question the approach's ability to classify a semantic element with syntactic meaning. As Neale (2000, p.204) states, while an element "lacking any kind of syntactic content might be regarded as an autonomous semantic unit, it is also plausible to suggest that" certain semantic elements, such as the shootout in a western, are part of a genre's syntax.

Although this flaw is difficult to remedy without changing the semantic/syntactic approach altogether, the thesis employs the term 'multifarious elements' to denote semantic elements with syntactic purpose and/or syntactic characteristics. The thesis discusses such multifarious elements in Chapter VIII, which uses the research findings from Chapters IV through VII to examine the overall development of the Korean gangster genre.

Aside from using the semantic/syntactic approach to conduct genre analysis, the thesis also uses this approach to chart genre development. In fact, Altman (1984, p.12) states that it is only when examining genre development that "the full value of the semantic/syntactic approach becomes obvious." Using the approach, Altman (1984, p.12) hypothesises that genres develop in one of two ways: "a relatively stable set of semantics...is developed through syntactic experimentation into a coherent and durable syntax, or an already existing syntax adopts a new set of semantic elements."

A benefit of using the semantic/syntactic approach to genre development is that it embraces "historical considerations" (Altman 1984, p.12). Indeed, Altman (1984, p.8) directly challenges more prescriptive conceptions of genre development that conceptualise

“history as nothing more than a discontinuous succession of discrete moments.” In addition, Altman (1984, p.8) recognises that genres develop differently, noting that one genre might develop slowly, change constantly, become remarkably successful and then establish a stable pattern, while another might “go through an extended series of paradigms, none of which may be claimed as dominant.”

Overall, Neale (2000, p.204) credits Altman’s (1984) conceptualisation of genre development with recognising the importance of history, “heterogeneity, and the possibility of difference, variation and change”. Even so, Neale (2000, p.201) subscribes to a different conception of genre development that highlights two central tenets: “the transience of generic hierarchies...[and] the role of hybridisation in the formation and dissolution of genres.”

Due to the importance of these two tenets, the thesis combines Altman’s (1984) concept of genre development with Neale’s (2000, p.201) hypothesis that dominant genres and defining elements within genres are constantly replaced and displaced.

The thesis borrows the idea of combining Altman’s (1984) and Neale’s (2000) concepts from Grindon (2007, p.405). After using both Altman’s (1984) and Neale’s (2000) conceptions of genre development to examine the American boxing genre, Grindon (2007, p.406) concludes that both concepts are “flexible concepts for charting a film genre’s history.” In addition, Grindon (2007, p.406) notes that each concept highlights a different aspect of genre development: whereas Altman’s (1984) approach highlights stability, Neale’s (2000) approach highlights change. Accordingly, the use of both approaches may result in a more comprehensive understanding of the Korean gangster genre’s development.

Aside from validating the benefits of Altman’s (1984) and Neale’s (2000) approaches to genre development, Grindon (2007) makes some important points of his own. Namely, Grindon (2007, p.409) notes that three categories of historical factors influence genre development: i) external social influences, which he argues are the primary

determinants of genre change, ii) film industry factors, such as censorship, new technologies or broader industrial shifts, and iii) internal changes within the genre.

The thesis considers all three of Grindon's (2007, p.408) categories – external social influences, film industry factors and internal genre changes – throughout Chapters IV through VII. The thesis also follows Grindon's (2007, p.409) assertion that “film genres are capable of offering genuine insight into the dramatic conflicts and social problems that generate [them].”

Overall, the different frameworks that inform the thesis's approach to genre development – Altman's semantic/syntactic approach, Neale's (2000) conception of genre development, and Grindon's (2007) points on historical influences – are all predicated upon the idea that genre is a process. Accordingly, this is the central principle governing the thesis's discussion of Korean gangster cinema.

3.3 The Gangster-hero: Defining Korean Gangster Cinema

As noted in the literature review, English-language discussion of the gangster genre has mainly focused on American gangster films, leading some scholars to imply that the genre is intrinsically American. In fact, genre theorist Barry Keith Grant (2007, p.105) implies that *all* genres are indebted to Hollywood. More specifically, Grant (2007, p.105, author's italics) suggests that while national iterations of genres address concerns specific to the nation making them, they also “*depend* on their generic American predecessors for their meaning.” Inherently, Grant (ibid.) seems to suggest that since the production of American genre films preceded the production of genre films in other countries, all genre cinema is secondary to American genre cinema.

This thesis dismisses such an idea, examining Korean gangster cinema solely using research, cinematic, historical and sociological, focused on Korea. Hence, this section is titled ‘Defining *Korean* Gangster Cinema’ and not ‘Defining Gangster Cinema’.

Although the thesis uses existing research to *examine* Korean gangster cinema, it does not use existing research to *define* the genre. Doing so would require accepting pre-existing understandings of the genre without first examining it. Since most English-language scholarship on the genre focuses on New Korean Cinema, a definition based on extant literature would not account for the genre's development before 1990 and after 2006. Considering the varying socio-cultural and industrial factors that have influenced specific periods of Korean cinema, a singular definition of the Korean gangster genre may not even be a viable possibility.

These issues are indicative of the difficult task of defining a genre. As Chandler (1997, p.2) notes, the practice of defining genres is a "theoretical minefield." Genre theorist Andrew Tudor (2012, p.5) describes how film scholars seeking to define a genre are "caught in a circle that first requires that the films be isolated, for which purposes a criterion is necessary, but the criterion is, in turn, meant to emerge from the empirically established characteristics of the films."²³ Langford (2005, p.13) describes this dilemma as the "inescapable and basic crux in trying to define individual genres."

Andrew Tudor (2012, p.5) states that there are only two possible solutions to this dilemma: i) establishing an *a priori* criterion or ii) relying on a "common cultural consensus." Unfortunately, neither solution is flawless. Tudor (*ibid.*) notes that the former solution only leads to the original dilemma, and Neale (2000, p.16) questions the latter solution, pondering how a scholar might establish a cultural consensus. Genre theorist Janet Staiger (2012, p.205) also criticises both solutions, noting that the first solution, the '*a priori* method' as she refers to it, is predetermined and that the second, or 'social convention method' as she refers to it, "raises questions about how a critic...determines cultural consensus."

²³ Although this citation is taken from Tudor's (2012) article as it appears in Grant's (2012) edited book *Film Genre Reader IV*, the article was originally published in 1973.

The family resemblances idea and prototype concept, the two flexible methods of defining genres discussed by Chandler (1997, pp.2-3) and Grindon (2012, pp.42-43), also pose issues. The family resemblances idea – which allows films to be classified as a particular genre even if they feature only a few of that genre’s traits – requires scholars to have already identified specific genre elements, and the prototype concept – which suggests that genres consist of well-defined films and lesser-known films – can only be used if a scholar has already identified a prototypical film emblematic of the given genre.

Due to the many issues that plague the task of defining genres, Staiger (2012, p.205) notes that most scholars accept the “theoretical shortcomings of genre study, and then just forge ahead anyway.” However, this thesis does not accept that it is necessary to accept such shortcomings when defining Korean gangster cinema, or, for that matter, any national version of the gangster genre. In fact, this thesis contends that these shortcomings result from scholarly efforts to develop an *overall* approach to defining *any* genre rather than a *specific* approach meant to define a *specific* genre.

Accordingly, the thesis posits that it is best to define the gangster genre using a tailored method rather than a general one. As noted in the literature review, the gangster genre is one of the few genres with a nomenclature centred on a character rather than a concept. Accordingly, the thesis takes it, at least for its purposes, that the gangster character is the *defining* element of the gangster genre. More specifically, the thesis proceeds using the assumption that a gangster *protagonist* is the defining element of the gangster genre.

The idea of using a gangster protagonist to define the gangster genre is drawn from Pate’s (2016) PhD thesis on Hollywood and Japanese gangster cinema. Pate (2016, p.11) uses the term ‘gangster-hero’ to distinguish between films that feature a gangster protagonist

and those that only focus on efforts to defeat gangsters or in which the underworld is just a backdrop to the film's narrative.²⁴

Before further discussing the gangster-hero term and its use in the thesis, it is necessary to state that the thesis's definition of 'gangster' is based on the Oxford Dictionary's (2024) definition: "a member of a group of violent criminals." Violent is the operative word in this definition as it differentiates gangsters from non-violent criminals such as thieves or smugglers. Indeed, while a character does not necessarily need to be violent to be a *gangster-hero*, *their gang* needs to be violent for them to be a *gangster*.

If a different term, such as 'hitman' or 'conman', more accurately describes a character than 'gangster', the thesis does not consider that character a gangster, *even if* they are part of a criminal group. In addition, the thesis does not include gangster films that only feature gangster *antagonists*; the gangster character *must* be a protagonist for a film to be included in the corpus. There is a final stipulation: if a film features *multiple* protagonists and *only one* is a gangster, the film is a gangster film only if the gangster-hero's role is equal to or greater than the role of the film's other protagonists.²⁵

Of course, the thesis acknowledges that using the gangster-hero as the sole criterion to define the gangster genre narrows its research scope. Pate (2016, p.11) notes that scholars could justifiably argue that using the gangster-hero to define the genre is overly restrictive and disregards other elements that typify gangster cinema. However, since a film must only feature a gangster-hero to be a gangster film, it may also feature elements not associated with the gangster genre or akin to other gangster films. Accordingly, the thesis's *a priori* definition allows for the possibility of genre-mixing.

²⁴ Many other scholars, including Gillespie (2016), Schatz (1981) and Choi (2010a) also use the term 'gangster-hero', although only as a substitute for 'gangster-character'. However, no other scholar uses the term to define the gangster genre nor to specifically refer to gangster-protagonists as Pate (2016) and this thesis do.

²⁵ The thesis primarily uses screen time to determine the extent of a gangster-hero's role in a film, with secondary consideration given to the character's influence on the film's narrative.

The flexibility of the thesis's *a priori* definition is made apparent by comparing it to Min et al.'s (2003, p.174) definition, which states that gangster films must be "first and foremost" characterised by a gangster, primarily focus on a young hero, hustler or professional killer, be set in Seoul, and feature stylistic characteristics such as an abundance of night scenes, a bleak noir tone, and fast-paced action scenes.

Such a prescriptive definition confines the gangster genre to predefined conventions, limiting the opportunity to examine unconventional films or to broaden understanding of the Korean gangster genre. Nevertheless, the thesis does not challenge existing definitions of the gangster genre nor argue that scholars must define gangster films using the gangster-hero. In addition, the thesis acknowledges that the gangster genre features many elements that certain scholars might justifiably argue are as fundamental to the genre's definition as the gangster-hero.

The thesis also acknowledges that its definition of 'gangster' may differ from other scholarly definitions, either in the fields of Film Studies or Criminology. Indeed, criminologist Seungmug Lee (2006, p.62) states that attempts "to define the concept of organized crime [and therefore gangsters] have met with only limited success, and no generally accepted definition has emerged."

Finally, it must be reiterated that while the term 'gangster-hero' is used throughout the thesis, it is only used in the methodology to create *a priori* definition of Korean gangster cinema. The semantic/syntactic approach and related methodological tools discussed in section 3.2 are not rendered obsolete by the thesis's decision to create an *a priori* definition of the gangster genre using the gangster-hero. Instead, the thesis's *a priori* definition allows the thesis to develop a film corpus, the first step in examining the Korean gangster genre.

Ultimately, the thesis's definition of the gangster-hero and its definition of the gangster genre are not designed to be declarative or definitive. Instead, they are simply meant to achieve the thesis's main research objective: to chart the Korean gangster genre's

development, with particular emphasis on the changing representation of gangster-heroes. As Chandler (1997, p.3) notes, “[h]ow we define a genre depends on our purposes: the adequacy of our definition...must surely be related to the light that the exploration sheds on the phenomenon.”

The thesis further reflects the spirit of Chandler’s (1997, p.3) quote in the three eras – Pre-Revival Era, Revival Era and Post-Revival Era – that it uses to discuss the Korean gangster genre.²⁶ These eras were developed because the periods commonly used to discuss Korean cinema – the Golden Age, the Dark Age, the Korean New Wave and New Korean Cinema – did not align with the development of the Korean gangster genre. Whereas the thesis applies these established periods when referring to Korean cinema and industry-wide developments, it uses the Revival framework as a tailored lens for discussing the Korean gangster genre.

The Pre-Revival Era overlaps with the Golden Age – which Abelmann and McHugh (2005, p.2) and Jeong (2006, p.130) periodise as between 1955 to 1972 – and the Dark Age – a period that scholars such as Lee, S. (2019, p.16) and Park (2007, p.16) describe as lasting from the early 1970s into the late 1980s. This era is characterised by strict censorship, the dominance of melodrama in the 1960s, and the declining quality of domestic films in the 1970s.

Although technically part of the same era, the thesis addresses Golden Age gangster films and Dark Age gangster films separately due to the unique industrial factors that characterise each period. Accordingly, it refers to the gangster genre of the Golden Age as ‘the Early Pre-Revival Era’ and the gangster genre of the Dark Age as the ‘Late Pre-Revival Era’.

²⁶ As these eras refer specifically to the Korean gangster genre, the thesis omits the phrase ‘gangster cinema’ when referring to a specific period of the genre. For example, rather than using ‘Revival Era gangster cinema’, the thesis simply uses ‘the Revival Era’. However, the Revival framework is still used in combination with specific terms when necessary. For example, it uses ‘Revival Era films’ to refer to films of the period, and ‘Revival Era gangster-heroes’ to refer to gangster-heroes of the period.

In contrast, the Revival Era saw a marked increase in both the production and commercial success of gangster films. This was mainly due to a new generation of filmmakers, who, with more creative freedom and industrial support, were able to make films that reckoned with the difficult realities of Korean society, particularly for those less fortunate. Beginning in 1990, the period overlaps with the final years of the Korean New Wave, which Paquet (2009, p.78) states ended in 1996, and New Korean Cinema, which Paquet (2009, pp.110-11) believes ended with the “bursting of the film finance bubble” and a sharp decline in film exports in 2006.

The Post-Revival Era refers to the gangster films made during the current yet-to-be-named period that has followed New Korean Cinema. This era is primarily characterised by more powerful and businesslike gangsters, and a notable increase in genre-bending, both of which have transformed several of the genre’s semantic and syntactic characteristics. Socio-cultural factors, including the rise of neoliberalism and worsening social inequality, have also influenced the genre, resulting in overt critiques of the upper class and institutional corruption.

3.4 Korean Gangster Cinema: Making, Refining and Establishing a Film Corpus

After establishing the *a priori* definition of the gangster film – a film featuring a gangster-hero – the process of finding potentially relevant films began with an examination of literature on Korean gangster cinema. Frequently mentioned films included *Green Fish* (Chologmulgogi, Lee 1997), *Beat* (*Biteu*, Kim 1997), *Friend, A Bittersweet Life, A Dirty Carnival* (*Biyeolhan geori*, Yoo 2006), *Nameless Gangster: Rules of Time* (*Beomjoewauwi jeonjaeng*, Yoon 2012) and *New World*.

As this list of films reflects, most scholars mention gangster films released during New Korean Cinema, which began in the late 1990s and ended in 2006. However, there are some exceptions. Jamier (2015, pp.46-47) refers to several gangster films made *after* 2006,

including *The Show Must Go On* (*Uahan segye*, Han 2007), *Breathless* (*Ddongpari*, Yang 2008), *Friend: The Great Legacy* (*Chingu 2*, Kwak 2013), and *Gangnam Blues*.

Choi (2016, p.220) is only one of two scholars – alongside An (2018, p.18) – who mention gangster films made in the 1960s and 1970s. Specifically, Choi (ibid.) mentions films such as *44 Myeongdong* (*Myeongdong 44 beonji*, Go 1965), *Myeongdong Blues* (*Myeongdong Beuruseu*, Kim 1970b) and the omnibus film *Cruel History of Myeong Dong*. Choi (2010a, p.48) also refers to a series of 1970s gangster films, beginning with the 1974 film based on the real-life gangster Kim Du-han, *A True Story of Kim Du-han*. An (2018, p.18) mentions the same series.

After considering literature focused on Korean gangster cinema, the thesis broadened its search and examined literature on Korean cinema. Jin (2020, p.121) refers to *General's Son* – a film frequently mentioned by scholars who discuss the Korean gangster genre – and the 1969 film *Gallant Man* (Kim 1969), which Jin (2020, p.121) refers to as “one of the first gangster movies in Korean cinema.”²⁷ Yecies and Shim (2016, p.164) refer to the film *Guns & Talks* as a noir gangster comedy, and Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.248) mention the comedy-gangster film *My Wife is a Gangster* (*Jopok manura*, Jo 2006).

The thesis also consulted online discourse on the Korean gangster genre to find relevant films. More specifically, the thesis consulted online reviews and the social-cataloguing service Letterboxd, which, among other things, allows users to create themed lists of films. The site also features a robust tagging and categorisation system, making it

²⁷ There is not much evidence to support this claim. Jin (2020, p.121) cites an article written by film critic Pierce Conran (2011a), to support their point, but Conran (2011a) refers to *Gallant Man* (Kim 1969) as the first Korean gangster film and attributes this fact to an article by journalist Yun Suh-yeong (2011) in *The Korea Times*. Yun's (2011) article is not much more than a press release announcing that The Korean Film Archive is showing nine Korean gangster films online for free. While it seems likely that The Korean Film Archive referred to *Gallant Man* as Korea's first gangster film, the page linked in Yun's article is defunct. Even if The Korean Film Archive referred to *Gallant Man* (Kim 1969) as Korea's first gangster film, this does not seem accurate as KMDb tags many films made before 1969 under '갱스터' (gangster). Unfortunately, *Gallant Man* (Kim 1969) is not available to download, stream or buy online, and does not seem to have ever been released on DVD. In addition, it is not mentioned or discussed elsewhere outside of Jin's (2020, p.121) work.

possible to refine results according to several parameters, including genre, nation of origin and decade of release.

However, even after considering various academic and non-academic sources, the thesis did not find many potentially relevant films made before 1990. Indeed, were it not for the Korean Film Archive's online database, KMDb, it would have been impossible to examine the entire development of the Korean gangster genre.

The Korean Film Archive (2024a) describes KMDb as “the nation’s largest Korean movie database.” The site allows users to search for films using many criteria, including film title, cast and crew, plot keywords, year of production, release date and country of origin. Individual film listings often include screenshots, a list of the most important credits – such as director, actors, screenplay, producer, and cinematography – and details such as the film’s release date, production company and total admissions.

Additional features, including an extensive selection of articles written by film critics and industry professionals, are only available on the Korean-language version of KMDb.²⁸ The Korean-language version of KMDb also features a more robust search tool than the English-language version; although you cannot search by genre on the English-language site, you can do so on the Korean-language site.

However, the genre search feature is flawed. Although users can pick ‘갱스터’ (gangster) from a preset list of genres, the tag system used to categorise films does not seem to have been implemented properly; a search using the tag ‘gangster’ returns a list of only fifty-three films, most of which were made during the 1960s. In addition, the list does not include many of the most frequently mentioned films in extant literature, such as *General’s*

²⁸ The site also features a VOD or ‘video-on-demand’ service that the Korean Film Archive (KMDb 2024) claims “offers approximately 350 films.” Despite this claim, the Korean-language version of the site only features 118 films, and the English-language version only features 106 films at the time of writing (April 2024), none of which appear relevant to the thesis. Although the feature is available on both the English-language and Korean-language versions of KMDb, information regarding the service and its sign-up process is in Korean. The service seems to be restricted to Korean citizens and overseas Koreans who must apply for a membership using an “ID card, driver’s licence, passport copy, alien registration card, etc.” (Korean Film Archive 2024b).

Son, Friend and *Green Fish*. It seems likely that the Korean Film Archive has either neglected to tag these films as ‘gangster’ or tagged them as a different genre. However, even if the tag feature had been fully operable, it would have meant relying on the Korean Film Archive’s definition of the gangster genre rather than the thesis’s own definition.

Accordingly, the thesis located potentially relevant films by using KMDb’s ‘keyword/plot’ criterion instead, which searches for specific words in the plot descriptions of films. Fortunately, both the Korean and English-language databases featured this criterion, and, since the two versions of the site use the same internal search engine, the results on both were the same. For example, inputting one of the three Korean terms for gangster, *깡패* (*kkangpae*), results in a list of 316 films on both versions of the site.²⁹

Using the ‘year of production’ criterion and ‘keyword/plot’ feature together, the thesis searched for films in each major period of Korean cinema – the Golden Age, the Dark Age, the Korean New Wave, New Korean Cinema, and the post-2006 period (2007 - Present) – featuring one of three *hangeul* terms for gangster – *깡패* (*kkangpae*), *조폭* (*jopok*) and *건달* (*geondal*) – in their plot description.³⁰

The results were as follows: i) 143 films made between 1953 to 1969 (8.4 films per year), ii) 150 films made between 1970 and 1979 (15 films per year), iii) 72 films made

²⁹ Kim (2019, p.498) notes that the term ‘*kkangpae*’ originated during the Korean War and has the closest translation to the English ‘gangster’. The two other Korean terms for gangster are *조폭* (*jopok*) and *건달* (*geondal*). Shin (2005, p.118) notes that ‘*jopok*’ is an abbreviation of the legal term for organised crime and has, compared to ‘*kkangpae*’ and ‘*geondal*’, “an added sense of someone belonging to an organised criminal group.” Kim (2019, p.498) notes that ‘*geondal*’ translates to ‘good-for-nothing’ and is generally used by gangsters to refer to themselves. Although most scholars use either ‘*kkangpae*’ or ‘*jopok*’, KMDb uses all three terms, with ‘*kkangpae*’ most often appearing in the plot descriptions of Pre-Revival Era films and ‘*jopok*’ and ‘*geondal*’ appearing most often in the plot descriptions of Revival Era and Post-Revival Era films.

³⁰ Although most scholars agree that New Korean Cinema ended sometime in the mid to late-2000s, scholars have yet to ascribe a specific name to the current period of Korean cinema.

between 1980 and 1996 (4.2 films per year), iii) 103 films made between 1997 and 2006 (10.3 films per year) and v) 135 films made between 2007 and 2024 (7.5 films per year).³¹

As these results indicate, the production of Korean gangster films peaked in the 1970s before dramatically decreasing in the 1980s. These results reflect Choi's (2010a, p.60) statement that the genre experienced a "long absence" before its resurgence in the 1990s and early 2000s. These results also reflect Mark R. Plaice's (2019c) quantitative analysis of the Korean gangster genre, which shows a lengthy fallow period separating the two cinematic periods of the genre which saw the highest production of gangster films, the Golden Age and New Korean Cinema.³²

Although these results provide an overview of the Korean gangster genre's development in quantitative terms, they do not accurately reflect the number of Korean gangster films made per period. As noted already, the 'keyword/plot' function only searches for keywords in a film's description. Accordingly, many of the films listed per period may only *feature* gangsters and may not be gangster *films*. This is particularly important to note considering that the thesis dictates that a gangster film *must* feature a gangster-hero.

Indeed, before the thesis included any film in the film corpus, it ascertained whether the film featured a gangster-hero. Sometimes, this was immediately apparent by reading the film's plot description, reading a film review or watching a trailer. However, in many cases, it was necessary to watch the film in its entirety.

Unfortunately, of the hundreds of films listed on KMDb, many were not accessible to view. This was particularly true of films made before 1990. In fact, of the pre-1990 films

³¹ These searches were conducted on the 14th of April 2024. Each total is the sum of three separate searches: *깡패* (*kkangpae*), *조폭* (*jopok*) and *건달* (*geondal*). For example, the 150 films made between 1970 and 1979 includes 121 for *깡패* (*kkangpae*), 0 for *조폭* (*jopok*) and 29 for *건달* (*geondal*). Again, it is important to reiterate that these results do not indicate that 150 gangster *films* were made between 1970 and 1979, but rather that 150 films made between 1970 and 1979 feature 'gangster' in their plot description on KMDb.

³² Unfortunately, Plaice (2019c) does not record how he collected his data, making it unusable in the thesis.

mentioned by Choi (2016, p.220; 2010a, p.48), An (2018, p.18) and Jin (2020, p.121), it was only possible to view *Cruel History of Myeong Dong*.³³

Although it may be possible that many pre-1990s gangster films, such as *44 Myeongdong*, *Myeongdong Blues* and *A True Story of Kim Du-han*, are accessible somewhere online, evidence suggests that they are only accessible within Korea, as the only sources that discuss them are in Korean. Indeed, it is important to emphasise that while Choi (2016, p.220; 2010a, p.48), An (2018, p.18) and Jin (2020, p.121) mention certain pre-1990s films, they do not discuss them.³⁴

The thesis was also unable to access recent films such as *A Man of Reason (Bohoja, Jung 2022)* and *Hot Blooded (Tteugeoun pi, Cheon 2022)*. Fortunately, only a small percentage of films made during the genre's current period have been produced in the last two years.³⁵

To be clear, these films are not deemed inaccessible because they were only available with Korean subtitles or only accessible via 'unofficial channels'. Rather, there were simply no copies of these films available to purchase, rent or loan from the researcher's residence in Ireland. The researcher even contacted several Korean and Asian Studies Departments, as well as two Korean embassies, and asked if they were aware of useful film databases or alternative methods of accessing Korean films online. Unfortunately, the few responses

³³ The spelling of 'Myeong Dong' in the film's title differs from the neighbourhood's conventional spelling, 'Myeong-dong', as well as its spelling in other film titles, such as *Whirl of Betrayals on Myeongdong (Myeong-dong Sam-gug-ji, Im 1972)*. As a result, the thesis only uses the spelling 'Myeong Dong' in the film's title and uses 'Myeong-dong' to refer to the actual area. To further avoid confusion, the thesis mainly refers to the film simply as *Cruel History*.

³⁴ The sources are 명동액션영화: 식민-해방-냉전기 기억의 소급적 상상. 비교한국학 [Myeung-Dong action films in early 1970's: retrospective imagination of colonial-liberation-postwar memories] by Song, H.J. (2013), 유신과 깡패, 1970년대 액션영화와 범법의 서사. 한국극예술연구 [Lawbreaking films in Park Chung-hee Era] by Yi, Y. (2016), and 반지성주의와 유신의 반영웅 -1970년대 전기영화 '김두한 시리즈' 연구 [Anti-intellectualism and antihero of Yushin - Research about mid-1970s 'Kim Du Han Series' as biography film] by Song, H.J. (2018).

³⁵ For example, of the fifty-eight films made between 2007 and 2024 that feature '조폭' (*jopok*) in their plot description, six were made between 2022 and 2024. Although this may seem significant, one film is an erotic drama, two are comedy films featuring gangster characters, and one is a documentary.

received all pointed to the Korean Film Archive's YouTube channel, Korean Classic Film. Although an invaluable resource, it was one the researcher was already aware of.

Of the films that the thesis was able to access and view, the thesis excluded many from the corpus in accordance with its definition of the gangster genre, which centres on whether a film features a gangster-hero. To be considered a gangster-hero, the gangster character had to be a protagonist. Accordingly, films that only featured gangsters as antagonists, no matter how prominent, were excluded from the thesis's corpus. This includes films such as *Nowhere to Hide* (*Injeong sajeong bol geot eobtda*, Lee 1999), *The City of Violence* (*Jjakpae*, Ryoo 2006), *The Man from Nowhere* (*Ajeossi*, Lee 2010), *Public Enemy Returns* (*Gangcheoljung: gonggongui jeok 1-1*, Kang 2008), *Man on High Heels* (*Haihil*, Jang 2014) and *The Outlaws* (*Beomjoedosi*, Kang 2017). Nearly all these films follow a policeman or detective as they pursue or battle a gangster. The only exception is *The Man from Nowhere*, which follows an ex-special agent.

The thesis also excludes *A Better Tomorrow* (*Mujeokja*, Song 2010), the Korean remake of the John Woo film of the same name, as the criminal identity of its protagonist, Kim Hyuk, is ambiguous. At once a police officer and an arms smuggler, Hyuk may work with the gangster Young-choon, but he is not strictly part of a gang. Additionally, Hyuk's time as a smuggler is short-lived; after he is betrayed and imprisoned for three years in Thailand, he begins life again as a taxi driver, only returning to the underworld to seek revenge on the man who betrayed him.

The thesis also excludes *Unstoppable* (*Seongnanhwangso*, Kim 2018), which follows an ex-gangster/fighter. Although the protagonist *was* a gangster, this fact is neither a fundamental aspect of his identity nor an integral part of the narrative. Indeed, the character is more akin to a cop or detective than the gangsters he battles.

For a similar reason, the thesis excludes the 1970s film *Wang Sib Ri, My Hometown* (*Wangshibri*, Im 1976). Overall, the film is far more akin to a melodrama than a gangster

film. In addition, while the protagonist is a gangster, this fact is largely inconsequential to his character arc or the film's plot. Unlike similarly melodramatic gangster films, such as *Failan (Pairan)* (Song 2001) from the Revival Era and *Man in Love (Namjaga saranghal ttae)* (Han 2014) from the Post-Revival Era, the protagonist in *Wang Sib Ri, My Hometown* is only revealed to be a gangster thirty-four minutes into the film. Even then, the film's gangster elements remain latent until the ending, which features a brief fight between the protagonist and his fellow gangsters.

Although the thesis excludes *Wang Sib Ri, My Hometown*, it takes a more flexible approach in terms of classifying Pre-Revival Era films due to the severe lack of existing research on, and available films from, the era. The decision to be more flexible regarding Pre-Revival Era films is also because the genre was in the early stages of development during this time. In addition, since Chapter IV considers *whether* the gangster genre existed during the Golden Age, it was pertinent to examine films with even the slightest association with the gangster genre. Accordingly, most of the earliest films included in the thesis's corpus are more akin to melodramas than gangster films. Nevertheless, each film features a gangster-hero and depicts organised crime.

Despite its exclusion from the corpus proper, *Wang Sib Ri, My Hometown* is still discussed in the thesis alongside the films *Break Up the Chain (Shwisaseuleul geunheola)* (Lee 1971) and *Returned Single-legged Man (Dol-a-on oedali)* (Lee 1974). Although the thesis does not classify these films as gangster films, Chapter V refers to them when arguing that censorship caused the dissolution of the Korean gangster genre during the 1970s.

Chapter VII also refers to several films *not* classified as gangster films, including *Public Enemy Returns, Veteran, The King (Deoking)* (Han 2017) and *Asura: The City of Madness*. It does so to emphasise the proliferation of genre-mixing during the Post-Revival Era, particularly in the mid to late-2010s. Indeed, although these films lack gangster-heroes, they feature prominent elements of the gangster genre.

Aside from the stipulation that a film must feature a gangster-hero, the thesis's *a priori* definition of the gangster genre dictates that the gangster-hero must have a role equal to or greater than a film's other protagonists if the gangster-hero is not the *sole* protagonist. This stipulation is why *The Devil's Deal* (*Daeoebi*, Lee 2023) is not included in the thesis. Although it features a prominent gangster character, their role in the film is secondary to another character, a local politician running for government. Conversely, this stipulation is why both *Inside Men* – which follows a gangster, a journalist and a prosecutor – and *The Gangster, The Cop, The Devil* (*Aginjeon*, Lee 2019) – which sees a detective ally with a gang boss – are *included* in the corpus.

Films were also excluded when the protagonist was either not violent or not part of a violent gang. Examples include *The Thieves* (*Dodukdeul*, Choi 2012) and *Tazza: The High Rollers* (*Tajja*, Choi 2006). Although both films feature a gang of criminals, they are not quite gangsters. Aside from the fact that they are not dependent on or defined by violence, each film's characters are better described by 'thief' and 'card shark' respectively than gangster.

The thesis excludes the film *City of the Rising Sun* (*Taeyangeun eobda*, Kim 1998) for similar reasons. Although it shares key crew members - screenwriter Sim San, director Kim Sung-su, and star Jung Woo-sung – with the gangster film *Beat*, it does not feature a gang. Indeed, while one of the film's protagonists, Hong-gi, schemes, dresses and wanders the streets like a gangster, he does not belong to a gang and his crimes are more sporadic than organised. Accordingly, he is better described as a hustler or a con man.

In contrast, while Sang-hun of *Breathless* also works alone, the nature of his work is far more characteristic of organised crime than Hong-gi's – whereas the former spends most of his time thinking up various 'get-rich' schemes, Sang-hun works as a debt collector and enforcer for a local loan shark that employs multiple men. Accordingly, the thesis includes the film in its corpus.

Several other films were excluded from the corpus because their protagonists were better described by a term other than ‘gangster’. Although the protagonist of *The Villainess* (*Angnyeo*, Jeong 2017) works for a criminal organisation, she is more akin to a spy or an assassin than a gangster. Similarly, although Yecies and Shim (2016, p.164) refer to *Guns & Talks* as a gangster film, the film’s four characters are more akin to assassins, or, as KMDb refers to them, ‘professional killers’. Yecies and Shim (2016, p.234) also describe *The Anarchists* as a gangster film. However, while the film’s four characters have gangster-like traits, they are guerrilla freedom fighters trying to undermine Japanese colonial rule in 1920s China. The thesis also excludes the film *Mutt Boy* (*Ttonggae*, Kwak 2003), mainly because its protagonist is more akin to a lowly, rural thug, especially when contrasted against the gangsters that feature as the film’s antagonists. Choi (2010a, p.73) seems to think similarly, stating that the film is not “strictly a gangster film”.

Aside from the many exclusions noted above, the thesis also excludes films defined as comedy-gangster films, such as *My Wife is a Gangster, Marrying the Mafia* (*Gamunui yeonggwang*, Jeong 2002), *My Boss, My Hero* (*Dusabuilche*, Yoon 2001), *City of Damnation* (*Yugamseureoun dosi*, Kim 2009), *Kick the Moon* (*Sillaui dalbam*, Kim 2001) and *Attack the Gas Station* (*Juyuso seubgyuksageun*, Kim 1999). This is not to deny the comedy-gangster sub-genre’s importance. The appearance of the sub-genre represents a notable milestone in the Korean gangster genre’s development. However, the sub-genre’s prominence is the very reason for its exclusion. As Choi (2010a, 83) notes, the comedy-gangster genre has distinct conventions and a unique tone. As a result, the thesis considers it distinct from the gangster genre proper. Even so, while the thesis does not include comedy-gangster films in its corpus, it still discusses them and the comedy-gangster genre in Chapter VI due to their importance to the history of the Korean gangster genre proper.

Although many films are immediately identifiable as gangster films, others are less so. Many films feature gangster-heroes but do not necessarily feature gangs or prominent

depictions of organised crime. For example, *Rosy Life's* (*Jangmibich insaeng*, Kim 1994) gangster-hero is forsaken by his gang and is alone for most of the film. Similarly, although the gangster-hero in *Sunflower* (*Haebaragi*, Kang 2006) was a gangster, he spends most of the film living a reformed life disconnected from organised crime.³⁶

Two more films included in the corpus warrant further explanation: *Hwayi: A Monster Boy* (*Hwayi: gwoemuleul samkin ayi*, Jang 2013) and *Coin Locker Girl* (*Chainataun*, Han 2015). In each film, the gangster-hero is only a gangster because their family is a gang. In *Hwayi*, Hwayi's family consists of five men who kidnapped him when he was an infant, and in *Coin Locker Girl*, Il-young's family is a gang headed by a woman, referred to as Mother, who raises orphaned and abandoned children as her debt collectors and thugs. Although each film's generic identity is debatable, the term 'gangster' most aptly describes each protagonist. The inclusion of these films is also informed by the overall focus of Chapter VII, which examines the influence of genre-mixing during the Post-Revival Era. Accordingly, Chapter VII examines many gangster films that feature non-typical genre elements.

Overall, the thesis's corpus features forty-five films: seven released during the Golden Age, one released during the Dark Age, fifteen released during New Korean Cinema and twenty-two released during the post-2006 period. It is important to emphasise that the thesis's corpus is not meant to be understood as a definitive list of Korean gangster films. Rather, it is meant solely to accommodate this thesis's research objective: to chart the Korean gangster genre's development, with a particular emphasis on the changing representation of gangster-heroes.

³⁶ Although both *Sunflower* and *Unstoppable* feature protagonists who were gangsters, the thesis only includes *Sunflower* in its corpus. This is because the film's protagonist is defined by his former life as a gangster. In *Unstoppable* the protagonist's life as a former gangster is used solely to explain his fighting skills.

3.5 Conclusion

The methodological choices outlined in this chapter assist in accomplishing three objectives:

i) defining genre, ii) defining the gangster genre, and iii) constructing a film corpus.

The first objective is accomplished through the combined use of Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach, which emphasises the recurrent use of genre elements, and Neale's (2000) theory of genre development, which emphasises the changing of genre elements. The idea of combining both approaches stems from Grindon (2007), whose work also informs the thesis's rationale that genre development is shaped by three factors: external social influences, film industry factors and internal genre changes.

The second and third objectives are underpinned by a single concept: Pate's (2016) gangster-hero concept, which the thesis adopts to create an *a priori* definition of the gangster genre: a film featuring a gangster-hero. Although this definition may seem overly restrictive, it enables the thesis to include a diverse selection of films in its corpus. Indeed, while various criteria are necessary for a gangster character to be classified as a gangster-hero, the fact that a film needs only to feature a gangster-*hero* to be a gangster *film* allows the thesis to consider films that feature elements not commonly associated with the gangster genre.

Chapter IV: Marginalised: The Early Pre-Revival Era (1958 - 1969)

4.1 Introduction

It is difficult to examine the origins of Korean gangster cinema as there is a dearth of English-language research on Korean gangster films made before 1990. Indeed, while scholars suggest that the genre experienced a revival in the 1990s and early 2000s – Kim (2019, p.510) refers to it as “a shift”, Plaice (2020, p.3) refers to it as a “new cycle”, Min et al. (2003, p.173) brand it “new gangster cinema” and Choi (2010b, p.49) refer to it as a “new era” – only two scholars acknowledge the existence of films made during Pre-Revival Era. These scholars are Jinhee Choi (2016, p.218; 2010a, pp.60-61; 2010b, pp.47-48), who briefly mentions films made in the 1970s, and Jinsoo An (2018), who examines a single 1970s film, *A True Story of Kim Du-han*, albeit only to discuss how marginalised figures shape colonial narratives.

Whether a similar research gap exists in Korean-language academia is difficult to parse, as English-language scholars rarely cite Korean sources. In addition, searches using the three *hangeul* equivalents of ‘gangster film’, *깡패 영화* (*kkangpae yeonghwa*), *조폭 영화* (*jopok yeonghwa*) and *건달 영화* (*geondal yeonghwa*), yield limited results on Korean-language academic databases such as *earticle*, *KISS* and *DBpia*. For example, out of 3,995,745 articles on *DBpia*, the three *hangeul* terms collectively return only 89 sources, many of which are unrelated to the gangster genre and none of which seem to examine gangster films made before 1970.³⁷

³⁷ Admittedly, the specified method of finding relevant Korean-language sources is rather simplistic. Nevertheless, even if relevant sources can be found elsewhere, the paltry number of results on *DBpia* (89 results), *earticle* (44 results) and *KISS* (47 results) seems to indicate that the gangster genre has not received much more scholarly attention in Korean-language academia than English-language academia. Indeed, some of these results are not even related to Film Studies, and there seems to be some overlap between each of the database’s results, so the number of relevant sources is likely much lower than it appears.

The lack of research may stem from the fact that “genre research is still in its nascent stage in Korean film studies” (Park 2019, p.109). Indeed, Lee, S. (2023, p.4) notes that no major English-language study of Korean cinema existed before 1980. Although Lee, S. (2023, p.11) notes that the field has since progressed significantly, he emphasises that it remains “challenging to find scholarly articles on pre-1990s Korean films.”

Regardless of the explanation, the lack of research on early Korean gangster cinema makes it presumptuous to assume that it existed before 1990. This does not mean that the theorists who suggest otherwise are incorrect. Rather, it seems pertinent to closely examine their claims, particularly due to the thesis’s unique requirement that a film must feature a gangster-hero to be classified as a gangster film.

The need to investigate whether Korean gangster cinema existed during the Golden Age is complicated by the dominance of melodrama, which, according to Jin (2020, p.110), accounted for 52.5% of all Korean films produced from the late 1950s to the late 1960s. Martin (2014, p.99) suggests that melodrama even formed a “hybrid relationship with other genres.”

A cursory glance at the seven gangster films examined in this chapter – *Forever with You* (*Geudaewa yeongwonhi*, Yu 1958), *The Flower in Hell* (*Jiokhwa*, Shin 1958), *A Bonanza* (*Nodaji*, Jeong 1961), *A Wanted Man* (*Hyeonsang buteun sanai*, Kim 1961), *The Barefooted Young* (*Maenbaleui cheongchun*, Kim 1964), *Black Hair* (*Geomeun meori*, Lee 1964) and *The Starting Point* (*Wonjeom*, Lee 1967) – substantiates Martin’s (2014, p.99) point.³⁸ Although a gangster-hero appears in each film, they are often only one of many protagonists. For example, *A Wanted Man* features four protagonists: Chang-o, the gangster-hero, his sister Ok, and his two childhood friends, Myeong-gu and Yeong-su.

³⁸ These seven films were found using KMDb, the most comprehensive online database of Korean films. For a full description of the process by which the thesis found and selected films to study, see section 3.4 Korean Gangster Cinema.

Considering the lack of research confirming the existence of pre-1990s gangster cinema and the marginal role of the gangster-hero in the films listed above, Chapter IV does not examine *how* the gangster genre emerged during the earliest period of Korean cinema, the Golden Age, but whether it emerged at all. Accordingly, the chapter's central research question is: '*Considering the thesis's definition of a gangster film, did the gangster genre emerge in the Golden Age?*' If the genre *did* emerge, a second question must be asked: '*What socio-cultural, industrial or generic factors influenced the genre's initial development?*'

The chapter addresses these research questions by first examining how gangsters and the underworld are represented during the Early Pre-Revival Era in section 4.2 Outcast. In doing so, it considers the influence of censorship and the realities of organised crime during the postwar period, finding that both are likely responsible for the Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-hero being more defined by his class than his criminality. Section 4.3 Sympathy for the Gangster follows this discussion by detailing how the dominance of melodrama during the Golden Age has further weakened the gangster's criminality, with most films focusing on matters of love rather than matters of the underworld. Many films also feature prominent elements of melodrama, such as the genre's emphasis on pathos and fate. The influence of melodrama is most apparent when considering how the films examined in this chapter render conflicts between modern and traditional values, a prominent conflict in melodramas, as discussed in section 4.4 Between Two Minds.

4.2 Outcast: The Elimination of Gangsters on Streets and on Screens

In the edited book *The Park Chung-hee Era: The Transformation of South Korea* (Kim and Vogel 2011), the word 'gangster' is used once. It appears in a direct quote from a speech Park Chung-hee made in 1972: "Wiping out *gangsters* is a case in point. If you have important tasks to implement, don't be constrained by the law!" (Park 1992 cited in Moon and Jun 2011, pp.129-130, author's italics).

Although scholars Chung-in Moon and Byung-joon Jun (2011, pp.129-130) use the quote to highlight Park's 'above-the-law' approach to national governance, it also illuminates Park's intolerance toward organised crime. Criminologist Jonson Nathaniel Porteux (2013, p.95) notes that within days of Park's 1961 coup, which saw him and the Korean military successfully seize power, 167 high-profile gangsters were arrested and paraded through Seoul's streets. To further humiliate the gangsters, the government forced them to carry signs stating, "I am a gangster, I will accept the people's judgement" (Mobrand 2016, p.664; Porteux 2013, p.95).³⁹

Criminologist Andreas Schloenhardt (2010, p.275) states that the government's swift campaign against organised crime – from 1961 to 1963, police arrested 13,000 organised criminals (Porteux 2013, p.50; Schloenhardt 2010, p.275; Lee 2006, p.65; Park, Y.K. 2004, p.61) – was motivated by the belief that it represented an affront to government authority.

Porteux (2013, p.96) implies that the matter was more complex, noting that such "anti-criminal campaigns" were enacted to win public support rather than eradicate social disorder. Mobrand (2016, p.664) notes that these campaigns targeted "politically-linked gang members", particularly those who had been allies of The Liberal Party, which had been in power from 1952 to 1960. Whatever the underlying reasons behind the campaign, the result was notable: the almost total eradication of gangsters from Korean society (Schloenhardt 2010, p.275; Lee 2006, p.65; Park, Y.K. 2004, p.62). As Park, Y.K. (2004, p.62) states, "crime groups almost vanished" during this period.

Golden Age cinema directly reflects the marginal status of gangsters in postwar Korea. Most gangster-heroes are more akin to petty hoodlums than organised criminals. Poor, marginalised and relegated to the seedy confines of Korea's underworld, their

³⁹ There are slight discrepancies between Mobrand (2016, p.664) and Porteux's (2013, p.95) recounting of this event. Mobrand (2016, p.664) states that only 150 gangsters were paraded through the streets, whereas Porteux (2013, p.95) states there were 167. In addition, while Mobrand (2016, p.664) states that only one gangster, Yi Jong-jae, was forced to wear a humiliating sign, Porteux (2013, p.95) implies that many gangsters wore such signs.

criminality seems more akin to a survival tactic than a blatant disregard for law and order. In *A Bonanza*, gangsters are so impoverished that withholding food is used as a disciplinary punishment. Yeong-ok, the film's gangster-hero, does not even seem to have a home – she is only ever seen in her gang's dank hideout or on city streets, making her more akin to a homeless hoodlum than a professional criminal.

The marginal status of gangsters is evidenced by the settings of most films. When gangster-heroes are not skulking in dark alleys or accosting passersby on city streets, they are hiding in their lairs or offices. In *A Wanted Man*, the gang is headquartered in a sordid lair, hidden behind a bookcase in a shady office. Similarly, in *The Barefooted Young*, the gangsters are rarely seen beyond their boss's office, secreted away in a nondescript building.

A gangster's rank does not change their marginal status. Although Dong-il, the gangster-hero of *Black Hair*, is a gang boss who owns a bar, he and his men are mainly situated in the bar's dank basement. Hyun S. Park (2015, p.99) states that the desolate backstreets and interiors that characterise *Black Hair* expose the realities of postwar Korea, undermining the government's efforts to modernise the country.

Although there is no evidence that the depiction of gangsters was censored during the Golden Age, the marginal status of gangsters seems indicative of Park Chung-hee's interest in eliminating gangsters from Korea. This idea is furthered by the particularly negative portrayal of the criminal underworld. In fact, every film released after 1960 included in the chapter's corpus ends with the gangster-hero's death. Although the gangster-hero's death is discussed more in 4.4 *Between Two Minds*, it is relevant to note that their death seems to serve as a condemnation of the underworld.

This condemnation of gangsters is particularly evident in the ending of *The Barefooted Young*. After Doo-soo commits suicide, his gang boss and his boss's lieutenant, Deok-tae, go to see his body. They are so disturbed and guilt-ridden by Doo-soo's death that they immediately surrender themselves to the police. Although neither man was directly

involved in Doo-soo's death, both men seem to believe they deserve punishment just for being gangsters. Dong-il seems to harbour a similar belief in *Black Hair*. As he bleeds to death at the end of the film, the gang boss condemns himself, saying, "*My death's no call for pity. I chose evil. Not even a bit of affection to mourn my death. In my final moments, I feel terrible loneliness for the first time. So, this is how I die. Without a single flower to mark my grave.*"

Dong-il's beliefs are at odds with his actions. Although he was not a good man, he was not outright evil. As Darcy Paquet (2019) notes, Dong-il is "a contradictory figure with a bit of the air of a tragic Greek hero." His death is at least pitiful – he dies protecting his wife and her new lover from his own men. A question arises then: is Dong-il simply blind to his admirable qualities, or blind to these qualities because of government censorship?

Indeed, while there is no evidence to suggest that censorship influenced the cinematic depiction of organised crime, it seems unlikely that it did not due to the extent of censorship during the period. As historian Bok-rae Kim (2018, p.19) notes, Park Chung-hee and his military government believed mass media was "a tool for promoting his regime's legitimacy, national unity as a whole, anti-communism and modernization." Accordingly, censorship was strict, extensive and all-encompassing. Shim (2010, p.32) states that soon after the 1961 coup, "all film producers and importers were forced to visit the censorship department...to introduce themselves and apply for censorship, with two copies of scripts and one censorship application form."

Darcy Paquet (2005, p.34) states that the government had the power to censor or modify films at will, with even seemingly innocuous material [being]...removed for mysterious reasons." By 1962, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.85) note that the government enforced both pre- *and* post-production censorship, suppressing subversive political messages and forcing filmmakers to imbue their films with state-mandated ideals such as militarism and anti-communism. Due to the implementation of strict censorship, Yecies and

Shim (2016, p. 20) believe that “the domestic film industry...was reduced to the status of a propaganda factory in which all productions were classified as either “hard” or “soft” propaganda.”

One aspect of government censorship that seems likely to have influenced the depiction of gangsters and the criminal underworld onscreen is the stipulation, added in the newly revised Motion Picture Law of 1966, that films featuring detailed depictions of crimes or violence were liable to be banned (Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.86). While most of the films included in this chapter were released *before* this revised Motion Picture Law, it seems logical to conclude that if the government banned excessive violence and criminality in 1966, both had been at risk of censorship in the years immediately beforehand.

This is substantiated by the depiction, or lack thereof, of violence and criminality in each of the seven films discussed in this chapter. Indeed, Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes are rarely particularly violent or criminal. In addition, knives and guns appear rarely and are used even more rarely. For example, *The Barefooted Young's* most violent scene is a brief knife fight that lasts for only thirty-five seconds.

In addition, gratuitous or excessive violence is usually depicted off-screen. This is most evident in *Black Hair*. After Dong-il's men discover that his wife, Yeong-shil, is cheating on him, they force him to punish her in accordance with their gang's rules.⁴⁰ In a bedroom, two gangsters restrain Yeong-shil as a third, armed with a broken bottle, stalks toward her. The blocking and framing heighten the threat of violence – the third gangster holds the broken bottle dramatically aloft throughout the scene, and director Lee Man-hee makes it the focal point of nearly every shot.

As the gangster nears Yeong-shil, the camera follows behind him. Yeong-shil is brightly lit, but the gangster and the bottle are in darkness, their silhouettes framed below

⁴⁰ Yeong-shil is not actually cheating on Dong-il. Rather, she is being raped and blackmailed by a rival gangster. Nevertheless, this constitutes cheating in the eyes of Dong-il's men and they blame her for infringing upon their gang's rules.

Yeong-shil's terrified face. A reverse shot depicts the gangster's face, veiled in shadow until he steps into the light, which reveals a set of gruesome scars across his right eye and cheek, telegraphing the potential nature of Yeong-shil's punishment. Park (2015, p.97) observes that the gangster's movement toward Yeong-shil heightens the tension between Yeong-shil and the gangster. Just before the gangster strikes her, there is a brief close-up of the bottle with Yeong-shil's face seen behind it, the jagged edges of the bottle lining up with her petrified eyes. However, despite having built up so much tension, Lee Man-hee obscures the violence by cutting to a medium-wide shot focused on the gangster's back as he strikes Yeong-shil.

When an Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-hero *does* commit a crime, it is usually petty or vague. In *A Bonanza*, Yeong-ok works as a pickpocket, and in *The Starting Point*, Seok-gu steals some nondescript files from a nondescript office building. Doo-soo's most heinous crime in *The Barefooted Young* is smuggling a batch of watches. In fact, the only other criminal acts Doo-soo commits are rather comical. In one scene, he swindles a man by resoling his shoes. In another, he bumps into people on the street while listening to a radio, claims that their clumsiness has made him break his radio, and pressures them into giving him money to fix it. Both criminal acts further Doo-soo's image as a hoodlum rather than a full-fledged gangster.

Although censorship was extensive during the period, it does not seem to be the sole factor influencing the depiction of organised crime in the Golden Age. As film genre theorist Grindon (2007, p.409) notes, external social influences, rather than industrial factors, are often the primary determinant of genre development.

The influence of external social influences on the development of the Revival Era is evidenced by the depiction of gangsters in *Forever with You* and *The Flower in Hell*. Although both films were released *before* Park Chung-hee's government assumed control of the film industry, they depict gangsters in a similar manner to films made afterwards.

Although the gang in *Forever with You* is more powerful than the gangs in most 1960s films – it masquerades as a company, *Dong-il Corp*, and operates a hostess bar – it consists of less than half a dozen men and is based out of a dingy office.⁴¹

Similarly, although *The Flower in Hell* features a lengthy action sequence in which the film's gang rob a train, the gangsters are more akin to a band of thieves than a criminal organisation. Before their grand heist, the gangsters strategise among the ruins of a shanty town. Instead of donning fancy suits, they wear ragged, ordinary clothes, as if they only work part-time as criminals. In fact, when the gang's leader, the gangster-hero Young-shik, is not planning heists with his men, he is hawking products on the streets.

The depiction of gangsters in *The Flower in Hell* and *Forever with You* contrasts with the reality of organised crime in the 1950s. As Lee (2006, p.64) notes, organised crime gangs were both “an influential force in the entertainment districts” and active participants in the political realm, “associating with politicians, guarding them from danger and disrupting the political rallies of competing politicians.”

While the gang's ownership of a hostess club in *Forever with You* may reflect organised crime's involvement in the entertainment business, it seems notable that neither it nor *The Flower in Hell* depict the gangster's role in Korean politics. In fact, based upon Lee's (2006, p.64) description of organised crime during the 1950s, *Friend: The Great Legacy*, a 2013 gangster film partly set in the early 1960s, is more historically accurate than *Forever with You*, *The Flower in Hell* or any of the Early Pre-Revival Era films examined in this chapter.

Overall, then, while censorship seems to have affected the gangster's portrayal, it does not seem to have *defined* their portrayal. In fact, the gangster-heroes of *Forever with*

⁴¹ Popular in Korea and Japan, a hostess bar is a bar which mainly employs female staff and caters primarily to men.

You and *The Flower in Hell*, as well as the gangster-heroes of 1960s gangster films, are defined more by social status than by violence or criminality.

For example, the gangster-hero in *Forever with You*, Gwang-pil, is only a boy when he first turns to crime. He seems to have no other choice – his hometown is a poor village, his mother is debt-ridden, and his father is dead.

Forever with You's (Yu 1958) unflinching depiction of life for poor Koreans reflects director Yu Hyun-mok's efforts to explore "themes around the human condition" in postwar Korea (Shim 2010, p.182). Shim (2010, p.182) notes that Yu mixed expressionist and modernist elements to create an "aesthetics of devastation" that embodied the despair which enveloped the period.

One brief example of Yu's style occurs early in the film when, after Gwang-pil and Dal-soo decide to settle a disagreement with their fists, Yu cuts to a shot of two mangy dogs fighting before cutting to a shot of the two boys fighting. The image of the two dogs mirrors the image of the two boys, highlighting the 'survival of the fittest' nature of lower-class life. Furthermore, Yu sets the scene on a set of railway tracks, using the *mise-en-scène* to position the young hoodlums on the literal fringes of society.

Despite being a gangster, Gwang-pil's life is not defined by his criminality so much as it is by his social status, or lack thereof. After pickpocketing a woman, Gwang-pil feels guilty when she begins to cry and suggests that they give her money back. To this, Dal-soo replies, "*What? Dude are you crazy? You must not be hungry to be able to say that.*" Dal-soo's disbelief suggests that money is not a luxury for the young boys but is as essential as food or water.⁴²

A lack of money defines the lives of most other postwar gangster-heroes. In *The Flower in Hell*, Young-shik is so focused on becoming rich that he refuses to return home

⁴² Although the word 'dude' is anachronistic to both the time of the film's setting and release, this line is reproduced here as it appears in the Korean Film Archive's translation of the film.

even after his younger brother, Dong-shik, begs him to do so and tells him that their mother is sick. Despite his refusal to return home, Young-shik is not an unlikeable character. He is not motivated by greed but by a desperate urge to escape poverty. Shim (2010, p.140) notes that *The Flower in Hell's* (Shin 1958) director, Shin Seong-il, often made films with characters seeking “questionable pathways” out of economic difficulty.

Gangsters are not the only people who are marginalised in postwar Korea. In Early Pre-Revival Era films, the postwar underworld is not only a hive of villainy but also a home to Korea's most desperate and impoverished citizens. Prostitutes, drug addicts, broken families and troubled youths all inhabit the same spaces as gangsters. In *The Flower in Hell*, Young-shik's gang live in the same shantytown as a cohort of prostitutes who ‘serve’ the US soldiers stationed in the nearby military base. There is an odd kinship between the prostitutes and gangsters, a makeshift community bonded by marginalisation and poverty.

Steven Chung (2019, p.137) states that the film “highlights some of the most pressing social problems of early postwar South Korea.” Darcy Paquet (2023) echoes this point, noting that the film is one of the few made in the postwar era which presents “the hard realities of day-to-day existence with...honest force”. Although neither Chung, S. (2019, p.137) nor Paquet (2023) describe what these ‘pressing social problems’ or ‘harsh realities’ were, it seems logical to assume that they are referring to issues relating to the extreme poverty present in Korea after the Korean War (1950 - 1953).

South Korea in the 1950s was a terribly depressing place, where extreme privation and degradation touched everyone. Cadres of orphans ran through the streets...;beggars with every affliction or war injury importuned anyone with a wallet, often travelling in bunches of maimed or starved adults holding children or babies; half-ton trucks full of pathetic women careened onto military bases for the weekend, so they could sell whatever services they had (Cumings 2005, p.318).

Although historians Byung-Kook Kim and Ezra F. Vogel (2011, p.1) note that socio-economic conditions quickly improved after Park Chung-hee seized power in 1961, historian Bruce Cumings (2005, p.218) notes that “[e]ven twenty years after the war ended Felliniesque [sic] residues of [the Korean War] remained, in the dreadful slums...in

downtown Seoul or the packs of orphans who still begged in the streets.” Indeed, Kim and Vogel (2011, p.1) note that while Park transformed Korea into an “industrial powerhouse”, its transformation came with “massive political, social, and economic costs.”

Among those left out of postwar, modernized South Korea were the workers, who were never adequately compensated for their labor; the poor, who stayed poor and became even more marginalized as the state sought to hide their existence within the newly industrializing nation; women, whose gender-based oppression never fundamentally changed; and even some men who did not fit the state-sponsored ideal of the new Korean masculinity (Jeong 2006, p.132).

As Jeong (ibid.) suggests, Korea’s economy may have flourished during the 1960s, but the lower classes languished in poverty and misfortune. This point is echoed by Park (2015, p.98), who notes that as Park Chung-hee’s regime modernised the country, political corruption and social inequality led to high rates of crime, violence and injustice in Korean cities.

Accordingly, it is unsurprising that the atmosphere of discontent which characterises *Forever with You* and *The Flower in Hell* – both made *before* Park took power – is present in every film in the chapter’s corpus made *after* Park took power. Indeed, nearly every film in the chapter’s corpus features distinct examples of the marginalised citizens Jeong (2006, p.132) describes.

For example, after Yeong-shil is mutilated and exiled by her husband, Dong-il, in *Black Hair*, she becomes a prostitute. Park, S. (2015, pp.95-96) states that the downward trajectory of Yeong-shil’s life “shows not only the gangster’s domination of urban culture but also the state of torpor in the socially outcast people’s daily experience.” In one scene, she brings a customer to a makeshift brothel that doubles as a family home for the woman who runs it. Children run amok as their mother haggles with Yeong-shil over the price of a room. Both women approach the situation with the same unfazed attitude that they might display while haggling over groceries. The mundanity of the exchange only heightens its horror.

The unflinching portrayal of life in Korea's underworld exemplifies director Lee Man-hee's efforts, according to Shim and Yecies (2016, p.69), to offer a truthful view of "a society that had survived the trauma of civil war." Indeed, it is likely no coincidence that both *Black Hair* and *The Starting Point*, both of which Lee directed, feature prostitutes in leading roles.

Much to his detriment, *The Barefooted Young's* (Kim 1964) gangster-hero, Doo-soo, defines himself by his lower-class status. While arguing with his upper-class girlfriend, Joanna, Doo-soo uses his troubled background to distance himself from her and the upper-class world she represents, telling her, "*My father died serving jail time and my mother was a prostitute.*" Doo-soo does not do this out of hatred for Joanna but rather out of embarrassment. Much to his chagrin, the class division between him and his girlfriend – Joanna is from a rich family, and Doo-soo is a poor orphaned hoodlum – overshadows their relationship.

Overall, Doo-soo's lower-class status, rather than his criminality, serves to marginalise him throughout *The Barefooted Young*. In one scene, Joanna takes Doo-soo to a family friend, hoping to get him a job in a factory. Unfortunately, Doo-soo's bad table manners – slurping his soup, eating steak with his hands and struggling to use a knife and fork – expose him as the lowly hoodlum he desperately wishes he was not. Humiliated, he lashes out, yelling, "*I'm just a street thug with no skills whatsoever*", and flees from Joanna and her efforts to help him. As film critic Hayley Scanlon (2017) notes, Doo-soo is trapped by every aspect of his life: the gangsters he works for, his troubled family background and "the general lack of opportunities for poor boys in...1960s Korea." Later in the film, Doo-soo tells Joanna, "*A scumbag like me doesn't deserve to be loved. You say you love me, but you don't know me. I'm a cancer to society. You have no idea what kind of people we are.*"

The fact that Doo-soo does not explicitly refer to himself as a gangster highlights the fact that he defines himself by poverty more than he does criminality. Indeed, Soonyoung

Lee (2023, p.52) suggests that Doo-soo's "life journey should be understood in terms of social class." Accordingly, while the 'we' in Doo-soo's sentence could be interpreted in various ways, it seems logical to assume that it refers to the lower class.

Alternatively, it might refer to Korea's postwar youth. As Chunghwa Chung (2016, p.12) states, *The Barefooted Young* represented the height of the youth film genre. A popular genre during the 1960s, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.93) note that Korean youth films often depicted a defiant young generation lashing out against the "conservative establishment with its rigid social hierarchies." In addition, Lee, S. (2023, pp.39-51) notes that the genre highlighted class division and the Korean War's destructive toll on the family unit.

...[the] biggest psychological problem in Korean [youth] films... the absence of family. The narratives of the Korean youth romance film genre are fundamentally driven by the desire to overcome the protagonists' state as orphans and to create a family [sic] (Lee, S. 2023, p.51).

Although Chung (2016, p.12) states that the youth film boom did not begin until 1963, *The Barefooted Young* is not the only film in the chapter's corpus which highlights issues relevant to Korea's youth. *The Flower in Hell*, *A Bonanza* and *A Wanted Man* all highlight class division and feature young protagonists with troubled family backgrounds. Another example is *The Starting Point*. Aside from featuring a young, orphaned protagonist, the film stars Shin Seong-il, who played Doo-soo in *The Barefooted Young* and was, according to Yecies and Shim (2016, p.94), the "leading young heartthrob in Korean cinema" at the time.

4.3 Sympathy for the Gangster: The Influence of Melodrama

In addition to being defined more by their class than their criminality, Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes are also rather unconcerned with matters of the underworld. Instead, most are concerned with matters of the heart.

For example, in *Forever with You*, Gwang-pil is more preoccupied with rekindling his relationship with his childhood love, Ae-ran, following his release from prison, than resuming his career as a petty criminal. *The Starting Point's* Seok-gu is largely indifferent

to being a gangster – after a job goes wrong, he refuses to apologise to his boss and seems unconcerned with the possibility of being kicked out of the gang. After being sent to the Taebak mountains to lie low, Seok-gu frets more about his burgeoning romance with the prostitute pretending to be his wife than his place in his gang. The fact that the film is almost totally set in the Taebak mountains further distances Seok-gu – and the film – from the underworld.

Even Dong-il of *Black Hair* – a film totally set in the urban underworld – is more concerned with matters of the heart than of the underworld: after his wife, Yeong-shil, is caught sleeping with another man, Dong-il’s men force him to punish her as per his gang’s rules, and he suffers great personal torment in the process.⁴³ The gang’s rules are so specific that they seem deliberately designed to catalyse the film’s romantic drama. As one gangster tells Yeong-shil, “*Bitches who cheat get their faces cut up. Anyone who helps her get rid of the scars will get it worse. Under no circumstances can she leave her lover.*”

The romantic and tragic plots of *Forever with You*, *The Starting Point* and *Black Hair* are each indicative of the influence of melodrama during the Golden Age. Indeed, melodrama was the dominant genre of the Golden Age: melodramas accounted for 50-70% of all Korean films produced in the 1960s (Jin 2020, p.110; Shim 2011, p.186; Min et al. 2003, p.43). Considering the genre’s widespread success during the period, it is unsurprising that Martin (2014, p.99) states that melodrama “pervades almost every popular [Korean] genre to some degree.”

According to Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.20), one of Golden Age melodrama’s distinct traits was its “focus on ordinary lower-middle- and working-class citizens.”⁴⁴ Paquet (2007, p.56) makes a similar point, noting that Golden Age melodramas often highlighted

⁴³ As noted previously in this chapter, Yeong-shil is not actually sleeping with another man but rather being blackmailed and raped, a fact Dong-il’s men ignore.

⁴⁴ This difference between American and Korean melodrama substantiates the importance of examining Korean cinema, whether it be Korean melodramas or Korean gangster films, using research specific to Korean cinema, history and culture.

economic strife, class differences and social issues. In the chaos and poverty of postwar Korea, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.21) state that “[m]elodrama sided with the underprivileged masses suffering social and familial alienation in the shadow margins of modernization and economic development.” In fact, McHugh (2001, pp.5-6) argues that Golden Age melodrama “has much less to do with individual morality and metaphysical clashes...than it does with an unrelenting emphasis on the fallibility of...social and political systems.”

As section 4.2 illustrates, most Early Pre-Revival Era films maintain the melodrama’s focus on the underprivileged masses. Yet, this is not the only characteristic that these films share with melodrama. The Pre-Revival Era features the same “precipitous falls...[,] dramatic and sudden reversals [and] remarkable coincidences” that Abelmann and McHugh (2005, p.2) state characterise Golden Age melodrama.

Together, these narrative characteristics create an overarching sense of fate throughout many of the films discussed in this chapter. Indeed, fate is so often the primary driver of narrative in the Pre-Revival Era that certain characters explicitly refer to it. In *A Wanted Man*, Chang-o’s transformation from a lowly orphan into a fearsome gang boss is blamed on fate by a former friend, who says, “*What happened to Chang-o is nothing but fate.*” Similarly, Gwang-pil explicitly blames fate for his despair in *Forever with You*, asking himself, “*What should I do with my bad fate?*” In each film, the character’s anguish substantiates Plaice’s (2020, p.7) note that Korean melodrama more often emphasises frustration and suffering than resolution.

Although fate is not always explicitly foregrounded by Early Pre-Revival Era films, it permeates the narrative of every film discussed in this chapter. Remarkable coincidences and sudden reversals are particularly common. In *The Flower in Hell*, the brothers Dong-shik and Young-shik are reunited by chance – despite not knowing where his brother might be in Seoul, Dong-shik spots him on a random street. In *The Barefooted Young*, lovers-to-

be Doo-soo and Ae-ran meet when Doo-soo happens upon a gangster threatening Ae-ran and her friend in an alley. In *A Bonanza*, a cruel twist of fate leads to the death of Yeong-ok's mother, who is hit by a train when she gets stuck on a set of train tracks at the rail yard where she scavenges for coal.

Although these fateful events might seem random or ephemeral, fate's influence on the Early Pre-Revival Era films is pervasive. To the sorrowful characters of early gangster cinema, fate brings only anguish and misfortune. If fate does not lead immediately to misfortune, as it does for Yeong-ok in *A Bonanza*, it works slowly and in the background. Indeed, while Dong-shik and Young-shik's chance encounter in *The Flower in Hell* initially seems fortuitous, it ultimately leads to Young-shik's death.

Overall, the Pre-Revival Era features the same "pathos" that Nancy Abelmann and Kathleen McHugh (2005, p.2) state characterise Golden Age melodrama. Indeed, it permeates the mise-en-scène of every film examined in the chapter. Tragedy underlies the first shot of *Forever with You*, which pans over the rooftops of a lower-class neighbourhood before lingering on three children playing in dirt beside a prison wall. Tragedy characterises the grimy underworld of *Black Hair*, a home to criminals, cab drivers, families and prostitutes alike. Tragedy also characterises the aimless, troubled life of Doo-soo in *The Barefooted Young*, who, as an orphaned working-class youth in postwar Korea, has little to do other than wander the city, wallow in bars and start pointless fights.

Although section 4.4 *Between Two Minds* discusses the gangster-hero's death in more detail, it is important to note that the tragic nature of Early Pre-Revival Era films is particularly evident in their endings. Indeed, except for *Forever with You* and *A Bonanza*, every film examined in this chapter culminates with the gangster-hero's death.

The most tragic death in any of the films examined in this chapter is Seok-gu's in *The Starting Point*. After he defeats a rival gangster in a lengthy one-on-one fight, it seems as if Seok-gu and his new lover, the prostitute Seon, will begin a new life together. However, as

Seok-gu climbs toward Seon, who is waiting for him at the top of a mountainside staircase, he is shot in the back by a sniper.

In an instant, Seok-gu and Seon's burgeoning romance ends, shattering their hopes of escaping the underworld together. Seok-gu literally slips away from Seon, stumbling against the staircase railing before crumpling to the ground. Now that Seok-gu is dead, Seon has no choice but to return to her dismal life working as a prostitute in Seoul. Director Lee Man-hee makes this fact explicitly clear by continuing the film *after* Seok-gu's death, cross-fading from the Taebak mountains to a dimly lit city street. The film's final shot mirrors an earlier one: Seon turns down a shady alley, and a man slinks behind her. Literally and figuratively, nothing has changed. Although Seok-gu saves her from death, Seon remains trapped in her horrid life. As the film ends, it is hard not to recall something Seon said earlier in the film: "*When a woman meets misfortune, she becomes a prostitute. What happens when a prostitute meets misfortune?*"

4.4 Between Two Minds: Tensions Between Modern and Traditional Values

In addition to the many melodramatic elements discussed in section 4.3, there is another prominent melodramatic element that characterises the genre's earliest films: tensions between modern and traditional values.

In fact, Plaice (2020, p.4) states that both melodramas *and* gangster films "address contradictions between tradition and modernity." Plaice (2020, p.4) implies that these contradictions were created, or at least heightened, by state-led modernisation in the postwar period. Moon and Jun (2011, p.116) note that after Park Chung-hee took power in 1961, "[c]ivil society was reorganized and mobilized...along the military ideals of order, discipline, and collectivism." Even before Park Chung-hee took power, modernisation was an important topic in the 1950s.

Public life in the postwar 1950s was suffused with debates about how South Korea should become modern...Which parts of traditional culture and society should be retained, and

which should be left behind? Which foreign ideas could be absorbed into South Korean life, and which should be rejected? Should all sectors of Korean life become modernized, or should some pockets be preserved in their traditional forms? And what about the pace of change: should South Korea seek to become modern all at once, or would a more incremental transformation be preferable? (Klein 2019, p.120).

These debates continued into the 1960s. As Yecies and Shim (2016, p.143) note, 1960s melodramas “began focusing more on the tensions between modern family life and Korea’s traditional Confucian and patriarchal family systems.”⁴⁵

Although Yecies and Shim (2016, p.143) infer that tensions between modern and traditional values were limited to the realm of family, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.25) note that Golden Age melodramas mediated “confrontations, conflicts and compromises among [many] rivalling values and camps...tradition and modernity; the ruling class and the working class; male and female; the urban and rural.”

Among the films discussed in this chapter, tensions between modernity and tradition are mainly rendered along the registers of gender (male vs. female), culture (American vs. Korean) and location (rural vs. urban), with gender being the most prominent.

Indeed, unlike subsequent eras of Korean gangster cinema, the Early Pre-Revival Era features prominent male *and* female characters. Although female characters mainly serve as love interests, they are often the crux of a film’s narrative. Ae-ran is bedridden in most of *Forever with You*, but the gangster-hero’s entire life revolves around her. As a kid, Gwang-pil fawns over her, competing with his gang’s leader, Dal-soo, for her affection. As a man, he tries to rekindle their love following his release from prison and is distraught when he discovers that she is now married to Dal-soo. Since Gwang-pil defines his worth by Ae-ran’s affection, he is emasculated, devolving from an admirable man to a pathetic one.

⁴⁵ As Yecies and Shim (2016, p.143) infer, traditional Korean values are informed by Confucianism, a conservative philosophy which, according to historian Bruce Cumings (2005, p.20), stresses “tradition,...ritual, disdain for material things, commerce,...obedience to superiors, and a preference for relatively frozen social hierarchies.” Since certain scholars such as Cumings (2005, p.20) and Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.47) have suggested that scholarly discussion focuses too much on Confucianism’s influence on Korean culture, the thesis has avoided discussing it. Even so, when this thesis refers to ‘traditional values’, this can be generally understood to refer to the tenets of Confucianism described by Cumings (ibid.).

Gwang-pil's emasculation is most evident when he first meets with Dal-soo after his release from prison. Director Yu Hyun-mok artfully blocks the scene so that Dal-soo is always in a position of power over Gwang-pil, emphasising the latter's fractured sense of masculinity. When the two men meet face to face, Dal-soo is ebullient and relaxed, but Gwang-pil is morose and tense. The camera looks down at Gwang-pil slumped in his chair while Dal-soo leers behind him. As the scene progresses, Dal-soo stands behind Gwang-pil, forcing him to talk over his shoulder, before leaning over and speaking directly into Gwang-pil's ear. When he finally sits down, Dal-soo sits back, puts his leg on the table between them and proclaims that Gwang-pil's relationship with Ae-ran, or "*my wife*" as he boasts, is "*in the past.*"

If, as Chung, S. (2019, p.167) and Kelly Y. Jeong (2019, p.167; 2006, p.154) suggest, female characters represent Korea in postwar melodramas, then the battle between Dal-soo and Gwang-pil for Ae-ran can be read as a battle for the nation's future. As the owner of a salacious hostess club, the corrupt leader of a gang, and an unfaithful lover, Dal-soo symbolises the encroachment of modern values in Korea. Conversely, the humble and honest Gwang-pil symbolises tradition.

Yu's use of Dal-soo and Gwang-pil to symbolise the tension between tradition and modernity reflects McHugh and Abelmann's (2005, p.3) statement that in Golden Age films, "the crises of the nation manifest themselves in persistent gender...trouble." Indeed, Yau (2007, p.277) argues that the male protagonist's desire to heal the female protagonist's trauma in certain melodramas "reflects the idea that Korean people should...protect their country and relieve their historical sufferings."

Although Gwang-pil does not try to relieve Ae-ran's suffering as much as he does his own, Yau's (2007, p.277) observation highlights how genders symbolise broader socio-political themes in Korean melodramas. In fact, Jeong (2019, p.167) echoes this point,

stating that *Aimless Bullet* (Obaltan, Yu 1961) “uses female characters...as a trope for the struggling nation [Korea].”

When viewing female characters as a trope for Korea, it seems evident that *A Bonanza* makes the same point as *Forever with You*, that Korea must be saved from modernity. *A Bonanza* illustrates this point by having its female character, Yeong-ok, join a gang, which becomes the foil to the film’s two traditionally minded male protagonists, Woon-chil, Yeong-ok’s father, and Dong-il, her prospective lover.

Whereas the gang are obsessed with status and money, the male protagonists are, at least comparatively, paragons of tradition. Although Woon-chil was once blinded by greed, he is now a reformed man, seeking to right his past wrongs and reunite with his daughter. Returning to civilisation after years of hunting for gold in the wilderness, he is appalled by modern society. Someone shoulders him on the street, children laugh at him, a jeweller tries to swindle him, hotel staff mistreat him, and conmen try to rob him of his hard-earned gold. Although Dong-il is not as stalwartly traditional as Woon-chil, he is one of the few characters who does not try to con Woon-chil. A reformed gangster attempting to care for his widowed mother, Dong-il is also directly opposed to the film’s gang and their modern values.

Considering that both men embody traditional values, the end of the film, which sees Woon-chil and Dong-il kill the gangsters, rescue Yeong-ok, and walk off into the sunset, seems to represent the triumph of traditional values over modern ones. Indeed, by the end of the film, both men appear to exemplify the disciplined, obedient, nationalistic male subject that Kelly Jeong (2006, p.134) notes the Park Chung-hee government idealised.

Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.73) note that underlying tensions between modern and traditional values were prevalent in films starring Kim Seung-ho, who plays Woon-chil. In fact, Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.72) note that Kim often played a vulnerable patriarch struggling to navigate “the clash between stereotypically traditional/Korean and modern/Western values and lifestyles...in a rapidly urbanizing, developing society.” By

rescuing Yeong-ok then, Woon-chil reclaims the patriarchal role he had abandoned many years before. Indeed, similar to Ae-ran in *Forever with You*, Yeong-ok seems to have two narrative roles: symbolising the nation and legitimising the male protagonist's masculinity.

In *The Flower in Hell*, love makes the gangster-hero subservient to the female protagonist, reversing traditional gender roles. In the film, Sonya, a prostitute Paquet (2023) describes as “predatory and dangerous”, preys on Dong-shik, a traditionally minded young country boy. From the sensual way she dresses to her casual attitude toward sex, Sonya embodies modern values, or more specifically, *Western* values. Chung, S. (2019, p.134) suggests that Sonya and her fellow prostitutes serve as “powerful conduits for the expression of Korean masculinist and nationalist anxieties in the face of American neocolonialist threat.”

Steven Chung's (2019, p.134) point is substantiated by the notable presence of American soldiers throughout *The Flower in Hell*. The film's principal setting, a small ramshackle neighbourhood home to Sonya and her fellow prostitutes, is located along the perimeter of a US military base. In addition, Sonya's first appearance onscreen is with an American soldier who has just availed of her 'services', and American soldiers are prominently featured in b-roll of Seoul.

The prominent depiction of American soldiers in *The Flower in Hell* symbolises the influence of American culture in Korea, which Jeong (2006, p.151) states was at its height during the postwar period. Yecies and Shim (2016, p.143, author's italics) note that Golden Age melodramas dealt “with interpersonal conflicts resulting from the clash between traditional patriarchal and Confucian values...and modern, *Western* ideas.” Accordingly, it seems logical to suggest that tensions between tradition and modernity in Early Pre-Revival Era films are less concerned with the encroachment of modernisation than the encroachment of American culture. Indeed, Park (2012, p.56) notes that “[t]raditional values...served as a

behavioural framework to which Korean people resorted...when they confronted precipitous flows of western modernization.”

The encroachment of American culture is depicted by many of the gangster films examined in this chapter, albeit less prominently than in *The Flower in Hell*. Lee, S. (2023, p.38) argues that *The Barefooted Young*'s frequent displays of youth culture are underlain by American culture. American music blares in the cafes and clubs frequented by the film's gangster-hero, Doo-soo. In addition, multiple scenes depict young people dancing the jive, a dance of American origin. Doo-soo even has pictures of American women and musicians stuck to the walls of his apartment.

Lee, S. (2023, pp.38-39) argues that American culture is not portrayed as being in opposition to Korean culture in *The Barefooted Young* but is merely indicative of the lower class, contrasting the European culture that characterises the upper class, as represented by Doo-soo's upper-class girlfriend, Joanna.

However, by making this point, Lee, S. (2023, p.40) implicitly acknowledges that Western culture, as in American *and* European culture, underlies both lower-class and upper-class Korean culture. Indeed, when Doo-soo and Joanna flee from Doo-soo's gang and Joanna's parents, they are not running from a specific class or type of Western culture, but from Seoul, society, and by extension, modernity. This is substantiated by the location they flee to and ultimately die in: a ramshackle barn in the countryside.

Accordingly, the film seems to link Western values with urbanity and traditional values with rurality. This point is substantiated by Steven Chung's (2019, p.141) statement that rurality is often portrayed as a sanctuary from Americanised modernity in postwar films, “therein [acting] as the seat of a truer and healthier Korean identity.”

The use of setting to underline tensions between modern and traditional values is seen in many other Early Pre-Revival Era films. In *A Wanted Man*, the countryside, where we are introduced to the film's four protagonists, is contrasted with urban Seoul, where the

characters are ultimately beset by strife, anguish and tragedy, and Chang-o is transformed into a gang boss.

In *The Starting Point*, rurality allows Seok-gu and Seon to escape the pressures and stigmas of modern society. Amidst the cold air of the Taebak mountains, they are just a man and a woman rather than a gangster and a prostitute. After Young-shik and Sonya are killed in *The Flower in Hell*, Dong-shik decides to leave Seoul and return home to the countryside. Unlike his older brother and Sonya, he does not succumb to the allure of modern life but rather turns his back on it, joined by a prostitute who shares his disdain for modern life.

As these examples illustrate, rurality is often synonymous with tradition, hope and freedom, whereas urbanity is often synonymous with modernity, moral decay and corruption. Urbanity is also home to the underworld, and so by relation, is associated with organised crime. Accordingly, it seems logical to assume that the gangster-hero is a symbol of modernity. Yet, this is not the case. Although certain gangster-heroes, such as Young-shik in *The Flower in Hell* and Chang-o in *A Wanted Man*, embrace the city and its modern values, others, such as Doo-soo in *The Barefooted Young* and Dong-il in *Black Hair*, are at odds with urbanity and modernity.

As noted above, Doo-soo flees the city with his girlfriend and spends his last waking hours in a rural area. In *Black Hair*, Dong-il frequently visits his rural family home, where he seems most at peace. Given Doo-soo and Dong-il's allegiance to traditional values, or at least their rejection of modern ones, it seems peculiar that both characters die at the end of their respective films. Although each gangster-hero dies, neither film suggests that modern values have triumphed over traditional ones. The opposite is true – both films herald the triumph of tradition over modernity. In *Black Hair*, Dong-il successfully defeats his gangster underlings, allowing his wife and her new lover to live happily together. In *The Barefooted Young*, Doo-soo's death prompts his fellow gang members to surrender themselves to the

police. In addition, his death spurs his best friend to leave Seoul and return home to care for his mother.

The contradictory nature of Doo-soo and Dong-il's deaths is particularly evident when considering the endings of *Forever with You*, *The Flower in Hell* and *A Bonanza*, each of which use the gangster's death to symbolise the inferiority of modern values. The symbolic role of the gangster's death is particularly evident in *The Flower in Hell*, which culminates with the gangster-hero, Young-shik, and his girlfriend, the prostitute Sonya, dying in a misty, nightmarish swamp, their corpses entombed in mud.

The only film in Chapter IV's corpus which seems to depict modernity triumphing over tradition is *The Starting Point*. Despite occupying societal roles often associated with modernity – a gangster and a prostitute – the film's two protagonists are not motivated by greed nor indulge in the superficial pleasures of modern society. Accordingly, when the film ends with the death of the gangster-hero, and the female protagonist, Seon, returning to a life of prostitution, it seems to represent the destruction of tradition.

Of course, it is important to acknowledge that the censorship and government interference that typified the Golden Age, as discussed in section 4.2, make it difficult to parse the true meaning or intent of the Early Pre-Revival Era. In addition, tensions between tradition and modernity were at play throughout the postwar era. Moon and Jun (2011, p.123) note that Park's nationalistic ideology "was not a constant, but a variable changing over time." Although Park initially dismissed and derided Korean history after taking power in 1961, Moon and Jun (*ibid.*) note that his views began to shift in the mid-1960s, and he soon became a proponent of celebrating the legacies of Korean culture and tradition. Perhaps then it is better not to ascribe a specific role or meaning to the gangster during the Pre-Revival Era. Indeed, Jeong (2006, p.130, author's italics) suggests that Golden Age films "offer insight into postwar Korean life and values, and betray Korea's deeply *ambiguous* feelings toward modernity."

4.5 Conclusion

Overall, the contradictory nature of the gangster-hero's death is one of many elements, including the lack of relevant films available to English-language scholars and the lack of research on early Korean gangster cinema, that make it difficult to make definitive statements regarding the gangster genre's existence and development during the Golden Age.

However, the lack of films available to study and the lack of extant research may themselves be statements – they suggest that Korean gangster films were not prominent or numerous enough during the Golden Age to warrant scholarly discussion or to be accessible today. As the chapter has noted, this opinion already seems to be the consensus of the Korean critics that, as Choi (2010a, p.60) states, refer to the gangster genre's emergence in the 1990s as if it were historically unprecedented.

This chapter finds that the matter of the genre's existence during the Golden Age is more complex. To answer the chapter's central research question, '*Considering the thesis's definition of a gangster film, did the gangster genre emerge in the Golden Age?*', it seems evident that the gangster genre did emerge during the Golden Age, albeit in a minor way. Indeed, while each film examined in this chapter features gangster elements – namely gangster characters and minor depictions of crime and violence – these are dramatically overshadowed by melodramatic and romantic elements.

To answer the chapter's second research question – '*What socio-cultural, industrial or generic factors influenced the genre's initial development?*', the genre seems to have been influenced by three factors. The first two factors are the marginal status of real-life gangsters in postwar Korea and the influence of government censorship, particularly after 1961. Although there is no evidence to suggest that the government had stipulations in place regarding the portrayal of onscreen gangsters, it seems logical that the gangster-hero's representation was at least partly influenced by the severe censorship that characterised the

period due to Park Chung-hee's well-publicised efforts to eliminate organised crime and the restrictions placed on depictions of crime and violence in Korean cinema.

The third factor is melodrama. As noted, most of the films discussed in this chapter feature a gangster-hero more concerned with matters of the heart than matters involving their gang. In addition, most films are characterised by elements derivative of melodrama, namely an emphasis on the lower classes, narratives based on fate, a tragic tone, and a focus on tensions between modern and traditional values. The melodramatic nature of these films is most apparent when considering that social status, not criminality, most defines the period's gangster-heroes. Indeed, all seven films examined in this chapter focus more on the harsh realities of postwar Korea than on the inner workings of the underworld.

Overall, it seems more apt to classify these films as members of a new melodramatic sub-genre – the gangster-melodrama – than members of the gangster genre. This supports the idea that genre-mixing catalyses genre development, a point made by genre theorist Grindon (2007, p.406). In fact, Grindon (*ibid.*) notes that the “experimental stage of a genre” – in this case, the Early Pre-Revival Era – “often arises as a spin-off from an established form.” While the gangster genre does not seem to have fully emerged during the Golden Age, the mere fact that it emerged at all during the postwar period represents an important finding.

Chapter V: Action Men: The Late Pre-Revival Era (1970 – 1989)

5.1 Introduction

In 1972, Park Chung-hee's presidency devolved into "full-fledged authoritarianism" with the passing of a new constitution, *Yushin* (Porteux 2013, p.99). Cumings (2005, pp.379-380) notes that *Yushin* removed all term limits, allowed Park to appoint and dismiss the cabinet and prime minister, to designate one-third of the National Assembly, and to revise the constitution at will. As Park (2007, p.16) notes, Park Chung-hee "...brought the political climate to what many consider the nation's lowest point."

Yushin brought intensified government control over the film industry. The 1972 revision of the Motion Picture Law (MPL) permitted only select companies to make films (Jin 2020, p.19), and the newly established Motion Picture Promotion Corporation (MPPC) pressured Korean filmmakers to realise the political and ideological goals of the government (Park 2012, p.59).

Censorship was so strict that any form of social or political commentary was liable to be censored (Yuk 2019, p.35), and filmmakers "seldom regarded film-making as a profit driven business" (Park 2012, p.58). Combined with the increasing market penetration of TV, government interference had a major impact on the Korean film industry (Cho 2019, p.48; Min et al. 2003, pp.51-52). Cho (2019, p. 48) notes that many performance metrics, including the number of films produced and annual viewership, plummeted in 1971. As a result, scholars have since dubbed the 1970s the "Dark Age" of Korean cinema (Jin 2020, p.119; Lee, S. 2019, p.16; Cho 2019, p.48; Yi 2019, p.79; Yecies and Shim 2016, p.81).

According to Jinhee Choi (2010b, p.48), the strict censorship implemented during the 1970s resulted in the gangster genre's decline, with Korean filmmakers struggling to depict gangsters and violence onscreen within the government's set parameters. Unfortunately, Choi (2010a, pp.61-62; 2010b, p.48; 2016, p.220) and An

(2018) are the only English-language scholars to have even *mentioned* 1970s Korean gangster cinema.

The lack of research on this period of the gangster genre extends to Korean-language academia. Searches using the three *hangeul* equivalents of ‘gangster film’, 강패 영화 (*kkangpae yeonghwa*), 조폭 영화 (*jopok yeonghwa*) and 건달 영화 (*geondal yeonghwa*), across three Korean-language academic databases, *DBpia*, *earicle* and *KISS*, return only two relevant sources.⁴⁶ The lack of research is mirrored by a lack of films available to study. Although KMDb lists 150 gangster films made between 1970 to 1979, only one film, the omnibus *Cruel History of Myeong Dong*, is available to watch online.⁴⁷

Chapter V acknowledges that it is impossible to state anything definitive about a genre by examining a single film. As a result, the chapter only aims to expand upon Choi’s (2010b, p.48) statement that the gangster genre declined in the 1970s due to censorship. As a result, unlike the other chapters in the thesis, Chapter V does not extensively discuss the gangster-hero. In addition, it does not consider the historical context of the period – due to the strict censorship at this time, it seems unlikely that *Cruel History* depicts prevailing socio-cultural issues.

Instead, Chapter V asks, ‘*How did government interference and censorship impact the gangster genre’s development during the Dark Age?*’ Indeed, while Choi (2010b, p.48) *notes* that censorship led to the genre’s decline, she does not *examine* how it influenced the genre’s development. This issue is not limited to Choi’s (2010b, p.48) work. Van den Troost (2020, p.194) notes that “there has so far been relatively little work” considering the link between genre and censorship.

⁴⁶ The two sources are an article by Song Hyo Joung (2013) titled 명동액션영화: 식민-해방-냉전기 기억의 소급적 상상 [*Myeung-Dong Action Films in Early 1970’s [sic]: Retrospective Imagination of Colonial-Liberation-Postwar Memories*] and an article by Youngjae Yi (2016) titled 유신과 강패, 1970년대 액션영화와 범법의 서사 [*Lawbreaking Films in Park Chung-hee Era*].

⁴⁷ For a full description of the process by which the thesis found and selected films to study, see section 3.4 Korean Gangster Cinema.

Due to the lack of writing on the period, it seems important to examine gangster films made during the Dark Age, if just to encourage future exploration of this area. According to Jin (2020, p.113), the Dark Age also “provides a clear historical background against which to compare the change and continuity of Korean cinema thereafter.”

Fortunately, *Cruel History* is set in Myeong-dong, an area of Seoul that featured in many 1970s gangster and action films (Choi 2016, p.220). In addition, section 5.2 Quota Quickies details how the film is exemplary of the nationalistic, colonial era set gangster films that Choi (2010b, p.48) and An (2018, p.76) state typified the period. Indeed, the film is emblematic of a “quota quickie” – a film made solely to meet foreign film import quotas (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.25).⁴⁸ As detailed in section 5.3 Style Over Substance, the film is also akin to the many action films that were popular during the Dark Age, lacking many of the melodramatic elements that characterised Early Pre-Revival Era films. One notable melodramatic element that the film lacks is a focus on socio-cultural issues. As section 5.4 details, the fact that the film is set in the colonial period rather than the 1970s, as well as the fact that certain non-gangster films of this time use the gangster as a narrative device, suggests that the film’s aversion to reflecting reality is due to censorship.

5.2 Quota Quickies: The Decline of the Korean Gangster Genre and Korean Cinema

As noted in this chapter’s introduction, this period saw the Korean film industry significantly contract. Yecies and Shim (2016, p.115) note that profits from producing and exhibiting fell sharply, and the number of cinemas decreased from 717 in 1971 to 423 in 1981. In fact, Yecies and Shim (ibid.) state that “the sole growth area at this difficult time was the

⁴⁸ Although the term ‘quota quickie’ is mainly used by scholars, such as Lawrence Napper (2007), to refer to cheap and quickly made 1930s British films designed to satisfy quota requirements, it has since been used by various Korean film scholars, including Min et al. (2003, p.16), Shim (2011, p.190), Yecies and Shim (2016, p.25), Park (2007, p.20) and Paquet (2009, p.48). Although informal, it offers the most accurate and succinct way to refer to the 1970s Korean films made primarily to earn import quota licences.

government's intervention in all aspects of the film industry, which, for all its good intentions, was ending up harming Korean cinema.”

Perhaps the principal intervention that harmed the Korean film industry was the introduction of the import quota system. Since film imports guaranteed stable profits, many domestic producers made films solely designed to earn the import licence quota, which allowed them to import foreign films if they made a certain number of domestic films in a year (Park 2012, pp.58-59). Produced cheaply and quickly, Park (2007, pp.18-19) notes that many of these films were shelved or sent to second-run theatres immediately after completion.

Although, as Min et al. (2003, pp.47-52) note, the government created the import quota system during the 1960s, the production of “quota quickies” – films solely made to meet import quotas – only became a significant issue when combined with the strict censorship of the 1970s. Indeed, since producers were forced to include specific ideology in their films to appease the government, realistic, socially critical and experimental films were replaced by the propagandistic quota quickies (Min et al. 2003, p.52).

One such reason *Cruel History* seems emblematic of a quota quickie is the film's nationalistic and patriotic tone, particularly evident in the film's opening, which seems to adhere to stipulations in the Film Policy Measure that dictated that films should promote nationalism, patriotism and national unity (Min et al. 2003, p.50). Over shots of 1970s Myeong-dong, a voiceover proclaims: “*This is Myeong-dong. Myeong-dong is precious to us. We love Myeong-dong. This is where the spring season of Seoul starts...Myeong-dong is the heart of Korea. But this film will show you the blood-stained and tragic past of the now beautiful and splendid Myeong-dong.*” Unlike the Early Pre-Revival Era films examined in Chapter IV, *Cruel History* portrays modern-day Seoul as an idyllic, thriving metropolis. The underworld's grimy alleyways and shadowy, derelict buildings are replaced by bustling city streets and the thriving hubbub of urbanity.

Following this voiceover, actor Heo Chang-kang, who stars as the bartender Dal-su in the film, directly addresses the audience. Chang-kang fondly recalls his experiences growing up in Myeong-dong during the colonial era, saying, *“I loved Myeong-dong. But I also despised Myeong-dong. Still and all, I never left the place.”* As he speaks, the film cuts to photos of Myeong-dong in the 1940s, and Chang-kang remarks that *“...a deep yearning to get back the country was on the verge of exploding.”*

Overall, historians Chung-in Moon and Byung-joon Jun (2011, p.123) note that nationalism was central to Park Chung-hee’s efforts to modernise Korea. In fact, in 1968, Park explicitly stated that reviving and fostering national spirit was the “historical mission of his time” (Moon and Jun 2011, p.123). As a result, it is unsurprising that Choi (2010b, p.48) states that the few gangster films made during the 1970s featured “nationalistic themes.” Indeed, Jin (2020, p.20) states that 1970s filmmakers had no choice but to portray “government-directed themes – such as...the establishment of national identity...– in return for government subsidies.”

The difference in terms of thematic subtlety between a typical Early Pre-Revival Era film and *Cruel History* is evident when examining the latter’s ending. Immediately after Sang, the gangster-hero of the film’s third and final part, gets his revenge against a group of rival gangsters, the film cuts to him stumbling toward a police station, and a voiceover proclaims: *“In Myeong-dong there was always a man who blazed like fire. But one man alone couldn’t dominate Myeong-dong. That’s because violence could never win over ethics or social order.”* As the voiceover continues, the film cuts to present-day 1970s Myeong-dong, ending with the following lines: *“Myeong-dong knows very well that a city’s beauty is nourished by law and its citizens’ love. Myeong-dong today is filled with love, romance and friendship. Its nightmares of the past linger no longer.”*

Although the voiceover never mentions Park Chung-hee, there is an implicit demarcation between the Korea *before* Park took power – the Korea of violence and chaos

– and the Korea *after* Park took power – the Korea supposedly dominated by ethics and social order. By having Sang surrender himself to the police, the film also satisfies the MPPC’s requirement, as noted by Park (2007, p.19), that films should convince the audience to “do the right thing.”

Cruel History’s bluntly nationalistic themes are not the only indicator that the film might have been a quota quickie. The film exhibits many subpar production characteristics that, according to Jang Mi-hee (2001 cited in Park 2009, p.47), typified 1970s Korean cinema: handicraft production, an obsolete film language, awkward directing, crude scenarios and a dearth of imagination. Although Jang (*ibid.*) does not believe these characteristics were limited to 1970s Korean cinema, the production quality of *Cruel History* is inferior to that of the Early Pre-Revival Era films discussed in Chapter IV.

The first part of the film is entirely characterised by subpar action, camerawork and editing. There is also an overuse of low-angle shots; although one might suggest that the director uses these shots to heighten the presence of the gangsters onscreen, their abundance diminishes their subtextual potential. Indeed, low-angle shots are even used during a casual conversation between the gangster-hero and his friend. The film’s first part is also characterised by crash zooms. Some are used to comedic effect, and others are used to dramatic effect, creating an overly exaggerated sense of melodrama.

The film’s latter two parts are also substandard in terms of production quality. Neither part features the clever blocking of *Forever with You* nor matches the impressive scale of the train heist or the haunting poignance of the swamp scene in *The Flower in Hell*. In addition, *Cruel History* lacks impressive location photography, a major difference between it and Early Pre-Revival Era films such as *The Barefooted Young* and *The Starting Point*.

Cruel History also features subpar editing. In its second part, the film cuts from a shot of the gangster-hero being handcuffed to a new scene. Although a careful editor would

have likely cut immediately on or after the sound of the handcuffs clicking shut, the shot lingers in silence for three seconds before the next scene begins. There is also an abrupt edit in the film's first part when the soundtrack suddenly stops at the end of the final fight scene. Instead of ending on a cut, the music ends a second or two *after* a cut, as if the sound and image are not synced correctly.

Aside from the subpar cinematography and editing, *Cruel History* also features lacklustre production design. Although the film is set between the 1930s and 1950s, the costuming does not noticeably change between decades. Certain outfits – namely those worn by extras or background gangsters – are not even period accurate, with many featuring large shirt collars, suit lapels and wide ties characteristic of the 1970s.

Often, the colour photography accentuates the poor production design, highlighting the gaudy colours that characterise some of the film's sets. The colour photography also negates the clever use of light and shadow that characterises Early Pre-Revival Era films, which were all shot on black and white film stock.⁴⁹ As a result, the underworld of *Cruel History* lacks the atmosphere that characterises Early Pre-Revival Era films such as *A Wanted Man* and *Black Hair*.

Despite its flaws, *Cruel History* is not devoid of creative merit. The film's second part features an elaborate sword fight shot in black and white, a stylistic flourish that distinguishes the scene from the film's otherwise poor production. The film's third part is also significantly better – in terms of production quality *and* narrative quality – than the preceding parts. A scene from the third part, in which the gangster-hero's lover, Hui, is raped by rival gangsters, is *Cruel History's* most impressively directed sequence due to the two-minute-long handheld shot in which the scene unfolds.

⁴⁹ Although Korea's first wide screen colour film was released in 1961, Chung (2016, p.19) notes that black and white cinemascope "prevailed in Korea right up until 1969" as most producers could not afford the more expensive colour film stock.

Such creative flourishes highlight the fact that *Cruel History* is worthy of some praise. Indeed, Martin (2014, p.101) emphasises that it would be inaccurate to entirely dismiss Dark Age cinema as uninteresting or lacking artistic merit.

In fact, despite the restrictions imposed on filmmakers during this time, the Dark Age saw the emergence of an important group of filmmakers called the Visual Age Group that challenged “the complicity between the institutional control of the government and the commercial interest of the film industry” (Park 2009, p.51). Influenced by the British Free Cinema and French New Wave movements, the group consisted of young filmmakers such as Lee Jang-ho, Ha Gil-jong and Kim Ho-seon, who sought to graft new film techniques and visual styles to conventional filmmaking (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.128). Speaking for the group, Ha Gil-jong argued that cinema had to make an effort to more accurately represent social reality (Park 2009, p.51). However, as Park (2009, p.52) notes, “it was difficult for the directors to maintain cutting-edge social realism in the face of the censorial bureau.”

Even so, Yecies and Shim (ibid.) note that the group “found creative new spaces for thinking about the form, style, and purpose of cinema.” Indeed, while Park (2009, p.53) notes that the group did not achieve all its ambitions, the group “served to awaken a pioneering spirit resulting in populist reverberations in university students in the 1970s.”

Another important group that emerged during this time was the Culture Centre Generation, a group of young adults that frequented film screenings at the French Cultural Centre and German Goethe Institute (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.128; Park 2009, p.53). Established by their respective governments for the purpose of introducing their culture to Koreans, these centres allowed budding Korean filmmakers and cinephiles to view films that would have otherwise been prohibited under the strict censorship at the time (Park 2009, p.54). At the French Cultural Centre, students were shown everything from the surrealism of the 1920s to the post-New Wave of the 1970s, and at the German Goethe Institute, they

were shown films by Wim Wenders and Werner Herzog, among others (Park 2009, pp.54-55).

Overall, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.128) note that these centres played an important role in bringing foreign film culture to Korea and shaping the future of Korean Cinema, with many in the Korean film industry hailing from the Cultural Centre Generation. Indeed, Park (2009, p.53) notes that the collective experience of the Cultural Centre Generation “nurtured a new generation of South Korean cinema.”

Nevertheless, any filmmaker determined to make a genuinely artistic film during the 1970s would have been forced to contend with the strict censorship that dominated the period. Park (2007, p.16) states that films were liable to be censored if they violated good taste or customs, harmed the interest and dignity of the country, praised North Korea and communism, or criticised the government. Park (2012, p.60) adds that 1970s films were meant to portray Korean society in a positive light, uphold government-mandated morals and appeal to all audiences. In addition, Park (2012, p.59) notes that since the censorship criteria were so ambiguous, there was “always...room for arbitrary interpretations by censors.”

Considering that the gangster genre was already susceptible to censorship in the 1960s, as described in Chapter IV, there seems to be no logical reason why a filmmaker would make a gangster film during the 1970s unless they intended to earn an import quota licence. As Yecies and Shim (2016, p.128) state, the production environment of this period was “sterile and utilitarian”, with filmmakers being pressured to “make films that served as a propagandistic mouthpiece for the government.” In fact, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.127) note that even the most famous directors of the Golden Age, such as Yu Hyun-mok and Shin Sang-ok, “found that opportunities for creative expression in their films were increasingly curtailed” during the Dark Age. Similarly, Hyoin Yi (2019, p.81) argues that many of the Golden Age’s most revered directors “failed to direct films that were comparable to their

works in the 1960s.” Indeed, Min et al. (2003, p.52) note that censorship “killed the creative fervour that had exploded in the [Golden Age].”

5.3 Style Over Substance: Rises in Action, Declines in Melodrama

While the seven Early Pre-Revival Era films discussed in Chapter IV were akin to melodramas, *Cruel History* is more akin to an action film. Indeed, although *Cruel History* is only five minutes longer than the shortest Early Pre-Revival Era film, *The Flower in Hell*, it features more action sequences than any of the films discussed in Chapter IV. In addition to many standoffs and fights, each of the film’s three parts features a prominent action scene: the first features a confrontation on a moving train, the second features a lengthy swordfight, and the third features a sequence involving explosives, firearms and melee combat.

The significant quantity of action in *Cruel History* may be due to melodrama’s diminished status during the 1970s: Min et al. (2003, p.43) note that while 73.5% of all postwar films were melodramas, only 44.2% of all films were melodramas during the 1970s (Min et al. 2003, p.53).⁵⁰ Conversely, action films were produced in greater numbers during the 1970s, with Park (2007, p.20) calling them a “dominant trend”. Indeed, although action films only accounted for 13.9% of Golden Age films, Jin (2020, p.110) notes that they accounted for 21% of all 1970s films (Jin 2020, p.116). Min et al. (2003, p.53) estimate that action films accounted for an even higher percentage of Dark Age films: 24.3%.

Park (2007, p.20) states that most action films followed “a swordsman or martial artist [who] would sacrifice everything to kill an adversary.” Although there are no swordsmen or martial artists in *Cruel History*, the film features two prominent swordfights. In addition, the film’s colonial setting is derivative of action films – Park (2007, p.20) notes that action films were often set in the colonial era.

⁵⁰ Jin’s (2020, p.110) estimates are more conservative, estimating that 52.5% of all films made between the late-1950s to late-1960s were melodramas, compared to 50% of all films made between 1970 to 1979 (Jin 2020, p.116). Even so, Jin’s data still registers a decrease.

Although there are not many other direct parallels between *Cruel History* and 1970s action cinema, Kim Soyung (2005, p.103) states that 1970s gangster films were “hardly distinguishable” from action films. Certainly, *Cruel History*’s gangster-heroes seem more akin to action heroes than their Golden Age predecessors. Whereas most Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes try to avoid violence, two of *Cruel History*’s three gangster-heroes, Min and Hyeon, seem eager for it. After being released from prison, Min immediately embarks on a quest for vengeance against a rival gangster. Similarly, following his own release from prison, Hyeon launches a one-man assault against his former gang in a desperate attempt to track down his treacherous boss.

Brimming with rage and unhesitatingly violent, Min and Hyeon contrast the dreamy, romantic gangster-heroes of the Golden Age. While both men are motivated by romance – Min works to free his wife from the clutches of a rival gangster, and Hyeon seeks to kill the man who married his wife while he was in jail – neither man is consumed by love in the same way that Doo-soo is in *The Barefooted Young* or Dong-il is in *Black Hair*. For Min and Hyeon, love seems more akin to an excuse to fight than a reason to live.

Sang, *Cruel History*’s third gangster-hero, differs slightly in this regard. A war veteran, Sang is level-headed, stoic and gentlemanly. Hoping to lead a quiet, normal life, he avoids becoming involved in a brewing gang war, only resorting to violence when a sisterly friend and his girlfriend are caught in the crossfire. Still, Sang is unlike most Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes – in seeking revenge for the deaths of his girlfriend and former gang boss, he seems to relish massacring those responsible.

Aside from the action genre, *Cruel History* may have also been influenced by the spy genre. Min et al. (2003, p.55) note that the James Bond series inspired many late-1960s Korean action films. Sangjoon Lee (2017, p.2) expands upon this point, stating that “with the unparalleled success of *From Russia with Love* and *Dr.No*, the South Korean cultural sphere faced a sudden explosion of James Bond-style espionage” films. Although Lee (2017,

p.22) notes that the “espionage craze” ended around 1970, the main antagonist in *Cruel History’s* first part, Hwang Du-shik, is seen stroking a cat like the famous Bond villain, Blofeld, who first appeared in *From Russia with Love* (Young 1963). Du-shik also resembles an evil villain more than he does a gang boss. Unlike his men, who all wear suits, Du-shik wears a flashy Japanese *kimono*. In addition, his office is more akin to a grand lair than a gangster hideout, and in one scene, he laughs like an evil villain for an almost comical twenty-five seconds.

Despite Du-shik’s similarities to a typical Bond villain, *Cruel History’s* gangster-heroes are not akin to spies. In fact, the film’s gangster-heroes, particularly Min and Hyeon, are almost stereotypical criminals. Aggressive, tough and masculine, they express a narrow range of emotions, namely rage and anger. Lacking complexity, they differ from the pitiful and often relatable gangster-heroes of the Early Pre-Revival Era. This may simply be due to a lack of screen time – since *Cruel History* is an omnibus, there is insufficient time to fully develop each of the three protagonists. However, as section 5.4 details more fully, *Cruel History’s* simplistic portrayal of gangsters may also reflect the government’s efforts to shape the public’s perception of organised crime.

The simplified depiction of gangsters in *Cruel History* may also reflect the diminished status of melodrama during the Dark Age. As noted in Chapter IV, a focus on the lower classes was one of the foremost elements of Golden Age melodrama and, by relation, the Early Pre-Revival Era. Young, poor and often orphaned, Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes were more often defined by their social status than by their criminality. Conversely, the gangster-heroes in *Cruel History* are defined more by their criminality than their social status. This is not to say that they have escaped poverty or are unaffected by class. Rather, social issues such as inequality are not explored in *Cruel History*, either through the backgrounds of its characters or in its narratives and themes.

The absence of socio-cultural themes is apparent when comparing *Cruel History's* underworld with that of the Early Pre-Revival Era. Whereas the latter's underworld is home to both gangsters and impoverished citizens, including prostitutes, drug addicts and troubled youths, *Cruel History's* underworld is the exclusive domain of gangsters. Accordingly, there is no suggestion of the wider social issues affecting Korean society, either during the three decades – the 1930s, 1940s and 1950s – in which the film is set, or during the 1970s, when the film was made.

Another important element of melodrama missing from *Cruel History* is strong female characters. Women barely feature in the film. For example, in the film's first part, the gangster-hero's wife, Wu-hui, appears in just two scenes: two brief cutaway shots at the start of the film, and then again in the film's finale, when she jumps in front of a bullet meant to kill the gangster-hero and dies. While the two female characters in the film's final part, Hui and Jo-yeong, are not as one-dimensional as those in the first two parts, they lack the agency and depth that characterise many of the Early Pre-Revival Era's female characters, such as Sonia in *The Flower in Hell* and Yeong-shil in *Black Hair*. Indeed, while female characters are mainly love interests in Early Pre-Revival Era films, they are often protagonists.

Cruel History's lacklustre female characters may stem from the fact that 1970s melodramas were often aimed at men, as compared to 1960s melodramas, which were often aimed at women (Park 2007, p.20). A new sub-genre of the melodrama, the hostess melodrama, emerged during the 1970s and featured notably sexualised and victimised female protagonists (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.147). Min et al. (2003, p.55) note that these films often blamed the moral degradation of women on men and ended with the female protagonist's suicide. Although hostess melodramas did not emerge until the *mid*-1970s, *Cruel History* closely resembles aspects of Min et al.'s (2003, p.55) description of the genre

– all three romantic interests in *Cruel History* commit suicide because of events caused by the film's male characters.

One element of melodrama that has not diminished in *Cruel History* is melodrama itself, which is often heightened to a contrived degree in the film. For example, while the respective deaths of Dong-il in *Black Hair* and Seok-gu in *The Starting Point* feel like natural conclusions to each film's preceding action scene, Wu-hui's death at the end of *Cruel History's* first part is sudden and contrived. Appearing a second before the antagonist, Du-shik, fires at her husband, the gangster-hero, Min, Wu-hui leaps in front of the bullet and dies. The scene's sensational tone is heightened by the sudden reveal of Kiddo, a character seen earlier in the film who murders Min moments after his wife is murdered by Du-shik. Unlike the deaths of Dong-il and Seok-gu, which occur without music, the deaths of Min and Wu-hui are dramatised further by a melodramatic violin score.

Contrived melodrama also characterises the film's second part. After Hyeon and his wife, Hye-suk, marry, they stare offscreen, cheek to cheek, and soliloquise about their hopes for the future. Furthermore, Hyeon tells Hye-suk, "*I will forget my dark past and start a new life for you*", only to abandon her a moment later when two gangsters barge into the church where the couple have just been wedded. Overall then, *Cruel History* substantiates Min et al.'s (2003, p.55) statement that 1970s melodramas are "silly and sentimental."

5.4 Hiding the Truth: The Representation of 1970s Organised Crime

As discussed in the preceding section, *Cruel History* lacks many of the melodramatic characteristics that defined the Early Pre-Revival Era, including its focus on the lower classes and socio-cultural themes.

Although the film's lack of social commentary may be because it is more akin to an action film than a melodrama, it may also reflect the government's efforts to restrict social commentary during the 1970s. Indeed, Min et al. (2003, p.49) note that "criticism [of] social

reality became the main target of censorship and often was regarded as procommunism [sic].” Lee Young Il (1988 cited in Park 2007, pp.16-17) expands upon this point, noting that “...even if...the films had contained social matters or had described social facts very truly and critically, [their] screenplays were regulated by the censorship authorities.”

This would not be the first time censorship influenced the development of a genre. In his work on censorship, Kristof Van den Troost (2020, p.202) details how Hong Kong censors “inadvertently encouraged filmmakers to more thoroughly explore local crime culture and social problems” when they acted against gratuitous depictions of violence. Grindon (2012, p.54) also highlights how censorship can affect a genre, noting that efforts to censor wisecracks in 1930s American romantic comedies led to the cultivation of visual innuendo.

One notable change that Korean filmmakers seem to have made to avert censors and produce gangster films during the Dark Age is to set them in the colonial period, a fact noted by both An (2018, p.76) and Choi (2010b, p.48). Indeed, the prominence of the colonial setting in the Late Pre-Revival Era – including *Cruel History* – represents such a stark departure from the Early Pre-Revival Era that it seems more akin to a shift than a development.

There is further evidence to suggest that *Cruel History* is set in the colonial period to avert censorship: the fact that, as noted by criminologist Seungmug Lee (2006, p.65), organised crime reemerged during the period. Another criminologist, Yook Sang Jung (1997, p.92), notes that several gangs engaged in violent battles throughout the 1970s, with one gang, ‘The Honam Family’, gaining dominance over central Seoul, including Myeongdong – where *Cruel History* is set – in 1975. Park, Y.K. (2004, p.62) makes a similar observation, noting that during the 1970s, crime groups “dominated the busy streets of the Myongdong area in downtown Seoul.”

Yook Sang Jung (1997, p.92), Park, Y.K. (2004, p.62) and Lee (2006, p.65) each note that these new gangs were particularly violent. Specifically, Yook (1997, p.92) states that 1970s gang violence was “characterized by vicious cruelty... [and] the use of knives to physically disable and even dismember enemies.”

Although Lee (2006, p.96) and Mobrand (2016, p.65) suggest that gang violence only reached its height in 1975, the ending of *Cruel History* makes it seem as if organised crime is non-existent in contemporary Korean society. As noted in section 5.2, the film's final scene depicts its third and last gangster-hero, Sang, walking towards a police station as a voiceover declares: “...*violence could never win over ethics or social order. Myeong-dong knows very well that a city's beauty is nourished by law and its citizens love. Myeong-dong today is filled with love, romance and friendship. Its nightmares of the past linger no longer.*”

The efforts of 1970s filmmakers to avoid depicting organised crime in contemporary Korean society are further evidenced by the role of gangster characters in non-gangster films. In the action film *Break Up the Chain*, the character Cheol-su is not a gangster but a caricature of one.⁵¹ Dressed in a fedora and double-breasted overcoat, he is first seen theatrically smoking a cigarette while wielding a Tommy gun. Aside from these iconographic elements, Cheol-su is barely a gangster: he is not a member of a gang, he relinquishes his gangster attire early in the film, and he is ultimately revealed to be a Korean freedom fighter.

Conversely, although the gangsters in the martial-arts film *Returned Single-Legged Man* are members of a gang, their iconography is so incongruous that they barely seem to be gangsters. Mismatched costumes featuring pastel and checked suits, western bow ties and large shirt collars lessen the stylistic cohesion of their gang. Similar to *Cruel History*, *Break*

⁵¹ A Manchurian action film is a Western-inspired action film set in colonial era Manchuria, a region above the Korean peninsula that was populated by a Korean diaspora and other national and social groups during the 1920s and 1930s (An 2018, p.74; Yecies and Shim 2016, p.91; Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.97).

Up the Chain and *Returned Single-Legged Man* are also set within the colonial period, further distancing the gangster from contemporary Korea.

In fact, only one 1970s film available to study online and available with English subtitles depicts a gangster-hero in contemporary society: the melodrama *Wang Sib Ri: My Hometown* (Im 1976). Even then, the gangster-hero's criminality is largely inconsequential to his character and the film's narrative.

Unlike similarly melodramatic gangster films – such as the Revival Era film *Failan* and the Post-Revival Era film *Man in Love* – the film's gangster-hero, Jun-tae, is only revealed to be a gangster thirty-four minutes into the film, when one of his comrades, Sasaki, pays him a visit. Even then, *Wang Sib Ri: My Hometown* does not transform into a gangster film. Instead, it remains focused on a melodramatic romance plot. In fact, Sasaki only reappears in two other brief scenes in the film – once to remind Jun-tae that the gang is keeping an eye on him, and a second time at the end of the film, when he tries to take Jun-tae back to Japan, only for Jun-tae to beat him and his goons into submission.

Considering the minor role of Jun-tae's criminality in the film, the only logical reason for its inclusion is that the filmmakers needed an explanation for his inability to return to Korea after fourteen years or to create a contrived dilemma – Jun-tae has limited time to resolve his personal issues before he must return to Japan and rejoin his gang.

Overall, the appearance of gangsters in *Break Up the Chain*, *Returned Single-Legged Man* and *Wang Sib Ri: My Hometown* highlight the unwillingness or the inability of filmmakers to depict the realities of organised crime during the 1970s. This is particularly apparent when considering that two films made in the 2010s and examined in Chapter VII, *Gangnam Blues* and *The Drug King* (Mayagwang, Woo 2018), more accurately depict organised crime in the 1970s than any of the films discussed in this chapter.

5.5 Conclusion

Unlike the Early Pre-Revival Era, the lack of English-language research on Late Pre-Revival Era gangster cinema and the lack of available films to study do not suggest that the gangster genre was non-existent during this time, or at least that gangster films were not prominent or numerous enough to form a full-fledged genre.

Conversely, 1970s gangster films were made in such great quantities that they spawned entire subsets of gangster films, such as a subset of films set in Myeongdong, as exemplified by *Cruel History* and films such as *Old Gentlemen in Myeongdong* (*Myeongdongnosinsa*, Kim 1970a) and *Myeongdong Blues* (Choi 2016, p.220). Another subset of films based on the real-life gangster Kim Du-han and typified by films such as *The True Story of Kim Du-han* (Kim 1974), *Kim Du-han 2: Righteous Fighter* (*Hyeobgag Kim Du-han*, Kim 1975) and *Kim Du-han III* (*Pokdan Yeolcha-pyeon*, Ko 1975), also existed during this time (Choi 2010a, p.61).⁵² In addition, the fact that *Cruel History* is actually about gangsters represents another significant milestone in the history of the genre. As noted in Chapter IV, Early Pre-Revival Era films may have featured gangsters but were rarely, if ever, about them or the underworld.

Instead, the lack of English-language research on Late Pre-Revival Era gangster cinema and the lack of available films to study are indicative of the genre's decline during this period. As the chapter highlights, *Cruel History* suggests that gangster films during the Dark Age were mainly quota quickies – low-quality, propagandistic films produced solely to meet import quotas. This is evident by the fact that *Old Gentlemen in Myeongdong*, *Myeongdong Blues*, *The True Story of Kim Du-han* and *Kim Du-han 2: Righteous Fighter* were all directed by the same director, Kim Hyo-cheon, during a short span of time. In

⁵² Kim Du-han and the Revival Era film *General's Son* that depicts his early life are discussed in Chapter 6.

fact, KMDb credits Kim Hyo-cheon with directing twenty-five films between 1971 and 1975, many of which appear to be gangster films.

It also seems likely that 1970s gangster films were quota quickies due to *Cruel History's* subpar production quality and nationalist themes. In addition, the decision to set the film in the past seems to have been made by its filmmakers in order to avoid depicting gangsters in contemporary Korea and therefore provoking the nation's censors. To answer the chapter's research question – '*How did government interference and censorship impact the gangster genre's development during the Dark Age?*' – restrictive government policies seem to have forced filmmakers to replace or omit many elements that characterised the Early Pre-Revival Era, namely its depiction of social issues, its emphasis on the lower class and its compelling, nuanced gangster-heroes.

Accordingly, the Korean gangster genre shed its identifying characteristics before it could develop from a sub-genre of melodrama and become a distinct genre. Considering the many action elements featured in *Cruel History* – and the fact that many scholars do not distinguish between 1970s gangster and action films in their writing – it may also be possible that Late Pre-Revival Era films are derivative of the action genre in the same manner that Early Pre-Revival Era films are derivative of melodrama.

Regardless, the development of the gangster genre during the 1970s culminated in its decline and “long absence” during the 1980s (Choi 2010, pp.60-61). In fact, of the 150 gangster films KMDb lists between 1970 and 1979, 80% were released between 1970 and 1974. Furthermore, KMDb lists only 38 gangster films released between 1980 and 1989.⁵³

⁵³ This result includes 21 films featuring the word 조폭 (*jopok*), 1 film featuring the word 건달 (*geondal*) and 16 films featuring the word 강패 (*kkangpae*) in their plot description. As with any search made using the keyword/plot description criteria on KMDb, this search does not necessarily mean 38 gangster films were made during the period. Rather, it means that 38 gangster films feature one of three Korean words for gangster in their plot description. Indeed, while some films, such as *Kim Du-han and Lot 1 of Seodaemun* (*Gim Duhangwa SeodaemunIbeonji*, Lee, 1981), *The Blues of Jong-ro* (*Jonglobuleuseu*, Kim, 1982) and *Challenge of Spite* (*Wonhan-ui dojeonjang*, Lee, 1983) appear to be full-fledged gangster films, other films, such as *Rice Cake* (*Tteuok*, Kim, 1988) and *When A Woman Applies Makeup Twice* (*Yejaga dubeon hwajanggal ttae*, Kim, 1984) do not.

Choi (2010a, p.60) attributes the genre's decline to censorship, which Cho (2019, pp.51-52) notes persisted after the assassination of Park Chung-hee in 1979 and continued under President Chun Doo-hwan. The continuance of censorship in the 1980s is likely why some scholars, such as Lee, S. (2019, p.16) and Park (2007, p.16), believe that the Dark Age continued into the 1980s.

However, it seems unlikely that the genre's severe recession was solely due to censorship. Yi (2019, p.82) notes that the government alleviated censorship in 1985, and Paquet (2005, p.35) states that the fifth and sixth revisions to the Motion Picture Law, enacted in 1984 and 1986, respectively, ushered in many positive reforms. Accordingly, it might be more accurate to state that the genre's decline was due to its low quality and lack of social relevance. As Grindon (2012, p.47) notes, a genre's failure to resolve prevailing social issues may "contribute to the fading of a genre's popularity." Due to the creative restrictions placed upon the genre by censors, it is also possible that filmmakers might have become wary of making gangster films. As Grindon (2007, p.409, author's italics) notes, without flexibility or variety, a genre fails not only to sustain an audience but also to attract filmmakers.

Chapter VI: The Young, The Poor and The Dangerous: The Revival Era (1990 - 2006)

6.1 Introduction

Korean gangster cinema underwent a dramatic revival during the 1990s (Plaice 2020, p.2; Kim 2019, p.510; Plaice 2019c; Choi 2016, p.218; Gillespie 2016, p.62; Choi 2010a, p.61; Choi 2010b, p.49; Min et al. 2003, p.173). Choi (2010b, p.49) states that the election of Korea's first civilian government in 1993 began "a new era" of South Korean gangster cinema. Plaice (2020, p.3) echoes this point, describing how a "new cycle" of gangster films emerged in the 1990s.

This new era coincided with New Korean Cinema, a period beginning sometime in the 1990s and ending in 2006 (Paquet 2009, p.114), and which Yecies and Shim (2016, p.2) state, began Korean cinema's journey to becoming "one of the most dynamic national cinemas in the world."

Although gangster cinema of New Korean Cinema, or as the thesis refers to it, the Revival Era, is the most researched period of the genre, there is some contention regarding the beginning of the genre's revival. As discussed in 6.2 Coming of Age, which examines gangster films made during the 1990s, this contention stems from the fact that the genre's return to Korean screens was marked by the 1990 film *General's Son*, a film more reminiscent of 1970s gangster films than those that would follow it. Indeed, it was not until the release of *Rules of the Game* four years later that some of the Revival Era's foremost characteristics, such as young protagonists, an emphasis on social inequality, and visceral violence, would begin to emerge.

Even then, the genre only fully established itself with the release of *Friend* in 2001, which, as discussed in 6.3 The Friend Effect, spawned a trend of gangster films directed by young filmmakers that reckon with youth, generational division and the aftermath of the 1997 IMF Crisis. Amongst other things, these films tackle social inequality, as discussed in

6.4 Working Class Heroes, examine the gangster-hero's struggle with identity, as addressed in 6.5 Identity Crisis, and the duality of violence as a force of liberation and destruction, as discussed in 6.7 A Means to an End. In addition to the introduction of many new elements, the Revival Era also saw the genre depart from its melodramatic origins, which, as 6.6 A Man's World details, is most evident in the genre's reductive portrayal of women.

The film addresses these many topics in answering the research chapter's two research questions: 'What elements define the Revival Era?' and ii) 'What socio-cultural, industrial or generic factors influenced the genre's revival?'

To answer these questions, the chapter examines the following films: *General's Son*, *Rules of the Game* (*Gameui beobjig*, Jang 1994), *Rosy Life* (Kim 1994), *No.3* (*Neombeo 3*, Song 1997), *Beat*, *Green Fish*, *Die Bad* (*Jukgeona hokeun nabbeugeona*, Ryoo 2000), *Friend*, *Failan*, *A Bittersweet Life*, *A Dirty Carnival*, *Gangster High* (*Pongnyeok sseokeul*, Park 2006), *Righteous Ties* (*Georukhan gyebo*, Jang 2006), *Cruel Winter Blues* (*Yeolhyeollama*, Lee 2006) and *Sunflower*. In particular, the chapter focuses on the films *General's Son*, *Green Fish*, *Die Bad*, *Friend* and *A Dirty Carnival*.

Ultimately, the chapter illustrates that in the absence of government censorship and socio-economic constraints, the Korean gangster genre began to form its own distinct identity. Indeed, the Revival Era represents the first period in which the Korean gangster genre began to develop and transform rather than diminish and recede.

6.2 Coming of Age: The Beginning of the Gangster Genre's Revival

Choi (2010a, p.61) and Plaice (2020, p.3) note that the Korean gangster genre's revival was marked by the release of *General's Son* in 1990. Similarly, Jamier (2015, p.42) states that the gangster genre's "first rumblings can be seen in Seventies and Eighties actioners, now hard to find, but its true foundational moment is *The General's Son*." A significant box office success, the film accrued 678,946 admissions. (Paquet 2009, p.33). In fact, both it and

its sequel, *General's Son II* (*Janggunui adeul II*, Im 1991), were each the highest-grossing domestic film upon release, in 1990 and 1991 respectively (Choi 2010a, p.61).⁵⁴

Although the film's success marked the Korean gangster genre's return to screens, it did not mark the genre's reinvention. Akin to a Late Pre-Revival Era film, *General's Son* is set in the colonial era and is based on the life of Kim Du-han – the same real-life gangster depicted in the Late Pre-Revival Era films *The True Story of Kim Du-han*, *Kim Du-han 2: Righteous Fighter*, and *Kim Du-han III*. *General's Son* follows a young Kim Du-han's rise through a gang in 1930s Seoul and his efforts to defend his neighbourhood from encroaching Japanese colonialists. As this plot description implies, the film is rather nationalistic, casting Du-han in the role of a heroic freedom fighter risking his life for Korean independence. The film's depiction of Japanese colonialists as tyrannical antagonists echoes their depiction in *Cruel History of Myeongdong*.

The nationalistic nature of the film is evident in its title, which refers to the fact that Du-han is the son of Kim Chwa-chin, an anarchist who fought for Korean independence (Kim 2019, p.507). Although this fact is not revealed until the film's final act, Du-han is fiercely nationalistic throughout the film. He even invokes his nationality when challenging a Japanese yakuza, Marouka, to a fight.

Although political scientist Eric Mobrand (2016, p.642) notes that certain evidence supports Kim's claim that he was the son of Kim Chwa-chin, Mobrand (ibid.) notes that Kim's reputation as a patriotic freedom fighter stems from Kim's disputable claims that he fought against Japanese police and yakuza sent to the peninsula to suppress Koreans.⁵⁵ Mobrand (2016, p.642) casts further doubt on Kim's nationalistic claims by noting that he

⁵⁴ A third film, *General's Son III* (*Janggunui adeul III*, Im 1992), was released in 1992.

⁵⁵ Mobrand (2016, p.642) states that "as early as 1925, Kim Tu-han was listed in a report as the child of Kim Chwa-jin. Though this evidence does not prove Kim's biological paternity, it does rule out the possibility that the link to Kim Chwa-jin was a myth constructed by Kim later in his career. Shortly after Kim Chwa-jin's death, the Andong Kim association announced in a newspaper a meeting to discuss the future of orphaned Kim Tu-han."

avoided fighting in the Korean War by assisting the authorities in creating a volunteer youth group, which mainly did construction work in the Seoul region. Another political scientist, Porteux (2013, pp.70-71), notes that Kim Du-han even worked with the Japanese for some time, organising and running the Police Assistance Association, “effectively making them [him and his gangsters] legal terrorists.”

One key difference between *General's Son* and Late Pre-Revival Era films is the former's positive depiction of the gangster-hero. As Porteux (2021, p.71) notes, the film “presents a romanticized version of Kim Du Han as a protector of Korean merchants...[and] conveniently leaves out his collaboration with the Japanese colonial government.” While ostensibly a criminal, Kim (2019, p.508) states that Du-han's resistance to the Japanese colonialists and his genuine compassion for the residents of Jongno, the area of Seoul he controls, configure him as a “proactive, morally upstanding masculine figure.”

The film may allude to the gang's role as enforcers and loan sharks, but it never shows Kim terrorising his fellow Koreans. Instead, *General's Son* depicts Kim as a compassionate, humble protector. He loans money to a friend he knew when he was homeless, steals from affluent Japanese households to stop a local hostess, Min-ja, from being sold off to pay her father's debts, and accompanies another hostess, Hwa-ja, to a temple outside of the city so that she can escape her abusive husband. Overall, the film barely suggests that Du-han is even a criminal. Although the police pursue him, it is more for his efforts to protect Jongno than for his connection to organised crime. Empathetic, honest and generous, Du-han is a figure of adoration and pride, a character audiences root for rather than against.

The depiction of the gangster-hero as a likeable figure is perhaps *General's Son's* greatest influence on the gangster films that followed it. Indeed, while subsequent films such as *Rules of the Game*, *No.3*, *Beat* and *Green Fish* feature more morally complex and nuanced

gangster-heroes, they do not portray them as outrightly amoral or responsible for society's problems, as Late Pre-Revival Era films do.

In fact, most of these films portray gangster-heroes as *victims* of society's problems. *Beat's* Min is a high school dropout living with an alcoholic mother. *Green Fish's* Mak-dong returns home from military service only to find his family fractured, and his dream of a simple life undermined by difficult socio-economic conditions. *Rules of the Game's* Young-dae abandons the drudgery of his small-town life to become a gangster in Seoul.

Still, the somewhat positive portrayal of the gangster-hero in these films is the only commonality they share with *General's Son*. Indeed, while *General's Son* may have marked the Korean gangster genre's return, it did not establish a template for it. Aside from the film's two sequels, no other Revival Era film is set in the colonial period.

Subsequent films are also grittier and more realistic than *General's Son*, as evidenced by their darker themes and more intense violence. For example, *No.3* features Ashtray, "a big lump of a character who brutalises people with his namesake, which he stores down his pants" (Pierce 2011). In contrast to the often honourable, stoic fistfights that characterise *General's Son*, the violence in *Rules of the Game* is chaotic and brutal – in one scene, gangsters brandishing knives and clubs ambush a rival gang in a nightclub. There is no sense of honour in the fight. Instead, there is only madness and rage, accentuated by formal characteristics not seen in *General's Son*, such as hand-held camerawork, slow motion, rapid editing and rock music (Min et al. 2003, p.178). Similar stylistic elements also feature in *Beat*, *Green Fish* and *No.3* – Pierce Conran (2011b) notes that the latter "employs a myriad of stylistic tricks such as: Colors; chiaroscuro lighting; composition; monochrome; music; fastforwarding [sic]; point-of-view; slow motion; freeze frame; strobe; and breaking the fourth wall (like staring into camera)."

Unlike *General's Son*, none of these films avoid depicting the brutal, unseemly nature of the underworld. Indeed, each film's gangster-hero is obviously a criminal. In *Rules*

of the Game, Young-dae sells his girlfriend into prostitution, and in *Green Fish*, Mak-dong murders a rival gangster to demonstrate his loyalty to his boss.

Another important difference between *General's Son* and the gangster films that followed it is the structure of the gangster-hero's arc. Whereas Du-han's arc in *General's Son* is almost a classic rags-to-riches story, the arcs of Young-dae in *Rules of the Game*, Min in *Beat*, Tae-ju in *No.3* and Mak-dong in *Green Fish* all follow the rise-and-fall arc, with each gangster attaining a certain amount of wealth and status before losing it all. In *Beat*, Min even loses his life when trying to save his friend, Tae-soo, from his treacherous gang bosses. Similarly, Mak-dong is murdered by his boss in *Green Fish*.

Overall, the most important difference between *General's Son* and the films that followed it is that the latter are far more socially relevant. As film critic John Atom (2019) notes, these films forgo a chivalrous representation of the gangster in “favor of a grittier alternative, often used in the service of social and political critique.” Although the social relevance of these films is discussed further in this chapter, it is important to note that the many other differences between these films and *General's Son* may be due to a reduction in censorship. This seems to be the belief of Choi (2010b, p.49), who states that the “easing of censorship in 1993” following the election of a civilian government gave rise to a new era of South Korean gangster cinema.⁵⁶

The films that followed *General's Son* also benefited from many structural changes that occurred in the Korean film industry in the 1990s. Paquet (2005, p.33) notes that there was “a simultaneous push” by both the government and filmmakers to revamp the film industry through building advanced technical infrastructure, opening film schools and seeking new sources of finance. These initiatives were enabled by the *chaebols*, which Yecies and Shim (2016, p.159) state “effectively retooled the [film] industry” by providing

⁵⁶ Although censorship was reduced beginning in 1993, it was not until 1995 that it was ruled unconstitutional (Jin 2020, p.30) and by 1996 that this ruling began to take effect (Yecies and Shim 2016, p.158) and Paquet (2009, p.40).

a surplus of funding, overhauling management and accounting systems, implementing box office tracking procedures, and introducing planning and internationalisation strategies. Yecies and Shim (2016, p.161) also state that these changes “enabled a host of new producers to make films that appealed to Korea’s large group of cinephiles under 40.”

Although Choi (2010a, p.64) does not refer to the industrial shifts discussed above, she seems to agree that industrial influences led to the Korean gangster genre’s revival. Choi (ibid.) highlights the emergence of new independent production companies, noting that some of the Revival Era’s most seminal works, *Beat*, *Green Fish* and *Friend*, were produced by Uno Film, East Film and Cineline, respectively.

Choi (2010a, p.61) also highlights the influence of Hong Kong gangster films, which first appeared on Korean screens in the mid-1980s and quickly became popular with audiences. Indeed, Choi (2010a, p.64) notes that John Woo’s *A Better Tomorrow* (Woo 1986) and *The Killer* (Woo 1989) were respectively ranked fifth and sixth on Korea’s box office charts upon release. Karen Fang (2004, p.77) notes that *A Better Tomorrow* was so impactful that it prompted Korean youth to don the protagonist’s famous clothing – a black suit and long, dark overcoat.⁵⁷ Similarly, Choi (2010b, p.49) states that young fans emulated the fashions and mannerisms of stars such as Chow Yun-fat, Leslie Cheung and Andy Lau.

The reasons for the success of Hong Kong gangster cinema in Korea are numerous. Jiyeon Pyeon (2024, p.4) states that Woo’s films were embraced in Korea as earnest texts that celebrated loyalty, male solidarity and honour, aligning with “Confucian traditions prevalent in Korean society.” According to Pyeon (2024, p.4), these values “provided an arena of fantasy for the Korean male subject to navigate modern anxieties.” Hong Kong films also provided a lucrative alternative for owners of small and second-run cinemas that could not afford the rights to Hollywood films (Choi 2010a, p.61). Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.58)

⁵⁷ A Korean remake of *A Better Tomorrow*, also called *A Better Tomorrow (Mujeokja)*, Song 2010), was released in 2010, with Woo serving as an executive producer (Kelso-Marsh 2020, p.60).

notes that the success of Hong Kong gangster cinema was also due to a general animosity toward Hollywood at the time, “as well as the rise of VCR and VHS rental.” A scene in Ryoo Seung-wan’s *Die Bad*, released in 2000, showcases this phenomenon – Kyu Hyun Kim (2015, p.112) notes that a young gangster in the film is briefly seen watching *A Better Tomorrow* on VHS.

By the 1990s, the success of Hong Kong gangster films had primed Korean audiences for domestic equivalents. Accordingly, when the Hong Kong film industry’s output suddenly decreased in 1997, due to the handover that saw Britain return the island to China, Korean producers seized upon the void that their absence left in the South Korean film market (Choi 2010a, p.49).

Despite *A Better Tomorrow*’s popularity in Korea, Korean filmmakers seem to have been more inspired by the *Young and Dangerous* series. Released ten years after *A Better Tomorrow* in 1996, the first film, *Young and Dangerous* (Lau 1996a), replaced the heroic figures that characterised Woo’s films with a host of young, violent and troubled gangsters that embody the anxieties of Hong Kong’s youth. David Desser (2009, p.180) notes that the film was very successful at the Hong Kong box office and was, in typical Hong Kong fashion, quickly followed within five months by two sequels, *Young and Dangerous 2* (Lau 1996b) and *Young and Dangerous 3* (Lau 1996c), and a spin-off, *Once Upon a Time in Triad Society* (Cha 1996).

[The series] centers on twentysomethings who have all the normal problems—finding good jobs, surviving love affairs, quarreling and reconciling with their elders...They are also triads. Resplendent in dragon tattoos, they run loan-sharking and car-parking rackets, scrap with other youngsters, stand loyally by their superiors, avenge their slain lovers, and commit murder on orders (David Bordwell 2011, p.17).

There are immediate parallels to the gangster-heroes of the Revival Era in Bordwell’s (ibid.) description of the series. The fact that *Young and Dangerous* supplanted the heroic gangsters of Woo’s films parallels the supplantation of the honourable gangsters depicted in *General’s Son* by the more morally complex gangsters of subsequent films such as *Beat*, *Green Fish*

and *Die Bad*. Furthermore, just as these films are gritty and realistic, so too is the *Young and Dangerous* series – Desser (2009, p.183) states that the setting of “housing estates, along along with the use of video arcades, mahjong parlors, nightclubs and the like, grounds the series in a very concrete reality, the reality of the young audience that has made the series so popular; the reality, especially, of working- class boys.” Revival Era films also feature many of the same stylistic characteristics that typify the *Young and Dangerous* films, such as swish pans, fast editing, freeze frames, speed ramping and various visual effects (Soe 2019, p.478).

Beyond *Young and Dangerous*, Choi (2010a, p.69) notes that there are numerous characteristics shared between both Hong Kong and Korean gangster cinema, such as tragic endings and betrayals, and Kwon (2023, p.4) notes that both gangster cinemas also “feature melodramatic male bonding and marginalize women characters.”

Whereas Choi (2010a) asserts that independent production companies and the influence of Hong Kong gangster films led to the revival of Korean gangster cinema, Shin (2005, p.123) argues that the revival of the gangster genre can be considered “a consequence of, and a response to” the IMF crisis. Indeed, while Choi (2010a, p.64) believes that the genre’s reemergence is better explained by industrial factors, especially since the genre reemerged before the crisis, the Revival Era’s representation of several issues incurred by the crisis – such as unemployment, a lack of faith in the education system, a national identity crisis, and worsening inequality – seems to be evidence of the crisis’s influence on the Korean gangster genre.⁵⁸

Although the influence of the IMF Crisis is discussed in section 6.3, it is relevant to note here that *General’s Son* is the only film in this chapter that does not feature or represent

⁵⁸ There is a parallel to Hong Kong gangster cinema here. Although Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.56) believes it is “overly reflectionist” to state that the rise of Hong Kong gangster films in the 1980s and 1990s was due to anxieties surrounding the 1997 handover, he contends that “it nonetheless stands that, at the very least, the films of Woo and his contemporaries were grounded in the socio-economic context of Hong Kong at the time.”

any of the societal issues mentioned in the paragraph above. The anomalous nature of *General's Son* is why Min et al. (2003, p.175) believe *Rules of the Game* is more exemplary of the gangster genre's resurgence in the 1990s. In fact, Min et al. (2003, p.175) even classify *General's Son* as "old" gangster cinema, mainly due to its colonial era setting. Although Choi (2010a, p.61) once suggested that *General's Son* marked the beginning of the genre's revival, she (2016, p.218) more recently suggested that *Rules of the Game* is a better marker of the gangster genre's revival.

Although *Janggunui adeul* (The General's Son, Kwon-taek Im, 1990), set in colonial Seoul, reignited the trope of gangster patriotism that was popular in Korean *hwalgeuk* (action films) of the 1970s, it was *Geimui beopchik* (Rules of the Game, Hyeon-su Jang, 1994) that signalled the beginning of gangster cinema set in contemporary Seoul, followed by a film cycle that appeared in 1997 (Choi 2016, p.218, author's italics).

Plaice (2020, p.3) seems to share the same opinion, noting that "[i]n the later 1990s, a new cycle of 'dark city' gangster films" emerged.

Of course, some scholars may disagree with this suggestion. Kim (2019, p.507) believes *General's Son* marks the beginning of "contemporary Korean gangster cinema" as the film was a significant box office success. Even so, it is undeniable that *General's Son* is largely distinct from every other gangster film released during the Revival Era. This is furthered by the fact that the film is directed by Im Kwon-taek, who at the time of the film's release was 54, much older than the directors who would helm subsequent gangster films.

Overall, then, it seems apt to state that while the gangster genre's return to Korean screens was marked by the release of *General's Son*, its revival did not begin until *Rules of the Game* was released in 1994. It is best then to consider, as Atom (2019) does, the 1990s as a transitional period for the Korean gangster genre.

6.3 The Friend Effect: High School, Hierarchies and Troubled Youths

While the genre's revival *began* with the release of *Rules of the Game*, Choi (2010a, p.62) and Plaice (2020, p.3) state that it was not until the release of *Friend* in 2001 that the gangster genre fully resurged. Based on the director, Kwak Kyung-taek's, own childhood, the first

part of *Friend* follows the lives of four boys as they navigate high school in the 1970s before focusing on two of the boys, Dong-su and Jeong-suk, as they join rival gangs.

As many scholars note (Choi 2010b, p.47; Paquet 2009, pp.77-78; Shim 2006, p.34; Shin 2005, p.118), *Friend* earned 8.2 million admissions upon release, becoming the most successful Korean film ever made. Shim (2006, p.33) suggests that the film's success was partly due to the film's rigorous production – the film's script was revised twenty-one times.

Still, the success of *Friend* was surprising as it lacked the typical characteristics of a blockbuster. As Paquet (2009, p.78) details, the film lacked a star actor, and Kwak was considered a dubious box-office prospect due to his first two films flopping. In addition, the film's setting of Busan – and the distinct Busan dialect of its characters – were unproven elements. Indeed, while Busan had featured as a backdrop to other films, Paquet (2009, p.78) states that “*Friend* was the first to highlight and even revel in the city's distinctive regional character.”

Despite this, several lines of the film became popular after the film's success (ibid.). Furthermore, Jamier (2015, p.43) states that the film led the production of many other films either set in Korea's authoritarian past or in Busan, and Paquet (2009, p.79) notes that *Friend* led to the production of many 1980s-set youth films.

Most importantly, the film marked a “turning point” for Korean gangster cinema, helping the genre “become a major trend” (Choi 2010a, p.62). Film programmer Samuel Jamier (2015, p.43) states that following the film's success, gangsters “became omnipresent [in Korean cinema]”, a statement Plaice (2020, p.3) echoes when he notes that the early 2000s saw gangster films account “for a higher proportion of domestic film production than ever before.”

More specifically, the film seems to have led to the production of several gangster films set totally or partly in high school, such as *Gangster High*. Indeed, Choi (2010a, p.69) notes that the high school appears frequently in Revival Era films.⁵⁹

A harsh, unforgiving environment, *Friend's* depiction of high school likely evoked both nostalgic and traumatic memories for audiences in 2001. Indeed, the part of the film set in high school is its most heartwarming, high school life is characterised by social and academic pressures, school rivalries and bullies, and the looming threat of adulthood.

In fact, the first scene of the film set in high school sees a teacher ritualistically humiliating and beating his students; after forcing each student to say what their father does for a living, he slaps them as punishment for supposedly wasting the education their fathers worked hard to provide. When Joon-suk tells the teacher that his father is a gangster, the teacher flies into a rage, slapping him repeatedly until he falls to the floor, where he kicks the teenager as he writhes in pain.

Shin (2005, p.123) posits that the “portrayal of the insensitive and brutal teacher [in *Friend*]...clearly criticises the violent and authoritarian education” that typified 1970s and 1980s Korea. Yet, Shin (2005, p.123) also suggests that *Friend's* (Kwak 2001) unflinching portrayal of Korea's past functions as a critique of contemporary Korea.

Shin's latter point is substantiated by the presence of sadistic teachers in contemporary-set high school gangster films released after *Friend*. In *Die Bad*, a teacher brutalises Sang-hwan – one of the film's gangster-heroes – with a bat for smoking a cigarette, and in *Gangster High*, a teacher referred to by students as a “gangster-wannabe” beats up two of the film's teenaged gangster-heroes, putting one of them in hospital.

High schools were also portrayed as sites of torment and strife in many Korean horror films released in the late 1990s and early 2000s. The first of these films was *Whispering*

⁵⁹ Despite the influence of Hong Kong gangster cinema, the high school setting seems to be a distinctly Korean addition to the gangster genre – Choi (2010a, p.69) notes that the high school setting is largely absent from Hong Kong gangster cinema.

Corridors (*Yeogo goedam*, Park 1998), which Jinhee Choi (2009, p.39) states was the third highest-grossing film of 1998. The film depicts school as so dismal and depressing that Daniel Martin (2019, p.401) argues that the vengeful ghost that haunts the school and takes revenge upon the students and teachers who drove her to suicide is a pitiful figure more than a frightening one. Martin (2019, p.387) notes that whereas horror films had previously focused on middle-aged characters in domestic settings, the film spawned a new cycle of horror films set in high schools and “firmly rooted in the lives (and fears) of the country’s youth.”

There is a clear parallel to the gangster genre here – although the films that preceded *Friend* were not focused on middle-aged characters, the Revival Era is particularly focused on issues relating to the country’s youth, with David Desser (2007) suggesting that films such as *Beat* are as much youth films as they are gangster films.

More specifically, Desser (2007, p.78) notes that *Beat* was particularly resonant with Korea’s youth – “it was fourth on the box-office chart of Korean films of 1997 and was selected as one of the Best Six Films of 1997 by the KMPPC.” A coming-of-age story, the film follows the lives of three young men after they drop out of school, and the tribulations faced by Min’s girlfriend, Romi, and her friends as they struggle under the intense pressures of Korea’s education system (Cansdale-Cook 2019). Pyeon (2024, p.1) notes that several elements of the film, including the line ‘*I had no dream*’ and a scene in which Min rides a motorcycle with his eyes closed and his arms outstretched, became iconic representations of Korea’s “wandering youth in the late 1990s.” There are some parallels to the Visual Age Group of the 1970s here. Yecies and Shim (2016, p.130) note that the group’s filmmakers focused on “capturing the youth culture of the times – young people wearing bell-bottom jeans, dreaming of freedom, far removed from the restrictive social norms of contemporary Korea.”

The emphasis on youth in the Revival Era may be due to the new generation of directors who debuted during the era. Indeed, most of the directors whose respective films are examined in this chapter were in their twenties or early thirties during the 1990s.⁶⁰ Most of these directors studied film and/or theatre in college, whereas the preceding generation learned their craft as apprentices to established directors (Paquet 2005, p.48).

Ryoo Seung-wan's film *Die Bad* is exemplary of the youth-focused gangster films of the Revival Era. An innovative low-budget genre mashup, *Die Bad* combines four short films that Ryoo made between 1998 and 2000 into one cohesive, yet stylistically varied, narrative. Due to this structure, Kim (2015, p.111) states that the film was considered a 'non-mainstream' film upon release. Despite this, Lee, N.J.Y. (2019, p.319) notes that the film broke even within one week of releasing on 16mm across four screens. Although this seems a minor feat when compared to the success of *Friend* the year after, Lee, N.J.Y. (2019, p.316) states that the film established Ryoo's reputation as a popular auteur director.

Just twenty-seven when the film was released, Lee, N.J.Y. (2019, p.317) states that Ryoo "put everything into the movie: his passion, his knowledge of his favorite movies, and his life experiences up until that point." Ryoo's young age and uncompromising efforts are reflected not only in the film's stylistic uniqueness but also in the many topics that the film touches upon, including "youth, the breakdown of the extended family and the gang family that substitutes for it, and the betrayal of youth by adults" (Desser 2007, p.82).

The betrayal of youth by adults, or generational division, is portrayed by varying interpersonal relationships in the film. In the film's first part, a middle-aged pool hall owner bemoans Korea's youth, stating, "*The government should crack down, like in the 1970s. Otherwise, kids these days? You can't control them.*" In the second part, one of the film's gangster-heroes, Sung-bin, is berated by his father over dinner, and in the third part, an older

⁶⁰ The only exceptions are Im Kwon-taek (born 1934), Lee Chang-dong (born 1954) and Kim Hong-jun (born 1956).

Sung-bin manipulates another of the film's gangster-heroes, the young and impressionable Sang-hwan.

Although the film is most powerful when highlighting issues pertaining to Korea's youth, it also succeeds in highlighting the dour mood of Korea at the time. Nikki J.Y. Lee (2019, p.326) notes that the film's characters struggle to lead good lives due to the hardships of Korean society. This is most apparent in the second part of the film, *Modern Man*, which cuts between a lengthy fight between a cop and a gangster and interviews with the same men. The interviews reveal that the cop and gangster have more in common than they might think – they both assumed their respective roles out of a desire for respect, are proud of the work they do, and are struggling under the pressures of Korean society. Indeed, when they are asked if they have any dreams, Tae-hoon, the gangster, replies, "*Dreams? Never had time for dreams. Not now, either,*" and Sung-bin, the cop, replies, *What do you mean a dream? I haven't used words like 'dream' or 'hope' for ages.*"

Although the film features a reappearing ghost and graphic violence, the interviews in *Modern Man* may be the film's most striking element. The "starkly mundane" quality that Kim (2015, p.113) says characterises Tae-hoon's interview responses deglamorises the gangster-hero, reducing him to a pitiful figure that is at once funny and realistic. As Kim (2015, p.113) states, *Die Bad's* ironically realistic elements, such as the interview segment in *Modern Man*, complement the film's "Expressionist techniques and styles, probing the psychological depths of the characters, de-romanticizing their motivations and the characters overall."

Die Bad's powerfully realistic depiction of Korea likely stems from the fact Ryoo was motivated to make the film by the same forces that motivate *Die Bad's* gangster-hero, Sang-hwan, to become a gangster: a fear of poverty and a resentment for the harsh realities of Korean society (Lee, N.J.Y. 2019, p.316).

At the time of its release, Korea was still reeling from the effects of the Asian financial crisis, which Korean Studies scholars Kim and Finch (2002, p.120) state transformed South Korea “from an economic miracle to an economic fiasco in the space of a few months.” Cho (2019, p.56) notes that the crisis forced the Korean government to avail of a large relief loan from the International Monetary Fund (IMF). However, the IMF only agreed to grant a \$57 billion loan if the Korean government reformed the nation’s economy according to IMF policies (Chung and Diffrient 2015, p.124). Sociologist Kwang-Yeong Shin (2012, p.294) states that these policies were based on American neoliberal reforms, which prioritised a flexible labour market, privatisation, open financial markets and the overhaul of Korea’s *chaebols*.⁶¹

Ultimately, these reforms incurred far-reaching social problems. Sociologist Park Gil-sung (2004, p.148) states that the IMF intervention led to unemployment and social inequality, and Chung and Diffrient (2015, p.124) note that the IMF’s reforms led to increases in “crimes, divorces, desertions of children, and suicides.” Overall, the IMF reforms impacted Korean society so dramatically that the 1997 Asian Financial Crisis is better known as the ‘IMF Crisis’ in Korea (Kim 2019, p.511). While the Korean government paid back the IMF loan in 2000, Kim and Finch (2002, p.135) emphasise that “the shadow of the crisis” still loomed over Korea afterwards.

As *Die Bad* and other gangster films of the time suggest, Korean youth were particularly affected by the IMF Crisis. Gil-sung Park (2004, p.159) emphasises that those aged 15 to 29 were most affected by the IMF crisis – rates of youth unemployment were double that of the general population and grew worse even as the economy recovered. In addition, Yoon Keun Lee (1998, p.161) notes that a study performed by the National Police Agency in 1996 revealed that “most gang members are composed of those in the 10’s [sic]

⁶¹ For the definition of a *chaebol*, see Chapter I: Introduction

or 20's [sic] who have graduated, or quit, middle schools or high schools." In fact, only 1.39% of criminals arrested by police had reached higher education (ibid.).

The fact that so many young people turned to crime during the late 1990s and early 2000s may reflect the diminished value of education following the IMF Crisis. Choi (2010b, pp.50-51) notes that "the chances of elevating one's social status through higher education" became increasingly slim after the financial crisis.

Although education was long considered the principal guarantor of success in Korean culture (Desser 2007, p.85), sociologist Andrew Eungi Kim (2004, p.223) notes that most college graduates hired after the IMF Crisis worked less secure and desirable jobs than the generation before them. In fact, over 30% of college graduates hired in late 2000 were temporary workers (ibid.). Choi (2010a, p.63) remarks that during the post-IMF period, "higher education no longer guaranteed employment, and employment did not ensure a stable future." As a result, a "residue of uncertainty" – as Kim and Finch (2002, p.120) describe it – enveloped South Korea.

Released the same year as the IMF Crisis, *Beat* seems prescient of the issues that would soon plague the country and its youth – Desser (2007, p.85) notes that the pressure to score high on college entrance exams takes its toll on the gangster-hero's girlfriend, Romi, and her friends. Romi is eventually hospitalised due to the stress, and her friend, In-kyung, jumps in front of a subway train when a low score stops her from entering Seoul National University. Similar themes are found in the high school horror genre, which Choi (2009, p.48) states portrays school as a "monstrosity" and the education system as depriving "students of their individual freedoms and happiness." Furthermore, Chi-Yun Shin (2013, p.139) notes that widespread corruption charges in education shocked Koreans throughout the early 2000s, challenging the meritocratic ideal long considered the reason for the

country's economic advancement since the 1950s: that the smartest and hardest working reap the greatest rewards.⁶²

In context, then, it does not seem unreasonable for the gangster-heroes of *Beat*, Min and Tae-soo, to drop out of school and pursue a life of crime. Indeed, while discussing the comedy-gangster film *Attack the Gas Station*, genre theorists Nancy Abelmann and Jung-ah Choi (2005, p.136) suggest that gang culture almost seems romantic when contrasted against “normative social life in which class marginality and difference...are punished.” This point is echoed by Choi (2010b, p.51), who states that the underworld of Korean gangster films represents an alternative route to achieving social mobility.

Unfortunately for the gangster-heroes of Revival Era films, the underworld is no less unforgiving than normal society or high school. In fact, the hierarchy between students and teachers is akin to the hierarchy between gangsters and gang bosses, with age being the defining factor of both. Just as teachers are older than their students, gang bosses are nearly always older than the gangster-hero. Often, the boss's age is enough to command respect from his underlings. In *Green Fish*, the power of seniority is clearly evidenced when the gangster-hero's boss, the forty-something Tae-gon, is brutally humiliated by his own boss, Kim Yang-gil, who is about ten to twenty years his senior.

Overall, the gang boss in Revival Era films is often prescient of his seniority and wields it to further manipulate his underlings. In *Green Fish*, Tae-gon takes the film's gangster-hero, Mak-dong, under his wing as one might a younger brother or son, offering him advice and confiding in him about his upbringing. Similarly, President Hwang offers Byung-doo fatherly advice in *A Dirty Carnival*, telling the young man to think of him “...as your big brother.” In both films, the bond between the gangster-hero and their boss is given

⁶² The comedy-gangster film *My Boss, My Hero* subverts the issue of corruption in Korea's education system by having gangsters fight to restore the system after one gangster, sent back to school to get a diploma needed for a promotion in his gang, discovers that his school is “corrupt on a grand scale” (Paquet 2009, p.81).

weight by the fact that neither Mak-dong's nor Byung-doo's father is alive. For them, their gang boss not only embodies a father figure but substitutes for one.

Of course, age is not the only tool used by bosses to command respect and loyalty. The most striking similarity between the teacher/student and gangster/gang boss dynamics is the brutal use of violence to enforce order and obedience. For example, in *Friend*, Joon-suk's boss punishes his disobedience by slicing his face and telling him, "*You need to suffer a little...you have to learn to be grateful.*" Another notable example occurs in *Failan*: after the gangster-hero, Kang-jae, fails to complete a job, his boss insults him, telling Kang-jae that he is "*not even human*" before whacking him with a metal tray and lashing him with a stick.

6.4 Working Class Heroes: Crime, Class and Social Inequality

Social inequality became an important issue following the IMF Crisis. Kim (2004, p.222) notes that the crisis resulted in thousands of businesses going bankrupt overnight and the unemployment rate doubling within a few months. As a result, the position of Korea's middle class deteriorated (Koo 2021, p.2; Lee 2015, p.194; Park, G. 2004, p.158; Kim and Finch 2002, p.123). In fact, Kim and Finch (2010, p.123) note that by May 1998, 80% of Korean households had experienced a significant decline in income, with many people feeling "they had been pushed out of the middle class." Furthermore, the percentage of Korean households under the poverty line increased from 2.8% in 1997 to 7.3% in 1999 (Kim 2004, p.230).

This stark decline in economic status for many Koreans is directly reflected in Revival Era films: of the fifteen films examined in this chapter, only *A Bittersweet Life* features a gangster-hero unburdened by economic difficulty. Accordingly, Choi (2010b, p.50) remarks that one of the central appeals of Korean gangster cinema might be its embodiment of "cultural anxieties over the rigidity of social hierarchy."

In many ways, the very act of becoming or being a gangster is linked to social inequality. De Caires et al. (2012, p.47) note “that there is a strong correlation between joining a gang and the limited access to legitimate means of acquiring culturally prescribed symbols of material success.” This is evidenced in the Revival Era by the fact that gangster-heroes are rarely drawn to crime out of ego or greed. Indeed, while Min et al. (2003, p.176) correctly state that Yong-dae in *Rules of the Game*, Tae-su in *Beat* and Tae-ju in *No.3* blindly pursue material gain, many Revival Era gangster-heroes only begin a life of crime out of a desire to escape poverty or a need to provide for themselves and/or their family.

In *Die Bad*, Sung-bin tries to live honestly after being released from prison, but his status as a juvenile ex-convict forces him into the underworld. In *Green Fish*, Mak-dong becomes a gangster to reunite his poverty-stricken family under one roof. Choi (2016, p.224) notes that Byung-doo has similar motivations for being a gangster in *A Dirty Carnival*, maintaining a life of crime so he can care for his mother and adolescent siblings.

Other gangster-heroes become gangsters for more superficial reasons: in *Die Bad*, Sang-hwan drops out of school to become a gangster due to his craving for respect and a naive belief that he will “*move up*” his gang’s ranks and eventually manage a business. In *Rules of the Game*, Yong-dae wants to become a gangster simply because he is bored working as a car wash attendant, and in *Cruel Winter Blues*, Chu-jik abandons his career as a Taekwondo instructor to earn more money as a gangster.

Even so, while the goals of Sang-hwan, Hong-ki and Chu-jik are relatively superficial, they nonetheless reflect the motivating factor of social inequality. As Kim (2019, p.501) notes, “the Korean gangster...is determined by his class.” Indeed, De Caires et al. (2012, p.47) note that “[real world] gangs and membership in them represent...a dialectical struggle against social irrelevance and an existential reaction to class domination and oppression.”

This may be why onscreen gangsters are so reluctant to abandon their gangs after they join them. For most gangsters, their criminality is a point of pride rather than shame, an act of defiance against a society that they feel has betrayed them or forsaken them. This defiant attitude is evidenced in a scene in *A Dirty Carnival*: although circumstances are so dire for Byung-doo and his men that they must dine on the floor of their overcrowded apartment, Byung-doo rallies his men by telling them, “*Though we may starve to death, we should never fail to respect ourselves.*”

Ironically, by fleeing to the underworld and becoming gangsters, Choi (2016, p.224) suggests that gangster-heroes such as Byung-doo maintain the very inequality they wish to overcome. Choi (ibid.) notes that Byung-doo helps his boss to unjustly displace tenants of a local neighbourhood so that it can be redeveloped, serving “to maintain and reinstate the social hierarchy...into which he painstakingly hopes to fit but will never be fully accepted.”

Byung-doo’s mistake – and one shared by many other Revival Era gangster-heroes – is his assumption that the underworld is fairer than normal society. In actuality, the underworld is more deadly and brutal; Byung-doo is eventually murdered by his right-hand man on orders from their boss. De Caires et al. (2012, p.51) state that “the moral of the story [*A Dirty Carnival* (Yoo 2006)] is...everyone feeds on one another for the sake of upward mobility.”

On a similar note, Choi (2010b, p. 51) states that the promises of the underworld are ultimately “symbolic, or even ironic since gangster society imposes a stricter hierarchy and demands the complete abandonment of one’s will.” Indeed, Byung-doo’s sad fate is not a unique one; gangster-heroes die in nine of the fifteen films in this chapter’s corpus. Furthermore, Byung-doo and the respective protagonists of *Green Fish*, *Die Bad*, *Friend*, and *Cruel Winter Blues* are each killed by someone they trust, be it a former friend, gang boss or fellow ‘brother-in-arms’.

The gangster-hero's death marks a notable parallel between the Revival Era and the Early Pre-Revival Era. Another similarity is the fact that the gangster-hero's death acts as a sombre statement on class. As Choi (2010a, p.69) observes, tragedy is not rooted in the protagonist's flaws, but rather in their social circumstances. Similarly, Jamier (2015, p.46) states, "the gangster's life is not his to begin with; it belongs to the social groups that are greater than he is, and toward which his debt is infinite."

Despite these similarities, there is an important difference between the Early Pre-Revival Era and Revival Era: while almost every Early Pre-Revival Era gangster, irrespective of their rank or narrative role, is impoverished and marginalised, there is a stark contrast in status between low-ranking and high-ranking gangsters in Revival Era films.

Indeed, the underworld not only reflects the inequalities of Korean society but replicates them. Most gang bosses enjoy a lavish lifestyle, replete with expensive cars, young mistresses and designer suits. Whereas Byung-doo must work tirelessly to secure his family's future in *A Dirty Carnival*, his boss, Chairman Hwang, casually embarks on a massive real estate venture. Whereas Tae-sik works in a garage in *Sunflower*, the local gang boss, Pan-su, is a city councillor who uses his status to invest in commercial real estate.

The social inequality of the underworld directly reflects the social inequality that characterised Korean society in the late 1990s and early 2000s. As Lee (2015, p.188) states, social inequality rose even as the Korean economy recuperated. This point is echoed by Kim (2004, p.229), who states that social inequality persisted into the new millennium even after the Korean government had paid the last instalment of the IMF's \$57 billion loan in 2001.

In fact, whereas the top 20% of Korean earners made 4 times more than the bottom 20% in 1996, the top 20% made 5.5 times more than the bottom 20% in 2006 (Lee 2019, p.24). In addition, sociologist Lee, Y. (2019, p.24) notes that the wealth of the top 10% rose from 34.7% of the national income to 44% between 1996 and 2006 (ibid.). The wealth of

the top 1% also rose, from 4.8% to 6.9% (ibid.). Simultaneously, the middle class grew smaller, and rates of poverty and unemployment increased (ibid.).

Although released in the same year as the IMF Crisis, *Beat* highlights class inequality through its depiction of Min and Romi's relationship. Desser (2007, p.74) states that "it is abundantly clear and an integral part of the drama that Romi is solidly middle class", and that Min is working class. It is Romi's class status that enables her to buy a dance with Min at a nightclub auction and to gift him one of the two pagers that she received for her birthday (Desser 2007, p.74). The class divide that separates Romi and Min echoes the division that separated Doo-soo and Ae-ran in the Pre-Revival Era film *The Barefooted Young*. Indeed, while the lives of Doo-soo and Min are very different, both are loners who are prone to getting into trouble, lack direction and struggle to relate to their girlfriends.

Overall, Desser (2007, p.87) states that "*Beat* is a veritable compendium of how and why a marginalized, underclass remains in Korea—the failure to attend a prestigious university, the presence of crime and violence, lack of concern on the part of the authorities, the rush to materialism, and concern for pretense over substance."

Most sociologists attribute the increase in social inequality to an issue not mentioned by Desser (ibid.): labour law revisions that allowed companies to replace permanently hired workers with temporary or non-standard workers (Koo 2021, p.4; Lee, Y. 2019, p.24; Lee 2015, p.189). Koo (2021, p.4) states that the proportion of irregular workers (temporary workers and daily workers) rose from 41.9% in 1995 to 52.1% in 2000. Koo (2021, p.6) also notes that the division between standard and irregular workers is a direct determinant of social inequality in Korean society, with the average income of irregular workers in 2005 being between 50.9% and 62.7% of that of regular workers.⁶³

⁶³ Koo (2021, p.6) uses two figures. The first, 62.7%, is based on the government definition of irregular workers. The second, 50.9% is based on figures provided by labor advocacy groups.

The disparity between regular and irregular workers is not limited to income. Lee (2015, p.188) notes that the lives of the “new underclass” of insecure irregular workers are characterised by job insecurity, minimal social protection, and “dismal prospects for promotion or social mobility.” Overall, Lee, Y. (2019, p.24) states that the “flexibilization of the labor market” created a division between the protected and unprotected.

In many ways, Lee’s (2015, p.188) description of irregular workers recalls the social situations of most Revival Era gangster-heroes: the gangster-hero also suffers from job insecurity; although they flee to the underworld due to its promises of loyalty, honour and status, they are subject to rigid hierarchies that prioritise their boss’s desires over their own interests and wellbeing. As one of Sang-hwan’s friends tells him in *Die Bad*, “*Don’t you see you’re nothing but a knife buffer for the big guys?*”

Overall, by joining the underworld, the gangster-hero forsakes any social protections that he might have had in normal society. At the mercy of their boss, they are guaranteed nothing. Second chances are rare, safety nets are nonexistent, and dissent is forbidden. Although Joo-jeong insists that he and his fellow gangsters have “*employment insurance*” in *Righteous Ties*, it does nothing to stop the treachery of his boss, who plots to have Joo-jeong’s friends, Chi-sung and Soon-tan, killed.

Lee’s (2015, p.188) final note on the “dismal prospects for promotion or social mobility” for irregular workers is particularly relevant to the Revival Era. The only gangster-heroes who successfully rise through the ranks of their gang are Kim Du-han in *General’s Son* and Joon-suk in *Friend*. Although Mak-dong in *Green Fish* and Byung-doo in *A Dirty Carnival* also ascend the ranks of their respective gangs, they are ultimately killed or imprisoned. Overall, while the underworld promises an alternative means of social mobility, it does not guarantee it, no matter how devoted, determined or loyal a gangster-hero may be.

The similarities between Korea's "insecure class" – a term coined by Lee (2015, p.185) – and Revival Era gangsters highlight the Korean gangster genre's tendency, whether intentional or not, to reflect prevailing social issues. In fact, Min et al. (2003, p.180) argue that the gangster genre's revival in the 1990s was "a cinematic response" to the repression and dysfunction of contemporary Korean society.

Although not all gangsters are as impoverished as they were during the Pre-Revival Era, Revival Era gangsters are not much more socially integrated than their Pre-Revival Era predecessors. Indeed, gangsters – no matter their rank – are often treated as 'second-class citizens'. Despite his wealth and status in *A Dirty Carnival*, Byung-doo's boss, Chairman Hwang, is ridiculed by a local prosecutor, who says, "*Fucking gangsters. Parasites of our society. Losers like this should be sucked up with a vacuum cleaner.*" This sentiment is echoed by the gangster-hero of *Righteous Ties*, Chi-sung. While in prison, he tells a fellow inmate, "*Don't get the wrong impression. There's no good gangster anywhere. Knights, justice...It's all bullshit. A gangster is just a gangster.*" Chi-sung's statement recalls Doo-soo's self-deprecating comments in *The Barefooted Young*, in which he refers to himself as a "scumbag" and "a cancer to society".

The status of Revival Era gangsters is most apparent when examining the era's iconography. Plaice (2020, p.5) notes that gangster films made during New Korean Cinema are typified by dark alleys, nightclubs, brothels, gambling dens, abandoned warehouses and dilapidated factories. Although Sun-woo manages a luxurious nightclub in *A Bittersweet Life*, he is often called upon to deal with troublesome patrons in the nightclub's grimy lower levels. In *Die Bad*, Sung-bin's gang is in a dingy bar at the bottom of a depressing concrete stairway, a literal connection between the normal world and the underworld.

When they are beyond their expected settings, gangsters are vulnerable. In *A Dirty Carnival*, Byung-doo is ambushed while meeting his girlfriend outside a bookshop. In *Sunflower*, Tae-sik's attempts to live a normal life are constantly interrupted – he is

assaulted and antagonised while working at a garage and forced to fend off gangsters when they raid his home. In *Die Bad*, a lack of domestic spaces makes it seem that the film's characters – namely the brothers Suk-hwan and Sang-hwan – do not have “a safe and secure place where they can relax and be protected” (Lee, N.J.Y. 2019, p.319).

6.5 Identity Crisis: Wrestling with Oneself, Brotherhood and Betrayal

Aside from their marginalisation, Revival Era gangster-heroes share another characteristic with their Pre-Revival Era predecessors: lives of strife and torment. However, whereas the Pre-Revival Era gangster-hero's strife stemmed mainly from external sources – such as the harsh realities of postwar Korea – the Revival Era gangster-hero's strife stems from both external – the harsh realities of post-IMF Korea as discussed in sections 6.2 and 6.3 – and internal – their struggle to accept or reconcile their identity as a gangster.

In *Green Fish*, Mak-dong is ravaged by guilt and sorrow after murdering a rival gangster at the behest of his boss. Soaked in his victim's blood, he sobs while staring at himself in a mirror. In *Friend*, Joon-suk struggles to reconcile his obligations as a gang leader with his loyalty to a childhood friend, and now rival gangster, Dong-su. Before he decides to have Dong-su killed, Joon-suk looks at an old photo of them together and contemplates the definition of 'friend'.⁶⁴ In *Righteous Ties*, Joo-jeong is similarly anguished when he must choose between obeying his gang and betraying his friends, Chi-sung and Soon-tan.

When forced to choose between their gang and their values, the Revival Era gangster-hero either commits to the twisted logic of the underworld, as Joon-suk does in *Friend*, or resists it, as Joo-jeong does in *Righteous Ties* when he murders his boss to save Chi-sung's life. Either way, the gangster-hero suffers a severe identity crisis.

⁶⁴ It is important to clarify that it is not clear whether Joon-suk is responsible for Dong-su's death in *Friend*. Although he pleads guilty, he does not privately admit that he ordered his friend killed. However, the film's sequel, *Friend: The Great Legacy*, confirms that Joon-suk *did* have Dong-su killed.

The identity crisis suffered by the Revival Era gangster-hero parallels the intense mental anguish that Choi (2010a, p.67) states plagued Hong Kong gangster-heroes. Indeed, Choi (2010a, p.72) highlights the fact that Hong Kong gangster-heroes are also forced to make difficult choices because of familial or other obligations.

Many scholars who discuss Hong Kong gangster cinema suggest the mental anguish suffered by the genre's protagonists reflects the anxieties of Hong Kongers during and after the 1997 handover. For example, Law (2008, p.535) believes the complex undercover narrative of *Infernal Affairs* (Lau and Mak 2002) reflects the "psychic tensions" and confusion of Hong Kongers at the time. Similarly, Lau (2016, p.60) suggests that *Election* (To 2005) reflects emerging issues that arose after the handover. The film's director, Johnnie To (cited in Lau 2016, p.60), remarked that the handover led to "immense change...beyond the ability of many Hong Kong people to handle."

The identity crises of Korean gangsters also seem to reflect socio-cultural issues, specifically those that arose following the IMF Crisis. Park, G. (2004, p.154) notes that before the crisis, "Koreans shared many common ideas, including...trust in business culture, beliefs about the nation's international status and prospects, and above all, pride in being Korean", but the financial crisis undermined these ideas.

Kim (2004, p.233) argues that the crisis not only undermined traditional values but "highlighted the dark side" of them.

Respect for authority, for example, often meant the inability to question those in authority as well as the blind respect for and pursuit of esteemed titles. Strict hierarchical social structure granted only the rights and privileges to superiors - which often led to corruption - while depriving the rights of subordinates. Emphasis on family led to nepotism or factionalism, while the accent on personal relationships bred cronyism and unhealthy school ties and regional ties. Moreover, emphasis on group interests often stifled individual creativity and an ability to innovate. Needless to say these problems have inspired Koreans to reassess the rightful role of Confucianism in Korean society (Kim 2004, pp.233-234).

Many of the values Kim (ibid.) describes are present in the underworld. As noted already in this chapter, the underworld is characterised by a strict hierarchical structure, social inequality and an emphasis on group interests over individuality. Paradoxically, the

underworld is, as criminologists De Caires et al. (2012, p.48) note, also a world that encourages independence, individualism and competition. Considering this paradox, it is no surprise that many actual Korean gangsters experience a “schism between two identities” (De Caires et al. 2012, p.48). Indeed, Ballard (2023, p.82) theorises that the Korean gangster’s “perpetually troubled character...[is] burdened by his connection to national consciousness...the concept of shared crisis and a developing Korean cognizance.”

In certain gangster films, the gangster-hero’s identity crisis is explored through rurality. Whereas the urban cityscape seems to entrap and ultimately destroy the protagonists of the Revival Era, rurality acts as a site of reinvention, allowing the gangster-hero to rediscover his values and morals. For example, in *Righteous Ties*, the countryside prompts gangster Joo-jeong to reflect on his childhood friendship with fellow gangsters Chi-sung and Soon-tan, ultimately leading him to betray his treacherous boss.

Cruel Winter Blues and *Sunflower* are also set in rural towns. Mark R. Plaice (2019a) – who has written extensively about the spaces of Korean gangster films – refers to Jae-moon’s moral transformation in *Cruel Winter Blues* as a “rural redemption.” Detached from the traditional spaces of the underworld, Jae-moon breaks free from the twisted logic that governs his gang. As Choi (2010b, p.52) notes, “the film poignantly dwells on the disorientation...of its characters, and the [Jae-moon’s] initial murderous agenda fades to the background.” Conversely, urban environments, being home to the underworld, corrupt and destroy protagonists. This is most evident in *Green Fish*, which sees its gangster-hero, Mak-dong, join a gang shortly after returning from military service to his newly urbanised hometown.

In certain films, the gangster-hero’s identity crisis is rendered through flashbacks. After Joon-suk has been tried and sentenced for ordering his friend’s murder in *Friend*, the film culminates with a brief scene depicting Joon-suk and his friend, Dong-su, as kids. Joined by two more friends, the boys splash around in the sea and work together to guide an

inflatable ring back to shore. *A Dirty Carnival* ends with a flashback to a moment between Byung-doo and his friend, Min-ho, before their relationship was destroyed, both by Min-ho's decision to use Byung-doo's personal recollections as material for his film, and Byung-doo's transformation into a ruthless, vengeful gangster.

Overall, flashbacks are used similarly – to encapsulate the gangster-hero's identity crisis – in many other films studied in this chapter. Often, a flashback occurs at the end of a film, accentuating the sombre tone of a scene set in the present. For example, *Die Bad* cuts from a flashback of two friends, Sung-bin and Suk-hwan, laughing together as teenagers, to a shot of an older Suk-hwan, his eyes gouged out and covered in Sung-bin's blood, screaming as he kneels over his friend's corpse. *Gangster High* reverses this order – the film transitions from a scene in which an imprisoned Sang-ho reads a letter from one of his dead friends, to a lengthy sequence of him and his friends playing football together in their schoolyard.

A fundamental theme evident in each of these flashbacks is brotherhood. Indeed, Shin (2005, p.118) notes that Revival Era gangs are often governed by a “homo-social hierarchy.” As noted in section 6.2, gang bosses often occupy a patriarchal role, convincing their underlings to think of them as a father or an older brother. However, the homo-social bonds of Korean gangs are not limited to the gangster/boss dynamic. Most Revival Era gangster-heroes view their *entire* gang as a family. Some gangster-heroes even refer to their fellow gangsters as ‘brothers’. As Kim (2019, p.500) notes, aside from “the boss-as-father...the rest of gang [sic] is structured as elder and younger brothers.”

The bond between Byung-doo and his subordinate, Jong-soo, is so strong in *A Dirty Carnival* that Jong-soo is willing to help Byung-doo murder a public prosecutor on behalf of their boss, President Hwang. “*I'm here because of you,*” Jong-soo tells Byung-doo, “*I'll go if you go.*” Byung-doo also maintains a close relationship with the six or so men under his direct command – in fact, he is not just their leader but their provider, feeding and housing

them. Another scene in which Byung-doo and his men drunkenly party in a karaoke bar further emphasises their bond not just as colleagues but as ‘brothers’.

In *Beat*, Min risks and ultimately sacrifices his life trying to save his friend Tae-soo. In *General's Son*, brotherhood transcends the boundaries of rival gangs when Du-han and his long-lost childhood friend, Dong-oe, rekindle their old friendship despite fighting on opposite sides of a Korean vs. Japanese gang war.

Overall, Revival Era gangster-heroes care deeply for their friends and look after their own. As De Caires et al. (2012, p.52) note, they “are loyal to their friends, and will fight on their behalf or in their defence when the situation demands.” Jamier (2015, p.46, italics in original) notes that “the archetypal Korean gangster story is that of a *boy's* tragedy—one of vivid suffering in which the protagonist’s gaze expresses an unrelieved anxiety, a lust for life, and the pounding heartbeat of vestigial boyhood.”

Released only months before the IMF Crisis, *Green Fish* seems prescient of the crisis of masculinity that would afflict Korean men later that year. As Kim and Finch (2002, p.131) note, traditional gender roles were shaken by massive layoffs, with many newly unemployed men struggling to acknowledge that they were now reliant on their wives. Indeed, Shin (2005, p.123) notes that the mass layoffs “problematized South Korean manhood.” Writing about *Friend*, Shin (2005, p.123) argues that the film’s protagonists “recover what cops, soldiers, teachers and fathers could never secure: dignity and self-respect...[and offer] catharsis to Korean men suffering from political and economic depression.”

Shin (2005, p.123) also argues that Korean gangster films, particularly *Friend*, celebrate and romanticise gang culture. This opinion seems to be shared by Min et al. (2003, p.177), who state that “the male hero of the new gangster film is an embodiment of untamed masculinity and repressed desire, who refuses to be contained within the system.”

However, the extreme trauma that most Revival Era gangster-heroes endure seems to contradict this idea. Indeed, De Caires et al. (2012, p.53) argue that *Friend's* (Kwak 2001) ending reveals brotherhood between gangsters to be “a useless and dead value.”

Like a fish out of water, Dong-Su dies an ignominious death in the gutter, alone, cold, and convulsing uncontrollably as life seeps out of him...The concept of loyalty in a gang is shown for what it is: a useless and dead value that is best left on the street, to be swept up by the falling rain and into the gutters...Such subtle messages, however, are apt to be missed if viewers concentrate on the appearance of loyalty (De Caires et al. 2012, p.53).

Choi (2010a, p.68) makes a similar point, noting that loyalty, friendships and surrogate father-son relationships rarely survive in the underworld. Similarly, Kim (2019, p.516, italics in original) makes a similar point: “often...brotherly ties are rendered moot in contemporary gangster cinema, as films such as *Friend* and *A Dirty Carnival*...are littered with instances of familial betrayal.” In addition, Jamier (2015, p.47) states that “betrayal is the main event [of Korean gangster cinema], always waiting to hack at the most noble of bonds or brotherhoods.”

Choi (2010a, p.68) notes that while betrayal afflicts Hong Kong gangster-heroes, they often undergo a “return of the hero” arc, in which they lose their social status, generally due to betrayal, but eventually regain their status and become heroes. Conversely, the arc of the Revival Era gangster-hero often ends in betrayal. In *Cruel Winter Blues*, Jae-moon is stabbed to death by Chi-gook, his otherwise docile underling. In *Righteous Ties*, Chi-sung’s boss orders him killed and arranges the murder of his parents. Despite them growing up together, Byung-doo is killed by his longtime friend Jong-soo in *A Dirty Carnival*, and in *Friend*, Joon-suk betrays his childhood friend Dong-su, urging him to lie low abroad, only to have him killed later. *Die Bad*, *Beat*, *Green Fish*, and *Failan* also see the gangster-hero betrayed and killed.

6.6 A Man’s World: The Decline of Melodrama and Reductive Portrayals of Women

Overall, the Revival Era’s increased focus on brotherhood and betrayal seems to have supplanted the prominent melodramatic elements that characterised the Early Pre-Revival

Era. While many Revival Era films feature a romantic subplot and other melodramatic elements, they are rarely defined by them. Although many films in this chapter's corpus, such as *Green Fish*, *A Bittersweet Life*, *A Dirty Carnival* and *Gangster High*, feature a romantic plot, only *Rosy Life* and *Failan* focus on a romantic plot.

This supplantation is most apparent when examining the role of women in the Revival Era. In *A Dirty Carnival* and *Sunflower*, women appear as love interests solely to humanise the gangster-hero and increase the stakes of the film's plot. This is most evident in *Sunflower*, which only includes a single, brief scene between Tae-sik and his former lover, Eun-mi. Accordingly, it would be remiss to state that *Sunflower* has a romantic subplot at all. Eun-mi's appearance is used solely to humanise Tae-sik and does not influence the plot. Shin (2005, p.124) observes something similar in *Friend* – Joon-suk's wife, Jin-sook, is used "to shed light on his character" but is otherwise "barely more than a sketch [of a character]." Shin (2005, p.124) notes that the depiction of Jin-sook highlights the problematic representation of women in New Korean Cinema. In a scene set in the 1970s, when the film's characters are high schoolers, Jin-sook 'offers' his friend, Sang-taek, the chance to kiss Jin-sook as a token of friendship (ibid). Although the subsequent scene in which Sang-taek plays the guitar for Jin-sook is rather heartwarming, it is at the expense of Jin-sook's agency and independence – she is commodified in the name of brotherhood.

Women are commodified in many other Revival Era films. Min et al. (2003, p.177) note that women often appear as objects of love or sexual pleasure. In *Green Fish*, Mak-dong's boss, Tae-gon, forces his girlfriend, Mi-ae, to have sex with a prosecutor for his own gain, and in *Rules of the Game*, Yong-dae sells his girlfriend, Tae-suk, into prostitution.

Although these films may be attempting to highlight the harsh realities of being a woman in Korean society, these attempts are undermined by the fact that Jin-sook, Mi-ae and Tae-suk are not granted agency by each film's filmmakers. Just as they are exploited onscreen, they are exploited by the filmmakers to propel the plot and the gangster-hero's

development. This is particularly apparent in *General's Son*. Although the film features women more prominently than most other Revival Era films, the female characters mainly serve as glamorous adornments to the gangster's lifestyle. A touching scene in which the gangster-hero, Du-han, helps a hostess, Hwa-ja, briefly flee from her abusive husband is undercut when it culminates with a sex scene. Instead of being a genuine moment between the two characters, the scene serves to gratify Du-han's masculinity.

Even when female characters affect a film's plot, they often lack agency. Choi (2010a, p.70) notes that in films wherein the gangster-hero develops feelings for their boss's lover – such as *Green Fish* and *A Bittersweet Life* – women serve as “unintentional femme fatale figures: they trigger the disintegration of a male relationship but fall short of being seductresses.”

Overall, the reductive portrayal of women in the Revival Era reflects the treatment of women in Korean society at the time these films were made. Kim and Finch (2002, p.127) note that following the IMF Crisis, companies considered their female employees expendable, laying off disproportionately large numbers of women. Sociologist Jayati Ghosh (2010, p.383) states that “women were laid off at seven times the rate of men” between 1998 and 1999.

Despite these disadvantages, Kim and Finch (2002, p.136, quotations in original) note that women were also expected to “preserve male privilege within the family by improving their husband's mood. Indeed, Hye Seung Chung and David Scott Diffrient (2007, p.125) state that the “IMF Crisis engendered a patriarchal backlash” which expected women to sacrifice their careers, preside over household affairs and care for their husbands. Furthermore, Chung and Diffrient (ibid.) state that whereas Korean media “actively buttressed the depressed patriarchy...women were often blamed for their overzealous consumption habits and lack of loyalty to their husbands.”

This attitude toward women is encapsulated by Joon-suk's horrible treatment of his wife, Jin-sook, in *Friend*. Shin (2005, p.124) notes that Joon-suk verbally abuses his wife in front of his visiting friends. "What are you staring at bitch?" he shouts at Jin-sook, "I should rip your pussy apart." Unfortunately, although Joon-suk's vile actions are not celebrated, *Friend* fails to challenge gender-based discrimination because it does not develop Jin-sook into a full-fledged character, limiting her role and restricting her impact on the plot.

The limited role of women in the Revival Era parallels the portrayal of women in Korean history. Despite their involvement in important historical movements, Chung and Diffrient (2007, p.125) state that Korean history has mainly celebrated women as mothers, wives and sisters, burying them "under an all male cast nationalist history." Indeed, it is important to emphasise that discrimination against women in Korea is not an issue born of or limited to the IMF Crisis, but one linked to Korean society more generally.

This is substantiated by the lacklustre representation of women in Revival Era films made before the IMF Crisis. This is apparent when considering *Rosy Life*, which follows several dissolute characters, including a gangster, who frequent a comic-book store run by a woman known simply as 'Madam'. Although she begins as an atypically strong-willed and independent character, Madam's central role in the film is usurped by the film's three male protagonists: the gangster Dong-pal, the writer Choi Yoo-jin, and Madam's brother, the political dissident Kim Ki-yeong. Most problematically, Madam enters a romantic relationship with Dong-pal, who effortlessly wins her affection just days after raping her.

Chun et al. (2006, p.585, author's italics) emphasise that "there is evidence that Korean women experience *significantly* more discrimination than their counterparts in many other countries at similar stages of economic development." Kim (2004, p.232) highlights that even four years after the IMF Crisis, the proportion of women in senior positions in Korea was just 5%, far lower than that of other Asian countries, such as Singapore (21%), Malaysia (21%) and the Philippines (33%).

This cultural aversion to women in positions of authority is not only reflected by the lack of meaningful female roles in Revival Era films, but also by the lack of female gangsters – none of the films examined in this chapter feature a female gangster. In fact, female gangsters only appear during the Revival Era in comedy-gangster films, where the mere concept of a female gangster is used for comedic purposes. Indeed, Choi (2010a, p.71) notes that the protagonist’s gender is used as a comic device in *My Wife Is a Gangster* (Jo 2001).

Despite the release of the comedy-gangster film *No.3* in 1997, Kim (2019, p.22) believes *My Wife Is a Gangster* is a better marker of the sub-genre's beginning.⁶⁵ This is due to the fact that *No.3* is, akin to *General’s Son*, rather anomalous. As Atom (2011) notes, the film “stands as a rather unique artifact...though its influence in modern Korean cinema is undeniable, its individual merits are often neglected or underappreciated.” The film’s uniqueness is partly because it merged commercial filmmaking with auteur sensibilities at a time when such films did not really exist (Paquet 2011). The film is also marked by its unique deployment of comedy. Conran (2011b) states that while later comedy-gangster films would lampoon gangsters, *No.3* is more compelling, mocking gangsters without wholly undermining them. One such example of this is the fight between the gangster-hero, Tae-ju, and Dong-pal, a prosecutor, which, although intense, is playfully undercut by its setting: a children’s playground.

Another reason for *My Wife Is a Gangster* being a better marker of the comedy-gangster genre’s starting point is the fact that the film was followed by a spate of comedy-gangster films, including *Kick the Moon*, *Hi, Dharma!* (*Dalmaya nolja*, Park 2001), and *My Boss*, *My Hero*, released in 2001. The success of these films is evident by the many scholars,

⁶⁵ Paquet (2011) believes *Attack the Gas Station*, not *No.3* or *My Wife Is a Gangster*, marks the starting point of the comedy-gangster genre. However, it could be debated whether the film’s four protagonists *are* gangsters – neither organised or particularly criminal, they act and appear more akin to a band of teenage thugs. In addition, their actions are generally “capricious and bizarre” (De Caires et al. 2012, p.54). Paquet (2009, p.80) actually refers to them as “four rowdy hooligans”, and Abelmann and Choi (2005, p.132) refer to the film as a “violent comedy” rather than as a gangster film.

– such as Park, Y. (2019, p.123), Choi (2010a, p.76), Paquet (2009, p.81) and Chi-Yun Shin and Julian Stringer (2005, p.117) – that mention them, and their box office rankings: Paquet (2009, p.81) notes that *Kick the Moon* earned 4.4 million nationwide admissions, *My Wife Is a Gangster*, 5.2 million, *Hi, Dharma!*, 3.7 million, and *My Boss, My Hero*, 3.3 million. The highest-grossing film of 2002 was also a comedy-gangster film, *Marrying the Mafia* (Jamier 2015, p.43; Shin and Stringer 2005, p.117).

Due to their modest budgets, comedy-gangster films proved to be very lucrative, often earning “twenty times their original cost” (Choi 2010a, p.76). Accordingly, *My Wife Is a Gangster*, *My Boss, My Hero*, and *Marrying the Mafia* each spawned a succession of sequels. Darcy Paquet (2011) states that individually, “any of these films would have been interesting but not especially noteworthy – but the emergence of a new trend created something that was greater than the sum of its parts.”

Whereas the gangster-heroes in *Friend* and in the ‘serious’ gangster films that followed it are brooding, complex and tragic figures, Paquet (2009, p.81) notes that the gangsters of comedy-gangster films “display a pugnacious, self-centred impudence that becomes an open target for ridicule.” The tone of comedy-gangster films also differs from their ‘serious counterparts’ – rather than being entirely comedic, comedy-gangster films often fluctuate between two extremes: comedy and melodrama. As Choi (2010a, p.83) describes, tone can fluctuate even within a single scene: in *My Wife Is a Gangster*, a comedic scene between the titular gangster, Eun-jin, and an incompetent gang boss is interrupted by a flashback depicting Eun-jin’s difficult childhood growing up in an orphanage.

My Wife Is a Gangster follows Eun-jin, a gang boss, as she navigates her marriage to Su-il, a meek government clerk, with whom she wed upon the request of her terminally ill sister. Paquet (2009, p.82) states that the film juxtaposes family life with the life of a gang boss, subverting traditional gender roles. Indeed, Eun-jin starkly contrasts the female

characters that characterise non-comedic gangster films – respected, feared and violent, she commands many gangsters, all of them male, and is subservient to no one.

It is hard to celebrate this fact when, as Choi (2010a, p.80) states, humour is derived from the conflicting gender roles Eun-jin occupies as gang boss and wife. In addition, Choi (2010a, p.71) emphasises that it is not Eun-jin's feminine characteristics that make her a compelling character, inferring that it is characteristics that are traditionally considered masculine, such as her fighting skills.

Although the lack of gangster-heroes in Ryoo Seung-wan's *No Blood No Tears* (*Pido nunmuldo eopsi*, Ryoo 2002) disqualifies it as a gangster film as per the thesis's criteria, it merits brief discussion as it eschews the reductive representation of women in both 'serious' and comedic gangster films. By focusing on two women, Soo-jin, the girlfriend of an abusive low-level gangster, and Gyung-sun, a world-weary ex-convict hounded for debts left to her by her ex-husband, Ryoo offers a different viewpoint of the underworld. Kim (2015, p.115) notes that Ryoo reconfigures the gender dynamics of a classical film noir – Soo-jin and Gyung-sun's plot to steal money from an illegal dogfighting ring run by Soo-jin's boyfriend, Dok-bul, is not just a desperate bid for wealth but an act of defiance against the world trapping them.

Ryoo seems to make a point of emphasising that this world is dominated by men. Soo-jin's boyfriend, Dok-bul, is just one of many unsavoury male characters in the film. Aside from contending with Dok-bul's abuse, Soo-jin must also suffer the creepy advances of a gangster nicknamed 'Pretty Boy'. Meanwhile, Gyung-sun must contend with two older gangsters chasing her for debts on behalf of their boss, another man. In stealing from the dogfighting ring run by Dok-bul, both women are also forced to contend with KGB, a fearsome male gang boss, and his stoic enforcer, Silent Man.

Ryoo's emphasis on the women's perilous place in the underworld is evident throughout the film, but particularly during the film's climactic fight between the two

women and Dok-bul. Kim (2015, p.116) notes that the fight is filmed in such a way as to remind the viewer of everyday scenes of domestic violence and patriarchal oppression. Notably, Dok-bul does not fight with the women as much as he does beat them. It is poignant then, that Gyung-sun kills Dok-bul using a key, an object known to be used by women in acts of self-defence (Kim 2015, p.116).

Some scholars might argue that the lack of female gangsters reflects the realities of organised crime. Indeed, men dominate the demographics of gangs to such an extent that no criminologist cited in this thesis remarks on the gender of real-life gangsters.⁶⁶ However, such an argument assumes that Revival Era films faultlessly depict reality. This is evidently not true by the fact that there are many unrealistic scenes – such as Sung-bin’s haunting in *Die Bad*, the climactic shootout in *A Bittersweet Life* and the fighter jet crash in *Righteous Ties* – throughout the Revival Era. In addition, the violence that typifies the Revival Era is not realistic. As criminologist Park, Y.K. (2004, p.63) notes, “security and order are fairly well maintained on the streets of Korea...we have rarely seen such incidents in Korea where...criminal groups fight each other with guns or knives.”

It seems particularly reductive that, aside from appearing as romantic figures, women most often appear in the Revival Era as maternal figures. Often, the maternal figure is representative of traditional values. In *A Dirty Carnival*, Byung-doo’s mother laments, “*I wish you’d stop living like that and start leading a normal life.*” After Tae-sik is imprisoned for killing a rival gangster in *Sunflower*, he is visited by the mother of his victim, who forgives him and offers him a small notebook as a gift. This simple act of kindness spurs Tae-sik to reform himself – he pledges to never drink, fight or cry again, writing each vow in his new notebook. Soon afterwards, the mother of the rival gangster adopts Tae-sik, and he returns to his hometown a changed man. He finds work at a local garage, consults a doctor

⁶⁶ De Caires et al. (2012, p.47), Lee (2006, p.68), and Park, Y. (2004, p.65) only mention women when discussing human trafficking.

about removing his gang tattoos and cares for his stepsister. In *Cruel Winter Blues*, Jae-moon, a gruff and rude mid-ranking gangster, undergoes tremendous personal growth due to his interactions with an elderly restaurant owner, Jeom-sim. In spending time with Jeom-sim, Jae-moon develops genuine empathy for her, so much so that he stops himself from killing her son, a rival gangster who murdered his best friend.

6.7 A Means to an End: The Meaning of Violence

Min et al. (2003, p.175) state that violence is the “central experience” of gangster films made during New Korean Cinema. Similarly, Jamier (2015, p.47) states that “in the Korean gangster genre, violence is at once foundational and final.”

Indeed, violence is often the central means through which the gangster-hero climbs the ranks of his gang and improves his social status. As Min et al. (2003, p.176) note, violence is the “only and ultimate means of social mobility available to the [gangster] hero.” In *Green Fish*, Mak-dong is promoted from a car park attendant to a low-level gangster when his boss learns that he bested a fellow gangster in a fight. Similarly, violence helps Yong-dae gain the attention of his boss in *Rules of the Game* (Min et al. 2003, p.176). For Tae-hoon, the gangster interviewed in the second part of *Die Bad*, violence is the *only* means of social mobility available to him – when asked why he became a gangster, he replies: “*No money, no connections, no brains even. But I can fight like hell. What else can I do?*”

Yet, the role of violence is paradoxical. Although it grants the gangster social mobility, violence often *denies* them social mobility and sometimes costs them their lives. The entire plot of *No.3*, which follows the gangster-hero Tae-ju as he tries to rise from being the third-highest to second-highest member of his gang, is catalysed by Tae-ju losing a bar fight.

The duality of violence – as a force of both liberation and destruction – is most apparent in *General's Son*: although the yakuza use violence to subdue the Jongno populace,

the Jongno residents use violence to defend themselves. In fact, Du-han's fighting skills are the only reason why the yakuza fail to conquer Jongno. In a world without violence, Du-han – and by proxy, the Korean people – might not have needed to defend themselves. Yet, a world without violence might also have led to their total defeat and subjugation. As Min et al. (2003, p.176) note, violence often represents the gangster's resistance to the dominant social system while also reaffirming that social system.

Aside from being a dualistic force of liberation and destruction, violence is also a means of expression for the gangster. Jamier (2015, p.44) notes that violence is the only method through which the gangster-heroes of *Green Fish* and *A Dirty Carnival* can define themselves. This is also true of Sun-woo in *A Bittersweet Life*. Frustrated by his inability to emotionally connect with his boss's girlfriend or understand his feelings for her, Sun-woo mulls in frustration while driving home. When some teenagers in a passing car harass him, Sun-woo gives chase, cuts the teenagers off in traffic and beats them up without hesitation. In doing so, Sun-woo momentarily reasserts control, relinquishing his sense of emotional impotence.

A similar scene occurs in *Rosy Life*. After Dong-pal narrowly escapes an ambush set by his former gangster comrades, he storms into a comic book store he frequents and rapes the owner, Madam, as if trying to reclaim some sense of power or to discharge his anger and frustration. Min et al. (2003, pp.176-177) note that “at a deeper level...violence serves to represent [the] repressed libido or subversive impulse, which...sedimented and fermented...in 1990s Korean society.”

More directly, the violence of the Revival Era reflects the lack of guns in Korea. As Min et al. (2003, p.174) note, “firearms are seldom used because private owning of firearms is categorically prohibited in Korea.” Criminologist Park, Y.K. (2004, p.63) notes that civilians even require police authorisation to use guns for hunting or other sports, and Porteux (2013, p.54) states that Korea has “some of the strictest gun controls in the

developed world.” As a result, there are only 0.02 annual gun deaths per 100,000 people in Korea (gunpolicy.org 2023a). In comparison, the rate of annual gun deaths in the USA is 15.27 per 100,000 people (ibid.). Although matters are less disparate between Korea and Hong Kong – Hong Kong only has 0.04 annual gun deaths per 100,000 people per year – the rate of civilian gun ownership is twenty-four times higher in Hong Kong than in Korea, at 3.6 per 100 people versus 0.15 per 100 people (gunpolicy.org 2023b).

The impact of Korea’s gun laws on organised crime is notably depicted in *A Bittersweet Life*. Seeking revenge against his former gang, Sun-woo is forced to purchase guns from a shady arms dealer headquartered in a run-down apartment. Even in Korea’s underworld, the buying and selling of firearms is monitored and controlled – the arms dealer only sells guns to people referred to him, and he only offers Sun-woo a single weapon, a Russian pistol. Aside from *A Bittersweet Life*, every film in this chapter’s corpus primarily features melee combat, with most gangsters wielding “knives, clubs, iron pipes, and broken bottles” (Min et al. 2003, p.174).⁶⁷

The reliance on melee weapons also reflects real-world violence in Korea. Porteux (2013, p.54) notes that real-life Korean gangsters typically use “iron rods, baseball bats, axes, swords [and even] fire extinguishers as their weapons of choice.” Even so, Park, Y.K. (2004, p.63) states that “security and order is fairly well maintained [in Korea]”, with incidents in which gangsters attack each other with guns or knives being rare.

Inaccurate though it may be, the use of melee weapons in the Revival Era has led to a brutal style of violence which Kim (2010, p.504) describes as “visceral, kinetic, and often desperate, accented by graphic displays of cuts and stabbings.”⁶⁸ Due to the lack of guns,

⁶⁷ Although *Righteous Ties* also features firearms, a gun is only used in one instance when Joo-jeong shoots his gang boss. Otherwise, there is no exchange of gunfire or gunplay. Firearms also appear in *Rosy Life* but they are brandished by police officers, and even then, only briefly.

⁶⁸ It is important to note that while the violence in *General’s Son* features melee weapons and fists, it would be remiss to term it brutal violence. In contrast to every other film studied in this chapter, the violence in *General’s Son* (Im 1990) is driven by codes of honour and is restrained and almost artful.

gangsters must attack their enemies up close, with combat often incurring both a physical and mental toll. In *Die Bad*, a lengthy fight between a cop and a gangster sees both men drenched in sweat, moving sluggishly and desperately. Lee, N.J.Y. (2019, p.319) notes that the unglamorous style of the scene stems from director Ryoo Seung-wan's decision to scrap the preplanned choreography and instead make the fighting wild and uncoordinated. As a result, the fight feels savage and gritty, a fact heightened further by the erratic, handheld camerawork and the grimy car park location in which the fight is set.

Another gruellingly violent scene occurs in *Green Fish*. As a demonstration of loyalty to his boss, Mak-dong assassinates a rival gangster in a toilet stall, stabbing him with a knife hidden in a magazine. Blood spurts from the rival gangster's wounds, gushing onto the floor and staining his white clothes. Although the gangster dies after just a few stabs, the scene continues as Mak-dong frantically washes the blood off the restroom floor, wailing and sobbing as he does. By murdering the rival gangster on behalf of his boss, Min et al. (2003, p.178) posits that Mak-dong's innocence is "brutally victimised" by his boss's sinister ambitions. It is not the murder that traumatises Mak-dong but the meaning of it; Mak-dong sacrifices his identity as an individual for his identity as a gangster.

This is just one of many scenes in which a gangster is transformed by violence. Indeed, Ballard (2023, p.81, italics in original) states that "there is a palpable difference between the disposition and condition of the gangster *before* entering a fight and the man he ultimately transforms into by its conclusion."

Another example of the transformative power of violence can be found in *Sunflower*. After his mother is murdered by a local gang, Tae-sik ambushes the gang's headquarters and single-handedly defeats everyone stationed there. The moment should be triumphant, but Tae-sik is teary-eyed and grief-stricken throughout the fight. In resorting to violence, Tae-sik reneges on his efforts to abandon his old life as a gangster. More importantly, he breaks a promise he made to his mother to never fight again. For this reason, Tae-shik decides to

kill himself even though he bests the enemy gangsters – ashamed and distraught, he remains in the gang’s headquarters as it burns to the ground.

The climactic fight in *Sunflower* is an example of a specific form of violence in Korean gangster cinema: the ‘one-versus-many’ fight. In the ‘one-versus-many’ fight, the gangster-hero fights alone against a group of opponents. The climactic battle of *A Bittersweet Life* is an example of this type of fight: in the film’s finale, Sun-woo storms the headquarters of his former gang, dispatching enemies with a pistol. A similar scene occurs in *Righteous Ties* when, armed with just his fists, Chi-sung battles dozens of his treacherous gangster comrades. In all three aforementioned films – *Sunflower*, *A Bittersweet Life* and *Righteous Ties* – the ‘one-versus-many’ fight serves as a cathartic release for the protagonist. Indeed, as Ballard (2023, p.82) notes, physical altercations rarely function solely as spectacle in Korean gangster cinema but are instead regularly used to mark critical narrative junctures or to convey important information.

Nevertheless, violence is rarely inflicted without cost in the Revival Era. Tae-shik’s decision to commit suicide in *Sunflower* echoes the suicidal nature of Sun-woo’s actions in *A Bittersweet Life*. Following his boss’s betrayal, Sun-woo has a chance at a normal life but forsakes it to seek revenge instead. Cagle (2009, p.140) suggests that “in killing off [his] opponents – the people who represent his choices in life, his experience – Sun-woo is killing himself. Violence is not, therefore, seen as liberating or positive, but rather, as wholly destructive.” Although Chi-sung does not die in his quest for vengeance in *Righteous Ties*, his decision to seek it leads to the death of his friend, Joo-jeong.

In addition to the one-versus-many fight, Kim (2019, p.503) identifies two more forms of violence in the Revival Era: i) the ‘one-on-one’ fight and ii) the brawl. Similar to the one-versus-many fight, the one-on-one fight also acts as a cathartic release for the gangster-hero, only instead of battling many opponents, they battle a single opponent. A particularly brutal one-on-one fight occurs between former childhood friends, Suk-hwan, a

cop, and Sung-bin, a gangster, in *Die Bad*. After a lengthy struggle, Sung-bin gouges Suk-hwan's eyes out, only for Suk-hwan to strangle him to death. As blood streams from his eyes, Suk-hwan lets out a pained yell. Although he wins the fight, he is nevertheless defeated.

As this example illustrates, the one-on-one fight is often intensely personal. Forced to engage in close quarters, an almost intimate connection forms between the duelling opponents. In most one-on-one fights, tight shots, shallow focus, and a lack of musical score accentuate the intense emotion.

The final form of violence in the Revival Era, the brawl, is anything but personal or emotional. Described by Kim (2019, p.503) as a staple of the Korean gangster genre, the brawl or *paessaum* (group fight) is a chaotic skirmish between many gangsters or entire gangs. Overall, brawls are less focused on the underlying meaning of violence than on the purely aesthetic qualities of combat. Accordingly, brawls are often accompanied by a high-tempo musical score intended to heighten the spectacle of the violence.

This is not to say that brawls are *never* meaningful. Although smaller in scale than other brawls, the final brawl in *Gangster High* between the TNT and Tiger gangs combines gripping action with intense melodrama. Although most of the brawl features rapid cuts, frenetic camerawork and a classical music-inflected score, the scene's aesthetics change when the Tiger gangster, Hong-gyu, is killed and his friend Sang-ho suddenly becomes aware of the barbarity of the brawl.

As Sang-ho watches his friends being stabbed and beaten by the vicious TNT gangsters, the musical score is replaced by a song: the 1959 track *Trouble of the World* by gospel singer Mahalia Jackson. As the song continues, the colours fade until the film is in black and white. Then, in a lengthy slow-motion shot, Sang-ho rampages with a metal pole, subduing the TNT gangsters and brutally executing their leader, Jong-suk. When the fighting ceases, the song ends and colour returns to the footage, revealing – in a slow-panning wide

shot – the gruesome, blood-drenched floors of the dingy billiard hall in which the gangsters, now all dead or seriously injured, were just fighting.

By heightening the spectacle of violence before melodramatising it, director Park Ki-hyung depicts Sang-ho's relationship with the ongoing violence. Although initially eager to fight the TNT gangsters, the death of his friend changes the meaning of the brawl for Sang-ho, transforming it from impersonal to deeply personal. Then, when he realises what he has done, the film emphasises the sight of the bloodied gangsters and the sound of their pained groans.

Ryoo Seung-wan deploys aesthetics to a similar effect in *Die Bad*. In the film's finale, a band of young, inexperienced gangsters is quickly outmatched by a rival gang. As the rival gangsters ruthlessly pounce on the youngsters, the brawl quickly turns into a slaughter. Countless shots show the youngsters being stabbed, sliced and brutally murdered. Rapid editing and handheld camerawork accentuate the chaos to such an extent that it is nearly impossible to differentiate between the gangs.

In an aesthetic shift similar to the one in *Gangster High*, the frenetic editing and camerawork stop when Sang-hwan is shoved against a wall and stabbed repeatedly in the gut. As he bleeds out, Sang-hwan looks around him at the unfolding bloodshed. Several shots depict his friends and comrades being mercilessly butchered, and, for a moment, the only sound is Sang-hwan's sad, pained grunting as his last breaths pass between his lips.

Overall, whether it takes the form of a brawl, a one-on-one fight or a one-versus-many fight, violence in the Revival Era is rarely ever honourable or glorious. Although violence allows the gangster-hero to ascend his gang's ranks, it is often responsible for his downfall or demise. In addition, violence often most afflicts those on the gang's lowest rung, whether in terms of rank or age. Although some bosses, such as Sang-chul in *A Dirty Carnival*, partake in gang violence, most interact with their men from the safety of their lavish cars and offices. Indeed, while many gangster-heroes are betrayed by their boss, only

one gang boss, Tae-gon in *Green Fish*, has the twisted decency to commit the murder himself.

6.8 Conclusion

Young, gangster-heroes, the high school setting, the encapsulation of issues such as generational division and social inequality, an emphasis on the gangster-hero's struggle with identity, and gritty visceral violence – these are some of the many elements, to answer the chapter's first research question, '*What elements define the Revival Era?*', that define the Revival Era.

Considering that many of these elements emerged during the Revival Era, it is understandable that, as Choi (2010a, p.60) notes, certain Korean critics believed the gangster genre was a “novel form” when it reemerged in the 1990s and early 2000s. Indeed, it is rather ironic, as Choi (2010a, p.60) notes, that the gangster genre's return to Korean screens was marked by *General's Son*, a film that resembles 1970s gangster films more than it does other Revival Era gangster films.

The novelty of the Revival Era is furthered by the fact that, unlike the preceding Pre-Revival Era, it explicitly depicts gang violence and organised crime, and features gangster-heroes that are clearly gangsters. This represents a notable development over the Pre-Revival Era, which saw gangster-heroes cast as both romantic leads and action heroes, but never clearly as organised criminals.

Since the Revival Era does not avoid depicting the criminality of its protagonists, it explores many aspects of the underworld that had, until this point, neither been explored nor depicted in Korean gangster cinema. These include the strict hierarchies that gangs are built upon, the inequality between low-ranking and high-ranking gangsters, the mental anguish suffered by gangsters as they struggle to reconcile their personal values with the values of the underworld, and the liberating and destructive nature of gang violence. The Revival Era

also explores the role of brotherhood in the underworld, highlighting its importance to gangsters, but also their tendency to betray it for selfish means.

The Revival Era's depiction of the underworld, as well as its many unique elements, is the result of many factors. These include industrial factors such as the eradication of censorship that began in 1993, the rise of independent production companies during the 1990s, and the void left in the Korean film market following the decreased production of Hong Kong gangster films. Another important industrial factor is the new generation of young filmmakers that emerged at the time and produced many of the films in this chapter's corpus.

Although Choi (2010a, p.64) questions Shin's (2005, p.123) suggestion that the gangster genre's revival was the result of the IMF Crisis, it would not be accurate to answer the chapter's second research question, '*What socio-cultural, industrial or generic factors influenced the genre's revival?*', without acknowledging the event's influence on not just the Korean gangster genre but Korean society during this time. Indeed, as Chapter VI shows, the Revival Era's depiction of the underworld embodies and reflects many issues, such as youth disillusionment, declining faith in education and the imposition of neoliberalism, often associated with the crisis.

Chapter VII: Business Class: The Post-Revival Era (2007 - Present)

7.1 Introduction

New Korean Cinema ended in 2006. Paquet (2009, pp.110-111) notes that rising production costs, a saturated market, and widespread equipment shortages made film production unsustainable. In addition, film exports crashed from a value of \$76 million in 2005 to just \$24.5 million in 2006 (Paquet 2009, p.111). 2006 also saw a reduction in the screen quota, from 146 days to 73 days (Jin 2020, p.39; Paquet 2009, p.111).⁶⁹ While Jimmyn Parc (2014, p.15) contends that the quota did not result in a “rush to...foreign movies”, he notes that there was a “sharp decrease...[in] admissions for Korean movies.” Indeed, the market share of Korean films fell from a high of 63.8% in 2006 to just 42% in 2008 (Jin 2020, p.48; Paquet 2009, p.112).

Following the end of New Korean Cinema, Choi (2010b, p.53) states that the Korean gangster genre was “followed and/or replaced by crime-thrillers.” Writing six years later after she made this statement, Choi (2016, p.231, author’s italics) reiterates this point, stating that “during the 2010s, gangster and noir cinema were *followed and/or replaced* by a cycle of crime films.” Although Choi (2010b, p.53) alludes to thematic “continuities” between crime-thrillers and gangster films, the phrase ‘followed and/or replaced’ implies that the gangster genre ended, or at least declined, in the late 2000s.

This contradicts the findings of Kim (2019), Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2020; 2019a; 2019b; 2019c), each of whom suggests that the gangster genre continued to evolve in the yet unnamed period that succeeded New Korean Cinema. For example, Kim (2019, p.518) suggests that recent films such as *New World* and *Veteran* indicate the gangster genre’s continued development and revitalisation. Similarly, Gillespie (2016, p.70) argues

⁶⁹ A screen quota mandates that domestic cinemas must exhibit domestic films for a certain number of days every year.

that the genre diversified in the 2010s, allowing for more nuanced and reflexive portrayals of the gangster character, and Plaice (2020, p.3) posits that “the gangster film...expanded, drawing gangsters into diverse new spaces and relationships.”

The difference in opinion between Choi (2010b; 2016) and Kim (2019), Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2020) is the basis of the chapter’s first research question: ‘*Has the Korean gangster genre, as Choi (2016, p.231; 2010, p.53) suggests, been followed or replaced by crime thrillers, or has it, as Plaice (2020, p.3; 2019b), Kim (2019, p.518) and Gillespie (2016, p.70) infer, diversified and expanded?*’ If the genre has diversified, another question arises: ‘*Has the genre diversified enough to create a new, divergent genre?*’

To answer these questions, the chapter discusses the following films: *The Show Must Go On, A Love (Sarang, Kwak 2007), Fate (Sungmyeong, Kim 2008), Rough Cut (Yeonghwaneun yeonghwada, Jang 2008), Breathless, The Yellow Sea, Hindsight (Pureunsogeum, Lee 2011), Nameless Gangster: Rules of Time*⁷⁰, *A Company Man (Hoesawon, Lim 2012), New World, Hwayi: Monster Boy, Friend: The Great Legacy, Man in Love, Gangnam Blues, Coin Locker Girl, Inside Men, The Merciless, The Drug King, The Gangster, The Cop, The Devil, Man of Men (Peopekteumaen, Yong 2019), Night in Paradise (Nagwonui bam, Park 2020) and Tomb of the River (Gangneung, Yoon 2021). Of these films, the chapter focuses most on *Nameless Gangster, New World, The Merciless and The Drug King.**

In discussing these films, the chapter highlights the newfound status of the era’s gangster-heroes, who are often as rich and powerful as upper-class businessmen. As section 7.2 Corruption notes, this has led to the disappearance of class issues – in both a narrative and thematic sense – from the gangster genre. Instead, the genre seems more focused on criticising neoliberalism and corruption. The higher class of the gangster-hero has also led

⁷⁰ From this point onwards, *Nameless Gangster: Rules of Time* is referred to as *Nameless Gangster*.

to the decline of the character's moral agency, with many gangster-heroes no longer suffering from identity crises or feeling guilt for their most heinous actions. As section 7.3 With Great Power details, the increased amorality of the gangster-hero seems to have led to a marked increase in extreme violence, which is often used to ascertain dominance or power rather than as a necessary means to an end.

In certain films, however, violence is less important than information, which is often exploited as a weapon in the Post-Revival Era. This is partly due to the use of information by 'the law', that is, cops, prosecutors and undercover cops, each of whom appear far more frequently in the Post-Revival Era than any preceding era of the genre.⁷¹ Section 7.4 *A Matter of Definition* argues that the frequent use of information and the appearance of the law are just two elements of many others that suggest that the gangster genre's development during this time has been influenced by genre-bending.

7.2 Corruption: The Gangster's Elevated Social Status and Its Implications

The most obvious difference between the Post-Revival Era and preceding eras of the genre is also the most important: the gangster-hero's social status.

In contrast to their earlier counterparts, the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero is rarely lower-class or underprivileged. Of the twenty-two films in the chapter's corpus, only four, *Breathless*, *The Yellow Sea*, *Man in Love* and *Coin Locker Girl*, feature lower-class gangster-heroes.⁷² Most gangster-heroes are instead middle-class or upper-class.⁷³

⁷¹ For brevity's sake, 'the law' is used throughout the thesis as a collective term for cop, prosecutor and undercover characters.

⁷² Although *Fate*'s (Kim 2008) protagonist, Woo-min lacks any social status, material possessions or even a home, he is more 'classless' than lower class as he makes no attempt to escape his class, nor does he pay any attention to class in general. In addition, while *Hindsight* features a lower-class protagonist, Se-bin, she is not a gangster-hero.

⁷³ The films featuring middle-class gangster-heroes are *The Show Must Go On*, *A Love*, *A Company Man*, *New World*, *Hwayi*, *Friend: The Great Legacy*, *Gangnam Blues*, *The Merciless*, *Man of Men* and *Night in Paradise*. The films featuring upper-class gangster-heroes are *Hindsight*, *Nameless Gangster*, *Inside Men*, *The Merciless*, *The Drug King*, *The Gangster*, *The Cop*, *The Devil* and *Tomb of the River*. As some of these films feature multiple protagonists, there may be overlap between films mentioned here and those mentioned with respect to middle-class and lower-class protagonists.

The improved social status of the gangster-hero has led to numerous semantic changes to the gangster genre. In contrast to their predecessors, Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes are rarely relegated to the shadowy underbelly of Korean society. Instead, they frequently appear in upper-class locations such as high-rise skyscrapers, lavish apartments and expensive restaurants. For example, in *Nameless Gangster*, Ik-hyun, a gang boss, bribes a politician in a lavish restaurant, securing permission to build a hotel and casino, and in *Inside Men*, Sang-goo chats casually with an influential political columnist in his high-rise office.

Although upper-class locations also appear in Revival Era films, they do so less frequently. In addition, these locations often reflect the gang boss's status rather than the gangster-hero's status. Conversely, upper-class locations in Post-Revival Era films often directly reflect the gangster-hero's status. Wealth and power permit the gangster-hero entry into a world previously denied to them. Indeed, just as Choi (2016, p.227, author's italics) argues that the spaces of Revival Era films "tied to class stratification and social *immobility*", the spaces of Post-Revival films are tied to the gangster's social *mobility*.

Whereas many Revival Era gangster-heroes, such as Byung-doo in *A Dirty Carnival* and Tae-sik in *Sunflower*, are confined to the underworld out of fear of being attacked during the day or in public, Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes often live beyond the confines of the underworld. In *Rough Cut*, the mid-ranking gangster Gang-pae works as an actor in a gangster film.⁷⁴ In *The Drug King*, Lee Doo-sam maintains a prominent public life, participating in community outreach programs, philanthropic events and anti-communist meetings.

⁷⁴ Gang-pae's [강패] name is a slight modification of the Korean word for gangster, *Kkangpae* [깡패]. This is one of the film's many self-referential elements. Although the New Korean Cinema film, *A Dirty Carnival* – in which gangster-hero Byung-doo works as a 'consultant' on a gangster film – also features self-referential elements, *Rough Cut* uses its premise – the film follows Gang-pae and an actor as they make a gangster film together – to deconstruct the tropes of the gangster film. Unfortunately, although the self-referential elements of both films merit further discussion, the topic did not fit within the scope or structure of the thesis.

In keeping with their newfound status, Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes are more often seen in suits than their Revival Era predecessors. Many gangster-heroes, such as Gang-pae in *Rough Cut*, Joon-suk in *Friend: The Great Legacy* and Gil-suk in *Tomb of the River*, are never seen wearing anything but a full suit. There is also greater uniformity in terms of gangster attire – whereas many of the lowest-ranked gangsters in Revival Era films such as *Green Fish* and *No.3* wear more casual clothes, even the lowest-ranked gangsters in Post-Revival cinema are seen wearing professional suits. Still, the differences in attire between both eras of the gangster genre are slighter than the differences in setting. Indeed, Sun-woo in *A Bittersweet Life*, Byung-doo in *A Dirty Carnival*, and other Revival gangster-heroes also mainly wear suits despite their lower social status compared to Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes.

A more obvious example of the Post-Revival gangster-hero's greater social status is the increased presence of firearms. The most obvious example of this appears in *The Drug King*, where in his marble-floored office, the gangster-hero, Doo-sam, hangs four guns on the wall behind his gleaming mahogany desk. Later in the film, he fires one of these guns at the police as they try to apprehend him, forcing them to call in the military because they do not carry guns themselves.

Firearms also appear in many other Post-Revival films, including *The Show Must Go On*, *Hindsight*, *A Company Man*, *Hwayi*, *Gangnam Blues*, *The Merciless* and *Night in Paradise*. However, despite their increased presence, firearms do not supplant melee combat as the dominant weapon of choice in the Post-Revival Era, indicating that they act more as status symbols.

Overall, the gangster-hero's greater social status has led to the disappearance of class issues – in both a narrative and thematic sense – from the gangster genre. Although debts burden the respective protagonists of *The Show Must Go On* and *Man of Men*, neither character is impoverished. In fact, both characters are only victims of economic stress due

to their own follies: In-gu is burdened with debt in *The Show Must Go On* because he purchases a house beyond his means, and in *Man of Men*, Yeong-gi is in debt because he foolishly invests his boss's money in a blatantly fraudulent company.

Class issues are also insignificant in *A Love, Nameless Gangster*, *Gangnam Blues* and *The Drug King*. Although each film's gangster-hero originates from a lower-class background, they disconnect from the lower classes when they become affluent. In addition, each gangster-hero prides themselves on their newfound status rather than on their humble beginnings. Conversely, the Revival Era gangster-hero, Du-han, never forgets his lower-class background in *General's Son*. Even after becoming a gang boss, he remains loyal to those he knew when he was poor and looks after those in the district where he grew up.

Only two Post-Revival Era films meaningfully explore issues such as social inequality and class division: *Breathless* and *The Yellow Sea*. This is particularly true of the former film, which is based on the film's director, writer and lead actor, Yang Ik-hyun's, life growing up in an abusive household in a poor neighbourhood in Seoul (Park, Lee and Wagner, 2017, p.371). Despite its small budget of ₩50 million, or approximately \$43,000, the film attracted 120,000 viewers when it was released in 2009 (Park, Lee and Wagner 2017, p.3), one year after its festival run, during which it won 21 awards and earned 6 nominations (Choi 2015, p.59).

In contrast to most Post-Revival Era films, *Breathless* depicts life for Korea's poorest citizens. Far removed from the upper-class world seen in films such as *New World* and *Inside Men*, *Breathless* follows Sang-hun, a frequently violent and aimless debt collector on the outskirts of Seoul who forms a bond with a high school girl, Yeon-hui (Choi 2015, p.59). Akin to the Revival Era film *Die Bad*, most of the film's key scenes take place on the streets, including the first time Sang-hun meets Yeon-hui, Sang-hun's attempt to save his father's life, and his own death (Choi 2015, p.59). Shot on location in *Junggye-dong*, one of "the last few urban poor neighborhoods in Seoul", the film offers an honest, even uncomfortable,

view of life for Korea's most underprivileged citizens (Park, Lee and Wagner 2017, p.371). In contrast to most other Post-Revival Era gangster films, the film depicts the poor as a fractured group – despite being poor himself, Sang-hun preys on the most desperate and unfortunate, invading their homes, threatening them and taking whatever they owe without mercy. As Park (et al. 2017, p.372) notes, the decision to make Sang-hun a debt collector “recasts poverty as an individualized and atomized experience rather than a communal one.”

Sang-hun's attacks on his fellow lower-class citizens are perhaps one of the film's only commonalities with other Post-Revival Era films. Indeed, most Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes are so far removed from the lower classes that they cause and sustain, rather than suffer from, social inequality. In a montage in *The Drug King*, scenes of Doo-sam's privileged life as a drug lord – shipping drugs abroad, laughing in his private vault and attending an award ceremony – are intercut with clips of his drugs being distributed on city streets, consumed in dank, overcrowded buildings, and lying discarded in an alleyway beside a corpse.

Many other Post-Revival Era films depict the gangster's part in sabotaging life for ordinary Koreans. In both *The Show Must Go On* and *A Love*, the gangster-hero harasses striking workers at a gangster-run construction site. In *Hwayi*, Hwayi's gang is hired to cajole a couple who refuse to vacate an area planned for redevelopment, and in *Gangnam Blues*, Jong-dae obtains vast amounts of land by swindling farmers and elderly landowners.

Despite the Post-Revival Era's lack of focus on socio-economic issues, social inequality increased during this time. Koo (2021, p.2) notes that social inequality worsened in the mid to late 2000s, with the ratio of income share for the upper 10% compared to the bottom 10% increasing from 3.30 in 1990 to 4.90 in 2010 and to 5.01 in 2016. Koo (2021, p.10) also notes that wealth became increasingly concentrated in Korea, with the income share of the top 10% earners rising from 29.2% in 1995 to 44.8% in 2012, and the income share of the top 5% rising from 19.2% to 30.1% during the same period.

Koo (2021, p.16) argues that the rise of Korea's new rich "is a consequence of income polarisation rather than gradual income growth for all." Indeed, despite a slight decrease in the percentage of irregular workers from 58.4% in 2000 to 51.9% in 2015, Korea's share of irregular workers remained considerably higher than that of other OECD (The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development) countries (Lee 2015, p.189).

Overall, then, the socio-economic issues prevalent during the Revival Era – as discussed in Chapter VI – only compounded during the Post-Revival Era. In fact, Jaecheol Kim (2022, p.5) states that the term 'IMF' still evokes a powerful emotional reaction from the Korean public two decades after the Korean government paid back the IMF loan in 2000.

The differences between the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero and their predecessors increase when considering that they are not often overtly criminal, with many gangs either operating or masquerading as legitimate businesses in areas such as construction (*The Show Must Go On* and *A Love*), entertainment (*Nameless Gangster* and *The Gangster, The Cop, The Devil*), resort management (*Tomb of the River*), importation (*The Merciless*) and even talent representation (*Inside Men*).

Although some Revival Era films feature gangs masquerading as or operating legitimate businesses – Sun-woo's gang owns a nightclub in *A Bittersweet Life* and Joon-suk's gang in *Friend* owns and runs a fish-processing plant – they do not seem intent on being a corporation as Post-Revival gangs do. For example, the gang in *A Company Man* – which specialises in high-profile contract killings – is referred to by its members as 'the company' and maintains a corporate reporting structure, with gangsters referring to each other by titles such as director, manager and assistant manager. The gang boss in *Man of Men*, Beom-do, seems unable or unwilling to even accept that he is a gangster. Throughout the film, he refutes the idea that his gang is a gang, referring to his men as executives and demanding that they not "*stand like gangsters.*" In one scene, Beom-do tosses a glass at a

subordinate's head when he refers to a colleague as a gangster and yells, "*What the hell are you saying? Think this is a gang?*" In *New World*, the Goldmoon gang is so akin to a business that even the police refer to them as one – in a briefing scene, a policeman refers to the gang as a "*mid-size corporation*" that owns eight subsidiaries.

The onscreen gangster's representation as a businessman and their involvement in legitimate businesses parallels the changing nature of real-world organised crime during this period. While crackdowns on crime in the 1960s and early 1990s prevented gangsters from prospering during Korea's period of military rule, criminologists Lee (2006, pp.65-67) and Park, Y.K. (2004, pp.61-63) note that many high-ranking criminals were released in the late 1990s and either subsequently reformed their old gangs or founded new ones. Lee (2006, p.67) and Schloenhardt (2010, p.276) note that these criminal organisations began to engage in 'white-collar' crimes such as financial fraud and blackmail.

Prior to globalization, these groups were primarily involved in crimes of a local nature, including blackmailing bars and stores in the entertainment districts and using violence and threats. But since the globalization of South Korea, organized crime has ventured into businesses with international linkages. Over the last few years, there has been a series of cases involving international organized crime groups engaged in drug trafficking, financial fraud, weapons smuggling, and human trafficking (Lee 2006, pp.67-68).

Although Lee (2006, p.67) does not directly refer to neoliberalism, their reference to globalisation is indicative of the latter's role in reshaping Korea following the IMF Crisis. Indeed, while *chaebols* were instrumental in reducing employee labour rights (Lee 2015, p.186), firing thousands of employees (Lee 2015, p.189) and building "highly unfair and exploitative business relationships" (Koo 2021, p.8) following the IMF crisis, it seems more apt to blame neoliberalism for the socioeconomic issues of the Post-Revival Era, as it is the political philosophy upon which these *chaebols* took the aforementioned actions.

Furthermore, while neoliberalism existed in Korea before the IMF Crisis, Lee (2015, p.187) states that the crisis resulted in neoliberalism's "unquestioned penetration into various domains of [Korean] public policy." Kim (2022, p.3, italics in original) states that the very

term ‘IMF’ is as synonymous with neoliberalism in Korea as it is with the 1997 economic crisis.

In fact, despite efforts to reform the *chaebols* following the IMF Crisis, Lee (2015, p.195) notes that neoliberal policies strengthened the *chaebol*’s political and economic power. From 2003 to 2012, the asset value of the top ten *chaebols* rose from 48% of Korea’s GDP to 84% (ibid.). Accordingly, Koo (2021, p.3) states that most analysts of Korean social inequality believe that the neoliberal reforms of the 1990s changed the nature of income distribution in the country.

Aside from increased social inequality, Wagner (2016, p.121) suggests that neoliberalism caused other issues, such as soaring consumer debt and privatisation. Wagner (2016, p.121) also suggests that neoliberalism allowed a unique social class, “neoliberal royalty”, to flourish after the IMF Crisis. Composed of elite business owners, politicians and entrepreneurs who prospered under Korea’s military governments, Wagner (ibid.) argues that these ‘neoliberal royalists’ gained control over Korea’s economy and culture.

Considering that Wagner and Unger (2024, p.6) suggest that neoliberalism created “new kinds of capital of an unethical and corrupt variety”, it does not seem illogical to suggest that the gangsters of the Post-Revival Era might also be considered ‘neoliberal royalty’. In fact, Gillespie (2016, p.67) argues that the gangsters in *New World* embody “neoliberal capitalist logic.”

Post-Revival Era gangsters are now also more akin to businessmen than organised criminals. Kim (2019, p.518, italics in original) suggests that more recent gangster films embody “a new amalgamated anxiety about the gangster, a corporate gangster who is indicative of the resentment towards the *chaebol* class.” Mobrand (2016, p.672) makes a similar point about real-life gangsters during this time, stating that underworld bosses are now “more like CEOs than street leaders since the real money is in private lending, money laundering, real estate, and other fields.”

Overall, the increasing involvement of the gangster in traditional business delegitimises the upper class. As Wagner and Unger (2024, p.19) note when discussing the films *The Yellow Sea* and *New World*, gangsters “destabilize[s] above-board professions.” This is heightened by the gangster’s involvement in other sectors of Korean society, including law enforcement and politics. Indeed, whereas Chairman Hwang in *A Dirty Carnival*, one of the most powerful gang bosses of the Revival Era, must appease a prosecutor who thinks he is scum, many Post-Revival Era gangsters mingle, dine, and even maintain friendships with prosecutors, policemen, businessmen and politicians.

In *Nameless Gangster*, Ik-hyun boasts of his high-profile contacts, brandishing a notebook and declaring, “*This contact list is worth a million dollars! They’ll never lock me in.*” Similarly, in *The Drug King*, Doo-sam tells a prosecutor, “*You want to know where I spend my filthy money? I don’t spend it like a powerful man but I spend it on powerful men.*” Even less powerful gangs, such as the one in *Hwayi*, boast connections to upper-class society – the gang knows a crooked detective who acts as a liaison between them and a wealthy property developer.

Overall, the gangster is rarely shown corrupting or coercing their contacts in the ruling class. Rather, these contacts are portrayed as inherently corrupt, or at least glad to be bribed. In *Nameless Gangster*, Ik-hyun is corrupt before he even becomes a gangster. While working as a customs officer at Busan’s port, Ik-hyun accepts a bribe from a merchant who assures him that “*We’re all family here.*” The corruption is casual, occurring in broad daylight and with little concealment. Ik-hyun and his colleagues accept bribes so regularly that they have a large stash of cash and expensive watches hidden in the restroom of the customs offices. Although Ik-hyun frames his actions as a necessary way to care for his family, he continues to be corrupt even after becoming a wealthy and powerful gang boss.

Overall, the underworld of the Post-Revival Era seems based less on crime than it is on corruption, an observation buttressed by statements made by certain directors. The

director of *New World*, Park Hoon-jung (cited in Lee 2013), described his film as being “about gangsters doing politics, in suits and ties” (Park 2013 cited in Lee 2013). Woo Min-ho (cited in Won 2015) remarked that he wanted *Inside Men* to “increase awareness (about the corruption around us)” and Yoon Jong-bin said he wished for “the vicious cycle of corruption” to end (Yoon 2012 cited in Korea JoongAng Daily 2012) when discussing his film *Nameless Gangster*. More specifically, Yoon (ibid.) stated that he was inspired to make *Nameless Gangster* by the memory of his father’s surprising wealth and influence as an official in the National Police Agency during the 1980s.

Indeed, corruption has been an issue in Korea long before the Post-Revival Era. Political scientist Tat Yan Kong (1996, p.52) states that “corruption was arguably ‘functional’ to Korean development during the authoritarian period [the 1960s and 1970s] in the sense that it cemented the government-business relationship.” Elaborating on this point, Kong (ibid.) notes that corruption during the authoritarian period resulted in several “intractable social problems” and “imposed painful costs on those sections of society outside [the government’s] charmed circle.”

Corruption only worsened in Korea following Park Chung-hee’s assassination in 1979. According to historian Hyung-a Kim (2003, pp.13-14), Park’s successor, the army general Chun Doo-hwan, was guilty of “embezzlement, nepotism and cronyism” and was involved in fourteen corruption scandals during his authoritarian rule from 1979 to 1987.

In the 1970s-set *Gangnam Blues*, corruption is not only depicted as an aspect of Korean society but the very basis of it. In fact, the film’s most vile, unlawful and corrupt characters are politicians rather than gangsters. In one scene, Yang, a feared gang boss, is humiliated in front of his men by a politician, Councillor Seo, who slaps and berates Yang when he refers to himself as a businessman. “*You subordinate bastard. Businessman? I created a monster by giving a hooligan a suit,*” yells Seo. One of the film’s two gangster-

heroes, Jong-dae, wages a lengthy gang war for Seo, all so the politician can consolidate wealth and political power.

The extensive corruption depicted in *Gangnam Blues* would seem farcical were it not for its basis in historical reality. As Moberand (2016, p.637) notes, the fifteen years following Korea's liberation from Japan in 1945 saw many gangsters working as both private agents of violence and servants to the "top state and political elites of the country."

One such gangster was Kim Du-han, the figure discussed in Chapter VI, whose early years were the basis of the Revival Era film, *General's Son*. Porteux (2013, p.76) describes one incident involving Kim Du-han, when he "unleashed his youth faction on April of 1947 and captured, beat and tortured 134 leftists" who had been campaigning against the then president of Korea's provisional government, Syngman Rhee. Although Kim Du-han and his followers admitted to murdering two of the leftists and were given the death sentence by the US Military government, Kim Du-han was granted amnesty by Syngman Rhee when he became president in 1948 (ibid.).

As this incident illustrates, gangsters were, as Moberand (2016, p.638) states, "at the nexus of state-building and party mobilisation" in the post-liberation period, with many patrons of gang violence, and even gangsters themselves, attaining political power. In fact, Kim Du-han became a politician after running as an independent candidate in the 1954 assembly elections (Moberand 2016, p.659). Although he was not an important legislator and failed to win re-election, Moberand (2016, p.660) states that Kim's example demonstrates that in "1950s South Korea it was possible for a street leader to make a serious bid for public office." As Moberand (ibid.) implies, such a possibility was at least partly due to links with political elites, which raised the public profiles of gangsters such as Kim Du-han.

Although corruption has been present throughout Korean history, it seems to have become a prominent theme in the Post-Revival Era due to the growing visibility of corrupt practices. Indeed, the beginning of the Post-Revival Era coincides with the election of Lee

Myung-bak in 2007, whose presidency, political scientists Eunjung Choi and Jongseok Woo (2012, p.456) note, was characterised by numerous corruption scandals. Choi and Woo (ibid.) add that “several of the Lee government’s cabinet nominees” were charged with crimes such as false address registration, tax evasion, and suspicious exemption from military conscription.

Although the full extent of Lee’s corruption was not uncovered until 2018, when he was sentenced to fifteen years in prison for bribery and embezzlement (Haas 2018; Fermin-Robbins 2018, p.4), sociologist Shin (2012, p.293) stated in 2012 that Lee’s election represented a significant setback for Korea’s “process of democratic consolidation.”

After ten years of liberal democratic rule, Lee’s election marked the return of Korea’s former authoritarian party, the Grand National Party, and the “revival of the state’s control over the media, repression of the labour movement, and infringement of civil rights by the police” (Shin 2012, pp.293-294). Furthermore, Lee, Y. (2019, p.31, italics in original) notes that Lee “pursued unapologetic business-friendly policies and introduced various relaxations in areas of *chaebol* regulation...and tax rates.” Accordingly, Shin (2012, p.305) posits that after twenty-five years of democratic transition, illiberal democracy “became a political fact” in Korea.

Of all the films examined in this chapter, *Inside Men* is the most thorough in detailing the pervasive nature of corruption in contemporary Korea. Although the film’s gangster-hero, Sang-goo, is more powerful than most Revival Era or Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes, he answers to Oh Hyun-su, the chairman of a *chaebol*, Mirae Motors.

Throughout the film, Oh serves his own ambitions at the expense of the Korean people, whom he refers to as “*dogs and hogs*.” In one scene, Oh reads aloud an article his friend, the conservative journalist Kang-hee, has written on his behalf. In it, Kang-hee declares Mirae Motors’ temporary employees’ union “*a danger to the state economy, rife with North Korean sympathisers*.” After reading the article, Oh remarks, “*These commie*

bastards. This is why you have to provide them just enough to live on.” Following this exchange, Pil-woo – a high-profile presidential candidate – arrives and tells the two men of his efforts to stop a temporary employee protection bill from being passed. *“It will end up in tatters. Rags and tatters,”* he says jovially, prompting the three men to laugh. As sickening and disturbing as any of the gangster genre’s most violent action scenes, the aforementioned scene in *Inside Men* suggests that corruption has totally eroded Korean society. At the time of its release, “Koreans had become increasingly frustrated by cronyism among chaebol (like Samsung, Hyundai, and Lotte), top-tier politicians (including the president), and even the media (e.g., conservative newspapers like Chosun Ilbo)” (Jin 2020, p.140). According to Jin (2020, p.140), the film “was like a reality show for many Koreans.”

The public’s frustration with corruption during this period is reflected by a survey performed by political scientists Choi and Woo (2012, p.456) in 2012, which revealed that 72% of Seoul residents “ranked the prevalence of corruption in Korean politics at 6 or higher on a 10-point scale, with the most frequent score being 8.” In addition, a 2012 study performed by Transparency International – a global organisation that examines and highlights corruption – indicated that “Koreans consider today’s political parties and parliament to be the most corrupt in years” (Choi and Woo 2012, p.456).

Corruption in Korea only worsened following the publication of these studies. Sociologist Lee, Y. (2019, p.31, italics in original) states that “the collusive relationship between *chaebols* and the political elite was most evidently revealed in the Park-Choi scandal in 2016-2017.”

Not only did Samsung pay billions of won to buy a horse for Choi Soon-sil’s daughter, an equestrian competitor, but further, “donated” 80 billion won (USD70 million) along with other chaebol corporations to two suspicious foundations that Ms. Choi created to offer an institutional asylum for President Park after retirement. In exchange, *chaebols* were guaranteed with policy concessions or a pass for their unlawful activities. This revelation was emblematic of a broader concern that the political system was rigged to serve the interests of powerful capital (Lee, Y. 2019, p.31, italics in original).

Jun et al. (2019, p.535) note that the scandal revealed the extent of corruption in Korea, undermining the legitimacy of three of Korea’s societal pillars: politics, business and

education. Indeed, although Lee Myung-bak's successor, Park Geun-hye, was at the centre of the scandal, Jun et al. (ibid.) note that it also involved Choi Soon-sil, an influential advisor to Park, Lee Jae-yong, the vice chair of Samsung Electronics – a subsidiary of Korea's most powerful *chaebol*, Samsung – and Choi Kyung-hee, the president of the prestigious Ewha Women's University.

Jamie Doucette (2017, p.6) emphasises that the scandal made the “public...feel that there is one set of rules for the elite...and another for ordinary people.” Erik Mobernd (2021, p.261) notes that Koreans were so furious after the 2016 scandal that a series of protests, later dubbed the Candlelight Movement, were held in late 2016. Journalists Choi Ha-young and Kim Bo-eum (2016) reported that approximately one million people took to the streets at one protest, the largest in Korea in thirty years. *Time* correspondent Charlie Campbell (2016) noted that the demonstrations “paralyzed the capital [Seoul], shutting down streets spanning out from palatial Gwanghwamun Square.”

The strength of popular sentiment expressed in the demonstrations stemmed from a sense that Park's wrongdoing was deeply connected to inequality and injustice. An awareness of and frustration with unjust privilege had in previous years grown in the public consciousness, with terms such as hell *Chosŏn* – suggesting that living in South Korea is “hell” – gaining prominence to express frustration with a sense of poor life chances (Mobernd 2021, p.261, author's italics).

Overall, while film theorist Caleb Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.61) notes that it might be “overly reflectionist [sic]” to suggest that Korean films directly criticise corruption, the increase of it and neoliberalism, as well as the gangster-hero's more businesslike nature, suggest that the genre underwent a significant shift during the Post-Revival Era.

In fact, Wagner (2016, p.124) states that “more media – especially cinema – [is] being modified not in terms of genre convention...but rather how various genres account for neoliberal policies, culture and subjectivities.” Specifically, Wagner (ibid.) argues that the protagonists of post-2006 Korean melodramas “absorb the freedoms of neoliberalism...at the expense of more civic or familial-centred environments of the past.” Kim (2022, p.18)

makes a similar point, arguing that Korean films produced in the late 2010s directly interrogate the lasting effects of neoliberalism.

Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes act similarly to the protagonists described by Wagner (2016, p.124). Although familial or romantic matters – discussed in more detail in 7.4 A Matter of Definition – remain prominent in some Post Revival Era films, they are minor or non-existent in most others. In addition, the businesslike iconography that characterises the Post-Revival Era mirror the tropes of what Wagner (2016, p.135) calls “neoliberal-orientated” genres: “excessive materialism, opulent spaces of consumption, corporate greed...[and]fashion choices that relate to elite taste.”

Unlike Wagner (ibid.), Gillespie (2016, p.70) does not believe that the gangster genre underwent a chronological or teleological shift during the Post-Revival Era, citing *The Man from Nowhere* and *Nameless Gangster* as counterexamples to this argument. However, in selecting these films, Gillespie (ibid.) only substantiates both Wagner’s (ibid.) and this thesis’s finding that the genre *has* undergone a shift. While *The Man from Nowhere* features gangster characters, the protagonist is not a gangster, but rather an ex-special agent. In fact, Choi (2016, p.219) does not categorise *The Man from Nowhere* as a gangster film, referring to it as a “crime action film.” In addition, Gillespie’s (2016, p.70) brief suggestion that *Nameless Gangster* emphasises “nostalgic localism” does not reconcile the fact that the film’s gangsters are more akin to businessmen than the small-time criminals of the genre’s previous periods. In fact, the film is more akin to *New World*, which Gillespie (2016, p.67) argues “transposes the gangster narrative to the elite domain of the boardroom, where sharp-suited henchmen meet on the uppermost floors of a faceless corporate skyscraper.”

Still, it is important to reiterate that not *all* Post-Revival Era films feature upper-class gangster-heroes. As noted at the beginning of this section, *Breathless*, *The Yellow Sea*, *Hindsight*, *Man in Love* and *Coin Locker Girl* all feature lower-class gangster-heroes. One could even argue that the gangsters of *New World* are not *truly* upper class. For one, Ja-

sung is not technically a gangster as he is an undercover cop. In addition, while he and his friend, Jung Chung, rise to become high-ranking members of the Goldmoon gang, neither man seems adjusted to their newfound status. This is especially true of Jung Chung, whose fashion sense and brash temperament mark him as an outsider. The inauthentic nature of his class is substantiated by a scene in which he gifts Ja-sung what looks to be an expensive watch, but which is in fact a counterfeit.

Nevertheless, whether either man thinks of himself as high class or not does not change the fact that they *are* – they wear expensive suits, are driven around in fancy foreign cars with plush leather seats and meet in the boardrooms of high-rise skyscrapers. Ja-sung only seems to find some amount of peace when he finally accepts his newfound class and identity, killing off his rivals and assuming the top position in his gang.

7.3 With Great Power: The Amorality of the Post-Revival Era Gangster-hero

In addition to their improved social status and businesslike appearance, the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero has changed in another fundamental way: they are often higher ranked than their Pre-Revival Era or Revival Era predecessors. While not all Pre-Revival Era or Revival Era gangster-heroes are strictly low ranking, the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero boasts more power due to the greater size and scope of the gangs they belong to. In fact, even mid-ranking Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes such as Jae-ho in *The Merciless* and Ja-sung in *New World* are more powerful than higher-ranked Revival Era gangster-heroes.

The increased power of the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero has undermined an important trait of the Revival Era gangster-hero that Choi (2010a, pp.72-73) highlights in her discussion of the gangster genre: the character's 'moral agency'. As Choi (ibid.) explains, a gangster often has moral agency – and the audience's sympathies – if external sources motivate their actions. Although Revival Era gangster-heroes commit morally dubious and immoral acts, it is generally understood, due to their dismal social status or rank,

that they do so out of necessity. Additionally, the Revival Era gangster-hero's most heinous actions are often tempered by their consequent guilt. For example, after Dong-pal rapes Madam in *Rosy Life*, he seeks redemption, pledging to do anything she wishes to right his wrong and earn her forgiveness.

Conversely, most Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes are willing participants in the underworld's chaos, bloodshed and treachery. This is apparent in the extreme violence that characterises the Post-Revival Era. Whereas violence was mainly a means to an end in preceding eras of the genre, it is now increasingly cruel and sadistic. Instead of simply killing or injuring their victim, gangsters now sometimes use violence to assert their power and humiliate their victim.

There are multiple examples of this extreme violence throughout the Post-Revival Era. When a rival gangster fails to show him respect in *Nameless Gangster*, Hyung-bae smashes multiple glass bottles on his head and extinguishes a cigarette on his cheek. When Sung-hoon's father verbally abuses his mother in *Friend: The Great Legacy*, Sung-hoon stabs his father in the eye with chopsticks and shoves his head into a vat of boiling oil. In *The Merciless*, Jae-ho kills a rival gangster who tried to have him murdered by tying him to a chair and pouring boiling oil over him.⁷⁵

Although *Breathless* is one of the few Post-Revival Era films that features a lower-class gangster-hero, it also features extreme violence. In fact, the film's opening scene features one of the most harrowing examples of extreme violence: after finding a boyfriend assaulting his girlfriend on the street, Sang-hun beats him until he is unconscious before kneeling in front of the sobbing girlfriend. Rather than comfort her, Sang-hun spits on her,

⁷⁵ The extreme violence in these scenes is likely representative of wider trends in film and media. As psychoanalyst Monisha C. Nayar-Akhtar (2016, p.510) notes, "media violence has not just increased in quantity; it has also become more graphic, sexual, and sadistic." Psychologists Peter M. Markey, Juliana E. French and Charlotte N. Markey (2015, p.165) make a similar point, noting that movies have become increasingly violent over the past fifty years. In addition, sociologists Raymond E. Barranco, Nicole E. Rader and Anna Smith (2015, p.82) describe how many studies have found that the phenomenon called "ratings creep" has occurred, "with adult content "creeping" into nonadult-rated movies."

slaps her and berates her for not fighting back against her boyfriend (Kahlon 2011, pp.76-77). The violence here is extreme, not because it is particularly gory or bloody, but because it is incredibly realistic and relates to the film's exploration of domestic violence, a topic that affects not just gangsters but ordinary people.

Not all Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes lack moral agency, however. As undercover cops, Ja-sung in *New World* and Hyun-su in *The Merciless* are forced to commit terrible acts in the name of the law, and in *Hindsight*, Doo-hyeon is unwillingly pulled from retirement when his former boss names him as his successor.

Nevertheless, moral agency has disappeared so notably in the Post-Revival Era that it has led to a decrease in identity crises. This is evidenced by the lack of elements that encapsulated a gangster-hero's identity crisis during the Revival Era: flashbacks, rural locations and maternal characters.

Whereas flashbacks in the Revival Era often accentuated the gangster-hero's identity crisis and heightened sentiments of brotherhood, flashbacks in the Post-Revival Era are often plot-driven, conveying plot information or framing narrative twists. Indeed, although flashbacks occur more often in the Post-Revival Era than in the Revival Era, most feature plot-driven rather than character-driven flashbacks.

Rural locations are almost totally absent from the Post-Revival Era – only one Post-Revival Era film, *Night in Paradise*, is set in a rural setting. Even then, the rural setting does not act as a site of reinvention or redemption in the film. Although the film's protagonist, Tae-gu, is physically disconnected from the underworld, he is never *psychologically* disconnected from it. Unlike Jae-mun in *Cruel Winter Blues* and Tae-sik in *Sunflower*, Tae-gu does not reconsider his criminality nor discover repressed personal desires or moral inclinations. In fact, until he discovers that his boss betrayed him in the film's third act, Tae-gu believes that his stay on Jeju Island is temporary. As a result, he spends less time reflecting on himself than he does waiting to return to the underworld.

Although maternal characters are not completely absent from the Post-Revival Era, the few that do appear no longer have the same narrative function – challenging the gangster’s perception of himself and the underworld – that they did in the Revival Era. For example, in *The Yellow Sea*, Gu-nam’s mother is only present at the start of the film when he visits her and his child before leaving for Korea. Although Hyun-su’s mother occupies a more important role in *The Merciless*, she mainly serves as a plot device, with her death motivating a succession of betrayals.

A grounding force in the Revival Era, the lack of the maternal figure in the Post-Revival Era is indicative of the genre’s increasing focus on the inner workings of the underworld. The gangster-heroes of the Post-Revival Era are simply ‘too far gone’ for a maternal figure to guide them or change them. In fact, In-gu is so committed to his gang in *The Show Must Go On* that even when an opportunity to leave the underworld arises following a prison stint, he chooses to join a friend’s gang, reneging on promises he made to his daughter and wife, who leave him and Korea as a result.

Ingu’s amoral actions pale in comparison to those of Ik-hyun in *Nameless Gangster* and Doo-sam in *The Drug King*, who both renege on their values in the process of transforming from lowly working-class men to powerful gang bosses. In addition to abandoning his wife and children, Doo-sam abandons his drug-addicted brother and his high-society mistress when they become bothersome. He even orders the deaths of certain allies, including a North Korean smuggler who considered Doo-sam to be his “*blood brother*.” Ik-hyun also betrays his allies, most notably the gangster Hyung-bae, who considered Ik-hyun family and trusted him completely.

As evidenced by these examples, betrayal is often heightened in the Post-Revival Era by supposed or actual family ties. Ik-hyun’s betrayal of Hyung-bae is particularly heartbreaking as Hyung-bae places immense trust in Ik-hyun throughout *Nameless Gangster*. In fact, Hyung-bae is only willing to attack a rival gangster with whom he “*rose*

together in the same family” for Ik-hyun when Ik-hyun reminds him that they are *actual* family. In another scene, Hyung-bae tells Ik-hyun, “*I don’t trust people easily...I was imprisoned five times, and it was all due to the people who acted like my brothers...So I had a huge revelation, there’s no one to trust except my family...I love you.*”

In *The Merciless*, Byung-gap pledges his allegiance to his boss and uncle, Chairman Ko, assuring him, “*You and I are bound by blood. This is a family business.*” Nevertheless, despite pledging allegiance to his uncle, Byung-gap later assists in murdering him. Soon afterwards, Byung-gap is killed by Jae-ho, his surrogate brother, who poignantly strikes Byung-gap dead with his CEO nameplate. Betrayal occurs again in the film’s final scene when Jae-ho is murdered by his protégé, Hyun-su.

In addition to betraying their allies, Doo-sam and Ik-hyun betray their country. Although both men justify their crimes as patriotic acts – Doo-sam tells a reluctant colleague that “*Selling crank to Japan is considered an act of patriotism. The Qing dynasty fell because of opium. We can make Japan fall with crank*” and Ik-hyun proclaims, “*What’s so wrong with selling some dope to the Japs?...How many years were we slaves to those fucking monkeys?...This is patriotism!*” – both men ultimately forge close ties with the yakuza.

While bonds between gangsters rarely survive in Post-Revival Era films, *Man of Men* and *The Gangster, the Cop, the Devil* both depict strong bonds developing between a gangster and a non-gangster character. In the former, an unexpected bond develops between the gangster Yeong-gi and the terminally ill ex-prosecutor Jang-soo. In the latter, an even more unexpected bond develops between a cop, Tae-suk, and a gang boss, Dong-soo.

Although both Tae-suk and Dong-soo are naturally distrustful of each other when they first start working together to find a deadly serial killer, a bond eventually forms between them out of mutual respect. This is most evident in a scene that sees Dong-soo’s gangsters and Tae-suk’s police colleagues dine together in a restaurant. Amidst jokes and banter, Dong-soo’s right-hand man, Oh-seong, makes a toast in which he proclaims, “*Our*

dicks may be many but we have one heart. Until then end of time, we are one.” There is also a funny moment when Tae-suk instinctively shows respect for Dong-soo by turning away from him before drinking a shot of soju.

Since Post-Revival Era gangsters are often members of the ruling class, betrayal is now representative of not just the underworld but also the upper echelons of Korean society. Indeed, it is not lowly, desperate gangsters who commit betrayal in the Post-Revival Era but the rich and powerful gangsters who typify the period. Although Doo-sam – the gangster-hero of *The Drug King* – drinks urine to save his cousin from thugs when he is lower-class, he refuses to help that same cousin with a drug addiction when he is a wealthy drug kingpin. Accordingly, betrayal does not seem to occur in the Post-Revival Era *despite* the gangster’s high rank and status, but *because* of it.

7.4 A Matter of Definition: The Influence of Genre-bending

Aside from its extremity, violence in the Post-Revival Era is not significantly different from violence in the Revival Era. As both a force of liberation and destruction, violence simultaneously permits and denies the gangster-hero social mobility. As Jamier (2015, p.47) notes, “violence isn’t an option in the gangster world...it’s the only way to go, the accepted protocol.” The aesthetics of violence have also not changed, with most films featuring the same kinetic melee combat that characterised the Revival Era, including the three forms of violence discussed in Chapter VI – the ‘one-on-one’ fight, ‘one-versus-many fight and the brawl.

A dramatic increase in the appearance of firearms does not even disrupt the forms, aesthetics, or meaning of the genre’s violence. While firearms appear in eight, or 38.1% of the films in the chapter’s corpus – 23.9% more than Revival Era films – firearms serve a more symbolic rather than purposeful role in the Post-Revival Era. Indeed, combat featuring guns is no less brutal or onerous than melee combat, and the inclusion of firearms does not

significantly affect the genre's deployment of the three types of melee combat discussed in Chapter VI.

Although violence has not changed significantly, gang warfare *has* changed due to the emergence of a new weapon in the gangster's arsenal: information. Many Post-Revival Era gangsters use information to undermine their enemies or solidify their power. For example, in *Gangnam Blues*, Jong-dae blackmails a politician with photos of him lying in bed with another man, and in *Inside Men*, Sang-goo works with a prosecutor to gather evidence against a corrupt businessman, journalist and politician, ultimately damning the trio with a covert recording of their sexual escapades.

Although Jong-dae and Sang-goo are lowly gangsters compared to their high-profile foes, information allows them to undermine the supposed legitimacy of the upper class. As Gillespie (2016, p.69) notes, "it is control of information – and especially the ability to reduce another person's existence to pure information... – that confers true power."

According to Plaice (2019b), information, or "dirt", undermines and even replaces trust in the Post-Revival Era, creating an atmosphere of paranoia. In *New World*, the gang is so lacking in brotherhood that trust is non-existent: after their boss is killed, rival gangsters, Jung and Joong-gu, conspire against each other, using information and surveillance to foil each other's efforts to become their gang's next leader. Gillespie (2016, p.69) notes that *New World* "remoulds the world of the South Korean gangster film...with those who control information best positioned to win out in the neoliberal power struggle."

The prominent role of information in the Post-Revival Era may be linked to the more prominent role of cops, prosecutors and undercover cops, or more collectively, 'the law'. Indeed, Gillespie (2016, p.69) notes that "the police force [in *New World*] ...wield power through information every bit as adeptly as the gangsters do. State power re-emerges as a technological surveillance apparatus, in control of vast tranches of information."

While the use of undercover cops in *New World* and *The Merciless* provides the police with unprecedented intelligence, the process is fraught with tension and animosity. In *New World*, Chief Kang is so paranoid that his undercover cop might double-cross him that he forces the agent's wife to spy on him. Similarly, in *The Merciless*, Chief Cheon is so suspicious of her undercover cop that she has him kidnapped and threatened at gunpoint to confirm his loyalty. Law (2008, p.530) suggests that such paranoia is unavoidable in an undercover operation as it exploits loyalties, encourages betrayal and “preys on the increasingly rare human virtue of fidelity.”

The frequent appearance of ‘the law’ in the Post-Revival Era is a notable genre development – while cops, prosecutors and/or undercover cops feature in just a few Revival Era films, *General's Son*, *Rosy Life*, *Die Bad*, they appear in almost half of all the films examined in this chapter. The inclusion of undercover cops in *New World* and *The Merciless* is particularly notable, as the archetype was absent from the Revival Era.

The inclusion of the undercover character seems to indicate the continuing influence of Hong Kong gangster cinema on its Korean counterpart. Unlike the Korean gangster genre, Law (2008, p.528) notes that the undercover cop has been a fundamental element of Hong Kong gangster cinema since the genre's emergence in the 1980s. Stuck between a world of justice and a world of lawlessness, Law (2008, p.530) describes the undercover cop as a “tragically bewildered figure.” Law (2008, pp.529-530) notes that while a “straight gangster-hero” film glorifies male bonding and loyalty, a film featuring undercover cops “engages the moral dilemmas when a protagonist must choose between personal loyalty and official duty.”

Infernal Affairs, one of Hong Kong's most popular and critically lauded films, features *two* undercover characters – an undercover cop and an undercover gangster. More specifically, the film juxtaposes overlapping plots that follow Chan, the undercover cop pretending to be a triad member and Lau, the undercover gangster pretending to be a police

officer. Bordwell (2011, p.204) states that this results in a rather cerebral film, with both characters attempting to track down their counterpart.

Despite, or perhaps because of, its complexity, *Infernal Affairs* was very successful – Bordwell (2011, p.203) notes that the film grossed twice as much as any other film at the Hong Kong box office in 2002, beating even *Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets* (Columbus 2002). The film’s success also overturned an industry slump that had seen imported films claim 60% market share and annual cinema attendance fall to an average of twenty million, forty million less than the average of the 1980s (ibid.).

The continued influence of Hong Kong gangster cinema on its Korean counterpart is substantiated by Younghan Cho’s (2016, p.60) and Kelso-Marsh’s (2020, p.60) respective statements that *Infernal Affairs* influenced *New World*. Although neither scholar elaborates on this point, a cursory analysis of *New World* reveals many parallels between it and *Infernal Affairs*. While the film only features one undercover character, Ja-sung, he is psychologically tormented by being an undercover cop in the same manner that Chan is in *Infernal Affairs*. Like Chan, Ja-sung has also been undercover for a lengthy time, further worsening his struggle with his identity. The film’s plot is also more complex than a traditional undercover film as it weaves Ja-sung’s story with two others – a plot that follows the power battle within Ja-sung’s gang between his friend, Jung, and his rival Joong-gu, and a plot that follows Ja-sung’s police handler, Kang, as he attempts to destroy the Goldmoon gang.

In addition to these similarities, *Infernal Affairs* emphasises the important role of information, just as *New World* and other Post-Revival Era films do. Bordwell (2011, p.204) states that *Infernal Affairs* replaces the “extravagant carnage” that characterised early triad films with “[t]railing, spying, making inferences, rigging surveillance, setting traps, and above all sending messages (by phone, computer, Morse code).” In fact, the first gunshot is not fired until after thirty minutes (ibid.).

New World shares many characteristics with another post-millennial Hong Kong gangster film: *Election*. Although the film does not include undercover characters, its plot is similar to *New World*, centring on a power struggle between two gangsters, Lok and Big D, as they vie to be the chairman of their gang (Jinde 2019, p.486). The contrast between Lok, who is calm and businessman-like, and Big D, who is brash and volatile, parallels the contrast between Joong-gu and Jung in *New World* – Joong-gu is businesslike and reserved, and Jung is vulgar and volatile.

Election is reminiscent of other Post-Revival Era films due to its depiction of gangsters as amoral businessmen. Kelvin Ke Jinde (2019, p.490) argues that the *Election* series offers the most salient counterexample to Warshaw's (1948) classic conception of the gangster as a tragic hero. As Bordwell (2011, pp.258-259) notes, "every major player [in the film] has a plan to take over the leadership of the triad family, and each one involves temporary alliances that will be betrayed." Indeed, Jinde (2019, p.487) states that the "presence of free-market capitalism...overthrows all notions of...brotherhood and solidarity."

It is important to note that any notions of brotherhood or solidarity that Ja-sung in *New World* or Hyun-su in *The Merciless* might have had upon entering the underworld as undercover cops are eroded and destroyed by the end of each film. Ultimately, the pressures of their respective undercover assignments lead them to suffer a mental breakdown from which they emerge as cynical, ruthless and vengeful. Hyun-su murders his friend and mentor, the gangster Jae-ho, and his police chief, in cold blood. Similarly, Ja-sung orders the deaths of his gangster rivals and his police handler, Kang, and assumes control of the Goldmoon gang in the process.

While the use of surveillance and information, the aura of paranoia they create, and the presence of 'the law' are indicative of the continuing influence of Hong Kong gangster

cinema, Plaice (2019b) believes that these elements suggest that the gangster genre and the noir have mixed.

There is further evidence to support this suggestion – as noted in section 7.3 With Great Power, the Post-Revival Era is characterised by flashbacks, a noir element identified by many theorists (Kelso-Marsh 2020, p.43; McCracken 2012, p.170; Grant 2007, p.11; Neale 2000, p.157). The fact that these flashbacks are mainly plot-driven rather than character-driven represents another commonality with the noir – Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.43) states that the use of flashbacks to create narratively complex or non-linear narratives is typical of the noir. Neale (2000, p.157, italics in original) makes a similar point, stating that “*film noirs* are usually characterized as complex - often confusing - and as frequently entailing the use of flashback.”

According to Neale (2000, p.164) and Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.43), moral ambivalence is also a distinct trait of the noir genre. Although Post-Revival Era gangsters are more obviously amoral than their predecessors, ‘the law’ is rather morally ambivalent. Indeed, there is rarely a binary opposition between ‘the law’ and gangsters in the Post-Revival Era. Of the ten films discussed in this chapter that feature a cop, prosecutor or undercover character, only two – *A Company Man* and *The Drug King* – depict ‘the law’ as morally superior to gangsters. The police chiefs in *New World* and *The Merciless* are so obsessed with apprehending gangsters that they often ignore morality, break laws, and drive their respective undercover cops to madness.

Despite the parallels between the noir and gangster genres, many noir tropes are absent from the Post-Revival Era. Grant’s (2007, p.25) statement that noir plots often “involve some variation of a man lured into a criminal act” does not apply to any of the films studied in this chapter. In addition, Post-Revival Era films lack femme fatales and voiceover narration, two noir elements identified by McCracken (2012, p.170). The Post-Revival Era also lacks “a distinct treatment of sexual desire and sexual relationships...and a distinct array

of male and female character types”, both of which many “commentators” identify as principal hallmarks of the noir genre (Neale 2000, p.151).

Overall, the inherently elusive nature of the noir genre makes it difficult to state whether the noir and gangster genres have mixed. As Neale (2000, p.144, italics in original) notes, there has been “considerable disagreement about basic criteria, about the overall contours of the larger *noir* canon, and some of the antecedents, roots and causes of *noir*.” Similarly, Martin (2015, p.125) notes that there is still disagreement amongst scholars about whether noir is a genre or merely a critical category. Accordingly, it seems more accurate to state that rather than being completely reconfigured by the noir genre, the gangster genre and the noir genre have mixed, undergoing the process of ‘genre-bending’.

Although genre-bending is not a novel feature of the Post-Revival Era, Jin (2020, p.124) notes that it was not until the 2010s that genre-bending became “very common” in the Korean film industry, with films being increasingly “hybridized through genre-bending.” Similarly, Gillespie (2016, p.62) states that filmmakers began diversifying traditional genres after the “glut of overproduction” and the decline of domestic film market-share in the late 2000s. Gillespie (2016, p.62) also states that filmmakers began combining gangster tropes with other genres. Similarly, Plaice (2019c) claims that the proportion of “gangster-mixed” films has increased significantly since the 1960s.⁷⁶

The prevalence of genre-bending during the Post-Revival Era is further confirmed by the fact that Post-Revival Era films feature notable elements from other genres besides the noir, such as the thriller.

Defined by Thomas Leitch (2004, p.17) as “films that focus on the victims of crimes, or of the criminal justice system,” Neale (2000, p.75) notes that one of the defining features of the thriller is “a lack of attention to official detectives or the police.” Although the thriller

⁷⁶ Plaice (2019c) does not directly make this statement. Instead, he uses a graph to illustrate the proportion of ‘gangster-mixed’ films from the 1960s to the 2000s. Unfortunately, he does not state how he selected his corpus of films or what he defines as ‘gangster-mixed’.

is understudied in Korean cinema literature, Korean genre theorist Park (2019, p.105) argues that thrillers rose in popularity throughout the 2000s to become a mainstream staple of 2010s Korean cinema. In addition, Park (ibid.) suggests that elements of thrillers became prevalent in the narrative structures of other Korean genres.⁷⁷

It is particularly evident that many Post-Revival Era films feature thriller-inspired narratives when considering the thriller sub-types identified by genre theorist Charles Derry (1988 cited in Neale 2000, p.75). *The Yellow Sea* features a narrative reminiscent of the “innocent-on-the-run thriller”, which, according to Derry (1988 cited in Neale 2000, p.76), depicts “an innocent victim’s coincidental entry into the midst of global intrigue.” Although the gangster-hero, Gu-nam, is not *totally* innocent, and the plot is not a global affair, the film’s narrative focuses on Gu-nam’s attempts to outrun the police and two gangs chasing him across Korea. Simultaneously, Gu-nam must unravel the mystery of his wife’s disappearance and find the man responsible for sabotaging the hit job he was tasked with completing. As a result, the film also features “a sense of the mysterious and a focus on a reasoning process”, two thriller characteristics identified by Park (2019, p.105). The prominence of thriller elements in the film is substantiated by the fact Hye Jean Chung (2019, p.35) refers to the film as a thriller.

The narratives of *Coin Locker Girl* and *Hwayi* are also somewhat akin to the ‘innocent-on-the-run thriller’. Although less focused on reasoning and the mysterious than *The Yellow Sea*, both films follow lone protagonists fleeing their former gangs. While neither protagonist is technically a victim of any crime, Derry (1988 cited in Neale 2000, p.75, author’s italics) notes that the thriller can “focus either on victims of crime *or* on pursued and isolated criminals.”

⁷⁷ Park (2019, p.105) uses the term ‘thriller’ to refer not only to “victim-oriented suspense films” – as Leitch (2004, p.17) and Neale (2000, p.75) do – but also to detective films and crime films in general.

Conversely, the narrative of *Inside Men* – which follows a prosecutor and a gangster’s combined efforts to expose a corrupt businessman, journalist and politician – is reminiscent of the “political thriller”, which focuses on “a plot to assassinate a political figure or a revelation of the essential conspiratorial nature of governments and their crimes against the people” (Derry 1988 cited in Neale 2000, p.75). Despite noting that one of *Inside Men*’s (Woo 2015) protagonists is a gangster, Jin (2020, p.136) actually defines the film as a political thriller.

The final thriller sub-type evident in the Post-Revival Era is the “thriller of moral confrontation”, which features “an overt antithetical confrontation between a character representing good or innocence and a character representing evil” (Derry 1988 cited in Neale 2000, p.76). Although the gang boss, Dong-soo, in *The Gangster, The Cop, The Devil* is far from innocent, the film clearly distinguishes between him and the serial killer he pursues. In the film’s finale, both cops and gangsters spring into action when they find out that the serial killer has murdered a young girl with whom Dong-soo had a pleasant interaction earlier in the film. Accordingly, the film positions Dong-soo and the serial killer as distinctly different criminals: whereas Dong-soo has friendly interactions with little girls, the serial killer heartlessly murders them. When the serial killer later asks Dong-soo, “*How are we different?*”, Dong-soo replies, “*That’s pretty obvious, isn’t it.*”

Overall, the existence of not one but *three* different thriller sub-types in the Post-Revival Era highlights how significantly genre-bending has influenced the genre. Even so, it is important to recognise that the thriller is, like the noir, somewhat related to the gangster genre. As Neale (2000, p.65) notes, the gangster genre and thriller often “overlap and cross-fertilize”.

However, the gangster genre has also combined with dissimilar genres during this period. Four Post-Revival Era films, *A Love, Hindsight, A Company Man, Man in Love*

and *Coin Locker Girl*, are more akin to romances than typical gangster films, focusing on romance as much as, or even more than, the underworld.

Man in Love is almost akin to an Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-melodrama due to the presence of not only prominent romantic elements but also prominent melodramatic elements, such as tragic turns of fate, pathos, dramatic reversals, remarkable coincidences and precipitous falls. Film critic Pierce Conran (2014) notes that the film is particularly melodramatic during its last thirty minutes when the film “turns on the waterworks...[and] the film’s measured tone gives way to melodramatic excess.” The melodramatic nature of *Man in Love* is substantiated by the fact that Tae-il, the film’s gangster-hero, is the only gangster-hero mentioned in the thesis who dies of natural causes, succumbing to cancer in the film’s final act.

Although other films feature melodramatic films, Conran (2014) notes that *Man in Love* combines four genres: the romance, the gangster film, the family drama and the “tearjerker.” Whereas the film’s first half focuses on a romantic relationship between Tae-il and a bank teller, the second half focuses on Tae-il’s troubled family life and his struggle with cancer. Many scenes centre around Tae-il’s interactions with his father, brother, sister-in-law and niece, with whom he lives.

Although no other film examined in this chapter focuses so much on family drama, many other films feature subplots and themes based on family drama. In fact, genre theorist Plaice (2020, pp.5-6, author’s italics) argues that the domestic setting was so prevalent in “gangster-themed” films of the 2000s that it led to the emergence of a new “hyphenated sub-genre”, the “family drama gangster film.”

While it is difficult to verify Plaice’s (ibid.) claim as he does not clarify what he defines as “gangster-themed”, there are indeed many examples of the domestic setting to be found throughout the Post-Revival Era. In *Man of Men*, Yeong-gi lives in an apartment with his younger brother, whom he sends to school with the money he makes as a gangster.

Although there are not many scenes between the two brothers, the domestic setting heightens the film's dramatic tension, making Yeong-gi's efforts to repay a significant debt feel more important. In *The Drug King*, the domestic setting serves a different purpose, highlighting the destructive nature of the underworld. Without it, there would be no significant sense of loss in the film as the gangster-hero, Doo-sam, would simply become rich and powerful after beginning a life of crime. Instead, Doo-sam's rise to power comes at the expense of family: although he cares for his family at the start of the film, he abandons them soon after he becomes a drug kingpin.

Whereas *Man of Men* and *The Drug King* only sparsely feature the domestic setting, it appears throughout *The Show Must Go On* and *Gangnam Blues*. In both films, the gangster-hero struggles to balance their family life with their criminal career, often at the expense of the former. *The Show Must Go On* ends with the gangster-hero's wife and daughter leaving Korea to start a new life without him, and in *Gangnam Blues*, the gangster-hero's decision to join a gang ruins his relationship with his adoptive father, who is ultimately killed in a gang war.

Breathless also features the domestic setting, though it is a place of suffering and trauma rather than of comfort or safety. Once abused by his father, Sang-hun now abuses his alcoholic father, who has returned home after being in prison for accidentally killing Sang-hun's younger sister during a bout of domestic violence. The teenage girl who befriends Sang-hun, Yeon-hui, is also a victim of domestic abuse – she shares a home with her mentally unstable father and abusive older brother (Choi 2015, p.59). Rupinder Kahlon (2011, p.77) states that as *Breathless* progresses, Sang-hun's traumatic domestic experiences, "travel out of the private realm of his mind and body into the openness of public areas." Kahlon (ibid.) describes a scene in which Sang-hun barges into a family's home, finds the patriarch beating his wife, and unleashes all his anger and trauma upon him, beating the patriarch senseless. For film critic Hyo-won Lee (2009), such scenes of domestic

violence, cruelty and revenge are why *Breathless* should be considered “a family drama that’s inappropriate for children.”

The respective domestic settings of *Hwayi* and *Coin Locker Girl* are similarly complicated as the domestic setting in *Breathless*. In *Hwayi*, Hwayi’s family is a gang of five men who kidnapped him when he was an infant, and in *Coin Locker Girl*, Il-young’s family is a gang headed by a woman, referred to as Mother, who raises orphaned and abandoned children as her debt collectors and thugs.

Aside from its unique incorporation of the domestic setting, *Coin Locker Girl* is also a notable film due to its depiction of female characters. Indeed, Korean film theorist Kelly Y. Jeong (2021, p.44) states that *Coin Locker Girl* is “noteworthy as a women’s film because it centres around two women, represented as complex people rather than feminine subjects situated to offer the audience visual pleasure.” As Jeong (ibid.) notes, the film not only has one notable female character but two: the film’s gangster-hero, Il-young, and ‘Mother’, Il-young’s gang boss and surrogate mother.

Both women challenge conventional portrayals of women in gangster cinema. Il-young is headstrong and confident, more comfortable wielding a knife and threatening men twice her age than she is socialising or wearing dresses. Although she soon falls in love with a boy her age, her unique identity is not significantly changed by their romance.

‘Mother’ is so different from a typical female character that Jeong (2021, p.51) notes that she defies heteronormative values and images, “making her impossible to categorize in terms of gender and age.” Indeed, Mother seems to have not just broken free from restrictive social norms but disregarded them entirely, behaving as any male gangster would. Moreover, the film never uses the gender-reversal of its gang boss for comedic purposes, as comedy-gangster films did during the Revival Era.

Mother and Il-young are not the only compelling female characters in the Post-Revival Era. Although Se-bin becomes romantically involved with the gangster-hero, Doo-

hyeon, in *Hindsight*, she is not reduced to an archetypal love interest. Se-bin is neither dependent on Doo-hyeon nor subservient to him. An independent and capable young woman, she is proficient with a sniper rifle and capable of surviving in the underworld.

Night in Paradise also features a strong female character, Jae-yeon. Forever scarred by the murder of her parents at the hands of the Russian mob, Jae-yeon grows up to become a distant and dispassionate woman unconcerned with the world or anyone in it, including Tae-su, the film's gangster-hero. When Tae-su arrives at her house to lay low with her and Kuto, her uncle, Jae-yeon, treats him as a stranger and an unwanted guest. Her world does not revolve around him, and she makes this fact clear.

Nevertheless, most other women in the Post-Revival Era are cast in the same minor roles, namely wives and lovers, that they occupied during the Revival Era. In addition, Post-Revival Era female characters often serve the same narrative purposes as their Revival Era counterparts: humanising the gangster-hero and/or increasing the stakes of the film's plot.

In certain films, unique female characters regress into reductive archetypes. In *Nameless Gangster*, Miss Yeo, a wealthy and headstrong nightclub manager, rebels against the gangster-hero, Ik-hyun, only to later succumb to his charms and become his mistress after he assumes control of her business. A similar relationship occurs between Jong-dae and Min Seong-hee, an affluent businesswoman, in *Gangnam Blues*, and between Doo-sam and Kim Jeong-ah, a wealthy lobbyist, in *The Drug King*.

Women are not the only figures that suffer from regressive and problematic portrayals in the Post-Revival Era. One of the most notable differences between the Post-Revival Era and the Revival Era is the latter's depiction of ethnically Korean Chinese, or *Joseonjok*.

Descendants of Koreans that migrated to Manchuria between 1860 and 1945, Asian Studies scholar Changzoo Song (2023) states that *Joseonjok* are "socially alienated,

culturally disregarded, and economically assigned to lower-wage jobs” in Korea.⁷⁸ Ironically, this is partly because they speak Korean and understand Korean customs. Ethan Waddell and Ann Meejung Kim (2015, p.102) state that since they are neither “wholly alien and not entirely familiar”, *Joseonjok* are often excluded from multicultural discourse, and their mistreatment is ignored by mainstream media. Song (2023) states that South Koreans also tend to discriminate against *Joseonjok* because they are often poorer than co-ethnics from wealthier Western countries.

Joseonjok were even excluded from the 1999 Overseas Koreans Act, which prevented them and *Goryeo saram* – ethnic Koreans descendant from those who settled in the Russian Far East before being forcibly relocated to Central Asia in 1937 – from getting entry visas and employment rights allowed to overseas Koreans (Song 2023). Even though the law was revised in 2004 on the grounds of “unconstitutional discrimination”, Song (2023) states that the government continues to control the entry visas and employment rights of *Joseonjok* and *Goryeo saram*.

Overall, Waddell and Kim (2015, p.105) state that most *Joseonjok* are represented onscreen as illegal immigrants or lower-class criminals. This is evidenced by their depiction in many of the films examined in this chapter. In *Coin Locker Girl*, Il-young's adoptive mother and gang leader, Mother, seems to be ethnic Chinese. Cold, cruel and violent, Mother forces Il-young and her ‘siblings’ to assist her with “loan-sharking, organ-harvesting, human trafficking activities, and producing false identification cards” (Jeong 2021, p.50). Mother’s foreignness is highlighted by the depiction of Incheon’s Chinatown, where Mother’s business and Il-young’s home are located – the round Chinese dining table, garish colours and general shabbiness highlight Mother’s otherness and “appear unusual for one’s home to Korean audiences” (Jeong 2021, p.54).

⁷⁸ During this time, some Koreans settled in the Russian Far East and before being forcibly relocated to Central Asia in 1937 – this group of ethnic Koreans is known as *Goryeo saram* (Song 2013).

Whereas it is rather ambiguous whether *Mother* is an ethnic Korean in *Coin Locker Girl*, *New World* explicitly depicts *Joseonjok*. As Wagner and Unger (2013, p.14) note, the Goldmoon gang outsources its more violent work to a small band of gangsters called the ‘Yanbian Hobos’. As if the name were not enough, the film emphasises the otherness of these characters by first depicting them entering the country at the Incheon International Ferry Terminal (Wagner and Unger 2013, p.14). Adorned in garish, shabby clothes and bantering in loud accents, the Hobos are almost comically foreign, reacting to the clean, modern surroundings of Korea with a mixture of surprise and awe.

Wagner and Unger (2013, p.14) note that while the Hobos are depicted as bumbling foreigners here, they are simultaneously depicted as deadly criminals later in the film, capable of kidnapping and murder. Gillespie (2016, p.69) states that the fact that the Hobos are from Yanbian and have been summoned to Korea by Jung Chung, an ethnic Korean, himself, “adds a xenophobic gloss” to the film. A later scene in which the Hobos are shown slovenly eating outside a Buddhist temple as a funeral takes place, further positions the Hobos as not just ‘others’ but a lesser people ignorant of Korean customs and culture.

According to The Korea Times, similarly reductive portrayals can be found in films such as the thriller *Traffickers* (*Gongmojadeul*, Kim 2012) and the cop films, *The Outlaws* and *Midnight Runners* (*Cheongnyeongyeongchal*, Kim 2017). The latter’s portrayal of Seoul’s Daerim-dong neighbourhood, which has a large Chinese Korean population, as lawless and crime-ridden was so egregious that sixty *Joseonjok* filed a lawsuit against the company claiming that the film had defamed them, forcing the company to issue a public apology and pledge to prevent similar portrayals following a court-mediated settlement (The Korea Times 2025).

Chung, H.J. (2019, p.38) suggests that such negative portrayals of *Joseonjok* may stem from the much-publicised murder and dismemberment of a Korean woman by a

Joseonjok man in 2012.⁷⁹ Alternatively, an article in *The Korea Times* (2025) points to *The Yellow Sea*, which features a *Joseonjok* protagonist and antagonist, as the progenitor of negative portrayals of the ethnic group in Korean media.

While the lack of negative portrayals of *Joseonjok* in the Revival Era seems to support this point, it is important to note that *The Yellow Sea's* portrayal of *Joseonjok* is actually one of Korean cinema's most complex. Although the film's gangster-hero, Gu-nam, is a *Joseonjok* who enters Korea illegally to kill a man on behalf of a *Joseonjok* gang boss, Myun, Waddell and Kim (2015, p.109) believe that the film suggests that while *Joseonjok* may engage in illegal acts or enter Korea illegally, "their motivations are not immoral, but forced by circumstances."

Indeed, the film's portrayal of Gu-nam is sympathetic – upon arriving in Korea, he is tricked, mistreated, discriminated against, and forced to endure great hardships; shivering outside, unable to buy proper clothes for the Korean winter, and residing in a decrepit, windowless room, unable to afford any level of comfort. Accordingly, Waddell and Kim (2015, p.109) state, "the audience comes to view Gu-nam's...impoverished conditions as a signifier of his relative moral purity." In fact, unlike many of the Korean characters in the film, Gu-nam's are not motivated by jealousy, revenge or fear of humiliation, but purely financial reasons (Waddell and Kim 2017, p.107).

Nevertheless, it would be remiss to describe the film's portrayal of *Joseonjok* as favourable. Wagner and Unger (2013, p.17) highlight the film's depiction of *Yanji*, the city from which Gu-nam hails – shot in a desaturated, grey colour palette, the city is an overcrowded and chaotic place of squalor and crime. It does not help that the film begins with a map displaying the Yanbian Korean Autonomous Prefecture in which Yanji is located, with the text: "About 800,000 Korean-Chinese known as JOSEONJOK reside here."

⁷⁹ Lee, J. (2019) emphasises that while statistics provided by the Korean Institute of Criminology and Statistics show that Chinese and ethnic Chinese Koreans commit more crimes than any other foreign group in Korea, this is simply because they make up 50% of Korea's foreign population.

Over 50% of Joseonjok population [sic] rely on illegal activities or legally live and work in South Korea in order to survive.”

The positive portrayal of Gu-nam is also largely undermined by the film’s portrayal of Myun, the gang boss who recruits Gu-nam, and the film’s antagonist. Boisterous and vulgar, Chung, H.J. (2019, p.37) states that Myun flaunts his otherness and makes no attempt to blend in when he arrives in Korea to find and kill Gu-nam. Accordingly, he seems dismissive of Korean culture, his arrogance at once an affront and a threat. Although Koreans also commit violence in the film, Myun is particularly violent, killing his enemies with a disturbing primitivism – Chung, H.J. (2019, p.37) highlights the fact that Myun is seen fighting with hatchets and even an animal bone. In addition, after killing a group of Korean gangsters, “Myun orders their corpses to be dismembered, decapitated, and fed to the dogs” (Chung, H.J. 2019, p.37). Waddell and Kim (2015, p.106) note that a scene depicting Myun and his men voraciously eating bare-handed from a large pot of boiled meat is also indicative of the film’s primitive portrayal of *Joseonjok*.

Overall, the emergence of both *Joseonjok* and unique female characters may not be products of genre bending as they are simply genre experimentation. Certainly, it does not seem that either *Joseonjok* or female characters appear frequently enough to have spawned a new sub-genre of the gangster genre. If a genre shift *had* occurred, there would likely be less variation between films and a greater uniformity in terms of their semantic and syntactic characteristics. Plaice (2020, p.2) seems to believe these variations are due to “the flexibility of gangster tropes...[which have] enabled the gangster film to produce new permutations and remain relevant to Korean audiences.”

The flexibility of the genre’s tropes is particularly evident when examining their use in *other* genres. Indeed, there are many films made during the Post-Revival Era that were not included in the thesis’s corpus simply because they do not feature a gangster protagonist. Although the protagonist of the thriller *Public Enemy Returns* is a cop, the film’s antagonist,

Lee Won-sul, is a gangster, and the film focuses on the inner workings of his gang and the underworld. Won-sul's gang is even characteristic of the more businesslike gangs of the Post-Revival Era. In the film's first scene, he addresses a legion of young recruits, telling them, "*I know I'm a gangster, but the world sees me as a company president. I still settle my differences with my fists but outside, I'm seen as a legitimate, successful entrepreneur.*"

The more businesslike nature of Won-sul's gang highlights that the gangster's higher social status in the Post-Revival Era is not limited to the gangster genre. In fact, *The Devil's Deal* and *Asura: City of Madness* both feature gangsters explicitly involved in politics. In addition, although the antagonists of *Veteran* are businessmen, they are akin to gangsters in terms of their hierarchical structure, iconography and general amorality. As the head of a large company, the film's main antagonist, Tae-oh, is not unlike a gang boss: he commands a legion of men who obey him unquestionably, boasts immense power and wealth, and is corrupt and amoral. Accordingly, Kim (2019, p.518) refers to the businessmen in *Veteran* as 'corporate gangsters'.

The King also features elements of the gangster genre. Depicting a young prosecutor's rise through the ranks of Korea's corrupt justice system, the film emphasises many themes associated with gangster films, namely social inequality, corruption and brotherhood. The prosecutors also work closely with gangsters, tasking them with the few overtly criminal tasks that they are not willing to do themselves.

Considering the many parallels between each of these films and gangster cinema, it seems no coincidence that they were each, that is *The King*, *Veteran*, *The Devil's Deal*, *Asura: City of Madness* and *Public Enemy Returns*, directed by someone who has either directed or written a gangster film.⁸⁰

Overall, both the use of gangster genre elements in non-gangster films *and* the influence of genre-bending have obfuscated the gangster genre's boundaries so significantly that it is difficult to state what defines the Post-Revival Era. In fact, there seems to be a lack of consensus regarding the generic identity of many post-2006 gangster films. Kwon (2023, p.16) refers to *The Merciless* as a "noir action" film, and Choi (2016, p.219) refers to *New World* as a crime action film. Jeong (2021, pp.44-46) refers to *Coin Locker Girl* as both a noir film and an action film, and Jin (2020, p.136) refers to *Inside Men* as a political thriller. While Chung, H.J. (2019, p.35) refers to *The Yellow Sea* as a noir thriller, Choi (2016, p.219) explicitly states that it is *not* a noir film, referring to it as a crime action film. Gillespie (2016, p.70) takes a more nuanced approach, noting that *The Yellow Sea* indicates the "increasing diversification and reflexivity" of the gangster genre.

These examples are not meant to denigrate these theorists nor imply that they are incorrect. Instead, these examples are used to support the thesis's claim that the Post-Revival Era is difficult to define. As film theorist Mark Jancovich (2001, p.35) notes, "a film which, for some, may seem obviously to belong to one genre may, for others, clearly belong to another genre altogether."

7.5 Conclusion

To answer the thesis's research question – '*Has the Korean gangster genre, as Choi (2016, p.231; 2010, p.53) suggests, been followed or replaced by crime thrillers, or has it, as Plaice (2020, p.3; 2019b), Kim (2019, p.518) and Gillespie (2016, p.70) imply, diversified and expanded?*' – the thesis states that Korean gangster genre *does not* seem to have been followed or replaced by crime thrillers. Although Park (2019, p.105) notes that thrillers rose in popularity in the 2000s and became a mainstream staple of Korean cinema in the 2010s, the gangster genre has neither disappeared nor waned during the Post-Revival Era.

Rather, the gangster genre seems to have mixed with not only the thriller, but also the noir, romance and family drama genres. In addition, while the thriller has only influenced certain gangster films discussed in this chapter, many noir characteristics – such as the use of information, the inclusion of ‘the law’, plot-driven flashbacks, non-linear narratives and morally ambivalent characters – are present throughout the Post-Revival Era.

Although, as noted in section 7.4, most genre theorists agree that hybridisation is a hallmark of genre, the extent of genre-bending during the Post-Revival era is significant. While genre-bending has occurred throughout the gangster genre’s history, it has led to the emergence of several novel elements for the gangster genre, such as high-ranked and high-class gangster-heroes, businesslike gangs, extreme violence, information warfare, and ‘the law’. Overall, then, the genre has not been followed or replaced, but rather, diversified and expanded.

The thesis’s answer to the chapter’s second research question, ‘*Has the genre diversified enough to create a new, divergent genre?*’, is a complex one. Certainly, some Post-Revival films might be considered divergent. *Hwayi* and *Coin Locker Girl* completely reconfigure the underworld, interweaving the gangster film with the family drama genre so intricately that the borders of each are impossible to distinguish. In drawing from Hong Kong gangster films such as *Infernal Affairs* and *Election*, *New World* and *The Merciless* are at once gangster films and undercover films. The emphasis on romance and melodrama in both *Man in Love* and *Hindsight* hark back to Early Pre-Revival films.

However, if a sub-genre had emerged during this time, it would likely manifest as a consistent trend in a manner similar to the comedy-gangster genre’s emergence during the Revival Era. Yet, the only trend that seems to have emerged during the Post-Revival Era is the prevalence of genre-bending. Indeed, despite Plaice’s (2020, p.6) assertion that a new sub-genre, “the family drama gangster film”, emerged during the 2000s, family drama elements are only prominent in a few Post-Revival gangster films and are otherwise

insignificant. Similarly, although recent trends show that many gangster films now cast *Joseonjok* as antagonists, this does not occur frequently enough, or reconfigure the genre significantly enough, to create a new sub-genre.

Nevertheless, the possibility that a distinct sub-genre emerged during this time requires further examination. This thesis's definition of a gangster film may be too narrow to encompass films that Plaice (2020) includes in his corpus. In addition, the fact that Plaice (2020) is the only theorist to have identified such a divergence may be because not many scholars have examined the Post-Revival Era, rather than the validity of his argument.

Although a sub-genre does not seem to have emerged during this time, the gangster genre has undergone such a significant transformation in the last two decades that it does not seem unreasonable to consider the Post-Revival Era as a distinct phase. In fact, the genre has changed so significantly during the Post-Revival Era that many extant studies of the Korean gangster genre now seem outdated. For example, Kim's (2019, p.501) statement that Korean gangsters are "almost always working class" conflicts with the upper-class status of most Post-Revival Era gangster-heroes. Kim's (2019, p.501) statement that "the gangster belongs to the...fringe of Korean society, alongside prostitutes, pimps, and the impoverished," also conflicts with this chapter's findings. As noted in section 7.2, gangsters are now often integral members of Korean high society.

Kim (2019) is not the only scholar whose findings on the Korean gangster genre seem outdated when applied to the Post-Revival Era. Choi's (2010a, p.69) insightful observations regarding the genre's use of the high school setting are rendered inaccurate by the Post-Revival Era – only one film in this chapter's corpus, *A Love*, features scenes set in a high school. In addition, Min et al.'s (2003, p.18) argument that the gangster genre – and

Korean cinema overall – lack “political consciousness and ideology” contradicts the prominent political and ideological themes underlying most Post-Revival gangster films.⁸¹

Even so, it may be “overly reflectionist”, as Kelso-Marsh (2020, p.61) states, to suggest that the issue of corruption shaped the development of Korean gangster cinema. It is also important to clarify that while the genre’s semantic elements have changed, its syntactic elements have not. Although Post-Revival Era gangster films emphasise corruption and do not depict social inequality as often as their predecessors, they still explore topics characteristic of the gangster genre: betrayal, brotherhood and social class. In addition, aside from more extreme violence, the Post-Revival Era’s aesthetic characteristics are not significantly different from the preceding era.

The prevalence of corruption throughout Korea’s history also complicates the hypothesis that corruption has influenced the Post-Revival Era. As a result, it seems more accurate to state that as social inequality persisted throughout the 2000s and 2010s, filmmakers sought new ways to represent the public’s growing frustration and resentment. Rather than highlight issues of social inequality – as they did during the Revival Era – filmmakers criticised and denigrated those they believed responsible for these issues, Korea’s ruling class, by reconfiguring the gangster-hero in their image.

⁸¹ In Min et al.’s (2003) defence, their work was published three years before 2006. Even so, the differences between their findings and those of this thesis highlight how drastically the Post-Revival Era diverges from the Revival Era.

Chapter VIII: Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

By charting the Korean gangster genre from its initial emergence in the late 1950s to its present existence in the 2020s, the thesis has demonstrated that the genre's development has been affected by various internal genre changes, external socio-cultural influences and industrial shifts. This is not a remarkable finding. As noted throughout the thesis, most film scholars agree that genres are ongoing processes affected by broader contextual changes. However, the *way* in which these determinants have shaped the gangster genre's central figure, the gangster-hero, *is* remarkable. Rather than progressively transforming, the Korean gangster genre has undergone three distinct shifts, each marked by an almost total reinvention of the gangster-hero.

The first shift substantiates the thesis's use of the terms 'Early' and 'Late' to divide the Pre-Revival Era. While these terms were initially used to distinguish between the two cinematic periods that overlap with the Pre-Revival Era, the Golden Age and the Dark Age, they also demarcate the distinctly different gangsters that typify each cinematic period. As described in Chapter V, the shift separating the Early and Late Pre-Revival Eras marks the gangster-hero's transformation, driven by increasingly strict censorship, from an underprivileged hoodlum representative of the most unfortunate Koreans into an amoral action-hero largely devoid of symbolic depth. The shift also marks the beginning of the gangster genre's decline and eventual disappearance in the 1980s.

The second shift, which separates the Late Pre-Revival Era from the Revival Era, marks the gangster-hero's revivification by a new generation of filmmakers. Young, lower-class and relatable, the Revival Era gangster-hero resembles Early Pre-Revival Era gangster-heroes while being distinctly representative of the many Koreans impacted by the 1997 IMF Crisis. Afflicted by identity crises and willing to commit terrible acts to survive in a rapidly

transforming Korea, Revival Era gangster-heroes are also more nuanced than their Pre-Revival predecessors.

The third shift, located between the Revival Era and the current Post-Revival Era, marks the most significant transformation of the gangster-hero to date. Wealthy, high-ranking and powerful, the Post-Revival Era gangster hero is as much a businessman as he is a gangster. Whereas the Revival Era gangster-hero is representative of those adversely affected by social inequality, the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero is representative of those responsible for social inequality, or at least, those most Koreans blame for social inequality: the rich and powerful.

8.2 Validating Extant Approaches to Genre Development

Initially, the Korean gangster genre's development seems to affirm Schatz's (1981, p.38) heavily criticised approach to genre development, which purports that a genre progresses through stages from "straightforward storytelling to self-conscious formalism".

However, although the genre's development may be divided into distinct stages, the genre has not developed for the reason Schatz (1981, p.38) would suggest: in a "concerted effort to explain itself, to address and evaluate its very status as a popular form." Rather, the genre has developed due to the determinants Schatz (1981) ignores in his work: socio-cultural and industrial influences. Indeed, while the genre's development *resembles* the process established by Schatz (1981), it reaffirms the prevailing scholarly consensus that a genre changes due to contextual shifts, whether socio-cultural, industrial or generic.

Central to understanding the genre's development is the gangster-hero. As a multifarious element – a semantic element with a syntactic purpose and/or syntactic characteristics – the gangster-hero reflects both semantic and syntactic change. Indeed, while the gangster-hero does not serve a structural purpose, as the genre's narratives and themes do, they bear the most meaning in the gangster genre. As evidenced by the genre's

development, one cannot change *any* aspect of the gangster-hero, whether it be their class, rank, temperament or morality, without it affecting every other element of the gangster film.

For example, changes in the gangster-hero's class have led to significant syntactic experimentation, one of the two factors that cause semantic/syntactic development. This is most apparent when considering how the genre's portrayal of social inequality has changed. Although Revival Era films emphasise social inequality by depicting the troubled lives of lower-class gangsters, Post-Revival Era films emphasise social inequality by highlighting the amorality of upper-class gangsters. The second cause of semantic/syntactic development, the adoption of new semantic elements, is also evident when considering how the genre's settings and iconography change to reflect the gangster-hero's social class. Ultimately, the gangster-hero's multifaceted role highlights that they are not just one of the genre's elements, but rather a critical lens through which the genre's broader evolution can be examined.

Of course, the thesis acknowledges that some scholars may justifiably argue that other elements are as pivotal to the gangster genre as the gangster-hero. Nevertheless, any scholar who attempts to define or examine the entirety of the Korean gangster genre will find that the gangster-hero is just one of a few elements present in each period of the genre. Although violence is a foremost characteristic of the Post-Revival Era, Revival Era and Late Pre-Revival Era, it is not in the Early Pre-Revival Era. Similarly, while brotherhood and betrayal are important themes in the Revival Era and the Post-Revival Era, they are not in the Pre-Revival Era. In addition, the theme of social inequality is not present in every period of the Korean gangster genre – while the Early Pre-Revival Era, Revival Era and Post-Revival Era reckon with issues relating to class, the Late Pre-Revival Era does not.

Although semantic and syntactic changes have led to the emergence of new genre elements, many elements of the Korean gangster genre have merely been reshuffled, either diminishing or increasing in prominence. The reshuffling of elements is apparent when

comparing the Early Pre-Revival Era and the Revival Era. Although both periods share many similar elements, they feature them in different ways and to differing extents. For example, although both periods mainly feature young, lower-class protagonists, only the Revival Era features the high-school setting and teenage gangster-heroes. In addition, although both periods explore issues relating to social inequality, the Revival Era specifically confronts class division, whereas the Early Pre-Revival Era is more general in its depiction of the issue.

Overall, the thesis affirms the three main ideas upon which it bases its approach to genre development: Altman's (1984) semantic/syntactic approach, which highlights semantic and syntactic change, Neale's (2000) hypothesis that dominant genres and genre elements are constantly reshuffled, and Grindon's (2007) research on the historical influences affecting genre development.

Through finding that both Altman's (1984) and Neale's (2000) conceptions of genre development are valid, the thesis confirms Grindon's (2007, p.406) suggestion that these approaches are complementary rather than contradictory. The thesis also confirms Grindon's (2007, p.406) argument that the three factors influencing genre development are external social influences, film industry factors and internal genre changes. In addition, the Korean gangster genre's socially relevant themes confirm Grindon's (2007, p.407) point that "social influences often exercise their impact on...the dramatic conflicts at the foundation of a genre's syntax."

Grindon's (2007, p.407) point that "social influences are the dominant factor propelling [genre] change" is more difficult to confirm. Although social influences seem to have been the dominant factor propelling change during the Early Pre-Revival Era and Revival Era, industrial factors, namely censorship and the film quota policy, seem to be the leading cause of change during the Late Pre-Revival Era. In addition, the Post-Revival Era seems to have been propelled as much by internal genre changes as socio-cultural influences.

Nevertheless, the thesis confirms the central idea underlying Grindon's (2007) work, as well as Altman's (1984) and Neale's (2000) work: that genre is a process. It also confirms three leading ideas in contemporary Genre Studies: i) that socio-cultural factors affect a genre's development, ii) that genre-mixing is inherent and inevitable, and iii) that genre boundaries are more flexible than strict.

8.3 The Pre-Revival Era: Uncovering the Genre's Origins

As the thesis details, the Korean gangster's origins are complex – although the genre emerged in the Golden Age, the gangster films of this time are more akin to melodramas than typical gangster films, with crime and violence being secondary to romance, pathos and fate. This is most evident when considering the era's gangster-heroes, who are often only one of many protagonists in a film and are often focused more on matters of romance than matters of the underworld. Furthermore, Early Pre-Revival gangster-heroes are so impoverished that they resemble hoodlums more than organised criminals.

Although the Late Pre-Revival Era would see the gangster-hero more closely resemble an actual organised criminal, it too was more akin to a sub-genre of another major genre, the action genre. Indeed, although gangster-heroes of this time are more overtly criminal, they are not significantly different from a generic action hero.

Still, the finding that the gangster genre existed at all before 1990 represents an important contribution to the field of Korean Film Studies – as noted throughout the thesis, Korean critics remarked on the Revival Era as if it were historically unprecedented (Choi 2010a, p.60). In addition, up until this point, English-language scholars have only mainly referred to the existence of pre-1990s gangster films indirectly when referring to the genre's revival during New Korean Cinema as a “shift” (Kim 2019, p.510), a “new cycle” (Plaice 2020, p.3) or a “new gangster cinema” (Min et al. 2003, p.173). For this reason, the thesis is

indebted to Jinhee Choi (2016; 2010a; 2010b), one of the only English-language scholars who directly mentions the existence of early gangster films.

However, while the thesis's examination of the Pre-Revival Era builds upon Choi's (2016, pp.220-221; 2010a, pp.60-61; 2010b, pp.47-48) notes on the era, it departs from some of her findings. Whereas Choi (2010a, p.60) finds that "Korean gangster films of the 1960s often dealt with an internal conflict within a gang or an external conflict between rival gangs", the thesis finds that this is only true of *Black Hair*. Even then, *Black Hair* focuses more on the romantic bond between its gangster-hero and his ex-wife than on the internal conflicts of the film's gang. Another point of difference between Choi's (2010a) work and this thesis is the finding that the 1970s gangster-hero was not often a "national hero" as Choi (2010b, p.48) suggests. While *Cruel History* is certainly nationalistic, the film's gangster-heroes are not more than one-dimensional action heroes.⁸²

One point of Choi's (2010a, p.60; 2010b, p.48) that the thesis aligns with rather than differs is the finding that censorship led to declining numbers of Korean gangster films during the 1970s and to the genre's almost total disappearance in the 1980s. As noted in Chapter V, of the 150 gangster films that KMDb lists between 1970 and 1979, 80% were released between 1970 and 1974. Furthermore, KMDb lists only 38 gangster films released between 1980 and 1989.⁸³

Although the abatement of censorship in the 1980s suggests that the genre's decline may have also been due to other factors, it is difficult not to conclude it was the foremost factor influencing the genre's development when Park Chung-hee made eradicating

⁸² It is possible that the thesis's findings differ from Choi's (2010, p.60) because it examines different films than her. Unfortunately, this is difficult to verify as Choi (2010a) does not expand upon her statement or mention a 1960s gangster film by name in her work (Choi 2010a; 2010b; 2016).

⁸³ As noted in Chapter III, this includes gangster films such as Kim Du-han and *Lot 1 of Seodaemun* (*Gim Duhangwa SeodaemunIbeonji*, Lee, 1981), *The Blues of Jong-ro* (*Jonglobuleuseu*, Kim, 1982) and *Challenge of Spite* (*Wonhan-ui dojeonjang*, Lee, 1983).

organised crime a priority upon seizing the Korean presidency in 1963, and depictions of crime and violence onscreen are known to have been censored.

8.4 The Revival Era: Questioning Newness

As noted in the preceding section and throughout the thesis, many scholars refer to the gangster films of the Revival Era as if they were a marked departure from the gangster films that preceded them. Min et al. (2003, pp.174-178) are particularly adamant about the ‘newness’ of early-2000s gangster films, citing their contemporary setting, the ruthlessness of their underworld and their efforts to criticise the Korean social system of the late-1990s and early-2000s. Min et al. (2003, p.174) even state that the gangster films of “the mid-1990s are radically different from their traditional counterparts.”

The thesis largely supports Min et al.’s (2003) findings. As Chapter VI notes, there are many differences between Revival Era films and earlier gangster films, most of which stem from the fact that the reduction of censorship allowed the Revival Era to fully depict and explore the underworld. Accordingly, it features elements, such as explicit depictions of organised crime and violence, and considers aspects of the underworld, such as the gang hierarchies, that the Pre-Revival Era does not.

Even so, the gangster-heroes of both eras are noticeably similar in some important ways – they are mainly young, low-ranking and lower-class, they are adversely affected by social inequality, and they are often reluctant and inexperienced criminals. In addition, while Revival Era gangster-heroes can be more ruthless and conniving than their Pre-Revival predecessors, they are nonetheless tragic, sympathetic figures representative of Korea’s most unfortunate citizens.

Overall, it seems unlikely that these similarities are due to deliberate choices made by the new generation of filmmakers who spearheaded the genre’s resurgence. Instead, these similarities appear to be incidental, reflecting the broader socio-cultural issues such as youth

disillusionment, social inequality, and limited social mobility that were pressing in both eras. As highlighted by Chapter VI, the Revival Era and the Revival Era gangster-hero seem to have also been influenced by Hong Kong gangster cinema.

Regardless of the reasons for the similarities between both the Revival Era and Pre-Revival Era, the gangster genre's long absence in the 1980s effectively 'reset' the genre's evolution, allowing filmmakers to produce gangster films aligned with their creative inclinations and the period's prevailing socio-cultural issues. Indeed, the thesis suggests that while the gangster genre's return to Korean screens was marked by the release of the rather traditional *General's Son*, it was not until the release of *Rules of the Game*, four years later in 1994, that the genre's revival began, and not until the release of *Friend* in 2001 that the genre fully resurged.

8.5 The Post-Revival Era: Expanding the Definition of the Korean Gangster Genre

Although the thesis supports most of Jinhee Choi's (2010a, p.62) writing on Korean gangster cinema, she does not align with her suggestion that the genre was followed or replaced by crime thrillers in the early 2010s (Choi 2016, p.231; 2010b, p.53). As Chapter VII notes, thrillers may have become a staple of Korean cinema in the 2010s, but the gangster genre has neither disappeared nor waned. Rather than replace the gangster genre, the thriller, along with the noir, romance and family drama, has mixed with it.

However, considering the differences between the Post-Revival Era and the Revival Era, it is understandable that Choi (2016, p.231; 2010b, p.53) suggests that the gangster genre was entirely replaced. Indeed, the gangster-hero has been considerably reconceptualised since 2007. Whereas the lower-class, low-ranking, relatable protagonists of the Revival Era represented the masses, the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero represents the rich and powerful, embodying the amoral, corporate and neoliberal ethos that many ordinary Koreans believe has ruined their country.

The few scholars who have examined the Post-Revival Era have remarked on the genre's significant transformation. The thesis verifies Gillespie's (2016, pp.62-63) many observations of recent gangster cinema, namely that "gangster tropes" have been increasingly combined with other genres, that certain elements of the genre should be reevaluated, and that "the gangster hero has diversified beyond the initial constraints of the genre formula." An important 'touchstone' for the thesis, Gillespie's work (2016) most closely hews to the thesis's position that the gangster-hero has undergone a fundamental transformation and is now representative of Korea's corporate elite.

The thesis also supports the work of Plaice (2019b; 2020), which emphasises how neoliberalism and genre-bending have shaped recent gangster films. In a similar manner to Gillespie (2016), Plaice (2019b) highlights the role of neoliberalism in shaping recent gangster cinema, "the corporatisation of [the] gangland" and the increasingly businesslike nature of the period's gangster-heroes. More so than Gillespie (2016), Plaice (2020; 2019b) emphasises the role of genre-bending in shaping recent gangster cinema, highlighting the many noir and family drama elements now present in the genre.

The thesis builds on Plaice's (2020; 2019b) observations by detailing how the gangster genre not only incorporates noir and family drama elements, but also thriller and romantic melodrama elements. However, although the thesis agrees with Plaice (2020; 2019b) that the gangster genre has been reshaped by extensive genre-bending, it does not support Plaice's (2020, p.6) argument that genre-bending has created a new sub-genre, the "family drama gangster film". There is simply insufficient evidence to indicate that a subset of films has diverged from the gangster genre.

In addition to genre-bending, the thesis argues that neoliberalism is responsible for reshaping Korean gangster cinema since 2006. The influence of neoliberalism is mentioned by both Gillespie (2016) and Plaice (2019b). Gillespie (2016, p.61) centres his work on neoliberalism, arguing that neoliberal ideology now underlies many gangster films. Plaice

(2019b) is more specific, arguing that recent gangster films incorporate tropes of “neoliberal noir”, a form of noir that highlights corporate and political corruption.

The thesis expands upon the work of both scholars by more fully detailing the continuing influence of the IMF’s neoliberal reforms on the gangster genre. Drawing on criminological and sociological research, it demonstrates that rising inequality and corruption caused by the IMF’s reforms have transformed the gangster-hero into a figure emblematic of Korea’s political and business elite. Unlike the working-class protagonists of previous eras, the Post-Revival Era gangster-hero is often a high-ranking, upper-class figure with significant societal influence.

Indeed, it is not neoliberal ideology that most distinguishes the Post-Revival Era from the genre’s preceding eras, but the gangster-hero’s high-ranking, upper-class social status, more businesslike appearance, and considerable influence in Korean society. This transformation reflects a shift in public sentiment: the gangster-hero now symbolises those perceived as perpetuating inequality, rather than those affected by it.

The finding that Korean gangster cinema has continued to evolve in recent years differs from film programmer Jamier’s (2015, p.47) finding that the genre shows “signs of exhaustion.” Jamier (2015) is just one of many scholars whose published work on the Korean gangster genre has been outpaced by the genre’s significant development in the Post-Revival Era. As noted in Chapter VII, scholarly work on the Korean gangster genre published as recently as 2019 does not account for the many new elements that characterise the Post-Revival Era.

Still, it is important to clarify that while the Post-Revival Era differs from the Revival Era, it does not represent a divergence but a development in the history of the gangster genre. Indeed, while the gangster-hero’s representation as an upper-class businessman is significant, the Post-Revival Era retains many elements, mainly syntactic, present in the

preceding era, such as similar aesthetics, similar depictions of violence, and an emphasis on themes such as brotherhood, betrayal and social class.

8.6 Broader Contributions, Limitations, and Recommendations for Future Research

Aside from the specific contributions outlined in the sections above, the thesis makes several broader scholarly contributions. Aside from the fact that the thesis is the first English-language text to examine pre-1990 Korean gangster cinema, it is also the first to enrich its discussion of the Korean gangster genre with a consideration of relevant criminological research. In addition, it is the first to specifically focus on the development of the genre's defining element, the gangster-hero. Indeed, while other scholars have commented on the depiction of gangsters, none have specifically highlighted the gangster-hero's transformation over the genre's successive periods.

Considering the American-centric nature of Film Genre Studies, any effort to expand the field's scope is a significant one. This is particularly true of this thesis due to the lack of English-language scholarship on non-American iterations of the gangster genre. As Wingsang (2008, p.523) notes, discourse on the gangster genre generally assumes "that within the global screenscape [sic], the gangster genre is American territory proper." Such an assumption is challenged by the mere existence of Korean gangster cinema, which has existed since the late 1950s, features hundreds of films and has spawned an entire sub-genre, the comedy-gangster genre. The argument for the significance of Korean gangster cinema made here also contrasts Langford's (2005, p.147) statement that "[f]ew [nations]...have used the figure of the gangster himself in the culturally and socially paradigmatic manner of his American incarnation." As this thesis illustrates, the Korean gangster-hero has directly embodied socio-cultural issues since the Early Pre-Revival Era and could certainly be described as paradigmatic. At the very least, it seems apparent that Korean gangster-heroes,

and by extension, Korean gangster cinema, do not, as Grant (2007, p.105) suggests, depend on their “generic American predecessors for their meaning.”

Of course, this thesis is not without its limitations. Due to the inaccessibility of a significant volume of relevant films, the thesis cannot be considered a definitive or comprehensive examination of the Korean gangster genre. This fact is compounded by the author’s inability to read Korean, which made it impossible to examine films that lacked English subtitles or to consult Korean-language literature on the Korean gangster genre.

Ironically, another of the thesis’s limitations stems from its broad scope. In discussing the entire development of Korean gangster cinema, the thesis considers numerous topics and genre elements. As a result, it lacks the focus that characterises more narrow studies of the genre. Accordingly, the thesis likely does not thoroughly examine elements and topics that other scholars might consider important. This limitation also stems from a general lack of research on Korean gangster cinema – there are simply too many underexplored aspects of the genre for one text to address.

Indeed, there are very few topics relating to Korean gangster cinema that do not necessitate further study. A notable topic deserving of discussion is the self-referential elements of both the Revival Era film *A Dirty Carnival* and the Post-Revival film *Rough Cut*. However, a priority for scholars may be to focus more on pre-1990s and post-2006 gangster films. Indeed, it is important to reiterate that the thesis is the *only* English-language text that examines gangster films made during the Golden Age and Dark Age.

One topic that merits further discussion is the career of director Kim Hyo-cheon, who made many gangster films throughout the 1970s and 1980s, often in quick succession. Indeed, as Chapter V notes, Kim directed many of the Late Pre-Revival films mentioned in this thesis, including *The True Story of Kim Du-han*, *Old Gentlemen in Myeongdong* and *Myeongdong Blues*. Accordingly, an understanding of Kim’s career might offer further insight into the Late Pre-Revival Era and the motivations of filmmakers such as Kim who

chose to make gangster films during a time when it was difficult to do so. The genre's existence before the Korean War – if it existed at all – is also a topic deserving of attention.

Korean film studies would also benefit from scholars considering the connections between Korean gangster cinema and other national gangster genres, particularly other Asian gangster genres such as Japanese yakuza cinema and Hong Kong triad cinema. Indeed, while the thesis briefly highlights the influence of Hong Kong gangster cinema on the development of the Revival Era, there is likely much more to discuss. The importance of this topic is substantiated by the fact that Choi (2010a, p.61) highlights it in her work on the Korean gangster genre, arguing that the genre “was reawakened in the 1990s by the popularity of Hong Kong action films, which began to appear in the mid-1980s.” Another of Choi's (2010a, p.60; 2010b, p.48) points that is worthy of further exploration is her observation that Early Pre-Revival Era films were influenced by Japanese yakuza films.

Although Choi (2010a) is the only scholar to have compared Korean gangster cinema with another national gangster cinema, some scholars have staged similar comparisons with genres adjacent to the gangster genre: Kelso-Marsh (2020) considers “transnational cinematic flows” between Japanese, Hong Kong and Korean noir, Soyoung Kim (2005) considers connections between Hong Kong and Korean action cinema, and Lee, S. (2023, pp.21-57) compares 1960s Korean “youth romance films” – including the gangster film *The Barefooted Young* – to Japanese and French New Wave youth films.

Further exploration of non-American versions of the gangster genre would follow the thesis's decision to heed Williams's (1984, p.124) advice to “get out of the United States.” This does mean denying the influence of Hollywood's role in the development of genre cinema. As Schatz (1981, p.6) makes clear, the genre-based studio system ensured that Hollywood cinema's “influence extended well beyond the United States.” However, focusing purely on American genres has limited understanding of specific genres and skewed discussion of genre cinema.

As noted already, certain scholars seem to assume that American genre cinema is more meaningful than other national genre cinemas. Even Korean genre theorist Jin (2020, p.126, author's italics) states that Hollywood genre films are "the global standard" and "reign supreme." More specifically, Jin (2020, p.127) argues that Korean efforts to blend Hollywood genres have diluted Korean culture and neglected "local sociocultural values to fit Western tastes." However, the idea that American genre cinema has diluted Korean genre cinema contradicts the scholarly consensus that Korean filmmakers have *transformed* American genres. In fact, Yecies and Shim (2016, p.209, author's italics) suggest that "genre appropriation and transformation are *necessary* and *constructive* processes of development for a national cinema seeking to break from Hollywood's long hegemony."

Indeed, it does not seem logical for Korean filmmakers to produce films to "fit Western tastes" as Jin (2020, p.127) suggests. Korean films neither aim to compete in the American film market nor struggle to compete with American films in their domestic market. As Lee (2018, p.124) states, "[u]nder the tsunami of the US products over the world's marketplace [sic], South Korean cinema has successfully defended itself." In fact, in 2020, Korean films represented 68% of all films shown in Korean cinemas (Kelso-Marsh 2020, p.25).

In addition, streaming networks such as Netflix have diminished Hollywood's power (Thompson 2020). Netflix invested \$1.2 billion in the Korean film industry between 2015 and 2020 (Kelso-Marsh 2021, p.25) and plans to invest \$2.5 billion over the next four years (Wan 2023). Also, China has replaced America as the world's biggest film market, forcing Hollywood to reshape its films to suit Chinese censors (Li 2021). Accordingly, while Hollywood remains a powerful force in the global film market, its dominance, or so-called 'superiority', has waned, a point John J. McDonnell and Jon Silver (2009, p.14) made as far back as 2009. As a result, it makes less sense now than ever before to limit Genre Studies to an American context. Instead, scholarly attention to film genre should expand beyond the

borders of America and reconsider ideas predicated upon the ‘superiority’ of American genre cinema.

8.7 Future Gangster Cinema: Closing Remarks and Final Thoughts

Nevertheless, it is difficult to predict how other national cinemas will interact with American genre cinema in the future. This is particularly true after the COVID-19 pandemic, which Xingzhen Niu (2023, p.1) states “greatly impacted” the global film market. Han Sunhee (2023, pp.109-110) notes that the Korean film industry was significantly impacted by the pandemic, with its market size in 2021 being only 40.8% of its market size in 2019. Sunhee Han (2023, p.111) notes that sales of domestic films fell during the pandemic to their lowest point since 2004. Journalist Patrick Frater (2024) states that since the pandemic, “Korea’s theatrical market has clearly become more uneven. Where Korea had previously enjoyed several hundred film releases per year, and a relatively level playing field, it has become increasingly polarized or hit-driven.”

Considering the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Korean film industry, it is logical to assume that it will also affect the development of the Korean gangster genre. Another factor likely to affect the genre’s development is the increasing footprint of streamers. Netflix is not the only international streamer to invest in Korea – Disney+, Apple TV+ and Prime Video all operate in Korea, as do many local platforms such as Tving and Wavve (Frater 2023).

Another factor that may influence the gangster genre’s future development is the persistent presence of corruption in Korea. Indeed, while Korea earned its highest ever rank – 31st out of 180 countries – in Transparency International’s 2022 Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) (Lee, J. 2023), the following 2023 study revealed that 55% of Koreans believe government corruption is “a big problem” in their country (Transparency International 2024). According to political scientists Faris Al-Fadhat and Jin-Wook Choi (2023, p.733),

Korea's current president, President Yoon Suk-yeol (2022 -), "has had to deal with corruption-like allegations against his spouse and mother-in-law." Many other prevailing socio-cultural issues may influence the gangster genre's future development, including worsening political polarisation, income inequality, a lack of job opportunities for young people, and continuing conflicts between rich and poor, each of which was a central issue during the 2022 election (Al-fadhat and Choi 2023, pp.735-737).

Although many of these socio-cultural issues are not particularly new, their combination with emerging industrial factors, such as the advent of streaming, could herald a significant genre shift and begin a new period of Korean gangster cinema. However, it is just as possible that upcoming gangster films, at least in the next five years, will either maintain or iterate upon the defining characteristics of the Post-Revival Era: its emphasis on corruption and social inequality, its businesslike gangster-heroes, and its critique of upper-class society. If the thesis has discovered anything about the Korean gangster genre, it is that the genre has just two constants: the gangster-hero and an inherent propensity to change.

Glossary

brawl (*paessaum*): a chaotic fight between many gangsters or often entire gangs

***chaebol*:** a large, family-owned conglomerate distinct to South Korea

Dark Age, the: the cinematic period of Korean cinema that lasted throughout the 1970s and 1980s; characterised by censorship and the decline of the Korean film industry

Early Pre-Revival Era: the initial stage of the Pre-Revival Era that spans the Golden Age, during which the Korean gangster genre originated

gangster-hero: a gangster who also serves as a film's protagonist, considered by the thesis as the defining characteristic of a gangster film

***geondal*:** a Korean term for gangster that translates to 'good-for-nothing'; often used by gangsters when referring to themselves

Golden Age, the: the period of Korean cinema that lasted from the mid-1950s until the early 1970s; characterised by the film industry's artistic and commercial growth

***Goryeo saram*:** ethnic Koreans from the former Soviet Union

***han*:** a uniquely Korean cultural concept that may be described, depending on the context, as a deep sense of resentment, grief, unfulfillment or resignation

hoodlum: a relatively old-fashioned English term for gangster that the thesis uses to refer to lower-class and less professional gangsters, namely those of the Pre-Revival Era

***Joseonjok*:** ethnic Koreans descended from Koreans who migrated to Manchuria between 1860 and 1945

***jopok*:** a more recent Korean term for gangster, abbreviated from the legal term for organised crime: *Jojik Pogryeokpae*

***kkangpae*:** a colloquial Korean term for gangster that originated during the Korean War and has the closest translation to the English term

Korean New Wave: the period of Korean cinema located between the Dark Age and New Korean Cinema, generally associated with the 1980s

Late Pre-Revival Era: the latter stage of the Pre-Revival Era that spans the Dark Age, during which the Korean gangster genre underwent a notable decline

neoliberalism: an economic and political ideology that emphasises deregulation, privatisation, and free-market principles

New Korean Cinema: the cinematic period beginning in 1990 and ending in 2006 that saw the resurgence, across various metrics, of Korean cinema

one-on-one fight: a fight scene in which a gangster faces off against another lone combatant, often highlighting personal rivalries

one-versus-many fight: a fight scene in which a single gangster faces multiple opponents

post-2006 period: the yet-to-be-named cinematic period that succeeded New Korean Cinema in 2007

Post-Revival Era: the period of the Korean gangster genre that parallels the post-2006 period, periodised between 2007 to the present day; primarily characterised by more powerful and businesslike gangsters, and a notable increase in genre-bending

Pre-Revival Era: the period of the Korean gangster genre that encompasses the Golden Age and the Dark Age, periodised between 1958 - 1989; primarily characterised by the genre's failure to develop fully due to the dominance of melodrama and strict censorship

quota quickie: a low-budget, often low-quality, film produced solely to meet government import quota requirements

Revival Era: the period of the Korean gangster genre that parallels New Korean Cinema, periodised between 1990 and 2006; primarily characterised by the genre's return to Korean screens and significant success

Revival framework: the model proposed in this thesis to chart and discuss the development of Korean gangster cinema

semantic elements: in genre theory, the recurring building blocks of a genre such as character types, settings, or iconography; defined by this thesis as the following visual

elements: a film's characters, settings and iconography (other visual elements such as props, mise-en-scène and specific actors)

syntactic elements: in genre theory, the structural relationships between characters, narratives, and situations that define a genre; defined by this thesis as the following underlying elements that lend semantics meaning: narrative, aesthetics (formal elements such as editing, cinematography and lighting), and themes

underworld: a figurative term used to refer to the world of organised crime

multifarious element: a semantic element with a syntactic purpose and/or syntactic characteristics

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